

**The International Rice Research Institute
Annual Report 1969**

INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE Annual Report 1969

IRRI

The International Rice Research Institute was established jointly by The Rockefeller Foundation and the Ford Foundation in cooperation with the Republic of the Philippines. It was incorporated in 1960 and dedicated in 1962 when the research program began. This annual report, the eighth to be published by the Institute, presents a detailed account of the work done in 1969.

The International Rice Research Institute

Annual Report 1969

The International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines, 1970

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* Arrived during year.

** Left during year.

† On study leave for part of year.

Director's Introduction

Program highlights

During 1969, the Institute named two new varieties, IR20 and IR22. They have the same yield potential as IR5 and IR8 the two varieties previously named by the Institute, but they are highly superior in grain appearance and should have a greatly increased market value.

IR20 has a medium-long, slender grain with little chalkiness. Its particular value is its disease and insect resistance. It has medium resistance to rice stem borers. It also has high resistance to bacterial leaf blight and to many races of the rice blast disease. Its resistance to the tungro virus disease is rated medium. Early trials have been so successful in East Pakistan that several hundred tons of IR20 seed have been imported by East Pakistan for extensive plantings in 1970.

IR22 has a long, slender, translucent grain in contrast with the bold and chalky grain of IR8. The head rice recovery of IR22 on milling is much higher than that of IR8.

IR20 formerly carried the designation IR532E576 and IR22 was known as IR579-160-2. A full report of these new varieties will be found in the Varietal Improvement section of this report.

IR20 and IR22 are only additional forward steps in the effort to produce better rice varieties for the tropics; much is left to be done. During the next 3 to 5 years the Institute's varietal improvement program is expected to develop varieties that possess strong resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper, that perform better under the cool temperatures that prevail in subtropical rice-growing regions during the winter months, and that have a range in crop duration from as early as 100 days to as late as 150 days, but with little sensitivity to photoperiod. Furthermore, the leaves will be tough enough to withstand high winds without tearing, and the levels of disease resistance will be greater than those of any of the new varieties now being grown. These varieties will be selected with the objective of at least maintaining present yield potentials and grain quality standards.

Improvements beyond the next 5 years should bring about varieties with increased protein quantity and quality, higher yielding upland varieties with increased drought resistance, and varieties with higher yield potentials, perhaps as much as 50 percent above those of the best varieties available today.

The Agronomy Department showed in 1969 that the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D, applied in granular form 3 or 4 days after transplanting, can give excellent control of grasses, annual sedges, and broadleaved weed species. At current cost relationships in the Philippines, weeds can now be controlled in transplanted rice with the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D at half the cost of hired hand labor. Although several other chemicals provide excellent control, at present prices they cannot compete successfully with 2,4-D. Obviously this situation may change in the future.

The Agronomy Department harvested its twenty-first rice crop on the same land in 7-1/2 years in its so-called maximum yield experiment. The three best treatments in 1969 gave a total yield of 23 metric tons per hectare in 12 months. This is 3 tons per hectare more than any yield previously reported from this

three-crops-a-year experiment. The higher yield can be attributed mainly to better insect control and to the use of higher yielding varieties with greater disease resistance.

A project for the development of genetic lines that have high resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper is going ahead, but it will take 2 or 3 more years to introduce this resistance into otherwise improved varieties.

The Entomology Department continues to study chemicals for insect control. Because the brown planthopper population on the Institute farm has developed resistance to diazinon, a renewed effort is underway to identify suitable systemic insecticides that can be applied in granular form and that have low toxicity to human beings and other animals. The trade names of some promising materials are Furadan, Dolmix, and Mipcin.

The Plant Pathology Department discovered during the year that a Dupont chemical called "Benlate" gives excellent control of the rice blast disease. It is a systemic fungicide and can be applied to the soil before planting or to the seeds, or sprayed on the leaves before neck rot infection occurs. The compound is indeed promising, but because it is very new, the economics of its use have not yet been determined.

The Plant Physiology Department has shown that there is no optimum leaf area index with respect to the grain yield of new varieties with the plant type of IR8. Rather there is a critical value between 5 and 6; higher indices do not result in yield decreases unless serious lodging occurs.

The Agricultural Engineering Department has developed an improved seed cleaner which greatly increases the efficiency of cleaning threshed grain. It is simple in design and durable. It may be manufactured commercially before the end of 1970.

The Department made further progress in developing a stripper for efficient rice harvesting on small farms, initiated studies of high-temperature grain drying, and continued its efforts to develop more effective land preparation equipment for both small and large rice farms. This work is largely supported by the U.S. Agency for International Development.

For the first time in its history the Institute conducted a 4-month training program in multiple cropping. The objective of the program is to train people engaged in extension and applied research in the practice of growing a crop of rice during the rainy season followed by a succession of upland crops during the dry season. Beginning in 1970, this course will have participants from several countries; the 1969 class was composed principally of Filipinos.

The rice production training course continued at its usual high level with 35 participants from 14 countries. At the peak of its training operations during the year, the Institute had scholars from 20 different countries.

Staff changes

The Head of the Office of Information Services, Mrs. Merry Lee San Luis, resigned on July 31, 1969, and she was replaced by Mr. Steven A. Breth, who joined our staff on November 1, 1969.

Mr. Rogelio D. Feliciano, Associate Editor, resigned in October 1969, and his replacement had not been found by the end of 1969.

Dr. James C. Moomaw, an Institute agronomist who has been on special assignment in Ceylon for the past 2 years, resigned from the Institute's staff on September 1, 1969. He is spending a study leave period at the University of

California and will join the staff of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture in Ibadan, Nigeria by July 1970. Dr. S. K. De Datta has been appointed as Head of the Department of Agronomy, a post he held in an acting capacity while Dr. Moomaw was in Ceylon.

Dr. K. C. Ling, Associate Pathologist, and Dr. S. K. De Datta, Associate Agronomist, were advanced to full-scientist positions on January 1, 1969.

Mr. Vernon E. Ross was hired by The Rockefeller Foundation and assigned to the International Rice Research Institute in June 1969 to head our Office of Rice Production Training and Research.

Mr. William G. Golden, Jr., Mr. Ross' predecessor, accepted a 2 year assignment in Ceylon, starting in September 1969. This program is made possible by a Ford Foundation grant to the Institute and to the Government of Ceylon. Its principal objective is the stimulation of rice production through research, training, and increased extension activities.

Trustees

Dr. Salvador P. Lopez, the President of the University of the Philippines was elected a trustee of the Institute on February 5, 1969. He replaced General Carlos P. Romulo, the former University President who is now serving as Secretary of Foreign Affairs of the Philippines.

On the same date, Dr. Sterling Wortman became an Institute trustee, representing The Rockefeller Foundation. He replaced Dr. Ralph W. Cummings who resigned from The Rockefeller Foundation on December 31, 1968.

Finances

Cash grants totalling \$2,345,181.03 were received by the Institute during 1969.

1. *The Ford Foundation* gave \$1,234,825. Of this amount \$890,000 represents its contribution toward the operating and capital expenditures of the Institute for 1969. It also supported the international rice research programs of the Institute in the following countries:

West Pakistan—\$80,000, which is a portion of a 4-year grant of \$550,000; East Pakistan—\$90,000 which is a portion of a 4-year grant of \$596,000; Ceylon—\$121,875 which is a portion of a 4-year grant of \$552,000; Philippines—\$40,950 which is a portion of a 32-month grant of \$240,475.

The Ford Foundation also gave \$12,000 to support the Institute's conference "Rice Research and Training in the 1970's." Furthermore, it is contributing toward the development of the East Pakistan Agricultural Research Institute. A grant of \$400,000 was made for this purpose in 1967. The whole amount was released to the Institute in previous years, but is still being expended.

2. *The Rockefeller Foundation* granted the Institute \$903,222 during 1969. Its contribution toward the operating and capital expenditures of the Institute amounted to \$890,900 of which \$642,000 was received in cash. The balance of \$248,000 represented the cost of its manpower contribution. The Rockefeller Foundation also supported the Institute's accelerated research and training program on cropping systems for tropical areas, under the direction of Dr. Richard Bradfield. For this purpose a grant of \$182,500 over a 3-year period was made in 1968 of which \$44,699.64 was expended during 1969. In addition, The Rockefeller Foundation made \$7,500 available to the Institute for research on the introduction of recombining genes from alien species into cultivated rice, to be carried out in cooperation with the Institute of Botany, Academia Sinica

in Taiwan. Through the University of Hawaii, The Rockefeller Foundation released \$5,722 to the Institute, enabling a junior scientist of the Institute, Mr. Joselito Silva, to work on a cooperative project on bacterial leaf blight of rice in Hawaii.

3. The *U.S. Agency for International Development* released \$399,747.30 to the Institute during 1969. Of this amount, \$144,564.05 was used on a project entitled "Research on Farm and Equipment Power Requirement for Production of Rice and Associated Food Crops in the Far East and South Asia (IRRI-AID Contract No. AID/csd-834)" and represents a portion of a 4-year budget of \$360,000 for the period ending October 28, 1969. This contract will be renewed for 2 years more with a budget of \$404,600. Under a contract to help accelerate rice research and training programs in India, USAID released \$118,458.71 to the Institute in 1969. This contract took effect on June 13, 1967 and has a budget of \$212,025, in addition to an Indian rupee budget managed by the USAID mission in India. Furthermore, USAID provided a grant of \$400,000 to expand the Institute's training and consultation services relating to rice growing in the Far East, South Asia, Latin America, and Africa. This grant was for the 1-year period ending June 30, 1969. During 1969, \$120,372.46 was released to the Institute under this grant. USAID also contributed \$16,352.08 toward the training program of the International Rice Research Institute in 1969.

4. Two years ago, the Institute entered into a contract with the *National Institutes of Health*. The Institute agreed to screen rice varieties for amino acid content, particularly lysine and threonine, and to study the genetic characteristics of lysine-rich varieties. During 1969, a total of \$20,236.73 was released by NIH to the Institute.

5. The International Rice Research Institute received the *1969 Magsaysay Award for International Understanding*. The award carried a stipend of \$10,000 which was applied toward the costs of the Institute's international training program.

6. *Stauffer Chemical Co.* contributed \$5,000 toward the general research program of the Institute.

7. *Union Carbide Asia, Ltd.* provided the sum of \$3,000 to assist in the rapid dissemination of the Institute's research findings, particularly in the field of entomology.

8. From *Monsanto Far East, Ltd.*, the amount of \$1,500 was received for partial support of the herbicide program of the Institute.

9. *The Shell Co., Inc.* gave \$5,000 toward the insecticide research program.

10. The sum of \$2,650 was received from the *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations* to support the training of Mr. Alpha Mommadou Diallo of Guinea.

11. The sum of \$3,500 was received from the *International Potash Institute*, toward the soil fertility studies of the Institute.

12. *Eli Lilly and Co.* (ELANCO) provided the sum of \$2,000 to partially support the Institute's weed control research program.

13. *Gulf Research and Development Co.* gave \$2,500 in support of the research on the chemical control of grasses and weeds.

14. *Dow Chemical International* gave \$1,200 towards research on weed control.

Crop Weather

The weather data collected at IRRI during 1969 were compared with the average of 3 previous years (1966-68). Figure 1 shows the curves of rainfall recorded at the Institute farm. The data for solar radiation (Fig. 2) were recorded by a pyrheliometer with the sensing element located on the rooftop of the Institute's laboratory building. The rainfall and solar radiation data were collected at the Institute this year because in recent years the pyrheliometer at the College Weather Station has reported persistently lower values of solar radiation than when it was new. The rainfall data are comparable between the two locations.

Less rain fell from April to June 1969 than the average for the same period from 1966 to 1968. The lower amount of rainfall was associated with a slightly higher amount of solar radiation received for the same period in 1969.

From September to November 1969 the amount of rainfall received was similar to that received in the same period in 1968, but lower than the average values for the previous 3-year period.

The high rainfall during the 1969 wet season

Fig. 1. Rainfall in millimeters (3-point moving average), for IRRI, Los Baños, Laguna.

Fig. 2. Solar radiation curve (3-point moving average), for IRRI, Los Baños, Laguna.

Table 1. Maximum velocity of winds recorded at the College Weather Station, Los Baños, Laguna, 1969.

Date	Maximum wind velocity (km/hr)
July 9	56
July 26	43
July 27	56
Sept. 8	37
Sept. 9	30
Sept. 10	32

(July to November) was more favorable for upland rice, which depends entirely on rain, than the rain received for the 1968 wet season. Table 1 shows the maximum velocity of winds recorded at the College Weather Station during tropical depressions from July to September. These tropical depressions, however, were not severe and caused no unusual damage to the rice crop in the area.

The rainfall received during December was higher than the previous 3-year average and considerably higher than during the same month in 1968.

Soil Microbiology

The maintenance of soil fertility in rice-growing areas of the developing countries largely depends on microbial activities that take place in the soil. One role of soil microorganisms in fixing atmospheric nitrogen was studied with a new acetylene reduction method.

The economy of fertilizer usage is greatly influenced by the activities of soil microorganisms. Transformations of nitrogen fertilizer were examined by using the isotope ^{15}N technique.

Soil microorganisms help protect the environment from pesticide residue problems. Some persistent insecticides, were found to degrade in flooded soils.

Biochemical functions in the rhizosphere are considered to be important for rice growth in the paddy. Chemical control of algal growth in the rice paddy was investigated.

Atmospheric nitrogen fixation

It is known that nitrogen is continuously available to rice in flooded soil, but how nitrogen becomes available is not wholly understood. Apparently microorganisms in paddy soil fix atmospheric nitrogen (N_2) and thus maintain soil fertility. This theory could not be unequivocally proved previously because no suitable method existed for measuring the fixation of N_2 in the field.

Recently, however, a method was developed (Hardy, R. W. R. *et al.*, 1968. *Plant Physiol.* 43:1185). The method is based on the reduction of acetylene (C_2H_2) to ethylene (C_2H_4). Although acetylene-ethylene assay is an indirect way to measure N_2 fixation, it is more rapid, sensitive, and economical than the isotope ^{15}N technique.

Last year (1968 Annual Report), we used the acetylene-ethylene assay to examine the possible role of microorganisms in the rice plant and in the soil in fixing N_2 . This year we carried out more detailed studies on N_2 fixation by the rice plant and by the soil, using the acetylene-ethylene assay. The amount of ethylene formed was analyzed by gas chromatography.

The results (Table 1) showed that N_2 fixation increased as the plant aged; however plants that had just germinated had more N_2 fixation activity than 1-week-old seedlings. When we assayed the tops of the plants we found that the N_2 -fixing activity was located in the stems rather than in the leaves. When we assayed the stems at the maximum tillering stage (50 days after transplanting), we found that the lower portion was more active than the upper portion.

The effect of nitrogen fertilization on the fixation of N_2 by plant microorganisms was tested at the maximum tillering stage. As shown in Table 2, rice plants grown in plots with 200 kg/ha N showed less N_2 -fixing activity than those in soil without nitrogen fertilizer.

The foregoing suggests that the tissues of the rice plant might have N_2 -fixing activity. To clarify this point, we used the acetylene-ethylene assay to compare the N_2 -fixing activity of 2-week-old rice plants grown under sterile conditions with that of rice plants grown naturally in flooded soil. The plants naturally grown in flooded soil reduced much more acetylene to ethylene indicating that the activity is due to microorganisms inhabiting the plants (Table 3). Although various plants such as apples, cantaloupes, and sweet potatoes form ethylene, no higher plants are known to reduce acetylene to ethylene except when nitrogenase (N_2 -fixing enzyme) is present. We found also that rice plant tissues produce small amounts of ethylene, but cannot reduce acetylene to ethylene. Thus the bacteria are either attached quite firmly to the surface of the plant roots and stems or are inside the plant tissue.

To determine the number of microorganisms on and in the plant we conducted further experiments. The plant roots were washed frequently with sterile water to remove all soil particles, leaving only microorganisms clinging to the roots. Other roots were washed with sterile water and then with sterile sand and water to remove both the soil particles and the microorganisms from the root surface. We found (Table 4) that the N_2 -fixing activity in the hystosphere (plant root tissue) was as high as in the rhizoplane (root surface). The aerobic N_2 -fixing bacteria counted on a nitrogen-free agar medium 34 days after transplanting were 1.31×10^6 per gram of the

Table 1. C_2H_2 - C_2H_4 assay of rice plant in different growth stages*.

Variety	Parts	Days after transplanting t		
		34 (nmole C_2H_4 g ⁻¹ fresh weight day ⁻¹)	52	80
IR8	tops	0.18 (0.14) ‡	0.19	0.0 † 84.0
	roots	7.1 (5.1)	17.0	217.7
Peta	tops	0.28 (0.14)	—	0.0 † 80.0
	roots	6.1 (3.8)	—	371.1

* The plants were taken from a field to which no nitrogen fertilizer had been applied. 134, 52, 80 days after transplanting were equivalent to the tillering, maximum tillering, and flowering stages.

† Numbers in parentheses show the assay result under anaerobic conditions.

‡ Leaves.

|| Stem.

Table 2. Effect of nitrogen fertilizer on the C_2H_2 - C_2H_4 assay of the rice plant*.

Ammonium sulfate added (kg/ha N)	Plant parts		
	Leaves (nmole C_2H_4 g ⁻¹ fresh weight day ⁻¹)	Stems	Roots
0	0.19	8.9	17.0
200	0.12	3.1	8.9

* Samples (IR8) were taken from field at the maximum tillering stage

fresh tops of the variety IR8, and 5.35×10^6 per gram of the fresh roots. A number of small-sized (2 to 3 mm) colonies were grown on *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* media. These bacteria were isolated and purified and then tested with the acetylene-ethylene assay. All isolates were positive (reduced acetylene to ethylene) in the assay, but the activities were small compared with the activity of azotobacter or clostridia.

We also applied the acetylene-ethylene assay to soil from a rice field. Surface soil had more activity under aerobic than anaerobic conditions; lower soil was more active under anaerobic than aerobic conditions. As in surface soil, activity in the rhizosphere was greater under aerobic than anaerobic conditions. Apparently a different group of microflora is dominant in different regions of the soil.

Soil in the greenhouse that was submerged and incubated for 3 weeks had much higher N_2 -fixing activity than fresh soil from the field (Table 5). This seemed to be due to the N_2 -fixing blue-green algae and the N_2 -fixing bacteria which become prominent after the soil is flooded for 2 to 3 weeks. In the previous annual report, we showed that the blue-green algae are the most important N_2 -fixing microorganisms in rice soils.

Among many isolates of N_2 -fixing bacteria from flooded soil, azotobacter and clostridia were the most active as measured by the acetylene ethylene assay. However, a number of bacteria have been isolated from the soil which can grow on nitrogen-free *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* media. These bacteria vary in their ability to reduce acetylene. Although they are less active in fixing N_2 than azotobacter or clostridia, their presence in flooded soil in large numbers should not be overlooked.

More extensive investigations on N_2 -fixing

Table 3. $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay of sterile and nonsterile rice plants.

Plant parts	Sterile plant		Nonsterile plant	
	IR8	Peta	IR8	Peta
(nmole C_2H_4 g ⁻¹ fresh weight day ⁻¹)				
Tops	0.03	0.12	0.44	2.49
Roots	0.06	0.02	3.56	16.09
Without acetylene				
Tops	0.04	0.12	0.03	0.16
Roots	0.05	0.02	0.06	0.06

Table 4. $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay of rice plant roots*.

Variety	Age (weeks)	Rhizoplane (nmole C_2H_4 g ⁻¹ fresh weight day ⁻¹)	Hystosphere
Peta	2	5.1	2.5
IR8	2	3.2	2.6
Peta	3	25.1	23.8
IR8	5	15.7	14.2

* Plants were taken from direct-seeded plots.

Table 5. $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay of flooded soils presubmerged under greenhouse conditions.

Submerged period (weeks)	Ethylene produced (nmole C_2H_4 g ⁻¹ dry soil day ⁻¹)
1	1.4
2	3.0
3	40.1*
4	50.7*
5	47.1*

* Prominent algal growth on soil surface.

activities in paddy soil under natural conditions are under way.

Nitrogen transformation

Several reports suggest that nitrification in the oxidized layer of flooded soils and the following denitrification process in the reduced layer are major influences on the efficiency of nitrogen use by rice. But no unequivocal evidence is available to show that this is true.

In 1968, we found that a large portion of added nitrogen, whether organic or inorganic, cannot be recovered as available nitrogen. We also found that the flooded soils (particularly soil to which ammonia fertilizers had been applied) contained a large population of nitrifying bacteria during the rice-growing period. But it was not certain whether the loss of nitrogen was due to the escape of nitrogen from the soil-water system or to immobilization of the nitrogen by soil microorganisms.

In experiments this year, we traced the fate of ammonium nitrogen in flooded soils by using the isotope ^{15}N technique. We made a model of the oxidized layer in the laboratory by flooding 20 g of Maahas clay soil in a 125-ml flask. The soils were presubmerged for 2 to 3 months before nitrogen tagged with ^{15}N was added. Inorganic or organic nitrogen was incorporated in the

Table 6. Amount of total tagged N remaining in flooded soil incubated at 30 C in the dark.

Tagged compound incorporated	Incubation period (weeks)				
	0	2	4	8	12
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	359.1	343.0	172.8	88.4	89.3
Alanine	361.3	278.0	106.3	81.1	78.6

flooded soils which were then incubated at 30 C in the dark. Every 4 weeks the amount of ¹⁵N was analyzed.

We found that the total amount of tagged N added to the soil as ammonium sulfate or alanine decreased during the incubation period. After 8 weeks only one-quarter of the original amount remained in the soil (Table 6), but no further loss of nitrogen was observed subsequently. The data suggest that organic or inorganic nitrogen added to the oxidized layer of flooded soils in the field would disappear from the soil and water system in a short time.

Table 7 shows that the amount of tagged N that was found in the hydrolyzable fraction of the soil treated with ammonium sulfate was small. The nitrogen in tagged alanine was not recovered as exchangeable ammonium nitrogen. Volatilization of ammonia was measured by trapping ammonia in an absorbent solution. We found, however, that the amount of volatilized ammonia was very small. Thus volatilization could not account for the loss of nitrogen in the experiment.

The results indicate that nitrification can take place in the oxidized layer, even in flooded soils. It is difficult to measure nitrification in flooded soils because nitrogen is simultaneously denitrified. Nitrate, an oxidized form of ammonium, does not build up in flooded soils unless the denitrifying activities are retarded. Denitrifica-

tion is retarded when the soil is incubated aerobically or when a denitrification inhibitor is added.

To study this point, we incubated soil samples (10 g soil with 200 ml water with various nitrogen sources in 500-ml flasks) at 30 C under aerobic conditions (flasks placed on a rotary shaker), facultative anaerobic conditions (standing flasks), and anaerobic conditions (flasks in a nitrogen atmosphere). By 4 weeks under aerobic conditions, most of the nitrogen, as ammonium sulfate, urea, and alanine, was converted to nitrate. None of the nitrogen under anaerobic conditions was converted to nitrate. But the nitrogen under facultative anaerobic conditions had gradually produced a significant amount of nitrate. Nitrification experiments using pure cultures of the nitrifying bacteria, *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrobacter*, under flooded soil conditions are in progress.

Pesticide residues

In previous years we reported that γ -BHC, a chlorinated hydrocarbon insecticide, degrades much faster in flooded soil than in upland soil. The findings were applied to other chlorinated hydrocarbon insecticides which have been considered persistent in soil. The residues of Aldrin, Dieldrin, Endrin, Chlordane, Heptachlor, DDT, DDD, and Methoxychlor in upland and flooded soil conditions were investigated. We used Philippine soils: Casiguran sandy loam (pH: 4.8, O.M.*: 4.0%, Total-N: 0.27%), Luisiana clay (pH: 4.7, O.M.: 3.2%, Total-N: 0.21%), Maahas clay (pH: 6.6, O.M.: 2.0%, Total-N: 0.14%) and Pila clay loam (pH: 7.6, O.M.: 1.5%, Total-N: 0.09%).

* Organic matter content.

Table 7. Amount of tagged N in fractions of flooded soil incubated at 30 C.

Tagged compound incorporated	N-fraction	Incubation period (weeks)				
		0	2	4	8	12
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	Exchangeable	365.5	204.6	83.7	0.1	0.1
	Hydrolyzable	0.7	14.6	10.2	7.9	9.1
	Residual	0.1	2.5	3.3	2.6	3.1
Alanine	Exchangeable	0.8	181.8	1.3	0.5	0.2
	Hydrolyzable	16.6	32.2	23.9	23.0	23.7
	Residual	0.1	9.3	10.0	7.5	7.6

Fig. 1. Degradation of Aldrin in four soils.

Fig. 2. Degradation of Dieldrin in four soils.

Aldrin left more residue in flooded soil than in upland soil (Fig. 1). The greater loss under upland conditions could be attributed to the greater volatilization rate of this insecticide under aerobic conditions. It could also be explained by the oxygen requirement for the epoxidation of the chemical. Dieldrin and Chlordane were very persistent in both upland and flooded soils. (Figs. 2, 3). Endrin, which has the same chemical components as Dieldrin but has a different configuration, was unstable only in flooded Casiguran soil (Fig. 4). Endrin degraded appreciably in the Casiguran soil in 2 months. Heptachlor, Methoxychlor, and DDT were

more degradable in flooded soil than in upland soil (Figs. 5, 6, 7).

The organic matter content of the soil was correlated with the degradabilities of these insecticides. Thus the higher the soil organic matter content was, the lower the amount of residues that formed. In the flooded Casiguran soil, all insecticides disappeared in 1 month. In Pila soil, which has the least organic matter among the soils tested, little significant degradation took place even in the flooded conditions.

Since the amount of residue under the upland conditions seemed not to depend on the soil type, some microbiological or chemical factors

Fig. 3. Degradation of Chlordane in four soils.

Fig. 4. Degradation of Endrin in four soils.

under anaerobic conditions appeared to be involved in the degradation of the insecticides. Previous studies (1968 Annual Report) showed that bacteria that degrade γ -BHC degrade DDT to DDD only under anaerobic conditions in a liquid medium. During DDT degradation in soil, DDD, a possible intermediate, also appeared within 30 days of incubation.

The amount of DDD accumulation depends on the soil, as shown in Table 8. Although more DDT was degraded in Maahas clay soil than in Pila clay loam soil, Maahas clay produced less

DDD at 30 days after incubation. An unknown compound which has a shorter retention time than DDT and DDD in the gas chromatogram was found in upland Maahas clay soil after 45 days of incubation. The intermediate, DDD, was more persistent than DDT, but the amount of residues in the flooded soil was not significant at 6 months in Casiguran soil and Luisiana clay (Fig. 8). In Maahas and Pila soil, however, the rate of DDD degradation under flooded and upland soil conditions was about the same for the experimental period.

Fig. 5. Degradation of Heptachlor in four soils.

Fig. 6. Degradation of Methoxychlor in four soils.

Organic transformations

Application of organic matter to the soil is generally considered a favorable practice for upland crops. It may not be quite as desirable in continuously flooded soil, however, where anaerobic metabolism is probably the major microbial function. In some rice soils under certain environments the oxidation-reduction potential (Eh) of the soil becomes extremely low and possibly stimulates the production of reduced toxins.

We examined the effect of organic matter on rice plant growth under flooded soil conditions. Boeun degraded soil, Yongnam heavy clay soil, and Honam reclaimed soil—all from Korea—and Maahas clay soil from the IRRF farm were used in a pot experiment. Green manure, rice straw, or cellulose were incorporated into each soil at a level of 0.5 percent by weight. To avoid initial evolution of various soil toxins, the pot was presubmerged for a few weeks before transplanting IR8 into the soil.

The incorporation of green manure and rice

Fig. 7. Degradation of DDT in four soils.

straw showed some inhibitory effect on plant height and number of tillers at early growth stages but both recovered to some extent at later stages. The application of cellulose clearly showed a detrimental effect on plant growth and in particular reduced the number of tillers during the entire growth period in all soils. This growth reduction was not due to nitrogen deficiency. The plants were supplied with nitrogen and did not show symptoms of nitrogen deficiency at any time. At harvest, the growth and yield of plants on soils to which rice straw and green manure had been added did not much differ from the control. But the addition of cellulose to each soil evidently caused a decline in yield.

To examine the transformation of volatile fatty acids, 100 ml of the solution that leached from each pot was collected every week. The

volatile fatty acids were analyzed by gas chromatography with a Thermistor detector using a column packed with acid-washed Chromosorb W. The solid support was coated with 35 percent dioctyl sebacate and 15 percent sebacic acid.

For several weeks after transplanting, the only prominent volatile fatty acid found in the soil was acetic acid. After 3 or 4 weeks, significant amounts of acetic, propionic, and butyric acid started to accumulate in the pots treated with cellulose. Five weeks after transplanting, the amount of organic acid reached its maximum value, but butyric acid appeared dominantly only in Boeun soil. The amounts of acetic, propionic, and butyric acid were highest in soil solution from Boeun degraded soil and lowest in soil solution from Maahas clay.

If volatile fatty acids are toxic to the rice plant and retard plant growth, the rhizosphere would be the site in which the toxins would show the most direct effect. We measured the activity of bacteria that produce organic acids in the rice rhizosphere. After being washed 15 times with sterile water, 7 g of fresh rice roots were incubated under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions in liquid soil-extract medium with and without glucose at 30 C.

None of the volatile fatty acids were produced under aerobic conditions or without glucose. Two kinds of volatile fatty acids, acetic and

Table 8. DDD formation during the incubation of DDT under flooded soil conditions*.

Soil	Time of incubation (days)			
	0	15	30	45
Pila clay loam	0	†	4.7	4.5
Maahas clay loam	0	0	†	2.1
Luisiana clay	0	0	5.8	12.5
Casiguran sandy loam	0	9.7	13.0	15.7

*17.5 ppm of DDT was added to each soil; this is equivalent to 15.8 ppm DDD if all DDT is converted to DDD. The soil samples are the same as shown in Fig. 7.

†Less than 0.05.

Fig. 8. Degradation of DDD in four soils.

butyric, were detected in the rice rhizosphere only under anaerobic conditions with glucose. More butyric acid was found than acetic acid (Table 9).

The results indicated that bacteria that produce organic acids inhabit the rice root surface and could ferment carbohydrate to organic acid when the root environment becomes favorable for anaerobic metabolism. The greater production of acids by rice roots grown in Boeun soil than by those in Maahas clay may be an indication of the reason that rice yields poorly on Boeun soil. More detailed studies on the organic acid transformation in paddy and rhizosphere soils are underway.

Rice rhizosphere

The rice plant in its natural environment is always exposed to microbial contamination from the air, the water, and the soil. Since the phyllosphere (surfaces of the leaves) and the rhizosphere are where plant pathogens penetrate and plant nutrients are absorbed, the microorganisms in the phyllosphere and rhizosphere should play an important role in plant growth.

A number of bacteria were found on the rice root surface even after the roots were washed 15 times with sterile water. To investigate the

microorganisms that affect rice roots, the root area was divided into the rhizosphere, the rhizoplane (root surface), and the hystosphere (root tissue). After successive washings with sterile water and water-sand solution, rice roots were macerated in a Waring Blender to prepare the rice hystosphere samples.

Bacteria were the most abundant microflora found. Aerobic bacteria were present in large numbers before transplanting and during the growth of the rice plant. But the number of anaerobic bacteria increased after transplanting, particularly, in degraded Boeun soil. Figure 9 shows that many bacteria in the roots are denitrifiers or acid-producers. Nitrifying bacteria were not found in the roots. More sulfide-producing bacteria were found in rice roots grown in Boeun degraded soil than in roots

Table 9. Organic acid production by excised rice roots*.

Incubation time (hours)	Organic acid produced	Rice grown in	
		Maahas clay soil (mmole/100 g fresh materials)	Boeun soil (mmole/100 g fresh materials)
24	Butyrate	0.1	0.1
	Acetate	0.0	0.0
48	Butyrate	0.4	1.3
	Acetate	0.2	0.5
72	Butyrate	1.7	3.9
	Acetate	0.4	0.5

* Rice plant: 6-week-old Peta in pot; Incubation: Anaerobic conditions under N_2 gas atmosphere.

Fig. 9. Number of functional group of bacteria in rice (IR8) roots (rhizosphere) in two soils (microorganisms measured per gram of fresh roots).

grown in Maahas clay soil. This may be another indication of the causes of low yields in Boeun soil.

The number of fungi was very small. No actinomycetes were found.

The biochemical functions of the root bacteria in relation to rice plant growth and pathogens are to be studied.

Algal control

Despite the important role of blue-green algae in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen, they and other filamentous algae in rice paddies cause problems in direct-seeded rice. These algae form a mat on the soil surface which newly germinated rice seedlings have difficulty penetrating. Seedlings that do penetrate the mat are often uprooted when the mat breaks free from the soil and floats to the surface of the water. These problems could become serious in many countries when direct seeding is adopted more widely.

Copper sulfate is the most commonly used algicide. We are searching for chemicals that are more effective and less phytotoxic to rice plants. In tests of several chemicals, each was sprayed into the paddy water at the rate of 0.5 and 2.5 kg/ha (active ingredient) 3 days after the direct seeding of IR8. Among the commercially available algicides and herbicides tested in 1969 Monoquat and Phygon were effective at both rates of application under the experimental conditions.

Chemistry

Studies in cereal chemistry emphasized the effect of the lipid and starch fractions and variety on grain properties; the improvement of the protein content of rice through crosses between IR8 and high-protein varieties; the effect of increased protein on properties of the grain; and the physicochemical nature of rice glutelin and prolamin. With the integration of the biochemistry program with cereal chemistry, studies were made on the metabolism of protein in lines differing in protein content and on the metabolism of starch in lines differing in amylose content.

Factors affecting grain quality

Lipids and changes in viscosity

The peak viscosity and gelatinization temperature as shown in the amylogram of milled rice (10% paste), are known to increase significantly during storage of rice above 15 C. Japanese workers have shown that these changes are caused by changes in the lipid (fat) fraction of rice, specifically by the formation of free fatty acid. Fatty acids readily complex with the amylose fraction of starch granules. Unsaturated lipids also undergo oxidation to form carbonyl compounds which may act as links between starch molecules, between protein molecules, or between starch and protein molecules. Oxidation also decreases the solubility of the starch and protein in water. Studies in Kyoto University have shown that proteins and lipids of the rice endosperm are localized in protein bodies. Because rice samples differing in amylose or protein content were available, freshly harvested samples were used to study the effect on amylograph characteristics of adding palmitic acid, of defatting, of accelerated storage, and of formaldehyde vapor treatment.

Four samples of freshly harvested rice differing in amylose content were chosen for the starch study. When the milled rice flour of the samples was defatted three times with refluxing 85 percent methanol for 2 hours the changes in the peak viscosities of their amylographs were inverse to their amylose contents (Table 1). The defatted high-amylose sample, IR8, was characterized by a longer gelatinization time and a lower, plateau-type viscosity than the untreated sample. C4-63 was only slightly affected. IR127-80 and IR253-16-1-2 had higher peak viscosities than the untreated sample. Japanese workers have reported a decrease in peak viscosity when flour from aged milled rice is defatted.

Adding 0.7 percent palmitic acid to the defatted rice restored the peak viscosity of IR8, had no effect on C4-63, decreased the peak viscosity of IR127-80, and further increased the peak viscosity of IR253-16-1-2.

In contrast with defatting with aqueous methanol, defatting with methanol plus chloroform (1:2 v/v) resulted in higher peak viscosities

and gelatinization temperatures for both IR8 and IR127-80. These changes must be a direct consequence of defatting with refluxing 85 percent methanol (67 C) since mere heating at the same temperature for the same period of 6 hours increased peak viscosity only slightly. In addition, free fatty acids constitute only a minor fraction of the lipids in freshly harvested rice. That may explain why the results differ from published data involving aged rice.

Palmitic acid was also added directly to the untreated samples. Adding palmitic acid up to 1.0 percent of the flour increased the amylograph peak viscosity for IR8; but a lower peak viscosity was obtained at 1.4 percent palmitic acid than at 1.0 percent (Table 1). For C4-63 and IR127-80, a slight increase resulted from adding 0.7 percent palmitic acid, but not from adding 1.0 percent. Adding palmitic acid to the waxy sample, IR253-16-1-2, decreased the sample's peak viscosity.

The formation of a fatty acid complex with the starch apparently involved the amylose fraction. The fatty acid concentration necessary for maximum effect on the peak viscosity of the amylograph increased with amylose content. Although Japanese rice starch has been reported to complex with 0.7 percent fatty acids, IR8, which has more amylose, showed still further complexing with up to 1.0 percent palmitic acid. The gelatinization temperature of the samples generally increased as palmitic acid was added. Complex formation probably occurs both before and during the gelatinization of the starch.

Accelerated storage of the milled rices at 40 C for 1 month resulted in a higher peak viscosity at a higher temperature for all samples. However, no further increase in peak viscosity was obtained by storage for 1.5 months more. Thus 1 month of accelerated storage at 40 C gave maximum changes in the amylograph viscosity of milled rice. At ambient temperatures, the peak viscosity usually increases and levels off after 3 to 4 months of storage. Gelatinization temperatures also increased upon accelerated aging.

The effect of carbonyl compounds formed during fat oxidation was simulated by exposing milled rice to formaldehyde vapors in a closed chamber for 24 hours. For the three nonwaxy

Table 1. Effect of various treatments on the amylograph peak viscosity of four samples of milled rice differing in amylose content.

Treatment	Change in peak viscosity (%)			
	IR253-16-1-2 (2.3) ^a	IR127-80 (15.0) ^a	C4-63 (23.6) ^a	IR8 (28.9) ^a
Defatting (reflux 85% methanol)	60	31	4	-26
0.7% palmitic acid added to defatted flour	70	22	3	0
Heated 6 hours at 67 C	5	4	3	3
Defatting (methanol/chloroform 1:2)	—	8	—	9
0.7% palmitic acid	-12	5	4	29
1.0% palmitic acid	-14	0	-2	33
1.4% palmitic acid	—	—	—	17
1 month at 40 C (milled rice)	41	24	15	17
2.5 months at 40 C (milled rice)	35	22	9	19
Formaldehyde-vapor treatment	29	-50	-46	-27

^a Percentage of amylose content of the milled rice.

samples, the treatment drastically delayed and reduced the value of the maximum viscosity; IR8 was the least affected by the treatment. In contrast, the waxy sample showed a higher peak viscosity upon formaldehyde treatment. The results indicate that low-amylose, nonwaxy rice is more affected by formaldehyde linking than either waxy or high-amylose rice. The protein content of these samples did not differ much (6.0 to 8.6%). The formaldehyde treatment increased the gelatinization temperature of the samples.

The addition of 3.2 g of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) to a slurry of 20 g of rice flour in 400 ml water gave an amylogram with a two-step viscosity increase which corresponds to the two stages of the gelatinization of starch. Defatting with 85 percent methanol decreased the maximum viscosity of the CMC-rice amylogram of IR8 only. IR253-16-1-2 had the greatest increase in maximum viscosity. No change in gelatinization temperature resulted from defatting. Accelerated storage increased the gelatinization temperature of the CMC-rice amylogram. The CMC-rice amylogram also showed that the formaldehyde treatment reduced the maximum viscosity, but had no effect on the gelatinization temperature.

These results showed that although amylose content may be related to the extent of increase in peak viscosity due to the complexing of starch and fatty acid, it cannot explain the increase in the peak viscosity of waxy rice during storage. Freshly harvested waxy rice and waxy rice from the previous crop have been shown to have similar taste-panel scores for tenderness, co-

hesiveness, and gloss despite their age difference. Presumably, amylograph changes in waxy rices during storage may not be reflected in the actual eating quality of the cooked rice.

To determine whether the protein fraction may be more involved than starch in the reaction with carbonyl compounds, samples of the same variety differing in protein content were treated with formaldehyde vapor for 72 hours. Results on three varieties showed that the drop in viscosity of the high-protein (10% or higher) samples tended to be even less than that of the low-protein (less than 10%) samples. Gelatinization temperatures were not affected by formaldehyde treatment. The results indicate that the amylograph of the low-protein rices was more sensitive to aldehyde treatment, but in the opposite direction to actual storage changes. Because of the proximity of protein and lipids in the rice endosperm, however, the effect brought about by formaldehyde vapors may not simulate storage changes.

Amylose content and eating quality

Previous work using varieties from different crop seasons has shown that amylose content is the principal influence on the texture of cooked rice. Since these samples were also cooked with a constant ratio of rice to water, it was important to verify whether this relationship persists even if the rices are cooked with adjusted ratios of rice to water to obtain similar degrees of doneness for all samples.

To eliminate differences in grain size and shape and in environmental factors, three pairs of lines from the same crosses differing in amylose content were obtained from the Varietal

Table 2. Properties of milled rice and taste panel scores of cooked rice from low- and high-amylose pairs from different crosses.

Property	Chianung 242/2 x Peta		IR8 x FF 36		IR8 x [Yukara x T(N)1]		LSD ^a (5%)
	low	high	low	high	low	high	
Amylose (% dry basis)	14.5	27.5	14.2	24.8	13.8	23.5	
Protein (% dry basis)	9.5	9.2	10.4	11.3	11.2	10.7	
Final gelatinization temperature (C)	62	62	60	60	63	62	
	Trial I (Identical water/rice ratio)						
Water/rice ratio	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	
Tenderness ^b	7.8	4.0	7.5	4.5	7.5	3.5	1.53
Cohesiveness ^b	7.2	3.5	7.0	3.5	7.2	3.2	0.81
Gloss ^b	9.0	5.2	7.8	4.0	8.0	4.0	1.14
	Trial II (Adjusted water/rice ratio)						
Water/rice ratio	1.6	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.6	1.8	
Tenderness ^b	6.5	3.5	6.8	5.0	6.8	3.8	1.10
Cohesiveness ^b	6.5	3.8	6.5	3.5	6.8	3.2	1.01
Gloss ^b	7.0	4.5	6.5	3.5	7.2	4.5	0.92

^a For the low- and high-amylose lines within each pair.

^b Mean of duplicate assessment by a taste panel of four judges. Numerical scores from 1 to 9 were assigned, a score of "1" representing the lowest expression of the property in question and a score of "9" the highest expression.

Improvement Department. They were evaluated by a taste panel at the Home Technology Department of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture. The trials were made with ratios of rice to water of 1 to 1.8 and with ratios adjusted to give an optimum degree of doneness. Samples with higher amylose content had significantly lower scores for tenderness, cohesiveness, and gloss, regardless of the rice-to-water ratio (Table 2). When cooked, high-amylose samples had higher weights and greater volume than the low-amylose samples. The difference within each pair in the amount of expansion in volume during cooking must have contributed to their differences in gloss scores.

Laboratory tests were done on the same pairs of lines. For four pairs tested, amylose content was not consistently correlated with head rice yield, grain hardness (Kiya hardness tester), cooking time (Ranghino test), elongation of presoaked rice when cooked, or volume-expansion and water-uptake ratios (Batcher laboratory cooking test). The amount of dissolved amylose in the cooking water (starch-iodine blue test) was higher for the high-amylose samples (0.26 to 0.37 absorbance units) than for the low-amylose samples (0.12 to 0.18). Since the cooking liquid of each member of a sample pair had similar quantities of solids (starch), values obtained in the starch-iodine blue test must reflect the amylose content of the exposed starch of the surface cells.

Rice hemicelluloses

Fractions of alkali-soluble bran and milled rice hemicelluloses obtained from column chromatography using diethylaminoethyl cellulose in a borate buffer at pH 9.2 were hydrolyzed with the methanol precipitate of Pectinol R-10 (Rohm and Haas) and a purified α -L-arabinofuranosidase preparation derived from it. During degradation of the hemicellulose, we measured the specific viscosity and the reducing sugars (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid and phenol). Hydrolysis of the hemicellulose fraction eluted by 0.3M borate with Pectinol R-10 resulted in a larger decrease in the viscosity and a greater degree of hydrolysis than with purified α -L-arabinofuranosidase (Fig. 1).

Essentially the same results were obtained with the other fractions. Arabinose was the only sugar detected by paper chromatography in the α -L-arabinosidase hydrolysates but it constituted 35 to 60 percent of the total present in the polysaccharides. All the Pectinol R-10 hydrolysates from bran and milled rice polysaccharides contained arabinose, xylose, and galactose. Those from milled rice also had glucose. Digestion of the residual polysaccharide with Pectinol R-10 after hydrolysis with L-arabinosidase liberated the same component sugars.

These enzymic studies showed that the arabinose residues of the hemicellulose fractions have the α -L-furanoside configuration, which is also characteristic of wheat flour pentosans. These

L-arabinose branches must be short since hydrolyzing the arabinose residues resulted in only a slight drop in the intrinsic viscosity of the hemicelluloses. The action of α -L-arabinosidase in the original polymer was probably blocked by a xylose or galactose residue in bran hemicellulose, or a xylose, galactose, or glucose residue in milled-rice hemicellulose linked to one of the nonreducing hydroxyl groups in the remaining arabinose residues.

Disc electrophoresis and gel filtration of the preparations demonstrated that the protein in the hemicelluloses is a contamination since it was readily separated from the carbohydrate fraction.

Other studies

A cooperative project was undertaken with Dr. M. S. Buttrose, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, Glen Osmond, Australia on the ultrastructure of rice starch granules corroded by hydrochloric acid. Waxy and nonwaxy rice starch granules showed similar corrosion patterns. Corrosion with α -amylase removed the centers from the granules, or produced large corrosion channels, or fragmented the granules. Few acid-corroded granules had a distinct shell structure (Fig. 2).

We continued a comparative study in which we examined the differences in the elongation of 370 Basmati, D25-4, and 349 Jhona when cooked. Milled Basmati samples had 1.29 percent pentosans and 0.80 percent crude fiber; milled Jhona samples had 1.04 percent pentosans and 0.70 percent crude fiber. When the samples were soaked in water at 30 C, fissures appeared in D25-4 faster than in 370 Basmati. In turn, fissures appeared faster in 370 Basmati after 7 minutes of soaking than in 349 Jhona.

Ten samples of rice from Lambayeque, Peru were analyzed. The samples had low or intermediate gelatinization temperature, 5.1 to 6.8 percent protein (except for one sample with 10.8 percent), and amylose contents ranging from 19.2 to 31.3 percent. Only three samples had high positive amylograph setbacks of more than 150 Brabender units and they had amylose contents of 27.2, 27.6, and 31.3 percent. The wide range of amylose content of the samples

Fig. 1. Crude pectinase (Pectinol R-10) extensively degraded rice hemicellulose as indexed by rapid changes in specific viscosity and reducing sugars, but its purified α -L-arabinosidase did not.

Fig. 2. Electron micrograph of starch granules of the rice variety 370 Basmati corroded with hydrochloric acid showing the layered structure characteristic of starch granules (M. S. Buttrose). Stain: potassium permanganate.

indicates the differing preferences for texture of cooked rice in Peru.

Improvement of the protein content of rice

Protein content of IR8 rice in farmers' fields

The protein content of brown rice (at 12% moisture) of IR8 from farmers' fields in Laguna, Philippines ranged from 6.8 to 9.9 percent (mean: 8.0%) in the 1968 wet season, 6.7 to 9.4 percent (mean: 7.7%) in the 1968-69 dry season, and 7.3 to 8.5 percent (mean: 8.0%) in the 1969 wet season. Corresponding 1968-69 dry-season values for local varieties were 6.2 to 7.1 percent for Intan and 7.2 to 8.4 percent for Malagkit Sungsong. The 1969 wet-season range for Malagkit Sungsong brown rice was 7.7 to 8.2 percent. These results indicate that IR8 in farmers' fields has as high a protein content as the indigenous varieties Intan and Malagkit Sungsong (waxy) even though it yields more grain. Thus, the figure of 8.0 percent protein for IR8 brown rice seems justified.

Protein analysis of improved lines

Raising the protein content of high-yielding varieties, such as IR8, from 8 percent to 10 percent is the objective of a cooperative project between Institute breeders and chemists started in 1966. Brown rice of F_4 and F_5 plants from crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties grown by the Varietal Improvement Depart-

ment during 1969 dry and wet seasons were analyzed for protein content. Brown rice of the F_4 plants had 1.4 to 2.6 percentage points higher mean protein content than IR8 (8.7% protein) in the 1969 dry season. In the 1969 wet season, the means of F_5 plants were 0.4 to 1.9 percentage points higher than IR8 (9.3% protein). The results (Table 3) indicated that although these correlations were highly significant, at most 25 percent of the variation in protein content is hereditary, indicating a strong interaction between the line and the environment. Dwarf lines were selected based on protein content and on plant type similar to IR8.

In the 1969 wet season, yield trials of 44 lines of better plant type from the six crosses between IR8 and high-protein varieties showed that most of these simple crosses were intermediate between IR8 and the high-protein parent in yielding ability. Rough rice yield and brown rice protein were negatively correlated. Breeding aspects of this project are presented in the Varietal Improvement section.

Possible sources of high protein content from lines with BPI-76 as a parent were analyzed. The cross IR251 (IR12-178-2-3 x BPI-76) showed 9.1 to 15.0 percent protein in 63 lines; IR1006 (IR8 x BPI-76-1) had 8.1 to 11.3 percent in 45 lines, and IR1163 (IR8/2 x BPI-76-1) had 7.5 to 13.2 percent in 102 lines. Screening of the Varietal Improvement yield trials revealed three high-protein entries: IR6-156-3-3 with 11.0 to 11.5 percent protein, IR160-27-3-1-1-3 with 11.1 to 11.6 percent, and IR586-11-3 with 10.3 to

Table 3. Protein content of F_4 , F_5 , and F_6 brown rice of the crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties.

Generation or correlation coefficient	Protein content ^a (%)					
	IR1100	IR1101	IR1102	IR1103	IR1104	IR1105
F_4 Range	6.0-13.7	6.0-13.8	7.5-13.0	7.6-13.8	5.4-13.8	7.0-15.2
Mean	10.52	10.25	9.95	10.38	10.29	11.02
F_5 Range	7.1-15.2	6.9-15.8	7.4-13.5	7.8-14.9	7.0-14.0	8.2-13.4
Mean	11.11	11.08	10.52	10.63	10.70	10.60
r (F_4 vs. F_5)	+0.554** ($n = 134$)	+0.317** ($n = 131$)	+0.424** ($n = 68$)	+0.470** ($n = 127$)	+0.412** ($n = 122$)	+0.456** ($n = 89$)
F_6 Range	7.3-15.7	7.5-15.4	9.5-14.5	6.5-14.9	9.2-12.7	8.4-14.2
Mean	11.86	11.77	11.65	10.90	10.89	10.71
F_6 Range	8.1-14.1	8.7-13.9	7.8-13.2	8.7-14.0	8.5-12.4	7.2-11.9
Mean	10.90	10.99	10.62	11.17	10.32	9.73
r (F_5 vs. F_6)	+0.548** ($n = 72$)	+0.494** ($n = 81$)	+0.184 ($n = 43$)	+0.415** ($n = 99$)	+0.407** ($n = 26$)	+0.551** ($n = 45$)

^a At 12% moisture.

** Significant at the 1% level.

Table 4. Amino acid content of F₄ brown rice of a low-protein and a high-protein line of crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties*.

Amino acid	Amino acid content (g/16.8 g N)				r (n = 12)
	Low protein		High protein		
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	
Alanine	5.52– 6.26	5.90	5.46– 6.38	5.97	0.094
Arginine	7.48– 9.06	8.55	7.78– 9.45	8.72	0.171
Aspartic acid	8.73– 10.4	9.60	8.98– 10.0	9.50	-0.118
Cystine	1.30– 2.25	1.70	1.59– 2.07	1.76	0.046
Glutamic acid	16.8 – 18.9	17.6	18.2 – 19.8	19.0	0.721**
Glycine	4.70– 5.04	4.81	4.46– 5.33	4.91	0.193
Histidine	2.21– 2.86	2.62	2.19– 2.59	2.39	-0.408
Isoleucine	4.29– 4.81	4.58	4.44– 5.06	4.72	0.360
Leucine	7.79– 8.02	7.90	7.95– 8.82	8.38	0.791**
Lysine	4.04– 4.57	4.38	3.47– 3.93	3.68	-0.838**
Methionine	2.16– 3.01	2.58	1.89– 2.45	2.26	-0.566
Phenylalanine	5.17– 5.79	5.48	5.34– 5.88	5.62	0.310
Proline	4.34– 5.45	4.93	4.32– 4.91	4.59	-0.495
Serine	4.95– 6.31	5.56	5.36– 5.84	5.60	0.073
Threonine	3.91– 4.23	4.04	3.55– 4.30	3.83	-0.532
Tryptophan	1.14– 1.57	1.37	0.92– 1.32	1.06	-0.752**
Tyrosine	4.46– 5.25	4.83	4.99– 5.29	5.15	0.584*
Valine	6.44– 7.47	6.73	6.22– 7.27	6.80	0.151
Ammonia	2.19– 2.79	2.49	2.17– 2.65	2.35	-0.272
Total	102.7 –109.2	105.6	104.1 –109.0	106.3	
Protein (% at 12% moisture)	5.4 – 7.6	6.7	13.6 – 15.3	14.4	

* Recalculated to 95% nitrogen recovery, excluding tryptophan. Mean nitrogen recovery was 93%. Corrected values for cystine, isoleucine, methionine, serine, threonine, and valine.

* Significant at the 5% level.

** Significant at the 1% level.

11.0 percent. In a yield trial in the 1969 wet season, IR160-27-3-1-1-3 gave the highest yield and protein content—5,450 kg/ha and 10.6 percent—of the three lines. The variety IR8 yielded 5,900 kg/ha with 10.2 percent protein.

Protein content, and grain and protein properties

The aminograms of F₄ brown rice of a low- and a high-protein line of each of six crosses (Table 3) were determined. The samples were hydrolyzed by a modification of the standard procedure. We introduced purified nitrogen into an evacuated hydrolysis tube, thawed the frozen sample, refroze the sample, reevacuated the tube, and reintroduced purified nitrogen. The procedure improved the tyrosine values. Values for cystine, isoleucine, methionine, serine, threonine, and valine were adjusted to compensate for incomplete liberation or degradative loss during hydrolysis. Protein content was negatively correlated with lysine and tryptophan, and positively correlated with tyrosine, leucine, and glutamic acid (Table 4). The trend was consistent for all six pairs for lysine, leucine, and tryptophan, and for five pairs for glutamic acid and tyrosine. These results are similar to those

previously found for samples of the same varieties differing in protein content due to environment.

The protein efficiency ratio (PER) of food is usually evaluated at 10-percent protein in the rat diet. Although the protein levels of the milled rice in high-protein lines are expected to be at least 10 percent (at 12% moisture), the levels of existing rice varieties, including IR8, are less than 10 percent. These latter samples cannot be assessed by the standard PER assay. A cooperative study was undertaken with Dr. Ricardo Bressani at the Instituto de Nutricion de Centro America y Panama (INCAP) using the local variety Intan and two IR8 samples to determine the growth rate of rats at protein levels of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 percent in diets which are 90 percent rice. The protein in the IR8 samples had lower lysine, methionine, and tryptophan content than Intan protein. The high-protein IR8 had lower cystine, glycine, and threonine content than the two lower protein samples (Table 5).

The results of the first experiment with up to 5-percent protein diets showed that protein intake was linearly correlated with growth dur-

Table 5. Amino acid content of milled rice samples sent to INCAP for protein quality studies.

Amino acid	Amino acid content (g/16.8 g N)				LSD ^a (%)
	Intan	IR8 ^b	IR8 ^c	BPI-76	
Alanine	5.99	6.04	5.66	6.24	n.s.
Arginine	7.90	8.78	8.82	8.58	n.s.
Aspartic acid	9.59	9.97	9.46	10.4	n.s.
Cystine	1.81	1.81	1.45	1.42	0.27
Glutamic acid	18.3	19.1	18.7	21.1	1.06
Glycine	4.82	4.80	4.52	4.66	0.20
Histidine	2.45	2.45	2.48	2.48	n.s.
Isoleucine	4.89	5.10	4.78	5.34	n.s.
Leucine	7.84	8.32	8.20	9.63	0.92
Lysine	4.27	3.77	3.69	3.35	0.32
Methionine	3.45	3.02	2.44	1.80	0.36
Phenylalanine	5.55	5.74	5.66	6.25	0.41
Proline	4.73	5.04	4.79	4.66	n.s.
Serine	6.31	5.68	6.27	6.92	n.s.
Threonine	4.10	4.10	3.78	3.75	0.20
Tryptophan	1.35	1.26	1.05	0.97	0.08
Tyrosine	5.02	5.34	5.34	5.85	n.s.
Valine	6.24	6.55	6.51	7.30	n.s.
Ammonia	3.70	2.98	2.86	2.28	0.46
Total	108.31	110.29	106.46	112.98	
Nitrogen recovery (%)	102.7	101.3	98.5	99.8	
Protein (%) ^d	5.68	7.32	9.73	14.3	

^a n.s. = not significant

^b Low protein.

^c High Protein ^d at 12% moisture

ing the 28-day feeding period (Fig. 3). The basal diet contained 4% mineral mixture, 5% refined cottonseed oil, 1% cod liver oil, 90% refined corn starch, and 5 ml/100 g of a complete B-vitamin mixture. Rice or casein was substituted for corn starch in this basal diet to provide 1-, 2-, 3-, 4-, and 5-percent protein. The diets were fed *ad libitum* to groups of five male and five female weanling white rats, 21 days of age, of the Wistar strain of the INCAP colony. The rats were placed in individual all-wire screen cages with raised screen bottoms and had water available at all times.

Based on the slopes of the regression lines of gain in weight vs. protein intake, Intan had 107 percent the protein quality of casein, IR8 (7.3% protein) had 101 percent, and IR8 (9.7% protein) had 94 percent (Fig. 3). The PER values obtained at the 5-percent protein level were 2.56 ± 0.06 for Intan, 2.20 ± 0.13 for IR8 (7.3% protein), and 1.94 ± 0.12 for IR8 (9.7% protein) compared with 2.20 ± 0.19 for casein. The nitrogen efficiency ratio was 4.88 for Intan, 4.05 for IR8 (7.3% protein), 3.45 for IR8 (9.7% protein), and 4.05 for casein.

The second experiment, with 90-percent rice diets, showed identical PER values (2.04 to 2.07) for the three milled rice samples with differing (5.5, 6.7, and 8.8%) protein levels. When these values were included in the regression line from the first experiment, they did not fit the curves at 5-percent protein or lower, whereas the corresponding casein values fitted the regression line for this standard protein (Fig. 3). These deviations in growth rate values for milled rice at a lower protein intake than is true for casein contradicts the original work of Hegsted. He found that the regression curves for vegetable proteins deviate from linearity only at protein intakes higher than those for casein. Whether the regression line for rice really falls off at this low protein intake had to be rechecked.

The only sample available for rechecking this relationship was BPI-76 (14% protein) which was grown in the 1969 wet season. The protein of this sample had lower levels of lysine, methionine, and tryptophan than the IR8 and Intan protein (Table 5). Most of the BPI-76 has been sent to Dr. R. Q. Blackwell of the U.S. Naval Medical Research Unit No. 2 in Taiwan for feeding experiments with school children. Dr. Blackwell's longevity study with Long-Evans white rats using 90 percent rice diets of cooked BPI-76 rice (11.7% protein, dry basis) or Intan (7.0% protein) was concluded this year. As in the INCAP trials, preliminary results in these feeding experiments also showed that the nutritive value of these two rice varieties paralleled their protein content in the diet.

These results indicate that although the protein quality of rice is mainly a function of the protein level in the diet, differences do exist among rice varieties at the same protein intake. These differences may be related to the lower levels of essential amino acids in high-protein rices, particularly lysine, cystine and methionine, threonine, and tryptophan.

Protein bodies from the endosperm of BPI-76 rice were identical in properties to those obtained from low-protein Japanese rice samples. In cooperative work at the Laboratory of Nutritional Chemistry, Kyoto University, chemists isolated and characterized protein bodies from rice polish (20% of brown rice) of high-protein BPI-76 grown at IRRI (14% protein in

brown rice and 13% in milled rice). Overmilling of BPI-76 brown rice removed an outer bran layer (5% by weight) with 17-percent protein and four successively 5-percent (by weight) rice polish fractions that had mean protein contents of 22, 23, 21, and 18 percent. These results showed that the protein in the endosperm is more evenly distributed in high-protein rice than in low-protein rice.

Examination with a light microscope showed that the protein was in discrete round bodies, and 1 to 3 μ in diameter. They stained yellow with iodine. The protein bodies isolated by enzymic maceration and centrifugation in a sucrose density gradient were 63-percent protein, 17-percent lipids, and 10-percent carbohydrates. The electron micrograph of the isolated protein bodies was very similar to the

micrograph of low-protein rice. It showed an outer membrane, a lamellar structure inside, and a highly dense region in the center (Fig. 4). Most bodies were spheroidal rather than spherical.

Because of the association of lipids with rice protein bodies, it was important to determine whether high-protein rices, which have more protein bodies in their endosperm, also have a high fat content. A high fat content would mean that milled high-protein rice has a higher concentration of surface lipids than normal rice and hence would be more prone to rancidity (hydrolytic and oxidative). In a previous study of 16 varieties grown in two crops, the higher protein sample of each variety was not necessarily higher in crude fat. The brown rice of low- and high-protein rices of three varieties was analyzed for crude fat, and the milled rice, for surface

Fig. 3. Regression lines of weight gain of rats with protein intake. Rats fed for 28 days on milled Intan (5.7% protein), low protein (LP) IR8 (7.3% protein), or high protein (HP) IR8 (9.7% protein), or on casein, at protein levels in the diet between 0 and 5 percent. Rice data above 5 percent in the diet deviated from the lines in contrast to casein.

Fig. 4. Electron micrograph of isolated BPI-76 rice protein bodies showing their well-defined structure (K. Murakami). Stain: uranyl acetate.

lipids. Brown rice samples of the same variety had similar crude fat contents. Some high-protein milled rice samples, however, had higher contents of surface lipids (0.15 to 0.26%) than the low-protein samples of the same variety (0.14 to 0.21%), probably because the former were relatively less milled than the latter. High-protein rice generally gives a lower bran-polish recovery than low-protein rice of the same variety, reflecting the greater resistance of the former to milling.

Assessment of screening techniques

We tested screening techniques developed for lysine and tryptophan in other cereal laboratories on rice. Rice flours were defatted and incubated in Pronase proteolytic enzyme solution to hydrolyze the rice protein. A study of four proteases showed that an alkaline protease gave better hydrolysis of rice protein than an acid protease as indexed by the tryptophan values obtained. One reason may be that rice protein dissolves more in an alkaline medium than in an acid medium. Tryptophan was determined by the intensity of the color at 545 $m\mu$ of an aliquot

of the hydrolysate with Opienska-Blauth reagent (0.013% ferric chloride in a 1:1 mixture by volume of acetic acid and 30 N sulfuric acid).

Lysine was determined in an aliquot of the protease hydrolysate by treatment with alkaline cupric phosphate reagent. The supernatant was treated with 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine and the excess reagent was extracted with ethyl acetate. The intensity of the color of the coupling product with the ϵ -amino group of lysine was determined at 390 $m\mu$. The results of this colorimetric assay were identical to those obtained by the standard column chromatography technique.

Udy and other workers reported that the quantity of Acilane Orange G dye absorbed by protein in the dye-binding capacity technique correlates well with the content of protein and the basic amino acids (lysine, arginine, and histidine) in cereal grains. Since the histidine and arginine content of rice protein is not influenced by the protein content of rice, dye-binding capacity has also been claimed to be a screening method for lysine content. To verify the suitability of this technique for lysine screening,

brown rice flours of 11 BPI-76 crosses of known lysine content (by the chloro-dinitro-pyridine method) were analyzed. A diluted dye solution (0.033%) was employed; 3.0 ml were shaken with 10 mg of defatted brown rice for 45 minutes, and then centrifuged. The color intensity of the supernatant fluid was determined in a 1-mm cell at 470 m μ in a spectrophotometer accurate to 0.001 absorbance.

The results showed good correlation between dye-binding capacity and the lysine and protein contents of brown rice (Table 6). For the 11 samples, the correlation coefficient between the dye-binding capacity, and the protein level of the brown rice was +0.88** and the lysine level, +0.94**. The protein content and the lysine content of protein of the sample were significantly correlated ($r = -0.72^*$). Essentially the same results were obtained with the eight IR951 lines alone.

Rice prolamin and glutelin

Prolamin and glutelin are the so-called insoluble seed proteins. Unlike albumin, which readily dissolves in water, and globulin, which dissolves in neutral aqueous salt solutions, prolamin requires an organic solvent, such as 70-percent ethanol, and glutelin needs an alkaline or acidic solvent.

Prolamin

Rice prolamin preparations are low in nitrogen—not more than 12 percent. They are also characterized by an anomalously high ultraviolet absorption at 280 m μ . A study was undertaken to find a way to purify the prolamin of milled IR8 rice and to examine the nature of its nonprotein constituent.

An assay for polysaccharide with a mixture of phenol and sulfuric acid indicated that the prolamin preparations may contain from 2 to 9 percent carbohydrate. Assay of the hydrolysates with glucose oxidase verified previous findings that the main sugar constituent of the polysaccharide fraction is glucose. However, the combined protein and polysaccharide content of the prolamin fractions usually make up less than 80 percent of the dry weight. Disc electropho-

Table 6. Protein, lysine, and dye-binding capacity of defatted brown rice of 11 BPI-76 lines.

Brown rice protein ^a (%)	Lysine content		Dye-binding capacity ^b
	(% of protein)	(% of brown rice)	
	IR951 lines (IR12-178-2-3 x BPI-76)		
9.1	4.2	0.38	0.804
11.6	4.0	0.46	0.944
13.3	4.0	0.53	1.053
13.3	3.5	0.47	0.952
13.4	3.2	0.43	0.970
13.4	3.8	0.51	0.962
13.5	3.5	0.47	0.958
15.0	3.2	0.48	1.028
	IR1163 lines (IR8/2 x BPI-76-1)		
7.5	4.4	0.33	0.600
10.3	3.6	0.37	0.796
13.2	3.1	0.41	0.954
Standard error	0.09	0.01	0.0087
LSD (5%)	0.28	0.04	0.0271

^a At 12% moisture.

^b Change in absorbance at 470 m μ .

resis of these preparations in a polyacrylamide gel using tris buffer (pH 8.3) and staining with Amido Black 10B showed two protein bands which also stain for polysaccharide (periodic acid and Schiff's reagent). Most of the protein and polysaccharide, however, remained in the sample gel. Evidently, whatever glycoprotein may be present in rice prolamin is just a minor constituent of the protein.

In gel filtration experiments using Sephadex G-100 columns (3.3 x 50 cm) and an 0.01N sodium hydroxide eluant, the protein (Lowry) peak coincided with the void volume. However, at least two ultraviolet (UV) peaks were noted, one at the void volume and one at v/v_0 ratio of 2.75. Carbohydrate fractionation was the least distinct and the peaks were not defined.

Runs were also made in Sephadex LH-20 columns using 70-percent ethanol as the eluant. The protein fraction at the void volume showed a higher UV absorption at 280 m μ than that obtained in Sephadex G-100 columns; a second UV peak followed right after the void volume. Presumably, 0.01N sodium hydroxide is a better solvent for dissociating the UV-absorbing contaminant of prolamin than aqueous ethanol. The prepared prolamin protein was also less soluble in 70-percent ethanol than the UV-absorbing contaminant. Polyphenols are known to dis-

* Significant at the 5% level.

** Significant at the 1% level.

sociate from their complex with proteins in alkaline solution and they absorb ultraviolet light strongly at 280 μ . Experiments are underway to verify these results using a direct 70-percent ethanol extract of milled rice as the sample (without prior extraction of albumin and globulin).

Table 7. Lysine content of milled rice protein fractions and the subfractions of rice glutelin (variety IR8).

Protein source	Lysine content (g/16.8 g nitrogen)
Milled rice	3.80
Albumin (water solvent)	4.92
Globulin (5% sodium chloride solution)	2.54
Prolamin (70% ethanol)	0.51
Glutelin (residue)	3.57
Glutelin subfractions	
70% ethanol with 0.6% β -mercaptoethanol	0.23
0.5M sodium chloride pH 10 sodium borate buffer (0.1M) with 0.6% β -mercaptoethanol	3.19
0.5M sodium chloride pH 10 sodium borate buffer (0.1M) with 0.5% sodium lauryl sulfate	4.14
Residue	3.46

Fig. 5. Schematic patterns of rice protein fractions and glutelin subfractions from starch-gel electrophoresis in the presence of urea. Stain: Amido Black 10B (alk red - alkylated reduced).

Glutelin

Glutelin constitutes about 80 percent of the protein of the rice endosperm. It is characterized by a high molecular weight due to the cross-linking of the disulfide bonds of the constituent polypeptide chains. Recent work on corn glutelin by French chemists showed that it is made up of protein subunits similar to the prolamin, albumin, and globulin fractions. We undertook a similar fractionation on rice glutelin and the extracts were characterized by amino acid analysis and electrophoresis in starch gel containing urea.

The starting glutelin material (8.3% glutelin) was the residue from IR8 milled rice after the albumin, globulin, and prolamin were serially extracted. First, the glutelin was extracted with β -mercaptoethanol in 70-percent ethanol. Then the residue from the first extraction was further extracted with 0.5 M sodium chloride in a 0.1 M sodium borate buffer (pH 10) with 0.6-percent β -mercaptoethanol. Finally, the residue was extracted with 0.5-percent sodium lauryl sulfate. Each extract was dialyzed and lyophilized. The reagent, β -mercaptoethanol, breaks the disulfide bonds which cross-link the protein subunits; the detergent, sodium lauryl sulfate, breaks the hydrophobic bonding between the hydrocarbon side chains of the amino acid residues of the protein.

The lysine content of these subfractions of glutelin showed that the glutelin subfraction released by β -mercaptoethanol in 70-percent ethanol was similar to prolamin, the one released by β -mercaptoethanol in salt solution was similar to globulin, and the one soluble in sodium lauryl sulfate was similar to albumin (Table 7). Each subfraction contained more lysine than the one extracted before it. The residual protein had the same lysine content as glutelin. French chemists obtained similar results previously with corn glutelin.

Starch-gel (12%) electrophoresis of the glutelin subfractions in an aluminum lactate buffer (pH 3.1) in the presence of 3 M urea gave diffuse bands but verified the aminogram data on the identity of these three extracts (Fig. 5). Relative mobilities obtained with rice protein fractions were similar to those obtained with wheat proteins. Globulin showed the fastest migration,

followed by albumin and then prolamin. Most of the glutelin remained at the sample well. Its few bands with mobilities similar to albumin, globulin, and prolamin are due to contamination or hydrolyzed subunits. Only prolamin and glutelin gave discrete bands. Albumin and globulin gave diffuse bands since they are lower in molecular weight and require a higher concentration of starch gel to show discrete bands.

Studies were made on rice glutelin that was reduced and then alkylated. Glutelin prepared by alkali extraction was purified by dissolving it in dilute sodium hydroxide and neutralizing it with hydrochloric acid. Then the precipitate was washed with a sodium chloride solution to reduce nucleic acid contamination. Starch-gel electrophoresis showed that this treatment removed the faster and slower bands of the glutelin (Fig. 5). Although the purification reduced the solubility of glutelin in dilute alkali, it also reduced its carbohydrate content from 6.0 to 2.8 percent. Gel filtration of rice glutelin in Sepharose 4B using 0.5 M sodium chloride with a 0.01 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 3 M urea as eluant showed that its molecular weight is 6×10^5 .

Reduction of precipitated glutelin with β -mercaptoethanol and alkylation with acrylonitrile resulted in a new fraction when filtered through Sephadex G-200 gel. The fraction had a molecular weight of 6×10^5 .⁴ The electrophoretic mobility of the modified glutelin was similar to that of the original glutelin, but had only two bands. In contrast, the reduction of globulin slowed down its rate of electrophoretic mobility to one similar to that of albumin.

Immunodiffusion by the double diffusion technique of Ouchterlony was performed on these fractions using immunosera derived from rabbits injected with rice protein (prepared by Dr. Robert Djurtoft, Technical University of Denmark). Glutelin gave at least five precipitin lines, reduced and alkylated glutelin gave two, albumin gave four, and globulin gave two. The two precipitin arcs of reduced alkylated glutelin were identical to those of globulin and reduced globulin. This similarity in antigenic properties is added evidence that glutelin has some protein subunits similar to globulin. In fact, these two fractions have similar aminograms.

A wheat protein extractant consisting of

phenol, acetic acid, and water (2:1:1 w/v/v) only extracted 76 percent of milled rice protein indicating that it is less efficient than dilute alkali for dissolving rice glutelin.

Protein metabolism

Relatively little work has been done on protein metabolism in plants. Chemists have shown that varietal differences exist in grain protein content of rice. The protein is stored in bodies 1 to 3μ in size in the rice endosperm. Knowledge of the biochemical basis of this difference in grain protein would be invaluable in the study of the interaction between environment and protein content. In the developing rice grain the rate of protein synthesis far exceeds the rate of protein breakdown. Protein synthesis is affected by the level of the synthetic enzymes, by the availability of all amino acid constituents, and by the level of ribonucleic acid (RNA). RNA level is affected by the level of ribonuclease (RNase). Protein breakdown is a function of proteolytic (protease) activity.

Preliminary studies on the developing grain were done on three varieties, Peta, IR8, and A2 torzs, that had low, medium, and high protein content, respectively. Plantings were scheduled so that the varieties flowered at about the same time. Grain samples were collected at 4-day intervals from flowering to maturity (32 days), cooled at 0 C, dehulled, and analyzed. The rate of spikelet filling was most rapid up to 12 days after flowering and continued to a plateau on the twentieth day. Although the absolute amount of protein per grain increased between the fourth and sixteenth day, the actual protein percentage decreased in the dehulled grain because starch accumulated faster. The protein content of IR8 and Peta was similar—10.4 and 10.5 percent, dry basis—while A2 torzs had 12.1 percent. The A2 torzs grain had a maximum free amino nitrogen level 1.5 times that of IR8 and 1.9 times that of Peta. Its maximum protease activity was 1.7 times that of IR8 and 1.9 times that of Peta. The maximum RNase levels in the three varieties were similar.

Because of the differences in yield and plant type among A2 torzs, Peta, and IR8, three pairs

Fig. 6. Changes in protein content and in factors related to protein metabolism in the developing F_3 rice grain of two lines from IR8 x Rikuto Norin 20 differing in protein content: IR1100-12-12 (11.7% protein) and IR1100-128-1 (8.6% protein).

of F_4 plant lines (from crosses involving IR8 and high-protein varieties) differing in protein content were used to verify the results. Of the three pairs selected, the members of the pair from IR8 x Rikuto Norin 20 had the same growth duration, grain weight, and yield: IR1100-12-12 (11.7% protein) and IR1100-128-1 (8.6% protein). IR1100-12-12 had a higher level of soluble amino nitrogen and a faster rate of protein synthesis, as measured by the ability of the grain to incorporate radioactive leucine into its protein (Fig. 6). Protease activity could be detected in the grain only after activation with cystine. The two lines had similar maximum RNA content and RNase activity, but IR1100-12-12 tended to have a higher RNA level than IR1100-128-1.

The combined data for the three pairs of lines also showed that a high protein content in the mature grain was related to a faster rate of incorporation of radioactive leucine and a higher maximum level of free amino nitrogen in the developing grain. The maximum RNA level tended to be associated with high protein content but no relationship was evident for the hydrolytic enzymes, RNase and protease.

These results indicate that a high-protein grain has a higher level of free amino acids and a greater inherent capacity to incorporate them into protein than a low-protein grain. Our present experiments seek to determine, by manipulation of the nitrogen supply during grain development, whether the inherent capacity to synthesize protein depends on the level of free amino acids in the grain. If such a relationship exists, differences in grain protein may be mainly due to varietal differences in how efficiently roots absorb nitrogen from the soil, as reflected by the level of free amino nitrogen translocated into the grain. The sap that goes to the panicle is being quantitatively analyzed to determine whether the levels of the individual free amino acids in low- and high-protein lines differ during the development of the grain.

Starch biosynthesis

The enzymic basis of amylose formation and integrity, and the genetic control of amylose level in the starch granule are not well under-

stood. Ideal samples for the study of starch biosynthesis are isogenic lines that differ only in amylose content. Such lines recently became available from the Varietal Improvement Department.

The major enzymes involved in starch metabolism are α -amylase, β -amylase, Q-enzyme (branching enzyme), phosphorylase (P-enzyme), R-enzyme (debranching enzyme), and starch synthetases. The action of α -amylase is random and the products include dextrans, maltose, and glucose. However, β -amylase hydrolyzes starch stepwise to maltose, exclusively. Q-enzyme converts amylose to amylopectin, while R-enzyme hydrolyzes amylopectin at the branch points into linear fractions. Phosphorylase reacts reversibly on starch. Stepwise phosphorolysis in the presence of inorganic phosphate produces glucose-1-phosphate; whereas synthesis involving a primer substrate and glucose-1-phosphate produces amylose and inorganic phosphate. Although phosphorylase was considered the major pathway of starch synthesis, recent work has shown that an alternate pathway exists. This pathway is essentially irreversible and involves adenosine and uridine diphosphate glucose as substrates. The enzymes involved are starch synthetases. These enzymes are reported to be mainly bound to the starch granule in nonwaxy rice, but they exist in a soluble form in the endosperm of waxy rice.

A survey of these enzymes and the levels of soluble sugars and starches was made in developing rice grains (variety IR8) to verify previous results showing that optimum enzyme levels occur during the milky stage of grain development. Quantitative assays for these enzymes have improved in recent years.

Protein was extracted by appropriate buffers from dehulled grain and precipitated by adding ammonium sulfate. The precipitate was re-dissolved and dialyzed at 4 C prior to the assay. The levels of α -amylase and R-enzyme were colorimetrically assayed at 540 $m\mu$ with amylopectin β -limit dextrin as the substrate. The activity was expressed as iodine-dextrin color units. The assay for β -amylase measured the amount of liberated reducing sugars as maltose. A correction was made for the partial hydrolysis of maltose into glucose by maltase by determin-

Fig. 7. The level and amylose content (blue value) of starch increased in the developing IR8 rice grain, but the content of soluble sugars and extractable protein decreased.

ing the glucose concentration with glucose oxidase. Phosphorylase was assayed by the inorganic phosphate liberated from glucose-1-phosphate in the presence of an amylopectin primer. Q-enzyme was assayed colorimetrically by the decrease in absorbance of an amylose solution at 660 $m\mu$. The activity of starch synthetase was measured by the incorporation of radioactive glucose from radioactive adenosine diphosphate glucose into the starch.

The results showed that starch synthesis was very rapid from 7 to 14 days after flowering (Fig. 7). This period coincided with the time of maximum soluble protein concentration (Lowry method) and the time of the slight reduction of soluble sugars in the developing rice grain. Amylose content of the starch, as indexed by

Fig. 8. Maximum activity of phosphorylase, Q-enzyme, and R-enzyme preceded the peak activity of α -amylase, but activity of starch synthetase bound to the starch granule increased with starch content in the developing IR8 rice grain.

blue value at $680 \text{ m}\mu$, increased during this period. That agrees with previous results on the same variety.

Among the six enzymes surveyed, the levels of phosphorylase, Q-enzyme, and R-enzyme paral-

leled that of soluble protein. The maximum concentration of the enzymes was close to the tenth day after flowering (Fig. 8). The hydrolytic enzymes, α -amylase and β -amylase, had their activities at later stages, but they both decreased in activity as the grain matured. The starch synthetase bound to the starch granule, however, increased with the starch content of the grain up to the twenty-first day after flowering. In contrast, the soluble synthetase activity decreased with increasing starch content and increasing amylose content of starch during maturation. The soluble fraction constituted 17 percent of total synthetase activity in the 7-day grain, 3 percent in the 14-day grain, and 2 percent in the 21-day grain. The specific activity (per mg starch) of the synthetase bound to the starch granule was higher in the 21-day grain. As a result of these studies, 8- to 10-day grain was used in subsequent studies on starch metabolism.

Two crops of isogenic lines were planted in pots at 1-month intervals and grown to maturity. Panicles were tagged at flowering and harvested at the midmilky stage (8, 9, or 10 days after flowering). The analysis showed almost the same levels of α -amylase, phosphorylase, and Q-enzyme for both waxy and nonwaxy IR253 lines. However, the activity of β -amylase, maltase, and R-enzyme was lower in nonwaxy rice than in waxy rice grain. The only synthetic enzyme activity in which the samples differed was that of starch synthetase. The waxy rice grain had a higher level of the soluble synthetase but a very low level of the synthetase bound to the starch granule (Table 8). These results agree with those of other biochemists working with different rice varieties.

Similar results were obtained with three pairs of lines with low and high amylose contents (Table 8). The pairs differed consistently only in the level of synthetase bound to the starch granule of the six enzymes assayed at the mid-milky stage. The low-amylose sample had a lower level of this enzyme than its high-amylose counterpart.

The combined data for the two sets of samples ($n = 10$) showed that amylose content was positively correlated with the activity of the synthetase bound to the starch granule of the grain and negatively correlated with percentage

Table 8. Activity of starch synthetase bound to the starch granule of the rice grain at the milky stage of lines differing in amylose content.

Lines	Amylose (% of starch)	Starch synthetase ^a (μg glucose $15 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ grain}^{-1}$)		Soluble enzyme (% of total)
		Soluble	Bound to the starch granule	
IR 253 lines				
Waxy ^b	0	1.7	0.6	73
Nonwaxy ^b	32	0.73	15.3	4
Low- vs. high-amylose lines				
IR450-3-3-1-2-1	18.9	1.5	3.6	29
IR450-3-1-1	34.4	1.8	17.0	10
IR478-26-2-2	18.4	0.9	3.3	22
IR478-43-2	31.4	1.2	6.2	16
IR583-40-2-1	15.7	1.0	4.1	20
IR583-10-1-1	30.4	1.3	17.2	7

^a Mean of duplicate analyses of two crops.

^b Mean of two lines.

of soluble synthetase. The amylose content and activity of soluble synthetase were not correlated.

The linear relationship between amylose content and the level of synthetase bound to the starch granule of the developing rice grain indicates that this enzyme is involved in the integrity of amylose in the starch granules. Under these conditions, the levels of the other enzymes involved in the starch metabolism are the same. This enzyme may be involved in the *in vivo* synthesis of amylose and in keeping Q-enzyme from converting to amylopectin by forming an insoluble amylose-enzyme complex.

Polyacrylamide-gel (8%) electrophoresis of the extracts and incubation of the zymogram with starch as the substrate revealed all the enzymes except soluble starch synthetase (Fig. 9). All the bands of the zymogram were identified by standard methods. The extracts showed one Q-enzyme band, three phosphorylase bands, two β -amylase band, two R-enzyme bands, and two

Fig. 9. Schematic zymogram (in 8% polyacrylamide gel containing 0.06% amylopectin) of Q-enzyme, phosphorylase (P), α - and β -amylases (A), and R-enzyme in the developing IR8 rice grain in three incubation media.

α -amylase bands. No change in the zymogram pattern of IR8 was noted during grain development. In a blue-purple, amylopectin-iodine background, the Q-enzyme band was brownish in color, the phosphorylase and α -amylase bands were light blue to white, the β -amylase bands were pink and the R-enzyme bands were deep blue. The α -amylase bands were very faint and could be seen clearly only when amylopectin was used as the substrate. The slower phosphorylase bands were not very distinct in some of the lines tested. The α -amylases in the developing grain had a slower electrophoretic mobility than those of germinating rice.

Plant Pathology

Studies were made on the pathogenic variability of the blast fungus, *Pyricularia oryzae*, and on the horizontal resistance of plants to it. The studies seem to show that because the fungus is so variable, its pathogenicity has a built-in weakness. That is, many of the new races produced by isolates of the fungus cannot infect the resistant varieties from which they were isolated. Thus it appears that varieties that have a broad spectrum of resistance can remain more or less stable in resistance even though new races of blast develop.

Several systemic fungicides for combating blast have been tested at the Institute and in farmers' fields. Compound 1991, now called Benlate, seems to be most effective and can be applied in several ways. Applying Benlate to soil protects rice plants from blast throughout the season. Foliar spraying in two applications also gives very good control of neck blast. Seed treatment protects seedlings through the nursery stage.

In studying the causal organism of bacterial leaf blight it was found that colonies of the same strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* vary in virulence. The virulence of strains may be built up by repeated selection of virulent daughter colonies or it may be reduced by repeated selection of weak colonies. These findings provide some basic knowledge about variation in virulence among strains.

Several studies relating to tungro disease were carried on during the year: Testing rice varieties and selections for resistance to the disease, investigating the differences between damage caused by the insect vector and damage caused by the virus itself, purifying the virus, and determining the adaptability of the progeny of *Nephotettix impicticeps* to Pankhari 203 (a variety resistant to the insect).

Research on grassy stunt disease showed that most *Oryza* species and rice varieties were susceptible, although the older the plants were at the time of inoculation, the less susceptible they were. One rice variety, Shan-san-sa-san, showed a striping symptom when infected. This variety could be used as a differential host of the disease. In addition, one line of *O. nivara* was found to have great resistance to the disease. But it was not highly resistant to the vector, *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Blast disease

Studies on varietal resistance

Pathogenicity of new races developed from single-spore cultures. Earlier studies (1967 and 1968 Annual Report) showed that conidia from single lesions, single conidial cultures, and single-cell cultures differ in their pathogenicity to the differential varieties and thus these monoconidial cultures were classified into many new races. Further studies on three isolates, FR-1, FR-13, and FR-78 confirmed the earlier findings.

The 97 conidia from isolate FR-1 were differentiated into 20 races; the 80 conidia of FR-13 into 30 races; and the 49 conidia of FR-78 into six races (Table 1).

The degree of variability in the isolates so far studied varies. A few are fairly stable, such as L-2-36 and L-4; most others are very variable.

The pathogenicity of the new races derived from most of the isolates, as indicated by the number of the differential varieties infected, varied from those which infect only one or two varieties to some which infect 11 or all 12 dif-

Table 1. Pathogenic races derived from single lesions (L-1 to L-5) and single conidia (L-1-43, L-1-49, L-2-36, L-2-42, FR-1, FR-13, FR-78) and their pathogenicity to the Philippine differential varieties.

Number of differential varieties infected	Philip. race designation	Number of monoconidial subcultures of each race developed from various cultures											
		L-1	L-2	L-3	L-4	L-5	L-1-43	L-1-49	L-2-36	L-2-42	FR-1	FR-13	FR-78
1	26	4											
2	25										1	1	
	38	1		1								1	
3	58	3				1							
	15			1								15	
	57	13		1				2	2			1	
	76							1					
4	128												1
	16	12		36				4	9		1	2	
	18											8	
	35											2	
	63		1										
	73	1							1				
	77								1				
	79								1				
	80						1				1		
	125											5	
	130											1	
	133											1	
	5	19										1	8
30		8		3				4	7			4	
32											1		
47								1	2				
56		4		1								1	
59		1											
64			2									1	
69		1											
70		1						3					
82										1			
91						1							
6	129											2	
	141										1		
	148											1	
	17			3				2			1	1	
	36		2								1		
	54	1										2	
	55	4										1	
	62		2					1			2	1	
	78								1				
	81							1			1		
7	102											2	
	134											1	
	8		24	1	34			6		25	18	37	2

continued

Table 1 continued

Number of differential varieties infected	Philip. race designation	Number of monoconidial subcultures of each race developed from various cultures											
		L-1	L-2	L-3	L-4	L-5	L-1-43	L-1-49	L-2-36	L-2-42	FR-1	FR-13	FR-78
	28			2									2
	66												1
	71		1										
	83			1									
	86					1							
	115					1							
	116					1							
	126											7	
8	6		1										
	12		11		5					4	25		
	52	2								3	3		
	111					1							
	113					4							
	118									1			
	131												2
	132										1		
	138									2			
	147										1		
9	50									12			
	90					4							
	112					4							4
	114					1							
	120												1
	142									2			
	149									1			
10	92					3							40
11	87									2			1
	89					2							1
	143									1			
12	150									2			
No. of races		14	8	10	2	12	10	9	1	4	20	30	6
No. of subcultures		56	44	50	39	24	25	25	25	25	97	80	49

ferential varieties. For example, of the 20 races derived from FR-1, one race infected only two varieties, two races infected four varieties, three races infected five varieties, three races infected six varieties, one race infected seven varieties, four races infected eight varieties, three races infected nine varieties, two races infected 11 varieties, and one race infected all 12 varieties. New races from other cultures similarly infected a variable number of varieties (Table 1). It seems that the new races with different pathogenicities are produced randomly: some are more pathogenic, others are less; some gain pathogenicity, and some lose it.

The number of single conidial subcultures of each isolate in this study was very small in comparison with the number of conidia produced on a lesion or in a culture. The conidia tested in the study were selected completely by chance. If more conidia are tested for pathogenicity, most

isolates would produce large numbers, if not all races known to us. It is also conceivable that large numbers of races are present in a culture or in a field.

The tendency of most isolates to produce many races with variable pathogenicity has an important bearing on the stability of resistance in some varieties.

Pathogenicity of isolates from resistant varieties to their original hosts. Several experiments were conducted to investigate whether the resistance of plants with few leaf lesions could be a type of horizontal resistance.

From the blast nursery, 78 isolates of *Pyricularia oryzae* were obtained from 76 varieties (two from the same varieties at different times) that showed few leaf lesions. They were inoculated back to the original host varieties and to a susceptible control variety, Khao Tah Haeng 17 (KTH). Some of the results are shown in Figure

Table 2. Lesion development of isolates and reisolates of *P. oryzae* from variety Tetep inoculated on Tetep and Khao Tah Haeng 17.

Isolate and reisolate	Lesions/seedling*	
	Tetep	KTH
FR-1	0.7	70.1
FR-4A10	14.7	54.2
FR-13-1a	1.4	47.2
FR-28	0.2	41.6
FR-30A2	1.6	20.7
-30A3	2.9	26.7
-30A5	13.3	45.0
-30A6	3.9	44.2
-30A7	9.3	63.7
-30A8	1.1	64.6
-30A42	1.9	19.8
-30A43	2.2	12.8
-30A44	1.6	17.0
-30A45	1.4	16.1
-30-1a	1.7	41.2
-30B1	3.3	14.8
-30B2	2.3	32.1
-30B3	0	16.3
FR-31	0.2	41.6
FR-35-1b	3.0	50.6
FR-50-1b	4.3	37.6
FR-52-1b	0	32.3
FR-54-1b	2.5	23.1
FR-56A2	3.6	16.3
-56A9	5.7	16.3
FR-57	2.2	36.4
-571b	1.0	23.1
FR-59A1	12.0	34.8
-591b	1.3	23.7
FR-78	2.4	33.3
-78A4(1)	16.2	36.4
-78A4(2)	4.6	20.3
-78-1a	5.8	24.8
-78-1b	2.8	14.1
Average	3.9	33.3

* Average of 20 plants.

1. A few isolates produced as many lesions on their host varieties as they did on KTH; for example, FR-2 on variety 221/BCIV/1/178/6. But most isolates produced fewer lesions on their host varieties than they did on KTH.

In another experiment, 34 cultures isolated from Tetep (one of the most resistant varieties as screened by the international uniform blast nurseries) were inoculated back to Tetep. The results of the inoculation are shown in Table 2. Again, the numbers of lesions produced on the original host, Tetep, by each inoculation of the reisolates were much smaller than the numbers on KTH which was inoculated at the same time.

These experiments seem to indicate that many varieties have a type of horizontal resistance in various degrees since even when numerous conidia are inoculated back to the original varieties only a small number of lesions are produced.

Disease development on resistant varieties in blast nurseries. Two series of experiments were made to observe the rate of disease development on some of the most resistant and susceptible varieties in the blast nursery. Ten rows of resistant varieties and 10 of susceptible varieties were planted alternately, 10-cm apart. The number of lesions that developed on 100 seedling samples was counted every other day starting when a few lesions began to appear.

In one series of experiments, we measured the rate of development from natural infection in the blast nursery. The rate of lesion development on resistant varieties was much slower than on the susceptible check (Fig. 2). The results of other experiments were very similar.

In the second series, the resistant varieties were inoculated with cultures which were isolated from the varieties about 2 weeks after sowing when virtually no lesions from natural infection were observed. One representative experiment is shown in Figure 3. The results of several experiments are similar to those of the natural infection experiments.

These observations indicated that the rate of disease development on resistant varieties is slower; and that the higher the degree of resistance is, the slower the rate of development. The slow development was not due to the late appearance of the pathogenic races, since lesions were observed quite early on these resistant varieties, particularly when they were artificially inoculated. These observations seem to substantiate the findings that many isolates produce only a few lesions on their original resistant host varieties, which indicates the presence of a type of horizontal resistance.

Pathogenicity of single conidial subcultures of isolates from a resistant variety. The preceding experiments have shown that the fungus produces many races as it multiplies, and that cultures isolated from a resistant variety do not cause many lesions when inoculated back to the same variety. This led to the suspicion that many of the new races produced may not infect the original host. To examine this idea, 100 single conidial subcultures of isolate FR-1 and 45 subcultures of FR-78, both isolated from Tetep, were inoculated to Tetep, and to KTH as a control. Likewise, 85 subcultures of isolate

Fig. 1. Reaction (average number of lesions per seedling) of resistant host varieties when each variety is inoculated with a culture originally isolated from itself. Khao Tah Haeng 17 is a susceptible control.

Fig. 2. Development of blast (number of lesions per 100 seedlings) on resistant varieties and on neighboring susceptible check variety Tjeremas (TM) in blast nursery.

Fig. 3. Development of blast (number of lesions per 100 seedlings) on resistant varieties and on neighboring susceptible variety Tjeremas (TM) inoculated with isolates from resistant varieties in blast nursery.

FR-13, which was isolated from Carreon but which also infects Tetep, were inoculated back to Tetep, Carreon, and KTH. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Among the 100 subcultures of FR-1, 83 did not infect Tetep, the original host. The others produced small numbers of lesions, but much fewer than on KTH. Among the 45 subcultures of FR-78, only one failed to infect Tetep. Most produced less than five lesions per plant; only five subcultures produced more than 20 lesions. Of the 85 subcultures of FR-13, 80 produced no lesions on Carreon, the original host, and 67 produced none on Tetep. The rest produced only a few lesions.

These inoculation experiments provide some evidence that conidia produced have different pathogenicities. The number of conidia that

cannot infect the original varieties from which they were isolated varies from a few to many. This offers an explanation of why only relatively few lesions were produced on the resistant varieties in the preceding experiments.

Our studies suggest a hypothesis about varietal resistance to blast. Since the blast fungus is changing all the time, new races or pathogenic types are produced as the fungus multiplies. Varieties with a broad spectrum of resistance may retain a degree of stability because many new races cannot cause any infection. In other words, pathogenic races may fail to build up on a variety because the fungus has a built-in weakness for pathogenicity towards these resistant varieties. Over a wide geographical area or a long period of time, a resistant variety may maintain its degree of resistance.

Table 3. Pathogenicity of single conidial subculture of isolates FR-1, FR-78, (both from Tetep) and FR-13 (from Carreon, but which also infects Tetep) on Tetep, Carreon, and Khao Tah Haeng 17.

Lesions/seedling*	Number of subcultures						
	FR-1		FR-13			FR-78	
	On Tetep	On KTH	On Tetep	On Carreon	On KTH	On Tetep	On KTH
None	83	1	67	80		1	0
Less than 1	4	0	10	2		5	0
Less than 5	12	9	6	2	1	15	1
Less than 10	1	14	2	1	4	11	7
Less than 20	0	34	1	0	13	8	10
More than 20	0	31	0	0	42	5	24
More than 50	0	11	0	0	25	0	3
Total		100			85		45

* Average of 20 seedlings.

For a particular season or locality, however, infection depends upon the pathogenicity of the prevailing races. The populations of each new race that develops are not the same; a new race (or races) may make up a large portion of the total population of races in a season or in a locality (Table 1). If the variety is susceptible to this race, severe damage may occur even if it is resistant to all other races.

Moderately resistant varieties therefore are not expected to be stable. Theoretically, if a variety is resistant to 95 percent of the existing races, it is relatively safe from infection not only because just a few races can infect the variety, but also because it has a much better chance of avoiding the pathogenic races with high populations. If a variety is resistant to just 50 percent of the races, not only would any of the other 50 percent of races infect the variety but also there is a one-to-one chance that the variety will be infected by a race (or races) of high population. A susceptible variety that is, say, resistant to only 5 percent of the races would inevitably be damaged. The hypothesis will be tested by further experiments.

New pathogenic races in the Philippines. Thirty-two new Philippine races and seven international race groups were identified in 1969. Altogether, 150 races have been separated by Philippine differential varieties and 67 race groups by the international set of differential varieties. The reactions of the new Philippine races are shown in Table 4. The seven new international race groups are IA-33, IA-37, IA-49, IA-69, IA-81, IB-46, and ID-1 according to the standardized race numbers.

Screening for varieties with intermediate reaction. Searching for horizontal resistance with type 3 lesion (intermediate reaction) continued. The 441 varieties previously selected for intermediate reaction have gone through five tests in our blast nursery. Many of the varieties became susceptible and were discarded in early tests. The number was reduced to 301 after the first test and to 265 after the second. In the third, fourth, and fifth tests, the number remained at about 200, indicating that these varieties have been exposed to most races of the blast fungus in the Los Baños area. The remaining varieties will be multiplied and tested in the international uniform blast nurseries. It appears that many of them may maintain their intermediate reaction.

The type 3 or intermediate lesions produced an estimated 50 to 250 conidia each night for about 3 to 7 days while type 4 or typical lesions produced 2,000 to 6,000 conidia each night for 7 to 14 days. Under favorable conditions, the reproduction cycle of the fungus is only 6 to 7 days. After a few generations, the conidial population in plants with type 4 lesions is much greater than those with type 3 lesions. Hence plants with type 3 lesions become much less damaged than those with type 4 lesions.

Controlling blast with systemic fungicides

Under the frequent monsoon showers of the tropics, systemic fungicides have advantages over conventional fungicides in controlling plant diseases. During the year several systemic fungicides were tried to control blast and other diseases. They were tested as soil treatments, foliar sprays, and seed treatments against both

Table 4. New pathogenic races from the Philippines based on reactions of Philippine differential varieties (• resistant; S susceptible).

Philippine differential variety	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	146	147	148	149	150				
Katakara DA-2	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S				
CI 5309	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S			
Chokoto	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S		
Co 25	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	
Wagway	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	
Pai-kan-tao	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	
Peta	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	
Raminad Str. 3	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Taichung TCWC	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Lacrosse	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Shatiao (S)	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Khao Tah Haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

leaf blast and neck blast. Because these fungicides reached us at different times, they were tested in various groups.

Soil treatment for controlling leaf blast. Five chemicals, Benlate, Kitazin, Milcurb, Polyoxin, and Thiabendazole, were tested. About 20 grams of seeds were sown in rows in trays containing about 11 liters of soil. The soil in the trays was treated with the chemicals 1 week after sowing in the greenhouse. After another week, the seedlings were placed in the blast nursery where abundant inocula are always present. We measured the degree of control by counting the number of leaf lesions once a week starting 1 week after the seedlings were exposed to the blast nursery. The soil was flooded during the tests.

Several experiments were conducted. Benlate was found to control the blast disease best (Fig. 4). Kitazin gave fair control for a short duration, but usually by the second reading the plants were badly infected. No other chemicals tested gave good protection (Table 5). Benlate was also found to have a very long residual effect in the soil. Treated soil gave very good protection to seedlings in four successive plantings during a period of more than 160 days. Benlate is remarkable for its truly systemic action in the rice plant and the long residual effect in flooded soil.

Soil treatment for controlling neck blast. Two series of experiments were made. In one series, plants were grown in large pots and exposed to the blast nursery. In the second series, the experiments were conducted in farmers' fields where severe epidemics of the disease occurred.

In the pot experiments, chemicals were applied to about 19 liters of soil in each pot. In one experiment, the chemicals were applied at the flower initiation stage, and in another, just a week before flowering. The pots were exposed to the blast nursery a few days before flowering.

Benlate was very effective in both early and late applications. Kitazin showed fair results while Thiabendazole had no effect (Tables 6 and 7).

In the farmers' fields, microplots of 2 x 2 meters were built and each treatment was replicated four times. Three experiments were made. In two of the experiments, the chemicals were applied too late because the fields were reported

Fig. 4. Soil treatment with Benlate to control leaf blast.

Table 5. Three experiments on soil treatment with systemic fungicides for controlling leaf blast.

Chemical	Rate (g/11 liter soil)	Lesions/seedling*		
		1st reading	2nd reading	3rd reading
Experiment 1 †				
Benlate	1	0.9	4.5	
Kitazin	5	7.4	120.5	
Control		62.8	188.5	
Experiment 2 ‡				
Benlate	¼	26.3	42.4	179.3
Benlate	¼	12.6	29.9	129.7
Benlate	½	13.6	31.9	58.8
Benlate	1	0	0	2.3
Thiabendazole	¼	53.0	253.0	Dead
Thiabendazole	½	38.6	200.2	Dead
Kitazin	5	39.8	264.4	Dead
Kitazin	10	33.2	183.0	Dead
Control		60.9	291.6	Dead
Experiment 3 ‡				
Polyoxin	2	163.8	170.8	246.4
Polyoxin	4	141.9	167.0	208.6
Kitazin	5	5.1	46.9	240.7
Kitazin	10	2.1	32.9	174.0
Benlate	¼	12.6	22.8	73.8
Benlate	½	4.7	9.8	13.8
Control		92.5	156.6	271.8

* Average.
 † Four replications of 20 seedlings each.
 ‡ Two replications of 25 seedlings each.

Table 6. Soil treatment with systemic fungicides for the control of neck blast—pot experiment; soil was treated at panicle initiation stage of plants.

Chemical	Rate (g/pot)	No. of panicles*	Plants with complete neckrot (%)	Plants with partial neckrot (%)	Healthy plants (%)
Benlate	¼	159	35.2	28.9	35.9
	½	159	0.6	7.6	91.8
	1	141	0	1.4	98.6
Kitazin	2	150	12.7	24.0	63.3
	4	117	13.7	43.6	42.7
	6	134	4.5	27.6	67.9
Thiabendazole	½	160	65.6	21.3	13.1
	1	146	58.9	30.1	11.0
	2	126	50.8	23.0	26.2
Control		169	63.9	28.4	7.7

* In four pots.

Table 7. Soil treatment with systemic fungicides in controlling neck blast—pot experiment; chemicals applied 1 week before flowering.

Chemical	Rate (g/pot)	No. of panicles*	Plants with neckrot (%)	Filled grain (%)	1,000 grain weight (g)
Benlate	¼	113	39.8	83.3	25.4
	½	91	8.8	86.9	24.9
	1	103	0	80.9	25.3
Kitazin	2	107	52.3	84.2	24.9
	4	108	50.9	82.3	23.9
	6	140	42.9	68.7	23.6
Thiabendazole	½	125	92.8	77.3	22.0
	1	124	90.3	66.8	21.1
	2	111	90.1	76.8	21.8
Control		62	95.2	70.6	18.2

* In three pots.

to us after the outbreak of the disease; in the other one, the disease development was only mild. Brief data from the three experiments are presented in Table 8. The results suggest that the effectiveness of the treatment increases as the rate of application increases. The quantity of chemical required is exceedingly high and is not practical for common use.

Foliage spraying for controlling leaf blast. The experiments were carried out in the blast nursery where abundant inocula were present every day. Microplots, 1 sq m in size, were used for each treatment. One-half liter of the chemicals was sprayed on each plot with an electric sprayer. The plot was guarded on four sides when spraying. In one experiment, a second spraying was done 1 week after the first. The degree of control was estimated by counting the numbers of lesions that developed on samples of 100 seedlings at different dates. Readings were made 1 week after spraying and weekly thereafter.

The results generally show that at the recommended dosage of each chemical, none of the chemicals gave very effective control. About 50 to 90 lesions were counted on each seedling at the first reading, and 230 to 240 lesions at the second reading. In experiments where very high dosages of the chemicals were used, the fungicides gave good protection for the first week (first reading). But they were not very effective by the end of the second week. When two sprayings were made, fair protection was observed at the end of the second week, but not in the third week.

Under very infectious conditions, such as those in the blast nursery, weekly spraying seems to be necessary to protect seedlings from which young leaves emerge every 5 to 6 days. Among the five chemicals, Benlate was somewhat better than Blasticidin-S or Kasumin. The others were not effective.

Foliage spraying with Benlate and Kasumin for controlling neck blast. Experiments were con-

Table 8. Soil treatment with Benlate for controlling neck blast in farmers' fields at two locations in the Philippines.

Benlate rate (g/sq m)	Expt. 1 (Sariaya)		Expt. 2 (Sariaya)		Expt. 3 (Candelaria)		
	Plants with neckrot (%)	Calculated yield (ton/ha)	Plants with neckrot (%)	Calculated yield (ton/ha)	Plants with neckrot (%)	Filled grain (%)	Calculated yield (ton/ha)
1	60.6	3.79	7.8	4.70	96.3	63.0	1.65
2	47.3	4.12	7.7	5.09	91.8	61.0	1.73
4	30.2	4.31	4.8	4.89	51.6	73.0	3.27
8	17.0	4.58	1.2	4.83	—	—	—
Control	68.3	3.84	21.8	4.73	98.0	55.7	1.10

ducted in farmers' fields by building 2- x 2-m microplots. Each treatment was made once at early flowering and once 1 week later and replicated three or four times. At one location the degree of control was evaluated by the percentage of neck-rot panicles and by the yield of the microplots. At another, the percentage of filled grains and the 1,000-grain weight were also measured (Table 9). In both experiments, two sprayings of Benlate at early flowering controlled neck blast very well. Kasumin had some usefulness but was much less effective.

Seed treatment with systemic fungicides for controlling seedling blast. Tests were done in trays 18 x 18 x 5 inches. Seeds treated with systemic fungicides at various rates were planted in the trays in duplicate and were flooded with water after germination. The seedlings were then exposed in the blast nursery. The degree of control was evaluated by counting the numbers of lesions that developed on 20 seedling samples. Readings were at weekly intervals starting the twentieth day after sowing (Table 10). Benlate at a high rate may protect the seedlings for about 25 days. It may do better under ordinary con-

ditions. All the other chemicals seem to be ineffective.

Uptake and movement of Benlate in rice plants. A preliminary experiment was conducted to determine how fast plants take up Benlate from the treated soil to prevent leaf lesions. Three-week-old seedlings were used. Ten milliliters of 0.1% dilution Benlate was added to 5-inch pots at different times before and after inoculation. The experiment seemed to show that by 12 hours after application the plants had taken up enough Benlate to prevent infection and perhaps also to cure infected plants somewhat (Table 11).

The movement of Benlate seems to be upward only. When sections of rice leaves were coated with Benlate, blast lesions developed immediately below the treated section while above it the leaf was completely free of lesions (Fig. 5).

Benlate and a few other systemics were not effective in controlling tungro virus and bacterial leaf blight through soil treatment. Preliminary tests seem to show, however, that young nymphs of both green leafhoppers and brown leafhoppers died before reaching the adult stage when they were hatched on plants grown on

Table 9. Foliage spraying with Benlate and Kasumin for controlling neck blast in farmers' fields at two locations in the Philippines.

Chemical	Rate (kg/ha)	Plants with neckrot (%)	Filled grain (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Calculated yield (ton/ha)
Sariaya					
Benlate	5	10.0	—	—	5.03
Benlate	10	4.8	—	—	5.11
Kasumin	2	49.7	—	—	3.95
Control		61.0	—	—	3.85
Candelaria					
Benlate	0.1	7.3	72.6	20.4	4.83
Benlate	0.2	3.3	77.0	20.8	4.97
Kasumin	2	94.4	55.0	15.5	2.60
Control		98.6	35.6	14.0	1.43

Table 10. Seed treatment with systemic fungicides for controlling seedling blast.

Chemical	Rate*	Lesions/seedling†		
		1st reading	2nd reading	3rd reading
Experiment 1				
Benlate‡	2g	41.3	Dead	
Benlate	4g	33.9	Dead	
Benlate	8g	0.3	92.0	
Thiabendazole	2g	60.7	Dead	
Thiabendazole	4g	62.7	Dead	
Thiabendazole	8g	61.7	Dead	
Control		55.4	Dead	
Experiment 2				
Benlate	16g	0	2.0	13.4
Kitazin	20g	99.4	149.3	166.1
Busan	1.0 ml	84.9	144.1	180.0
Busan	2.0 ml	73.4	96.8	158.7
Control		76.2	154.6	189.5

* Per kg of seed.
 † Average of 20 seedlings.
 ‡ Surfactant added.

Benlate-treated soils. The green leafhopper is the vector of tungro and the brown planthopper is the vector of grassy stunt.

Bacterial leaf blight

Screening varieties for resistance

Continuing the screening of the world collection maintained at IRRI, an additional 1,770 varieties were tested in the field for resistance to bacterial blight in 1968 and 1969 using a virulent strain of the bacterium, B15-37. Varieties showing resistance were subjected to a seedling test in the greenhouse. A number of resistant varieties were found. These varieties may be tested in other countries to determine whether they are also resistant to other strains of the leaf blight

organism. The most resistant varieties are listed in Table 12.

Variation in virulence among colonies of single strains

Variation in virulence among daughter colonies of single strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* was further studied. Strain B15, a virulent strain, and B23, a weak strain, were used. One hundred single-colony subcultures from each strain were isolated, cultured, and inoculated separately by needle to Zenith, a resistant variety, and JC-70, a susceptible variety. For each subculture 10 seedlings of each variety were inoculated. The reactions were rated 20 days after inoculation on a scale of 0 to 9.

The 100 subcultures from each strain varied in their pathogenicity. Their distribution among the various disease scales was more or less in normal curves. One very virulent and one very weak subculture was selected, and 100 single-colony subcultures were isolated from each of them, cultured, and inoculated to Zenith and JC-70. The process of selection toward more virulent and less virulent subcultures was continued for three or four generations.

Altogether, 1,000 subcultures have been inoculated to 20,000 seedlings. The results are summarized in Tables 13 and 14 and Figures 6 and 7. From B15, the subculture B15-37 is more virulent than the original and a further selection, B15-37-109, seems to be even more pathogenic to both Zenith and JC-70. The subculture

Table 11. Rate of uptake of Benlate by rice seedlings to prevent leaf infection.

Application time (hours before inoculation*)	Total lesions	Lesions/seedling
30	0	0
24	0	0
12	0	0
8	8	1.5
4	7	0.5
3	41	3.4
2	27	2.1
1	80	6.1
0	34	2.6
-24	62	6.8
-48	95	5.0
Check	146	8.1

* Minus sign indicates after inoculation.

Table 12. List of varieties resistant to bacterial leaf blight in the Philippines.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.
H59, PI 245704-2	10400
Taihoku-iku 73	10471
Tainan No. 7	10475
Tainan-iku 504	10480
Takao No. 20	10489
Takao No. 25	10492
Takao-iku No. 12	10501
Takao-iku No. 39	10506
Takao-iku No. 49	10513
Takao-iku No. 55	10519
CI 8920-4	10659
Boa Vista	10741
Secano do Brazil	10745
H59-50	10852
H30-9	10854
Fukei 71	10904
Vary Lava 4	10957
Vary Vato 277	10993
Royofotsy 743	10999
Vary Lava 701	11024

B15-37-109 caused complete killing (kressek) of variety JC-70. Among the less virulent colonies, B15-1 is less pathogenic than B15 on both varieties, but a further selection, B15-1-99, did not seem to show a further decline in virulence. Similarly, when strongly virulent colonies of strain B23 were selected, subcultures tended to become more virulent. But when weakly virulent colonies were selected the tendency to become less virulent was not significant.

These inoculation experiments were conducted from September 1968 to July 1969. During the warm months (March to April), the lesions on the inoculated plants tended to be larger than those developed during the rest of the year. This may partly explain why B15-1-99 and B23-56 produced slightly larger lesions than expected. However, since the monthly average temperature during the year is about 24 to 28 C, the temperature difference would affect the disease scale only slightly.

The study demonstrates not only the difference in pathogenicity among colonies of single strains, but also the danger of isolating a single colony of the organism from diseased tissues and calling it representative of the specimen.

An isolation experiment was made to illustrate this point. A diseased leaf tissue was crushed in a water suspension and 100 colonies were picked up. These 100 colonies were inoculated separately on variety Zenith. The patho-

Fig. 5. Movement of Benlate in rice leaves. The first leaf (at left) was untreated, lesions developed throughout the leaf; the fourth and fifth leaves were treated at the upper portion, lesions developed immediately below the treated area, indicating no downward movement; the second and third leaves at the middle were treated at the lower portion, almost no lesions at the upper portion, indicating upward movement.

genicity range of the 100 colonies on Zenith varied from 3 to 9; most had a reaction of 7 (Fig. 8). Thus, single colonies with either very high or very low pathogenicity if picked up during isolation do not represent the specimen.

Retention of tolerance to streptomycin

By repeated selection of colonies which tolerate increasing concentrations of streptomycin in the media, several strains of *X. oryzae* were obtained in earlier experiments. In 1969, we attempted to find out whether streptomycin-resistant strains lose their resistance after growing in ordinary media for various lengths of time.

Three strains, B29-S200, B29-S400, and B29-

Fig. 6. Variation in pathogenicity among single-colony subcultures of strain B15 (*Xanthomonas oryzae*).

Fig. 7. Variation in pathogenicity among single-colony subcultures of strain B23 (*Xanthomonas oryzae*).

S4000, resistant to 200, 400, and 4,000 ppm streptomycin, respectively, were selected. Each was transferred as soon as good growth had appeared. Each transfer was considered as one generation. After each strain had 40 generations (F40) in an ordinary medium, a new transfer was made from the F10, F20, F30, and F40 of each and it was tested against the level of strepto-

mycin to which the original resistant strain was tolerant. The actual testing generations were therefore F11, F21, F31, and F41. The original strain, B29, which has no tolerance to streptomycin, was also included as a control.

All three strains retained their resistance to specific levels of streptomycin up to 41 generations, the maximum number of generations

Table 13. Variation in pathogenicity among single-colony subcultures of strain B15 (*Xanthomonas oryzae*).

Bacterial strain and inoculation date	Test variety	Distribution of single-colony subcultures (%)										
		Disease scale*										
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
B15 (Sept. 14, '68)	Zenith	9	13	7	48	21	2					
	JC-70				4	11	6	15	9	7	48	
B15-37 (Jan. 8, '69)	Zenith				4	24	28	27	12	5		
	JC-70									3	97	
B15-37-109 (Apr. 18, '69)	Zenith			3	11	19	17	21	26	3		
	JC-70										100	
B15-1 (Mar. 3, '69)	Zenith	2	8	67	23							
	JC-70	1	1	1	17	43	30	7				
B15-1-99 (Mar. 24, '69)	Zenith		10	38	52							
	JC-70					38	45	17				

*0 = no lesions; 1 = most resistant; 9 = most susceptible.

tested in the experiment. The original strain, B29, did not show any sign of growth. It appears that the streptomycin-resistant strains do not lose their resistance quickly.

Effect of temperature on viability of bacterial cells and bacteriophages

Bacterial cells of *X. oryzae* and phage Bp X, to which the bacterial strain is sensitive, were suspended in water separately and were subjected to different temperatures from 24 to 36 C. Tests for survival were made every 3 days. The results (Fig. 9) show that the phages live much longer than the bacterial cells. For example, at 36 C the cells lived for only 3 days while the phage lived for 45 days; at 28 and 24 C, the cells died in 33 and 57 days while the phage still was alive after 130 days.

The presence of a bacteriophage has been used in many ecological studies as an indicator for the presence of the bacterium. Our experiment shows, however, that the presence of phage does not necessarily mean the presence of the bacterium. The longevity of the bacterial cells as well as the phage particles may vary when they are suspended in different media.

Tungro disease

Varietal resistance to tungro disease

Testing and selecting rice varieties for their reaction to tungro disease was continued. Seedlings, 11 to 13 days old, were tested by mass screening. A total of 2,395 entries, consisting of 97 varieties, 1,770 selections of IRRI crosses,

Fig. 8. Pathogenicity of single-colony isolates from a single naturally infected leaf lesion on variety Zenith.

191 entries of genetical materials, and 337 entries of duplicates, were tested in 1969.

Most varieties were susceptible. However, about 17 percent of the selections of IRRI crosses were resistant (Table 15). The cross, IR822 (IR8/2 x Pankhari 203), had the highest number of selections in the resistant group—151 out of 250 tested selections.

Resistance to vector versus resistance to virus

The resistance of a rice variety to the tungro virus is not always correlated with its resistance to the insect vector. Preliminary results from experiments this year indicated that the life span of the adult green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, on IR8 seedlings was shorter than on Pehkahok Kimkan seedlings. The percentage of IR8 seedlings with tungro, however, was much higher than the percentage of Pehkahok Kimkan seedlings infected. In other words, IR8 is more resistant to the insect, but more susceptible to the virus than Pehkahok Kimkan.

Table 14. Variation in pathogenicity among single-colony subcultures of strain B23 (*Xanthomonas oryzae*).

Bacterial strain and inoculation date	Test variety	Distribution of single-colony subcultures (%)										
		Disease scale*										
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
B23 (Jan. 5, '69)	Zenith	3	12	41	43	1						
	JC-70		4	5	13	17	23	18	11	7	2	
B23-13 (Mar. 27, '69)	Zenith		1	8	68	20	3					
	JC-70								2	98		
B23-13-10 (Apr. 30, '69)	Zenith		3	13	72	12						
	JC-70							16	15	20	49	
B23-13-10-33 (July 16, '69)	Zenith			3	44	46	6	1				
	JC-70					1	1	5	12	16	65	
B23-56 (Mar. 12, '69)	Zenith	3	3	15	62	12	3	2				
	JC-70						8	28	40	20	4	

*0 = no lesions; 1 = most resistant; 9 = most susceptible.

Insect damage versus the effect of the tungro virus

Since the tungro virus is transmitted by *N. impicticeps*, the effect of the virus on rice plants involves the damage caused by the insect (1966 Annual Report). An investigation was made to distinguish damage caused by the insect itself from damage caused by the insect plus the virus.

Virus-free and viruliferous insects were confined on seedlings of several rice varieties for different lengths of time. The plant height was measured at various intervals.

Seedling mortality. The feeding of *N. impicticeps* could kill rice seedlings even if the seedlings were of a variety resistant to the insect. The percentage of seedling mortality that occurred depended on the number of insects per seedling and the number of days the insects were allowed to feed. In general, the greater the number of

insects per seedling or the longer the feeding duration, the higher the percentage of dead seedlings. When less than 100 percent seedling mortality occurred, however, varieties, such as IR8 or Pankhari 203, that are resistant to the insect, had lower percentages of dead seedlings than varieties, such as Taichung (Native)1, that are susceptible to the insect.

Thus, the insects with the virus caused a higher percentage of dead seedlings than insects without the virus (Table 16). This shows that the virus could cause the death of seedlings. Nevertheless, except for the varieties Chinese 1 and Chinese 2, most dead seedlings caused by viruliferous insects were actually due to insect damage because the difference in the percentage of seedling mortality between virus-free and viruliferous insects was small. The mortality of IR8, especially, seemed little due to the tungro virus.

Plant growth. The effect of green leafhopper on plant growth has often been overlooked. Our results (Tables 17 and 18) indicated that the insect could retard plant growth especially just after insect feeding occurs. The damaged plants gradually recover although severely damaged plants take a longer time. The degree of retardation of plant growth was determined by the number of insects per seedling, by the number of insect feeding days, and by the susceptibility of the variety to the insect.

The growth of the rice plant was consistently retarded by infection with the tungro virus not only at the early stage of growth after the insects' feeding, but later, too. The virus retarded plant growth much more than insect damage did.

We previously found that, "Reduction in plant height was also influenced by the number of viruliferous insects used for inoculation. The effect was generally greater when more insects were used, especially if inoculation was effected at an early growth stage." (Ling, K. C. and M. K. Palomar. 1966. Studies of rice plants infected with the tungro virus at different ages. *Phil. Agr.* 50:165-177). Although that was true when the variety was susceptible to both the insect and the virus at later growth stages the plant height of a variety resistant to the insect was not reduced in proportion to the increasing number of viruliferous insects used for inoculation (Table 17) or to increasing number of inoculation days (Table

Fig. 9. Viability of *Xanthomonas oryzae* and phage Bp X in water suspension at different temperatures.

Table 15. Reactions of IRR1 crosses to tungro disease, grouped by degree of infection.

Cross no.	Parents	No. of selections showing an infection range of:		
		0-30%	31-60%	61-100%
IR 159	Basmati 370 x Taichung (N)1	3	3	3
IR 262	Peta/3 x Taichung (N)1	3	4	2
IR 400	Peta/4 x Taichung (N)1	2	2	2
IR 407	Peta/3 x Dawn	1	0	0
IR 482	Peta/5 x Taichung (N)1	2	3	0
IR 564	Peta/6 x Taichung (N)1	3	3	3
IR 580	IR8 x TKM-6	9	10	28
IR 626	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	1	11	3
IR 665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	5	10	17
IR 822	IR8/2 x Pankhari 203	151	89	10
IR 825	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x [Peta/6 x T(N)1]	79	79	9
IR 854	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x IR262-43-8-11	13	16	1
IR 977	IR8/2 x (Dawn x Pankhari 203)	6	29	10
IR 932	IR8/3 x Pankhari 203	5	14	0
IR 1364	IR262-43-8-11-2-2-2 x HR-21	10	121	86
Other 136 IRR1 crosses		13	256	639
Total (152 crosses, 1,770 selections)		307	650	813

18). Hence, a part of growth retardation of infected plants was due to the damage of the insect.

Transmission of tungro by the *N. impicticeps* nymph

Both the nymph and the adult of the green leafhopper can transmit the tungro disease. Most available experimental results, however, do not specify which instar of the nymph was used. We studied the ability of nymphs to transmit tungro immediately after hatching and after each molting. We found that after a 24-hour acquisition feeding the nymph of each of the five instars could transmit the disease. Since, on the average, the mandible of a first instar nymph measures 235 μ and the average maxilla, 280 μ, the stylet of a first instar nymph could theoretically reach the vascular bundle of the leaf blade when the insect feeds on the plant. Consequently, the positive transmission result of the first instar nymph raises the possibility that the inoculation site of the nymph and the adult may be the same.

Transmission by *N. apicalis*

As reported in the last year's annual report, *N. apicalis* is also a vector of tungro virus although its transmissible ability is less efficient than that of *N. impicticeps*. Last year's tests however, were made only on the susceptible variety Taichung (Native)1. In this year's tests none of the 276 seedlings of Pankhari 203

inoculated by individual viruliferous *N. apicalis* became infected, although 24 out of the 134 inoculated seedlings of Taichung (Native)1 became infected. In addition to confirming the ability of *N. apicalis* to transmit the virus, the results indicated that *N. apicalis* did not alter the susceptibility of rice varieties to tungro disease.

Weeds as hosts of *N. apicalis*

Three species of *Echinochloa*, *E. colonum*, *E. crusgalli*, and *E. crusgavonis*, were used to study the host range of *N. apicalis* and of the tungro virus. We found that the average life span of adult *N. apicalis* on *Echinochloa* spp. was 17.4 days, while on Taichung (Native)1 it was 9.3 days. On *Echinochloa* spp. the number of eggs deposited by a female was 49.4 and on Taichung (Native)1, 19.2. The number of progenies that reached adult stage were 30.6 on *Echinochloa* spp. and 8.3 on Taichung (Native)1. Consequently, *Echinochloa* spp. were better hosts for *N. apicalis* than Taichung (Native)1.

Table 16. Seedling mortality due to insect (*Nephotettix impicticeps*) and to insect plus tungro virus.

Variety*	Seedling mortality (%)	
	Virus-free insect	Viruliferous insect
Chinese 1	12.0	23.7
Chinese 2	12.0	26.7
IR8	18.9	20.8
Pankhari 203	19.7	28.3
Taichung (Native)1	58.0	65.1

* Among varieties, number of insects per seedling was different.

Table 17. Effect of number of insects (*Nephotettix impicticeps*) and of insects plus tungro virus on the growth of IR8 and Taichung (Native)1 seedlings.

Kind of insect	No. of insects (1-day feeding)	Average plant height (cm)			
		Before treatment	2 weeks after	4 weeks after	8 weeks after
IR8					
Control	0	16.8	54.4	78.8	91.5
Virus-free	2	16.5	53.7	77.8	86.4
	4	16.2	49.2	75.8	89.9
	8	16.6	47.2	72.6	87.3
	16	17.2	44.3	71.0	83.7
Viruliferous*	2	16.8	36.6	48.4	57.8
	4	17.1	32.6	48.2	57.1
	8	16.5	27.5	42.2	55.6
	16	17.3	24.8	34.9	48.2
Taichung (Native)1					
Control	0	14.3	53.9	85.2	87.3
Virus-free	2	14.3	47.2	79.2	88.3
	4	14.9	44.6	79.2	88.4
	8	15.5	38.1	69.5	81.2
	16	15.0	35.3	66.1	75.8
Viruliferous*	2	15.1	25.5	33.8	40.2
	4	16.0	23.4	28.3	32.4
	8	16.0	21.1	23.7	26.7
	16	16.4	18.3	21.6	25.9

* Seedlings were infected with the tungro virus after feeding.

Table 18. Effect of number of feeding days of *Nephotettix impicticeps and of insects plus tungro virus on the growth of IR8 seedlings.**

Kind of insect	No. of feeding days	Average plant height (cm)			
		Before treatment	2 weeks after	4 weeks after	8 weeks after
Control†	0	15.6	49.5	82.5	92.4
Virus-free	1	15.3	47.2	83.5	97.2
	2	15.6	43.4	77.3	93.3
	3	15.6	40.2	74.0	92.9
	4	15.0	37.9	68.5	90.9
Viruliferous‡	1	15.9	28.1	44.4	55.8
	2	15.9	25.4	43.3	55.3
	3	15.9	24.0	41.4	54.6

* Three insects per seedling.

†No insects.

‡Seedlings were infected with the tungro virus after feeding.

Two hundred seedlings of *Echinochloa* spp. were inoculated by viruliferous *N. apicalis* at 20 insects per seedling for 24 hours. None of the seedlings developed symptoms of the disease. Nor did any of the seedlings serve as a source of the virus. When insects were allowed to feed on the *Echinochloa* seedlings and then were transferred to Taichung (Native)1 seedlings, none of the latter developed the disease.

Purification of tungro virus

Extraction and clarification. After being cut into small pieces, diseased leaves were homogenized under cool conditions in different buffer solu-

tions ranging from pH 6.8 to 7.0. The homogenate was squeezed through cheesecloth, heated at 40 C for various lengths of time, and centrifuged for 10 minutes. The supernatant fluid was a yellowish clarified extract.

The degree of clarification of the extracts obtained from different treatments was determined with a spectrophotometer since the optical density of the extract at a wavelength of 540 m μ was related to the degree of visible greenness of the extract. The results indicated that the amount of green pigments remaining in the extract was primarily determined by the pH value of the homogenate before heating and by

the duration of heat treatment at 40 C.

The pH value of the homogenate was usually lower than the pH value of the buffer solution used for homogenization. The pH value of the homogenate was affected by the concentration of the buffer solution and amount of leaf tissue in the solution. When 0.01 to 0.03 M EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetate), potassium phosphate, and tris (hydroxymethyl) amino methane buffer solutions (pH 7.0) were used, the pH of the homogenates ranged from 5.5 to 6.8. The lower the pH of the homogenate, the lower the absorbance at 540 m μ was. This has been confirmed by adding HCl solution to the homogenate. The extract was free from green color. In contrast, the extract mixed with NaOH, remained green after being centrifuged.

Heating the homogenate could reduce the optical density of the extract at 540 m μ . The longer the heating, the better the clarification especially when heating went on long enough to make the green stuffs coagulate. The time required for coagulation was determined by the pH of the homogenate.

Centrifugation. The clarification extracts were centrifuged in the No. 30 rotor of a Model L Spinco Ultracentrifuge at 30,000 rpm for 2 hours. The pellets were resuspended in a buffer solution and centrifuged at 7,500 rpm for 20 minutes. Then the samples were placed on the top of density-gradient columns. The columns were made by layering, in order, 4 ml of a buffer solution containing 100 mg/ml sucrose and 7 ml each of solutions containing 200, 300, and 400 mg/ml sucrose in plastic centrifuge tubes. The tubes were allowed to stand in a cold room overnight for diffusion before use. Then the tubes were centrifuged in SW 25.1 rotor at 24,000 rpm for 2 to 3 hours. After being centrifuged, the sucrose density-gradient column was examined with a light beam shining down through it. The column often showed a narrow zone located about 3 cm below the meniscus, and immediately below a wide zone that extended to the bottom of the column (Fig. 10a). A sample of the narrow zone was removed from the column with a syringe and subjected again to the sucrose density-gradient centrifugation. A single zone was often obtained in the column (Fig. 10b).

Absorbancy. The absorbancy of the preparation

Fig. 10a. Centrifuged sucrose density-gradient column of a rice tungro virus preparation showing that the zones were not clearly separated.

Fig. 10b. Centrifuged sucrose density-gradient column of a rice tungro virus preparation from narrow zone of the first density-gradient column showing a single zone.

Fig. 11. Ultraviolet absorption spectrum of a preparation of rice tungro virus from a centrifuged density-gradient column.

of tungro virus obtained from centrifuging the density-gradient column was measured in a spectrophotometer. The absorption curve (Fig. 11) showed a peak at around 260 mμ. After the preparation was boiled for 1 hour, the absorption curve remained similar in shape except that the ratio of absorbance at 280 mμ to the absorbance at 260 mμ was slightly decreased. Consequently, it remains unclear whether the absorption curve could indicate the infectious property of the preparation since the results obtained so far from the bioassay of the preparation were negative.

Feeding green leafhopper on solution

Since tungro virus cannot be transmitted by mechanical means and the virus does not propagate in the vector, we attempted to develop a

bioassay based on insect feeding. As a first step, we tried to find a feeding solution for *N. im-picticeps*.

Several solutions such as glycine, sodium diethyldithiocarbamate, and mercapto ethanol, were used in preparing the virus to be fed to the insects. Most insects usually died within 24 hours of feeding. In other words, a primary cause of the failure of the bioassay of the virus was the mortality of the insects fed the virus preparation. Finding a solution that would give the insects a longer life span became essential because the transmission study showed that within 5 days, longer acquisition feeding periods raised the percentage of infective insects.

Sugar. The average life span of 60 adult insects of *N. im-picticeps* that fed on water through a membrane was 4.3 days. The life span was 7.6 days on a 0.25% sugar solution, 10.5 days on 0.75%, 12.5 days on 1%, 12.0 days on 3%, 10.4 days on 5%, 8.3 days on 7%, and 5.8 days on 10%. It seemed that a 1-percent sugar solution was the best for the insect.

Insects feeding on a 1-percent sugar solution did not die as fast as those fed on water (Fig. 12). Five days after feeding, the mortality of the insects on water was 78 percent while on a 1-percent sugar solution it was 27 percent. On water, the insects reached 50 percent mortality within 4 days. On the sugar solution, it took about 10 days for the insects to reach 50 percent mortality.

We also compared various buffer solutions with and without 1-percent sugar. On EDTA alone, the insect life span was 1.7 days, while on EDTA with 1-percent sugar it was 1.5 days. On a potassium phosphate buffer solution, the life span was 2.8 days without sugar and 6 days with sugar. On tris, the life span was 2.8 days without sugar, and 5.2 days with sugar. Thus addition of 1-percent sugar to all feeding solutions, except EDTA, increased the life span of the insect.

Buffer solution. At pH 7.0, the average life span of the insect on EDTA was 1.6 days; on potassium phosphate, 4.5 days; and on tris, 5.9 days. The EDTA solution may have been toxic to the insect.

The life span of the insect was determined not only by the kind of buffer, but also by its concentration (Table 19). In general, the life span of

the insect became shorter when the concentration of the buffer solution was higher than 0.02 M. None of the insects were able to survive for 24 hours on any of the three buffer solutions when the concentration was 0.16 M. Among the treatments, tris solution at a concentration of 0.01 M with addition of 1-percent sugar seemed to be the best for the insect.

pH value. The effect on the life span of *N. impicticeps* of various pH values of 0.02 M phosphate buffer solution and 0.2 M tris solution was studied. The range of pH values of the phosphate buffer was 4.75 to 9.0. From pH values of 5.5 to 7.5 this solution caused no striking difference in the life spans of the insects fed on it. However, the life spans seemed slightly longer at pH 5.5 and pH 6.0. In contrast, the life spans of the insects fed on tris solution were similar when the pH values were from 4.0 to 8.0, but the life spans of the insects seemed slightly longer when pH values were 6.0 and 7.0. Nevertheless, a pH lower than 4.0 or higher than 8.5 reduced the life span of the insect.

Adaptability of progeny of the green leafhopper to Pankhari 203

The rice variety, Pankhari 203, is resistant to tungro disease and to the disease vector, the green leafhopper. We attempted to determine whether the insect could adapt, over several generations, to Pankhari 203 if it was the only plant available to the insect, and thus change the ability of Pankhari 203 to transmit the disease.

The insects and their progeny were reared continuously on Pankhari 203 seedlings. These insects were designated the "P203 colony." Insects raised on Taichung (Native)1, a variety susceptible to both the leafhopper and the disease, were designated the "T(N)1 colony" and served as the control.

We found that insects of the T(N)1 colony died sooner on Pankhari 203 seedlings than on Taichung (Native)1 seedlings. The life span of the insects of the P203 colony on Pankhari 203 seedlings was 6.8 days for the first generation. It gradually increased to 16.0 days for the sixth generation indicating that the progeny of the insect became more and more adapted to Pankhari 203. Nevertheless, the life span of the seventh to tenth generation of the P203 colony

Fig. 12. Mortality of *Nephotettix impicticeps* fed through a membrane on water (average life span, 4.2 days) and on 1% sugar solution (average life span, 9.5 days).

Table 19. Life span of *Nephotettix impicticeps* fed on buffer solutions at pH 7.0.

Buffer	Concentration (M)	Life span (days)	
		No sugar	With 1% sugar added
EDTA	0.005	2.77	2.90
	0.01	3.17	1.77
	0.02	0.95	1.10
	0.04	0.07	0.12
Phosphate	0.005	3.47	8.57
	0.01	3.00	7.68
	0.02	3.03	4.95
	0.04	1.83	3.07
Tris	0.005	4.12	7.90
	0.01	4.55	10.44
	0.02	3.70	9.07
	0.04	2.77	4.29

was shorter on Pankhari 203 seedlings than that of insects of the T(N)1 colony on Taichung (Native)1 seedlings (Table 20).

After five generations, an average female of the P203 colony produced more progeny that

Table 20. Life span of female *Nephotettix impicticeps* of successive generations of "P203" and "T(N)1" colonies on seedlings of Pankhari 203 and Taichung (Native)1.

Generation	Life span (days)			
	P203 colony		T(N)1 colony	
	On Pankhari 203	On Taichung (Native)1	On Pankhari 203	On Taichung (Native)1
1	6.8	11.4	4.6	17.3
2	7.6	16.5	3.9	16.0
3	8.9	14.8	6.4	14.2
4	11.3	19.3	8.1	18.0
5	14.0	12.8	5.9	16.3
6	16.0	—	7.0	17.8
7	15.4	13.0	2.9	18.1
8	14.5	17.8	10.0	17.4
9	16.8	15.5	4.2	19.1
10	15.6	18.7	5.1	18.0

reached the adult stage when raised on Pankhari 203 seedlings than did the average female of the T(N)1 colony. But when raised on Taichung (Native)1 still more progeny of the P203 colony, or of the T(N)1 colony, became adults (Table 21).

The percentage of infective insects in the P203 colony and the T(N)1 colony was not distinctly different no matter whether Pankhari 203 or Taichung (Native)1 seedlings were used as test plants. In other words, Pankhari 203 remained resistant to the disease even when inoculated by insects of the P203 colony so far obtained.

Grassy stunt disease

Resistance to grassy stunt

The mass screening test for grassy stunt resistance (1968 Annual Report) was used to search for resistant rices. A total of 4,403 entries, consisting of 2,540 varieties, 824 selections from IRRI crosses, 43 entries of *Oryza* spp. other than rice, and 995 entries of duplicates were tested this year. None consistently showed less than 30 percent infection.

Eleven species of *Oryza* (Table 22), from seeds provided by the Varietal Improvement Department, were infected after inoculation. Hence, they were also the hosts of the causal agent of grassy stunt disease. But one line of *O. nivara*, identified by Shastry, showed a low percentage of infected seedlings in the repeated tests. The other three tested lines of *O. nivara* were susceptible to the disease.

Table 21. Number of insects that reached the adult stage produced by a female *Nephotettix impicticeps* of successive generations of "P203" and "T(N)1" colonies on Pankhari 203 and Taichung (Native)1 seedlings.

Generation	No. of adult insects			
	P203 colony		T(N)1 colony	
	On Pankhari 203	On Taichung (Native)1	On Pankhari 203	On Taichung (Native)1
1	13.1	48.3	18.1	79.6
2	11.8	78.0	16.0	86.0
3	19.0	64.3	14.2	90.4
4	26.4	71.6	22.0	88.1
5	38.5	55.6	12.6	106.2
6	56.1	—	15.0	112.0
7	49.8	76.9	18.3	98.3
8	51.0	63.4	21.4	88.3
9	44.2	69.0	14.0	121.3
10	56.3	72.1	16.3	106.5

The seeds harvested from the inoculated plants of the line showing a low percentage of infection were tested again by the mass screening method together with three rice varieties serving as controls. This line had a significantly lower percentage of infected seedlings than the controls. It is the most resistant line tested so far (Table 22).

Confining adult brown planthoppers, *Nilaparvata lugens*, on seedlings of *Oryza* spp. showed that none of the tested species was highly resistant to the insect (as measured by the life span of the insect). However, on the *O. nivara* line resistant to grassy stunt, insects lived longer than on Mudgo (Table 23). In other words, *O. nivara* is not as resistant as Mudgo to the brown planthopper itself, although it is more resistant than Taichung (Native)1 or Shan-sa-san.

Symptoms on Shan-sa-san

The symptoms of plants with grassy stunt are severe stunting and excessive tillering. The leaves are short, narrow, pale yellow or pale green, and erect. Often they have numerous small dark brown dots or spots of various shapes. These symptoms generally occurred on diseased Shan-sa-san except that the leaves often showed a striping symptom and the number of tillers was not excessive. The stripes appearing on the leaf blade were narrow, yellowish-white, parallel to the midrib, and located at the basal portion of the leaf blade or extended to the whole length of

the leaf blade (Fig. 13). Due to the distinct striping, the variety could serve as a differential host for grassy stunt.

Shan-san-sa-san is susceptible to grassy stunt disease (Table 23). The causal agent is carried by the brown planthopper from infected plants to healthy seedlings of the same variety or of other varieties. The transmissive ability of brown planthoppers that acquired the causal agent from Shan-san-sa-san did not differ significantly from that of the insects that acquired the causal agent from Taichung (Native)1 as measured by the percentage of infective insects, average length of incubation period, and number of disease-transmitting days.

Although the symptoms of grassy stunt on Shan-san-sa-san were somewhat similar to rice dwarf disease, none of 114 tested insects of *N. apicalis* and *Recilia dorsalis* transmitted the disease after acquisition feeding on infected plants of Shan-san-sa-san during 28 days of observation. These two species of insects are reported to be the vectors of rice dwarf in Japan.

Plant age and infection

At the time of virus infection, the older the plant is, the less susceptible it is. This has been demonstrated for tungro in previous annual reports. Although the causal agent of grassy stunt might not be a virus, the susceptibility of the plant seems to have a similar relationship to the age of the plant (Fig. 14). The degree of decrease with increasing age of the plant differs among rice varieties, however.

Weeds and the vector

To determine the alternative hosts of the causal agent of grassy stunt disease, a total of 20 species of weeds collected at Los Baños were inoculated artificially, but none became infected.

Weeds in a rice field could serve as temporary hosts of the vector, the brown planthopper, since it could survive for more than 6 days after being confined on *Cyperus iria*, *Digitaria adscendens*, *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, and one unidentified weed species.

Viruliferous brown planthoppers are able to lay eggs on weeds and the eggs can hatch. In fact, nymphs were obtained from *Cyperus iria*, *C.*

rotundus, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Digitaria adscendens*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Panicum maximum*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *P. scrobiculatum*, and one unidentified species. The ability of 35 nymphs collected from these weeds to infect rice with grassy stunt was tested by daily serial transmission until the insects' death. None of the 468 rice seedlings exposed to these insects became infected. That shows that the weeds did not serve as alternative hosts of the causal agent. Furthermore, it confirms that the

Table 22. Reaction of *Oryza* spp. to grassy stunt disease.

Species	No. of lines	Infected seedlings (%)
<i>O. breviligulata</i>	7	83.4—97.1
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	9	74.4—100
<i>O. granulata</i>	1	83.3
<i>O. minuta</i>	1	68.4
<i>O. nivara</i>	4	6.0—100
<i>O. officinalis</i>	1	66.7
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	8	73.4—96.9
<i>O. perennis</i>	9	66.9—100
<i>O. perennis</i> subsp. <i>balunga</i>	2	81.5—87.5
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	1	82.8
<i>O. spontanea</i>	5	67.7—91.2

Fig. 13. A portion of a rice plant (variety Shan-san-sa-san) which has grassy stunt disease showing stripes on the leaf blades.

Table 23. Reactions of seedlings of *Oryza nivara* and three rice varieties to grassy stunt disease tested by mass screening.

Plant	IRRI acc. no.	Seedlings inoculated (no.)	Infected seedlings (%)	Ave. life span of <i>N. lugens</i> (days)
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	101508	177	5.7	7.9
Mudgo	6663	195	81.6	2.6
Shan-san-sa-san	4512	197	80.5	15.5
Taichung (Native)1	105	188	82.0	16.0

Fig. 14. Percentage of infected seedlings of rice varieties inoculated with grassy stunt at various plant ages.

causal agent did not pass through the eggs to the progeny of viruliferous adults.

We tested the ability of viruliferous brown planthoppers to infect rice after being confined on *Fimbritylis miliacea*, *Monochovia vaginalis* or *Imperata cylindrica* for 2 days; on *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Echinochloa colonum*, *Eleusine*

indica, *Eragrostis pilosa*, or *Ischaemum rugosum* for 4 days; or on *Echinochloa crusgalli* for 8 days. The weeds did not alter the infectivity of the insects.

Infective insects at the IRRI farm

The incidence of grassy stunt disease remained high at the IRRI farm in 1969, especially from April to June. To investigate the occurrence of infective insects, brown planthoppers were collected from the field at monthly intervals from June to November and tested individually for their infectivity. The results (Table 24) revealed that the infective insects were present at the farm every month during the period. The percentage of infective insects, however, was lower from October to November.

The infective insects were widely distributed at the farm. They were collected from seedbeds, growing rice fields, harvested rice fields, levees, and idle areas.

Although most seedbeds were treated with insecticides, 79 out of 652 insects collected from seedbeds from June to November were infective. This means that the seedlings in the seedbeds could be infected since young plants were more susceptible to the disease (Fig. 14). In fact, 35 out of 300 seedlings transplanted from the seedbeds to pots in the greenhouse became diseased. Thus, intensive control of the insects in seedbeds could reduce the incidence of grassy stunt disease in the field. Since most of the insects collected from the seedbeds were adults they must have migrated to the seedbeds. Preventing migration would reduce the number of insects in seedbeds.

The insects on volunteer rice plants in rice fields after harvest and on weeds on the levees and in the idle areas of the farm could also be sources of the migrants. Of the 473 brown planthoppers collected from volunteer rice plants, 40 were infective. The percentage of infective insects in rice fields after harvest was affected by the incidence of grassy stunt disease in the preceding crop. In addition, two out of 52 brown planthoppers collected from weeds were infective. Hence, to control the brown planthopper on a farm, the insects on volunteer rice plants and on weeds should not be neglected.

Table 24. Percentage of *Nilaparvata lugens* transmitting grassy stunt disease at the IRRI farm, 1969.

Month	No. of insects collected and tested	Infective insects (%)
June	562	8.7
July	693	11.5
August	200	16.5
September	53	11.3
October	147	6.1
November	193	5.2
Total	1848	10.1

Seedling treatment and infection

Several experiments were made in an attempt to find a way to prevent grassy stunt infection through seed treatment. Rice seeds were treated with Diazinon, Gusathion, Temik, Terracur, and Uden at the rate of 2 kg/100 kg of seeds. Then the seedlings were inoculated with the grassy stunt virus. There were no significant differences in the percentage of infected seedlings in the treated seeds and the untreated control.

Rice seedlings of Taichung (Native)1 and Shan-san-sa-san after being dipped in Temik and Uden solutions at various concentrations for 16 and 24 hours were inoculated with grassy stunt at different intervals after treatment. The leaf blades of the treated seedlings showed some tip burn, but the percentage of infection of treated seedlings was not significantly less than that of the untreated controls. However, on the treated seedlings, more brown planthoppers died than on the untreated control.

Adaptability of the brown planthopper to Mudgo

Mudgo is not resistant to grassy stunt (Table 23), but it is known as a variety resistant to the vector, the brown planthopper, in contrast with Taichung (Native)1 which is susceptible to both the disease and the vector. Investigations were made to determine whether the insect could adapt to the variety and thus change in its ability to transmit the disease in succeeding generations if the variety was the only plant available to the insect. Macropterous females of the insect were used to start the colonies. The females and their progeny reared on seedlings of Mudgo, were designated as the "Mudgo colony" and those reared on Taichung (Native)1 were designated as the "T(N)1 colony." The life span of each

generation was determined from the average life span of 10 females.

We found (Table 25) that the average life span of 10 generations of the insects of the T(N)1 colony on Taichung (Native)1 seedlings was 18.5 days and on Mudgo seedlings, 4.3 days. Obviously, Mudgo was more resistant than Taichung (Native)1 to the insects of T(N)1 colony, as shown by the antibiosis of the variety to the insect. The life span of the insects of the Mudgo colony on Mudgo seedlings increased from 4.2 days for the first generation to 15.4 days for the fifth generation. Thereafter, the life span of the insects of succeeding generations increased slightly.

Apparently, the life span of the insects of the Mudgo colony on Mudgo seedlings was shorter

Table 25. Life span of female *Nilaparvata lugens* of successive generations of "Mudgo" and "T(N)1" colonies on seedlings of Mudgo and Taichung (Native)1.

Generation	Life span (days)			
	Mudgo colony		T(N)1 colony	
	On Mudgo	On Taichung (Native)1	On Mudgo	On Taichung (Native)1
1	4.2	14.2	3.2	16.8
2	5.9	16.0	2.1	19.0
3	8.8	15.3	4.4	18.3
4	13.8	17.1	3.2	19.5
5	15.4	18.0	5.6	18.6
6	15.0	14.3	2.2	19.8
7	14.8	18.2	6.8	20.1
8	15.6	15.5	5.9	16.9
9	16.8	18.8	5.0	19.0
10	16.0	17.8	4.4	17.0

Table 26. Number of insects that reached adult stage produced by a female *Nilaparvata lugens* of successive generations of "Mudgo" and "T(N)1" colonies on Mudgo and Taichung (Native)1 seedlings.

Generation	No. of adult insects			
	Mudgo colony		T(N)1 colony	
	On Mudgo	On Taichung (Native)1	On Mudgo	On Taichung (Native)1
1	21.6	54.3	36.1	126.2
2	26.4	72.9	24.2	105.0
3	47.0	68.7	29.5	121.3
4	66.4	86.0	25.8	136.0
5	63.9	94.5	26.3	122.4
6	74.8	80.0	23.3	129.0
7	79.8	66.4	41.1	154.3
8	70.3	102.2	39.0	121.5
9	81.4	90.3	20.5	140.2
10	78.3	89.4	26.3	151.0

than that of the insects of the T(N)1 colony on Taichung (Native)1 seedlings, but it was significantly longer than that of the insects of the T(N)1 colony on Mudgo seedlings. In other words, the progeny of the Mudgo colony did build up their adaptability to Mudgo.

An average female of the Mudgo colony produced more progeny that, when raised on Mudgo seedlings, reached the adult stage than

did the average female of the T(N)1 colony. However, more progeny of the average female of the Mudgo colony and of the T(N)1 colony, reached the adult stage when raised on Taichung (Native)1 seedlings than when they were raised on Mudgo seedlings (Table 26).

A disease transmission study did not reveal any distinct difference between the insects of the Mudgo colony and those of the T(N)1 colony.

Statistics

Aside from providing consultation and analytical services to research workers, the Department conducted research with emphasis on improving field plot techniques in rice research, evaluating and developing statistical procedures for analyzing and interpreting rice data, and collecting rice statistics from farmers' fields.

Field plot technique studies

As a continuation of a study begun in 1968, several field experiments were conducted in the 1969 dry and wet seasons in cooperation with the Agronomy Department.

Effects of unplanted borders

All trials confirmed the previous finding that the row adjacent to an unplanted border gives a higher grain yield than the center rows give (Table 1). The average increase in grain yield was 130 percent. The second outermost row, however, tended to show significant decreases in grain yield, especially in fertilized areas where the grain yields of the outermost row were very high. The average yield of the second outermost row was 14 percent lower than that of the center rows in fertilized areas. The second outermost row apparently suffered from excessive shading and insufficient nitrogen caused by the very vigorous plants in the outermost row. In all trials, the border effects did not extend beyond the second row. These results support a previous recommendation that, when determining plot yield, two border rows from each side of the plot should be removed to eliminate border effects.

Increases in the number of panicles of the row adjacent to an unplanted border were also significant in all trials. These increases averaged 87 percent (Table 1). However, the percentage increase in panicle number was smaller than that of grain yields. Apparently, the increase in panicle number was not the only cause of in-

creased yield in the outermost row. Other contributing components were the increase in number of grains per panicle and the reduction in the percentage of unfilled grains (Table 2).

Border effects on plant height were not as clear-cut or as consistent as on grain yield and panicle number. Plant height seemed to have been affected by the orientation of rows as well as by the fertility level of the plot. In unfertilized plots, plants in the outermost row tended to be taller than those in the inner rows, while the reverse was true in fertilized plots (Table 1). In either case, the second outermost row generally had shorter plants than the inside rows. For plant height, two forces seem to work in opposing directions. While the absence of competition for nutrients (the adjacent area was unplanted) tends to favor growth in the outermost row, the greater competition for light in the center rows seems to make plants taller.

Plants in the border rows had a different tillering pattern than plants in the center rows. In particular, the tillers of the outermost row continued to increase even after those of the center rows had started to decline (Fig. 1).

Confirming the 1968 results, the differences in grain yields between the outermost and center rows increased as the width of the unplanted spaces between plots increased up to 100 cm. The grain yield of the plot determined without eliminating border rows, and including the area of the unplanted alley, tended to be lower than the yield obtained from the center rows only (Table 3). The average reduction was higher

Table 1. Grain yield, panicle number, and plant height of border rows of IR8 adjacent to unplanted space, from six trials. IRRI, 1969 dry and wet seasons.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Number of replicates	Grain yield (kg/ha)			Panicles (no./sq. m)			Plant height (cm)		
		Row 1	Row 2	Center ^a	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^a	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^a
Dry season										
0	66	12,452**	4,845	5,055	518**	268	258	84**	79	79
0	43	11,832**	5,392	5,693	511**	311	320	81*	79	80
120	29	15,760**	6,212**	7,046	595**	345	353	85	84*	85
Wet season										
0	66	12,490**	5,555	5,416	400**	209	196	93	92*	93
0	36	13,072**	5,245	5,587	388**	202	208	90	91	91
120	22	14,532**	5,180**	6,245	482**	265	285	95**	94**	97
Weighted average										
0	211	12,443**	5,246	5,388	457**	247	242	87**	85	86
120	51	15,230**	5,766**	6,700	546**	310	323	89**	88**	90

^a Average of three inner rows.

* Significantly different from the center at the 5% level.

** Significantly different from the center at the 1% level.

Fig. 1. Tillering patterns of the row adjacent to unplanted borders and of the center rows (Variety IR5 and selection IR400-5-12-10-2). IIRRI, 1969 wet season.

with the wider spacing between plots. In fact, only in the 100- and 140-cm spacings was the reduction significant. This suggests that where very small plots are used and not enough plants are available to be discarded as borders, the unplanted alley between plots should be narrow or eliminated. When an unplanted alley is needed, plot yields can be determined with the inclusion of the alley areas, if the alley is not wider than 60 cm.

Effects of nitrogen competition

Experiments started in 1968 to evaluate the effects of applying different levels of nitrogen on adjacent plots were continued with some modifications and additions:

1) Plot size was increased from 14 to 28 rows to insure that a sufficient number of center rows would be completely free from the effects of nitrogen competition.

2) This year's study included an evaluation of the effects of nitrogen competition not only between fertilized and unfertilized plots, but also between plots receiving different rates of nitrogen.

3) A comparison was made between the effectiveness of a 20-cm levee and a 40-cm unplanted

Table 2. Effects of unplanted borders on grain yields and yield components (average of 22 replicates) of IR8 plots receiving 120 kg/ha N. IIRRI, 1969 wet season.

Characteristic	Row position			cv (%)
	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^a	
Grain yield (kg/ha)	14,532**	5,180**	6,245	12.7
Panicles (no./sq. m)	482**	265	285	8.5
Grains (no./panicle)	141**	104	109	22.9
Panicle weight (g)	0.84**	0.59	0.62	16.2
Panicle length (cm)	23.6**	21.4	21.4	7.8
Unfilled grain (%)	25.3**	31.7**	27.7	12.6
100-grain weight (g)	3.12	3.11	3.14	1.9

^a Average of three inner rows.

** Significantly different from the center at the 1% level.

Table 3. Plot yields (kg/ha) of IR8 computed with the inclusion of alley areas compared with yields of center rows, for different spacings between plots. IIRRI, 1969.

Spacing between plots (cm)	Dry season				Wet season		Average decrease compared with center rows (%)
	0 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N		60 kg/ha N		
	Plot	Center rows	Plot	Center rows	Plot	Center rows	
40	4,097	4,115	6,758	6,882	4,764	4,790	1.0
60	4,187	4,282	6,095	6,197	4,944	4,989	1.8
100	4,216	4,383	6,550**	7,085	4,927	5,177	5.5
140	3,921*	4,208	6,475**	7,070	4,962	5,367	7.6
cv (%)	11.0		9.8		11.6		

* Significantly different from the center rows at the 5% level.

** Significantly different from the center rows at the 1% level.

Table 4. Effects of nitrogen competition on grain yields (kg/ha) of IR8 between the 0 kg/ha N and the 120 kg/ha N plots separated by a 20-cm levee or a 40-cm unplanted alley. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Position	0 kg/ha N plot		120 kg/ha N plot	
	Adjacent to 120 kg/ha N plot	Control ^a	Adjacent to 0 kg/ha N plot	Control ^a
Separated by a levee				
Row 1	7,827	7,697	8,642	8,396
Row 2	4,439	4,377	5,956	5,932
Row 3	4,431	4,334	6,345	6,186
Row 4	4,391	4,415	6,112	6,447
Center rows	4,503		6,448	
Separated by an unplanted alley				
Row 1	7,750*	6,313	6,958**	8,772
Row 2	4,778	4,361	5,717	5,917
Row 3	4,492	4,542	6,222	6,202
Row 4	4,242	4,317	6,238	6,558
Center rows	4,270		6,294	

^a Adjacent to similarly fertilized (or unfertilized) plot.
 * Significantly different from control at the 5% level.
 ** Significantly different from control at the 1% level.

alley as buffer against the effects of nitrogen competition.

Experiments were conducted in both the dry and wet seasons of 1969 with IR8 as the indicator variety.

The effects of nitrogen competition were measured as the difference between grain yields of border rows adjacent to similarly fertilized (or unfertilized) plots and yields of border rows adjacent to plots receiving different rates of nitrogen. In trials where the adjacent plots, receiving 0 and 120 kg/ha N, were separated by a 20-cm levee, no significant competition effects were observed (Table 4).

When adjacent plots were separated by a 40-cm unplanted alley, some competition effects were detected. Competition effects between adjacent plots receiving 60 kg/ha and 120 kg/ha N are shown in Table 5. Only in one case was the effect of nitrogen competition significant.

Between fertilized (either 60 kg/ha or 120 kg/ha N) and unfertilized plots, however, significant effects of nitrogen competition were repeatedly detected in most trials, confirming the results obtained in 1968. In general, the outermost row of an unfertilized plot adjacent to a fertilized plot gave higher grain yield than an outermost row adjacent to an unfertilized plot. Averaged over the three trials where significant competition effects were observed, the increase in grain yield was about 14 percent. Likewise, the grain yield of the outermost row of fertilized

Table 5. Effects of nitrogen competition on grain yield (kg/ha) of IR8 between the 60 kg/ha N and the 120 kg/ha N plots separated by a 40-cm unplanted alley. IRRI, 1969.

Position	60 kg/ha N plot		120 kg/ha N plot	
	Adjacent to 120 kg/ha N plot	Control ^a	Adjacent to 60 kg/ha N plot	Control ^a
Dry season				
Row 1	7,680	7,761	7,805	8,379
Row 2	5,337	5,297	5,519	6,163
Row 3	5,781	5,386	5,602	6,148
Row 4	5,506	5,414	6,086	6,371
Center rows	5,609		6,274	
Wet season				
Row 1	8,086*	7,528	7,942	8,344
Row 2	5,483	5,180	5,265	5,542
Row 3	5,530	5,552	5,802	5,790
Row 4	5,747	5,622	5,771	6,062
Center rows	5,458		5,786	

^a Adjacent to similarly fertilized plot.
 * Significantly different from control at the 5% level.

plots adjacent to the unfertilized plots was generally lower than that of the row adjacent to similarly fertilized plots. The average decrease was about 10 percent. Furthermore, there was an indication that the effects of nitrogen competition could extend beyond the second outermost row. These results again agreed with those obtained in 1968.

The persistence of the effects of nitrogen competition beyond the first and even the second outermost row of a plot presented two major problems. The first is the uncertainty about the number of rows affected as well as the difficulty of eliminating more than two border rows. The second, and probably the more important problem, is that the extent of the competition effects does not seem to agree with the estimated mobility of nitrogenous fertilizer. It is unlikely that nitrogen can move horizontally as much as 1 meter from where it was originally placed.

Of the many possible explanations of our results, the most promising seems to be the possibility that nitrogen, which was incorporated into the soil 2 days before transplanting, was mechanically moved by transplanters from one plot to another. The plots in all trials were so arranged that the rows were perpendicular to the path of the transplanters. Thus, if nitrogen were actually moved at transplanting, the competition effects should not have been the same on both sides of the plot. The results of the experiments in fact showed that in unfertilized

plots, competition effects were significantly higher on the side (side 1) first reached by the transplanters coming from heavily fertilized plots (Table 6). Grain yields of side 1, even up to the fourth row, were consistently higher than those of the opposite side (side 2) and those of control.

Further experiments will be conducted to confirm these findings.

Table 6. Effect of movement of transplanters and orientation of plot rows on nitrogen competition in unfertilized IR8 plots. IRR1, 1969 dry season.

Position	Grain yield (kg/ha)			Control ^b
	Side 1 ^a	Side 2 ^a	Average	
Adjacent to 120 kg/ha N plot				
Row 1	8,588**	6,912	7,750*	6,313
Row 2	4,978	4,578	4,778	4,361
Row 3	4,862	4,122	4,492	4,542
Row 4	4,517	3,966	4,242	4,317
Row 5	4,678	3,728	4,203	4,358
Adjacent to 60 kg/ha N plot				
Row 1	5,546**	4,729*	5,137**	4,227
Row 2	3,470	2,996	3,233	3,135
Row 3	3,424	3,025	3,225	2,965
Row 4	3,419	3,010	3,215	3,165
Row 5	2,862	2,990	2,929	2,952

^a Side 1 is the side of the plot first reached by transplanters coming from fertilized plot; side 2 is the side opposite side 1.

^b Adjacent to unfertilized plot.

* Significantly different from the control at the 5% level.

** Significantly different from the control at the 1% level.

Effects of varietal competition

The effects of planting different varieties in adjacent experimental plots were investigated using two varieties and one selection that differ in tillering capacity and plant height: IR8 (short and high-tillering), Peta (tall and medium-tillering), and IR127-80-1-10 (medium-short and low-tillering). Two experiments, one without added nitrogen and another with 120 kg/ha N, were conducted in both the dry and wet seasons of 1969. In each experiment, all possible pairs of the three varieties were planted side by side with no unplanted alley between adjacent plots.

IR8 and IR127-80-1-10 did not lodge; however, Peta lodged as early as 2 to 4 weeks before any of the other varieties were harvested. Lodging was so severe in the wet season that no yield data were collected from the fertilized Peta plots.

Grain yields in the border rows of the plots of IR8 and IR127-80-1-10 which were adjacent to Peta were significantly lower than yields of the center rows (Table 7). The average reduction was 15 percent for the unfertilized plots and 30 percent for the fertilized plots. Data on yield components showed that the border rows of IR8

Table 7. Effects of varietal competition on grain yields of border rows. IRR1, 1969.

Border variety or selection	Position	Grain yield (kg/ha)			
		Dry season		Wet season	
		0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N
IR127-80-1-10	Row 1	4,910**	6,330	4,973**	5,911
	Row 2	3,950	5,830	4,473	5,719
	Row 3	3,874	5,934	4,227	5,948
Peta	Row 1	3,362**	4,582**	3,541**	3,178**
	Row 2	3,701	4,875**	3,659*	4,162**
	Row 3	3,735	5,209*	3,923	4,856**
Control	Center rows	4,037	5,891	4,127	5,732
IR8	Row 1	3,818**	5,498*	4,112	5,692
	Row 2	4,311	6,284	4,091	5,811
	Row 3	4,572	6,142	4,334	5,722
Peta	Row 1	3,455**	4,391**	3,861	4,170**
	Row 2	4,345	5,426.	4,025	4,856**
	Row 3	4,329	5,932	4,173	5,233
Control	Center rows	4,415	6,080.	4,112	5,455
IR127-80-1-10	Row 1	5,878**	7,178**	5,986**	—
	Row 2	4,560	5,656**	4,774*	—
	Row 3	4,352	4,988	4,239	—
IR8	Row 1	4,872*	6,882**	4,951**	—
	Row 2	4,795	6,398**	4,424	—
	Row 3	4,288	5,169	4,354	—
Control	Center rows	4,447	4,731	4,112	—

* Significantly different from the corresponding control at the 5% level.

** Significantly different from the corresponding control at the 1% level.

and of IR127-80-1-10 had lower percentages of filled grains, fewer panicles per hill, and fewer grains per panicle. Apparently the reason the border rows produced less was that Peta shaded them early in the season and lodged into them later in the season. On the other hand, the border rows of plots of Peta adjacent to either IR8 or IR127-80-1-10 had relatively higher yields than the center rows. The average yield increase was 25 percent in rows adjacent to IR8 and 43 percent in rows adjacent to IR127-80-1-10.

Border rows of IR8 adjacent to IR127-80-1-10 gave significantly higher grain yields than the

center rows, but only in the unfertilized plots. The border rows of IR127-80-1-10 adjacent to IR8, however, had lower grain yields than the center rows.

In magnitude (difference between border and center rows) and in extent (number of rows affected) the effects of competition between two varieties differing in tillering capacity seemed less marked than between varieties differing in plant height. Significant effects of competition reached to the third border row only in fertilized plots of IR8.

Table 8. Average percentage increase in grain yield, panicle number, and plant height of individual hills immediately adjacent to the missing hill (or hills) compared with that of the normal hills, IR8 and IR154-61-1. IIRI, 1969.

Pattern of missing hills	Adjacent hills (no.)	Average increase (%)					
		Dry season			Wet season		
		Grain yield	Panicle number	Plant height	Grain yield	Panicle number	Plant height
One missing hill	4	30**	36**	3**	27**	19**	2*
Two adjacent missing hills	6	46**	40**	1	45**	30**	1
Two missing hills with standing hill in between	7	20**	32**	2**	32**	26**	2*

* Significant at the 5% level.
** Significant at the 1% level.

Table 9. Percentage increase in grain yields of IR480-5-9-3-3 hills immediately adjacent to a missing hill (or hills) compared with normal hills (Data are averages of five replicates). IIRI, 1969.

Type of missing hills pattern ^a	Hill position	Number of hills	Grain yield increase (%)					
			Dry season		Wet season		Average	
			0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N		
	A	2	30	12	20	35	24	
	B	2	49	30	42	45	42	
	A	2	60	37	35	49	45	
	B	4	34	27	33	42	34	
	A	2	46	47	37	28	40	
	B	4	52	36	22	47	39	
	C	1	90	67	50	64	68	
	A	4	30	72	31	36	42	
	B	4	42	31	56	36	41	
	A	4	40	28	27	19	28	
	B	4	74	31	37	20	40	
	A	2	52	21	34	46	38	
	B	6	40	11	18	39	27	
	A	2	17	43	31	20	28	
	B	6	24	22	15	44	26	
	C	2	27	54	46	66	48	

^a Rows run horizontally (25-cm spacing between rows and 20-cm between hills within row); □ = missing hill; [A], [B] and [C] = measured hill; [X] = unmeasured living hill.

Table 10. Estimates of soil heterogeneity index, *b*, and optimum plot size computed from eight uniformity yield trials. IRRI, 1968-1969.

Season and year	Variety	Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Number of basic units	<i>b</i>	Optimum plot size (sq m)	
					Bordered ^a	Unbordered
Dry, 1968	IR8	0	648	0.235	14.4 (5.9)	6.6
Dry, 1968	IR8	120	648	0.256	11.4 (6.6)	7.4
Dry, 1968	IR5	0	648	0.318	14.5 (8.9)	10.0
Dry, 1968	IR5	120	900	0.369	17.7 (11.2)	12.6
Wet, 1968	IR8	0	864	0.273	12.2 (7.2)	8.1
Wet, 1968	IR8	60	1,512	0.320	14.7 (9.0)	10.1
Dry, 1969	IR8	0	864	0.263	11.7 (6.8)	7.7
Wet, 1969	IR8	0	864	0.319	14.7 (9.0)	10.1
Average				0.294	13.3 (8.0)	9.0

^a Values in parentheses refer to the actual testing area; i.e., excluding borders.

Effects of missing hills

An experiment, started in the 1968 wet season, involving two varieties and three patterns of missing hills was repeated in the dry and wet seasons of 1969 with one modification—four control hills (a control hill is one which is completely surrounded by living hills) were measured from each plot. This allowed each plot to have its own control hills.

In the 1968 trial, the absence of one hill did not show significant effects on the grain yields of surrounding hills. In the 1969 tests, however, all hills adjacent to the missing hill (or hills) showed significant yield increases in all missing-hill patterns and for both varieties (Table 8). Furthermore, the panicle number and height of plants adjacent to the missing hill (or hills) also increased. Thus it is advisable to avoid measuring plant height and panicle number on hills adjacent to the missing hill (or hills).

Additional experiments involving IR480-5-9-3-3 and two levels of nitrogen, 0 and 120 kg/ha N, were conducted in the dry and wet seasons of 1969. Seven missing-hill patterns involving one to three missing hills were evaluated. In all trials, hills immediately adjacent to a missing hill consistently gave significantly higher yields than normal hills (Table 9). But the position of the hill in relation to the missing hill (or hills) seemed to affect the magnitude of the yield increase. For example, hills lying between two missing hills, gave higher percentage increases than hills adjacent to only one missing hill. These results confirm our 1968 findings which indicated that, in addition to the number of missing hills, the pattern of distribution of the missing hills also affects yields.

There were some indications, although none was significant, that plants not immediately adjacent to the missing hills were also affected. Further investigation, possibly with more replicates, is needed to verify this trend.

Optimum plot size in rice

The optimum size of plot is one that gives the maximum information per unit cost. It was estimated as

$$x = \frac{b(K_1 + K_g A)}{(1-b)(K_2 + K_g B)}$$

where K_1 is the part of the cost associated with the number of plots only; K_2 is the cost per unit area; K_g is the cost associated with the area of borders; B is the ratio of the side-borders to the test area; A is the area of the plot end-borders; and b is the measure of soil heterogeneity. If unbordered plots are used, K_g is taken to be zero.

Grain yield data from eight uniformity trials conducted at the IRRI experimental farm during the 1968-69 crop seasons were used in estimating b , the measure of soil heterogeneity. Basic information regarding the trials is in Table 10. Cost figures (Table 11) were computed for agronomic experiments on rice based upon IRRI's standard cultural and management practices. The areas for borders per plot were assumed to be composed of two border rows and two end hills. The width of the plot was fixed at 3 m and the plant spacing used was 20 x 20 cm.

The adjusted b values estimated from the eight uniformity trials ranged from 0.235 to 0.369 with an average of 0.294 (Table 10). Corresponding estimates of optimum plot size ranged from 10 to 18 sq m for bordered plots, and from 7 to 13 sq m for unbordered plots. For

Table 11. Estimates of costs^a in man-hours for conducting a rice field experiment. IRRI.

Operation	Man-hour/sq m	Man-hour/plot
Land preparation	0.0258	—
Seedbed preparation	0.0011	—
Laying out plots	0.0012	0.2200
Transplanting	0.0170	—
Fertilization	0.0011	—
Insecticide application	0.0008	—
Hand weeding	0.0223	—
Labelling tags and making stakes	—	0.1033
Plot observation ^b	0.0039	0.8925
Measurement of plant characteristics ^c	—	1.2330
Harvesting	0.0094	0.1893
Threshing	0.0042	0.0622
Blowing and docking	0.0500	0.0419
Weighing grains and determining moisture content	—	0.0333
Statistical analysis	—	0.1750

^a Costs other than labor were ignored since they were relatively negligible. Relative monetary costs of man-hours for the various procedures were not considered.

^b Observing panicle initiation date, flowering date, lodging, incidence of pests and diseases, etc.

^c Measurements of tiller number, plant height, and dry matter production at three growth stages were made on sample hills.

Fig. 2. Relationship between sampling variance as percentage of the mean and size of sampling unit for grain yield of fertilized and unfertilized plots (18 sq m plot size).

all trials, the average optimum size was 13 sq m for bordered plots and 9 sq m for unbordered plots. The present estimate of optimum plot size is appropriate only under conditions similar to those at IRRI. For other experiments in which the relative costs of experimental procedures and

the variability of the soil differ appreciably from the ones presented here, a new estimate of optimum plot size must be found.

Sampling in replicated field experiments on rice

In field experiments on rice, certain characteristics like plant height or tiller number are measured on sample plants for each plot. Sampling may even be used for yield determination if the plot size is very large. A study was conducted to determine the type of sampling unit, the sample size, and the selection procedure that might be used for each characteristic. Attempts were also made to identify the factors affecting variability, the major consideration in the design of any sampling scheme.

Grain yield. Uniformity trial data were utilized in the study. Sampling variation was generally higher in fertilized than in unfertilized plots (Fig. 2), possibly due to non-uniform application of fertilizer. In both fertilized and unfertilized plots, however, the percentage of sampling error decreased considerably as the sampling unit increased from 1 to 5 sq m. Over 5 sq m, only a very slight decrease in sampling error was observed. The relative loss in information from sampling one unit of 5 sq m compared with harvesting the whole plot of 10 sq m was about 20 percent. For unfertilized plots, the strip method of sampling (i.e., taking only one sample cut from the center of the plot) is comparable to either random sampling or stratified random sampling. For fertilized plots, however, the efficiency of the random method of selecting several smaller sized cuts relative to the strip method was about 18 percent. The efficiency of stratifying the plot was not substantial.

Preliminary studies revealed a relatively larger sampling variation in broadcast plots than in transplanted plots. The demarcation of sample cuts for harvest in broadcast plots was also more difficult. Further studies are underway to find the most efficient sampling procedure for broadcast plots.

Plant height and panicle number. Data on panicle count and plant height collected from a total of 4,500 hills of IR8, planted in a 10 x 18 m area in both the dry and wet seasons of 1969, were used in our study. The degree of precision of different sizes of sampling unit, ranging from

Table 12. Appropriate sample sizes^a for various degrees of precision in measuring plant height from experiments with different plot sizes and numbers of replicates.

Margin of error ^b	Sampling unit							
	1-hill			2-hill				
	2	No. of replicates		5	2	No. of replicates		
		3	4			3	4	5
				Plot size: 10 sq m				
2%	---	11.3	6.2	4.2	---	5.8	3.2	2.2
3%	5.0	2.7	1.9	1.4	2.6	1.4	1.0	0.8
4%	2.2	1.3	1.0	0.7	1.2	0.7	0.5	0.4
5%	1.3	0.8	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.2
6%	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2
				Plot size: 18 sq m				
2%	16.2	7.7	5.0	3.7	9.1	4.3	2.8	2.1
3%	4.3	2.6	1.8	1.4	2.4	1.5	1.0	0.8
4%	2.1	1.3	1.0	0.8	1.2	0.8	0.6	0.4
5%	1.3	0.8	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.4	0.3
6%	0.9	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.2

^a The number of sampling units taken per plot.

^b As percentage of mean.

Table 13. Appropriate sample size^a for various degrees of precision in measuring panicle number from experiments with different plot size and numbers of replicates.

Margin of error ^b	Sampling unit							
	1-hill			2-hill				
	2	No. of replicates		5	2	No. of replicates		
		3	4			3	4	5
				Plot size: 10 sq m				
6%	39.4	18.6	12.2	9.0	17.4	8.4	5.6	4.2
7%	21.8	11.8	8.1	6.2	9.9	5.4	3.7	2.8
8%	14.4	8.3	5.9	4.5	6.6	3.8	2.7	2.1
9%	10.4	6.2	4.5	3.5	4.8	2.9	2.0	1.6
10%	7.9	4.9	3.5	2.8	3.6	2.2	1.6	1.3
				Plot size: 18 sq m				
6%	51.7	21.0	13.2	9.6	39.1	11.6	6.8	4.8
7%	25.2	12.8	8.6	6.4	14.5	6.6	4.3	3.2
8%	15.8	8.8	6.1	4.7	8.4	4.4	3.0	2.3
9%	11.1	6.5	4.6	3.6	5.7	3.2	2.2	1.7
10%	8.4	5.0	3.6	2.9	4.2	2.4	1.8	1.4

^a The number of sampling units taken per plot.

^b As percentage of mean.

one to 25 hills for panicle number, and one to 12 hills for plant height, was evaluated. The results show:

1) To obtain a similar degree of precision, about four to six times more sample plants should be taken for panicle number than for plant height.

2) For plant height, a one-hill sampling unit is optimum, while for panicle count, a sampling unit made up of two adjacent hills or a square of four hills is better.

3) In an experiment with four replicates and plots measuring 10 sq m, a sample of six random hills per plot gave estimates with margins of error of 2 percent for plant height and about 10

percent for panicle number. Tables 12 and 13 give the minimum sample sizes required to get various degrees of precision for different types of sampling unit taken from experiments with varying plot sizes and numbers of replicates.

Evaluation of statistical procedures for rice data

The split-plot analysis

The most common type of split-plot design used in rice experiments is one in which the whole-plot treatments are placed in a randomized complete block arrangement. The conventional use

of pooled subplot error is based on the assumption that the interactions of the replication with 1) the subplot and with 2) the interaction between the subplot and main plot are negligible or have the same expectations. To evaluate whether this assumption is true, data from 34 rice field experiments in split-plot design conducted by the Agronomy Department from 1967 through 1969 were used. Grain yields and data on plant height, tiller number, and other yield components were considered. Preliminary tests of significance, with $0.20 \leq \alpha \leq 0.50$ and assuming a mixed model (the replication is considered as random and all other factors as fixed) for all tests, indicated that 27 of the 34 sets of yield data, or 79 percent, violated the assumption. For other characteristics, 74 percent violated the assumption. The results suggest that in the split-plot analysis of rice data, the pooled subplot error should not be used unless its validity is indicated by a preliminary test of significance.

Analysis of data from repeated measurements

Rice researchers commonly make repeated measurements on the same plots over time (e.g., tiller count at different growth stages). The usual univariate procedure, simulating a split-plot analysis with time as the ultimate subplot treatment, is valid only when the assumption of equal variances and equal covariances among times holds. It is doubtful that such an assumption, generally referred to as the "symmetry" assumption, is valid for all data. For example, a common observation is that the measurements

taken at shorter time intervals are more highly correlated than those taken at longer intervals. This condition, if true, would invalidate the symmetry assumption.

Data on the plant height and tiller number of the same plants at different growth stages, taken from 11 agronomic experiments at IRRI were used in our study. For each trial, Wilk's likelihood ratio test was applied to test the validity of the symmetry assumption. The results of the χ^2 -test, presented in Table 14, indicated that the assumption is generally not fulfilled for these data. For plant height, highly significant results were obtained in all trials, and for tiller number, only one out of 11 trials showed non-significant results. It seems, therefore that the usual univariate analysis is not appropriate for such data. The use of certain multivariate procedures should be considered. Further tests will be made on other rice characters and attempts will be made to find suitable multivariate analyses for the situations where the univariate analysis is not valid.

Collection of rice statistics

Estimates of rice production obtained through interviews with farmers may be underestimated due to the failure of farmers to report certain components of rice production. The accuracy of assessing the unreported components by deeper probing during interviews was evaluated in 1968 and 1969 from surveys of rice farmers in Laguna, Philippines. The results showed that farmers are unable to give reasonably accurate estimates of two components: 1) the harvester's share with heaping or shaking*, and 2) the amount of grains recovered by gleaning. An objective method for estimating these components is clearly needed.

Harvester's share. The 1969 survey confirmed the previous findings reported in the 1968 Annual Report that the harvester's share comprises about 18 percent of the total production. If the amount of heaping or shaking is not taken into account in the estimation of the harvester's

Table 14. Chi-square values for testing the validity of the "symmetry" assumption on height and tiller measurements repeated over time.

Test number	Measurements (no.)	Degrees of freedom	χ^2 -test criterion	
			Plant height	Tiller number
1	4	8	45.19**	25.86**
2	4	8	51.88**	48.24**
3	4	8	97.65**	45.42**
4	6	19	112.92**	159.84**
5	6	19	77.40**	59.21**
6	6	19	50.90**	28.41 ^{n.s.}
7	6	19	50.03**	36.90**
8	6	19	2,661.33**	89.66**
9	6	19	170.30**	409.43**
10	6	19	127.18**	260.94**
11	6	19	47.92**	87.16**

** Significant at the 1% level.
 ** Not significant.

* The container is heaped or shaken only when the harvester's share is being measured. Thus each harvester actually receives more grains than what is specified by the harvester-farmer sharing ratio.

share-a 3- to 5-percent under-estimation in the total production may result.

A relatively simple way of estimating these quantities involves two steps. First, find out the ratio of the farmer's share to the harvester's share. This ratio is the basis for estimating the harvester's share without heaping or shaking. Second, find out whether heaping or shaking, or both are practiced; and if so, the kind of sharing container used. The second item is helpful in arriving at a better estimate of the harvester's actual share when heaping or shaking or both are practiced. For example, Laguna farmers commonly use three types of sharing container: a new kerosene can, an old kerosene can with a circular open end, or a wooden container locally known as a "panega." The amount of grain heaped in the first type of container is approximately 9 percent of its contents; in the round, open-ended container, 11 percent; and in the "panega," 13 percent. The amount of increase caused by shaking is about the same as that caused by heaping.

Gleaning. Two paddies were randomly selected from each of 20 sample farms in the dry season and from each of 28 sample farms in the wet season. A 10 x 10 m area was located at random in each selected paddy. The area was in turn divided into three sub-areas measuring

Table 15. Estimated amount of gleaning and variance components based on different sizes of sampling areas. Laguna, Philippines, 1969.

Sampling area (m)	Dry season			Wet season		
	Gleaning (kg/ha)	$\hat{\sigma}_f^2$ ^a	$\hat{\sigma}_p^2$ ^a	Gleaning (kg/ha)	$\hat{\sigma}_f^2$	$\hat{\sigma}_p^2$
2 x 10	43	593	180	55	642	276
3 x 10	41	384	108	61	881	413
5 x 10	42	389	92	59	643	190
8 x 10	41	394	72	58	731	184
10 x 10	42	415	69	58	694	166

^a $\hat{\sigma}_f^2$ is the estimated variance among farms, and $\hat{\sigma}_p^2$ is the estimated variance among paddies within a farm.

5 x 10 m, 3 x 10 m, and 2 x 10 m. Gleaning was done separately in each area soon after harvest. The results are summarized in Table 15. The estimated amount of gleaning based on the largest sampling area (10 x 10 m) was 42 kg/ha (1.0% of total production) in the dry season and 58 kg/ha (1.7% of total production) in the wet season. In both seasons, no significant differences were detected among estimates of the amount of gleaning obtained from different sampling areas ranging from 30 to 100 sq m. In the wet season, the smallest sampling area tested (20 sq m) seemed to give an estimate slightly different from the others. Further studies are needed to establish a suitable size of sampling area for estimating the amount of gleaning.

Varietal Improvement

Two new varieties, IR20 and IR22, were named in 1969. They resulted from efforts to combine improved plant type with other desirable traits, such as grain appearance and insect and disease resistance.

Tetep and Carreon, varieties with broad resistance to blast, have been crossed with improved plant-type selections and their F_3 lines are being evaluated. Selections and varieties resistant to blast, tungro, and bacterial leaf blight were sent to rice-growing countries in Asia for evaluation.

A series of indica x japonica crosses and backcrosses were made to combine improved plant type with cold resistance and several other japonica traits that make rice production successful in temperate regions.

Cooperative tests with Thai scientists have demonstrated that the floating habit can be combined with the semi-dwarf stature and sturdy stems, erect leaves, and high tillering.

About 40 of the 1,600 pedigree lines from the F_5 generation of crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties had good plant type and through three plant generations had an average protein content 2 percentage points higher than IR8.

The seed increase project conducted in both seasons yielded valuable information on uniformity, reaction to insects and diseases, lodging resistance, and grain qualities of the 176 entries, and aided in seed purification of the promising lines.

Genetic studies were made on plant characters related to a physiologically efficient plant type in the tropics; on the comparison of parents, F_1 hybrids, and F_2 hybrids in diallel cross and on the yield and related plant characters in Peta x Taichung (Native)1 backcrosses.

A study of the cytogenetic nature of the sterility of F_1 plants of crosses between tropical and subtropical varieties showed that sterility in such hybrids may stem from complex genic interactions. Histological examinations were made on the relation between leaf structure and wind damage.

Genetic studies with several varieties resistant to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers have shown that resistance to each is simply inherited. Single factors for leafhopper resistance in ASD7 and IR8 appear to be non-allelic to that of Pankhari. On the other hand, single factors for planthopper resistance in CO22 and MTU15 appear to be identical to that of Mudgo.

Varietal testing and development

World collection

During the year, 292 new accessions in the form of cultivars or breeding lines were received, increasing the total number of accessions to 11,349. About 2,150 accessions were planted during the year for seed increase, for testing for bacterial leaf blight, or for recording morphological and agronomic descriptions. Complete descriptions were completed for 122 varieties, increasing the total to 9,979.

From the collection, about 5,800 seed packages were sent abroad to 101 requesting institutions in 44 countries. Another 2,070 packages were supplied to research scientists in other departments of the Institute. Near the end of the year, seed samples of 1,700 accessions were processed for shipment to the U.S. National Seed Storage Laboratory in Ft. Collins, Colorado, for long-term storage.

In another collection of genetic testers and wild taxa, 200 African rices in the form of pure strains or mixed populations were received from Dr. J. Harlan of the University of Illinois (U.S.A). This African collection consisted of both cultivated and wild forms that were grown by local farmers or found in adjacent areas. About 120 viable accessions were grown for seed increase and re-identification.

From the collection of wild forms, 287 seed packages were supplied to 19 requesting agencies during the period 1968-69. The recipients covered 12 institutions in nine countries.

Breeding program

Efforts to combine the improved, nitrogen-responsive plant type (typified by IR8) with other desirable traits continued. Desirable traits include earlier maturity, insect and disease resistance, tough leaves, and higher protein in the grain. In addition, to meet varying consumer preferences, the traits should be available in varieties that differ in the size, shape, and amylose content of their grain. Attaining these goals will take many seasons but new strains combining one or more of the desired traits make the outlook for success encouraging. IR20 and IR22, the two new varieties released by the Institute in 1969, are good examples.

Often, varieties or lines that have improved plant type also possess other improved traits. When these varieties or lines are used as parents, it should be possible to select good plant-type lines combining many of the desired traits from the resulting crosses.

As new varietal sources of resistance to insects and diseases become available, they are used in the breeding program. Entomologists and pathologists are gradually improving their methods for screening breeding lines for resistance to insects and diseases.

Another important breeding objective is to find lines that have higher yield potentials. Since yield potential cannot be determined in any other way, the varieties must be grown under conditions that allow them to express their maximum production potentials.

Agronomists and physiologists are assisting the breeders in finding reliable ways to test yields. Many breeding lines are turned over to them for field evaluation. In this way, cultural techniques for high-yielding varieties such as seedbed management, plant spacing, etc., are constantly being improved. In addition, the identification of breeding lines that have slight modifications in plant type or in efficiency of internal plant mechanisms, e.g., tillering ability, leaf angle photosynthetic efficiency, etc., could result in varieties with higher yield potential than IR8. With precise management, superior strains can be identified.

Pedigree nurseries

Pedigree nurseries were sown in November and December 1968 and in January, February, May, and July 1969. In these plantings, 45,661 pedigree rows were grown. Of this number, 2,283 rows consisted of parental check varieties planted every 20th row.

As shown in the 1968 Annual Report, many of the breeding lines grown in pedigree rows were derived from crosses in which IR8 was used as one of the parents. Often one or more backcrosses to IR8 were made. Consequently, many of the breeding lines have plant types similar to IR8. Due to the wide divergency of the varieties crossed with IR8, the breeding lines developed combine the IR8 plant type with many other traits, such as improved disease and

insect resistance, early maturity, weak photoperiod-sensitivity, moderate tillering, dark-green leaves, tough leaves, non-shattering grain, strong dormancy, various grain sizes and shapes, and high, intermediate, and low amylose content of the grain.

Many lines developed from this series of crosses are now being advanced to yield trials. The more promising ones are being used as parents in new crosses. As superior lines are identified, they replace IR8 as a parent in new crosses. In the future IR8 is not expected to be used extensively in the breeding program.

F₂ and F₃ bulk populations

The F₂ populations of many cross combinations were grown. These populations were made up of single cross combinations, three-way cross combinations, and first backcross combinations. A three-way cross combination results from crossing the F₁ plant of a single cross to a third variety or a true breeding line, or from crossing a single-cross F₃, or a line of a later generation, to a third variety or line. Usually, 3,000 to 4,000 plants of single crosses are grown. For other combinations, F₂ plant populations of only about 100 plants are grown.

A limited number of bulk hybrid populations were grown. Bulk hybrid populations seldom are carried beyond the F₄ generation. Selections are made from these populations to be grown in pedigree rows. IR20 and IR22 were both selected from F₄ bulk hybrid populations.

Maturity

High-yielding, very early maturing varieties adapted to transplanting or direct-seeding methods are being sought. Rapid seedling and vegetative development (including early tillering) are essential traits for high-yielding, early maturing varieties.

To evaluate very early maturing varieties, precise management practices must be used so that their full yield potential is achieved. So far, yields of very early maturing varieties have seldom exceeded 5,000 kg/ha. Probably the full yield potential has not been reached. We are revising seedbed management and insect and disease control practices and raising the rates of basal application of nitrogen with the aim of

more nearly achieving the full yield potential of these varieties.

New crosses which combine very early maturity with vigorous early vegetative growth are being made. Widely divergent lines showing early vegetative vigor are being intercrossed as another means of obtaining better strains. Also, genes for insect resistance (particularly resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers) are being combined with genes for early maturity and early vegetative vigor.

In much of tropical Asia, weakly photoperiod-sensitive varieties are required under present-day production practices. In East Pakistan during the Aman season, for example, farmers usually plant from mid-June to early August or before heavy rains. If planted in mid-June, non-sensitive varieties that resemble IR8 in growth duration ripen before the end of the monsoon season when the weather is unfavorable for harvesting and drying of the crop.

Weakly photoperiod-sensitive varieties with a basic vegetative period like that of IR20 can be seeded early (June 10) and they will mature only after the rains have diminished (mid-November). When seeded late (early August) their growth duration will be shortened due to the shorter days, and the crop will ripen by early December or before widespread water shortages. Such growing conditions apply to a part of the rice crop in many Asian countries. To identify weakly photoperiod-sensitive breeding lines, we are growing many lines in East Pakistan and elsewhere.

Disease and insect resistance

Blast. Screening of improved plant-type selections for resistance to the major diseases was continued and several new crosses were made. Blast-resistant lines from crosses involving Zenith, Sigadis, B589A4-18, Dawn, H-105, T. 172, Nahng Mon S-4, Leuang Yai 34, and Tadukan continued to show resistance in the tests conducted in several seasons.

A nursery consisting of 175 selections and varieties selected on the basis of their resistant reaction at Los Baños was sent for tests in Thailand, Indonesia, Ceylon, East Pakistan, India, Colombia, and Guyana. These lines were also tested in Leyte, Philippines, where races

of blast differ from and are more virulent than those at Los Baños. Selections from crosses involving Sigadis, a variety from Indonesia, were found resistant in Thailand, Ceylon, Guyana, and Colombia, but not in Indonesia. Selections from crosses involving H-105, T. 172, and B589A4-18 proved resistant in the Philippines, Indonesia, Ceylon, Guyana, and Colombia, but susceptible in Thailand. Selections from the crosses with Zenith and Dawn, however, were resistant at all testing locations. It therefore appears that of all the varieties used in the Institute's breeding program, Zenith and Dawn have the broadest spectrum of resistance to the blast fungus.

Recently plant pathologists identified two varieties, Tetep and Carreon, that appear to have an even broader spectrum of resistance than Zenith and Dawn. These varieties have been crossed with improved plant-type selections and we are evaluating the F₃ lines cooperatively with the plant pathologists.

Selections from these crosses that have improved plant-type and that are resistant at Los Baños will be evaluated for blast resistance in several countries.

Tungro. Screening of selections for resistance to tungro virus was continued in cooperation with the plant pathologists. Several highly resistant selections were obtained from Pankhari crosses. Some have good grain quality but their plant type is somewhat inferior.

The tungro resistance of Sigadis has also been transferred to lines with improved plant type. IR127-2-2-19 and IR127-80-1-10, selections from the cross CP-SLO x Sigadis, are resistant to tungro and have been used extensively in the hybridization program. Promising selections, such as IR661-1-140 and IR661-1-170, from the cross IR8 x IR127-2-2-19 also have the tungro resistance of Sigadis.

Peta is another good source of tungro resistance. Many selections with extremely good plant types have been selected from Peta crosses and backcrosses, but most of them are only moderately resistant to tungro.

Several selections from TKM-6 crosses are resistant to the virus but most have weak stems. Some selections from the cross IR8 x Tadukan

have shown a good level of resistance to tungro virus.

A fine-grained variety from India, HR 21, found to be highly resistant to the tungro virus by the plant pathologists, was crossed with a Peta/3 x Taichung (Native)I line and the F₃ pedigree rows were grown during the wet season. Several tungro-resistant lines with good grain type have been selected.

Approximately 800 selections from IRRI crosses were tested for their reaction to tungro under field conditions at Bangkhen Experiment Station, Thailand, in cooperation with Thai plant breeders and plant pathologists. Many resistant selections were identified.

Grassy stunt. Rice planted during the months of February, March, May, October, and November at the IRRI farm shows a high incidence of grassy stunt compared with plantings made in December and June. Moreover, if insecticides are not used during the seedling stage and if brown planthopper populations are allowed to build up, the incidence of grassy stunt usually is high.

Two grassy stunt nurseries were planted, one in November 1968 and one in May 1969. The November nursery consisted of 365 varieties and selections. Chianung 242, a ponlai japonica variety from Taiwan which is highly susceptible to grassy stunt, was planted every third row to spread the disease throughout the nursery. Several IR8 check rows were also planted. By February 1969, when the scoring was done, the incidence of grassy stunt was so high and so uniform throughout the nursery that almost all plants in the Chianung 242 rows were severely infected and 90 percent of the plants in the IR8 check rows were infected. A few varieties showed some resistance to the virus: TKM-6, Leuang Hawm, Khao Nam Kahng 92, Khao Pah 8-5-41, Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105, Puang Nahk 16, Niaw San Pah Tawng, Emata, HR 35, H-105, BPI-76, Pah Leud, H-8, and Khao Selti. Generally, 30 to 60 percent of the plants of these varieties did not show virus symptoms. Several selections from crosses involving some of these varieties showed a level of resistance similar to that of the parents.

Progeny rows from non-infected plants were

Table 1. Percentages of non-infected plants of some varieties and their progenies^a grown in the grassy stunt nurseries. Parents were grown in the nursery planted November 1968; progenies were grown in the nursery planted May 1969.

Variety or selection	Non-infected plants (%)		
	Parents	Progenies	
		Mean	Range
Khao Dawk Mali	41.0	59.8	19-60
Puang Nahk 16	31.1	30.2	9-50
Niaw San Pah Tawng	56.3	77.5	60-96
Emata	67.7	30.6	19-57
H-105	66.1	53.2	23-56
Pah Leuad	59.1	54.7	36-58
H-8	52.3	25.9	15-30
Khao Selti	50.7	47.6	26-64
IR12-178	46.0	33.0	12-39

^a Five non-infected plants of each variety were selected.

grown in the May-seeded virus nursery to determine whether the varieties were true-breeding or a mixture of susceptible and resistant genotypes. As shown in Table 1, the proportion of non-infected plants in the progenies was as high as in the parent varieties. Evidently, these varieties are not mixtures of susceptible and resistant genotypes, rather they have some field resistance to the virus or the vector. Accurate interpretation of field reaction requires a better understanding of the relationship between varietal resistance to the vector and varietal resistance to the virus.

In addition, several hundred varieties from the world collection were tested in the May 1969 grassy stunt nursery. Varieties with a low incidence of grassy stunt are listed in Table 2. These varieties will be retested in 1970. Meanwhile, wild taxa of the genus *Oryza* that are intercompatible with *Oryza sativa* are being screened cooperatively with plant pathologists for sources of higher levels of resistance to the grassy stunt virus.

Bacterial leaf blight. Improved plant-type lines classified as resistant to bacterial leaf blight from crosses involving Zenith, Sigadis, B589A4-18-1, Malagkit Sungsung, Tadukan, and TKM-6 continued to show resistance during both the dry and the wet seasons of 1969. In addition, F₃ lines from the cross (Peta/3 x TN1) x BJ-1 were grown during the wet season and screened for bacterial leaf blight resistance. Several lines equal to BJ-1 in level of resistance were selected

and will be retested during the 1970 dry season. Selections from the BJ-1 cross have inferior plant and grain type so one or more backcrosses to lines of improved plant and grain type will be needed to transfer its resistance to high-yielding lines.

A nursery consisting of 320 lines and varieties which showed some resistance to bacterial leaf blight at Los Baños was sent to Indonesia, Malaysia, and Ceylon. This nursery was tested at three locations in Indonesia and at three in Ceylon.

In Indonesia, several selections, mainly from crosses and backcrosses of Sigadis, were resistant at most locations. Sigadis was resistant at all locations. TKM-6 and Tadukan were moderately resistant at one location.

In Ceylon, Sigadis was moderately resistant, but one selection from a second backcross of Sigadis x Taichung (Native)1 (IR425-1-13-8-3), was highly resistant at all three locations. Zenith was moderately resistant at one location in Ceylon and moderately susceptible at the other. Tadukan and TKM-6 were moderately resistant at all locations. Varieties DZ 192 and PI 215936 were highly resistant at all locations in Ceylon. Several selections from the cross

Table 2. Some resistant varieties from the May 1969 grassy stunt nursery.

Variety	IRRI Acc. no.	Origin	Non-infected plants (%)
Nga-Kywe Tawng Pyan	11142	Burma	80
Tjere Mas	34	Indonesia	65
Co-13	10633	India	84
T 608	10604	India	77
No. Ch. 47	10612	India	70
PB76-66D-113	10295	Philippines	64
PB76-66D-14	10296	Philippines	61
HP 134	10160	India	64
Bhurci	10138	India	63
HP 129	10156	India	76
Abor 'A'	10043	India	64
Sail Paddy Bao Paddy	9934	India	73
Dumai	9953	India	68
J. C. 49	9108	India	65
J. C. 50	9109	India	67
T. D. 55	8286	Thailand	84
J. C. 125	9064	India	66
UCP 13	8719	E. Pakistan	68
Dahanala 2014	3469	Ceylon	72
Murunga 308	3473	Ceylon	71
59-811 x (Mas x Ptb 16)	167	Ceylon	76
No 10022	249	India	67

IR8/2 x Zenith were moderately resistant at one or more locations.

A new nursery of lines resistant to bacterial leaf blight has been sent to Indonesia, Malaysia, Ceylon, East and West Pakistan, and India for a thorough evaluation in cooperation with plant pathologists from IRRI and from other countries.

Bacterial leaf streak. Screening for bacterial leaf streak continued. During the wet season, natural infection of bacterial leaf streak occurred several times, especially after wind and rain storms. Varieties with tough leaves suffer less injury by strong winds than those with soft leaves. Consequently, the bacterial leaf streak organism has less opportunity to enter the leaves. Varieties and selections like Zenith, Nato, B589A4-18-1, R.L. Gopher, PI 215936, CP-SLO, and IR127-80-1-10 have tough leaves and also carry resistance to bacterial leaf streak. Many resistant lines with improved plant type have been selected from the crosses of these varieties. Screening is mainly confined to observing the field reaction during the wet season when natural outbreaks of this disease are common.

Brown planthoppers. Breeding for resistance to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers received major attention during the year. Mudgo and EK 1263 from India were used in the hybridization program. Both are highly resistant to brown planthoppers. F₃ progeny rows from the crosses of these two varieties were grown in the wet season and evaluated for resistance to brown planthoppers in cooperation with the entomologists. The F₄ selections will be evaluated in 1970. Selections from these crosses have poor grain and plant characteristics, so as soon as homozygous resistant lines are identified, they will be crossed with disease-resistant lines with improved plant and good grains. Selections with improved plant type from crosses involving H-105 that carry resistance to several diseases and to brown planthoppers, are available. These selections are being used as parents in the crossing program.

In a yield trial involving 55 early maturing selections, all but two were completely destroyed by planthoppers. IR747B2-6-3 (TKM-6/2 x TN1) and IR1154-243 (IR8/2 x Zenith) showed no damage and when subsequently tested in the greenhouse they were found to be resistant to

brown planthoppers. None of the parents involved in these two selections are highly resistant to the insect. These selections are being used in the breeding program as sources of resistance.

Green leafhoppers. Several varieties used extensively in the Institute's breeding program, such as Peta, Sigadis, IR8, and Pankhari 203, are resistant to green leafhoppers. As a result, many breeding lines from the crosses of these varieties are resistant to green leafhoppers, but not all have been evaluated for resistance. Our testing facilities are being expanded so that tests can be conducted more rapidly.

Resistance to major diseases and to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers have been combined with improved plant type. Some lines possess resistance to more than one disease and to more than one insect species. It should be possible to select genotypes which not only are resistant to the main diseases and insect species, but also have superior agronomic traits and high quality grain.

Indica x japonica crosses

As early as 1965, a series of indica x japonica crosses and backcrosses were made to combine improved plant type with cold resistance, early maturity, and several other traits of japonica varieties that are essential for successful rice production in temperate regions. These studies have been conducted in close cooperation with Korean scientists. Varieties possessing the IR8 plant type (high-tillering, erect leaves, and short, sturdy stems) might permit the use of higher nitrogen rates in Korea and thus increase grain yields. Present-day Korean varieties lodge severely at high rates of fertilization.

In 1969, Korean scientists selected several promising lines from the IRRI crosses. In 1970, a number of these lines will be tested in yield trials at IRRI and in Korea. To screen the lines for cold resistance they were seeded in East Pakistan in November. Previous studies in Korea at the seedling stage indicated that they differ widely in reaction to low temperatures.

Deep-water rice

Crosses made at IRRI between floating or deep-water varieties and semi-dwarf types have

Table 3. Yield data of lines grown in observational yield trial, 1969 dry and wet seasons.

IRRI cross no.	Parents	No. of lines		Yield range of the lines grown (kg/ha)					
		Dry season	Wet season	Dry season			Wet season		
				High	Low	Mean	High	Low	Mean
IR781	IR8/2 x [Yukara x TN1]	20	11	6401	3517	5102	6373	3860	5032
IR667	IR8 x [Yukara x TN1]	10	4	6808	4123	5456	6248	4131	5063
IR773	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	2	6	6714	6519	6616	5396	3814	4820
IR874	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4)	5	14	6866	5781	6304	6351	3589	4909
IR878	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	9	27	7706	5655	6580	5933	3377	5281
IR841	IR262-43-8-11 x Khao Dawk Mali	8	14	7909	6175	6778	6185	4717	5576
IR844	IR262-43-8-11 x Puang Nahk 16	3	9	7843	7264	7472	5995	4841	5220
IR789	IR8 x Muey Nahng 62M	8	3	8269	5804	7009	5334	4972	5171
IR790	(IR400-5-12-10-2 x IR8) x [IR4-253-3 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x TN1)]	7	17	8581	5816	7254	6668	3134	5330
IR578	IR8 x (Sigadis x TN1)	11	7	7590	5179	6490	6689	4115	5478
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	16	10	7820	5406	6685	6151	4216	5072
IR751	IR8/2 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	13	7	8170	5670	7090	6133	5350	5748
IR661	IR8 x IR127-2-2	14	17	8145	5252	6137	5687	3768	4840
IR579	IR8 x Tadukan	24	24	8185	5210	6982	6163	3619	5111
IR930	IR8 x IR12-178-2-3	21	10	8537	6849	7494	6575	4566	5553
IR580	IR8 x TKM-6	28	21	8929	6242	7685	6415	3507	5029
IR532	(Peta/3 x TN1) x TKM-6	47	27	8818	3928	7032	6368	3113	4800
IR710	IR262-24-3/2 x TKM-6	10	6	8030	5485	6808	5534	3504	4803
IR747	TKM-6/2 x TN1	3	13	7324	6267	6647	5911	2768	4462
IR8 (check plots)		27	22	8071	5923	6999	6657	5179	5808

demonstrated that the floating habit (the ability of stems to elongate in the vegetative stage of growth under deep-water conditions) can be combined with the semi-dwarf stature along with sturdy stems, erect leaves, and high tillering.

Cooperative work with Thai scientists has resulted in many promising strains. New crosses to combine this trait with insect and disease resistance, tough leaves, and a wide range in growth duration are being made.

Protein content

In the breeding program for high protein content, the F_4 and F_5 plant generations of pedigree lines from crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties were grown in 1969. Of approximately 1,600 pedigree lines from the F_5 generation (grown during the wet season) less than 9 percent had good plant type.

About 40 lines had good plant type and consistently showed high protein content through three plant generations. The lines averaged 12 percent protein, or 2 percentage points more than IR8 check plants. Some are breeding true for most visible traits so they will be advanced to replicated yield trials.

BPI-76 (photoperiod sensitive) has consistently

shown a higher protein content than other commercial varieties in the Philippines. This variety and BPI-76-1, a weakly photoperiod-sensitive selection, have been used as parents in several IRRI crosses. Some lines with good plant type that were selected from these crosses show reasonably high protein content (12%), indicating that the higher protein content of BPI-76 has been transferred to some of the progeny. Several of these lines will be tested in replicated yield trials in 1970.

Observational yield trials

In both the wet season and the dry season over 600 entries were grown in non-replicated, observational six-row, 5-meter-long, yield trial plots. Thirty-three of the dry-season entries and 53 of the wet-season entries were check varieties, the rest were promising selections from the pedigree nurseries and the previous observational yield trials. Data on yield, agronomic traits, and disease resistance of the plants of important crosses and on milling and cooking quality of their grain were obtained. Table 3 shows the yield range of lines of these crosses.

In the dry season, yields were considerably lower than in other years because of a heavy

Table 4. Yield data of lines grown in yield trials, 1969 dry and wet seasons.

IRRI cross no.	Cross	No. of lines		Yield range of the lines grown (kg/ha)					
		Dry season	Wet season	Dry Season			Wet season		
				High	Low	Mean	High	Low	Mean
IR661	IR8 x IR127-2-2	4	7	7875	5702	6769	6012	4639	5278
IR773	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	2	3	6370	6229	6299	5219	4994	5085
IR874	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4)	1	2			7907	6130	4558	5344
IR878	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	2	6	7143	6031	6587	5758	4713	5349
IR532	(Peta/3 x TN1) x TKM-6	8	13	7778	4832	6865	4872	3356	4185
IR580	IR8 x TKM-6	3	8	7500	6783	7175	5604	4504	5199
IR578	IR8 x (Sigadis x TN1)	4	2	7791	6346	6873	4779	4451	4615
IR305	Sigadis/2 x TN1	5	4	7399	6777	7063	5771	5294	5500
IR790	(IR400-5-12-10-2 x IR8) x [IR4-253-3 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x TN1)]	5	8	7677	7013	7137	5977	5018	5503
IR579	IR8 x Tadukan	1	8			7250	5946	4627	5355
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	10	7	7496	4178	6610	5438	4909	5241
IR751	IR8/2 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	4	3	7385	6156	6681	5465	4659	5140
IR442	(Peta/2 x TN1) x Leb Mue Nahng	7	2	6776	4754	5864	3267	3168	3217
IR8 (Check plots)		5	7	7474	6842	7161	5794	5019	5445
IR5	Peta x Tangkai Rotan					6309			4598
IR20	(Peta/3 x TN1) x TKM-6					6894			4641
IR22	IR8 x Tadukan								5946
Peta						4603			2073
Taichung (Native)1						7158			4227

build-up of brown planthoppers after flowering. Only 30 entries (two of them IR8) yielded over 8,000 kg/ha and none exceeded 9,000 kg/ha. In the wet season, 52 entries (eight of them IR8) yielded over 6,000 kg/ha. The average yield of IR8 was 6,999 kg/ha in the dry season and 5,808 kg/ha in the wet season. All the high-yielding lines were semi-dwarf and all resembled IR8 in plant type. Some had better grain quality and a higher level of disease resistance than IR8.

Replicated yield trials

Replicated yield trials, each with 189 entries, were planted in January and July. These trials were replicated three times in 6-row, 5-meter-long plots. In both experiments one plant was used per hill and the hills were spaced at 30 x 15 cm. The same fields were used for both experiments. In the dry-season experiment 120 kg/ha N was applied and in the wet season experiment, 90 kg/ha N. All entries in the two trials were evaluated for plant type and other agronomic traits, resistance to diseases and insects, and grain quality.

In the dry-season experiment, a serious attack of brown planthoppers at the post-flowering stage caused serious grain yield losses. Only one entry yielded over 8,000 kg/ha and only 14 entries yielded over 7,500 kg/ha. All these

entries were improved plant type, semi-dwarf selections. The yield of IR20 was 6,894 kg/ha. IR8, the check variety, averaged 7,161 kg/ha. The highest yielding entry was IR825-23 ([IR8 x Pankhari 203] x [Peta/6 x TN1]). It yielded 8,084 kg/ha. IR5 yielded 6,309 kg/ha; Taichung (Native)1, 7,158 kg/ha; and C4-63, 6,888 kg/ha.

Yields in the wet-season experiment were affected adversely by wind damage and a subsequent attack of bacterial leaf streak. Seven entries yielded over 6,000 kg/ha and 35 yielded over 5,500 kg/ha. All of these high-yielding entries were improved plant type, semi-dwarf selections. The highest yielding entry was IR506-1-36 with a yield of 6,290 kg/ha. The average yield of IR8 was 5,445 kg/ha; of IR5, 4,598 kg/ha; of IR20, 4,641 kg/ha; of IR22, 5,946 kg/ha; of Taichung (Native)1, 4,229 kg/ha; and of C4-63, 5,226 kg/ha.

Promising crosses entered in the two replicated yield trials are shown in Table 4. Information on the agronomic traits, disease resistance, and grain quality of the most promising lines is given in Table 5.

Seed increase

The seed increase project was greatly expanded during the dry season when 176 entries were grown. The seed increase project serves two

Table 5. Agronomic, disease, insect and quality data on selected varieties and lines grown in replicated yield trials at two plantings (January 1969 and July 1969), IIRRI.

Variety or selection	Grain yield (kg/ha)		Maturity ^a (days)		Plant height (cm)		Panicles (no./plant)		Lodging (%)		Diseases ^b		Insects ^b		Seed dormancy (%)		Milled rice (%)		Gel. temp. ^c	Amylose (%) Jan.
	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Tungro	BLB ^d	BLS ^e	Blast	Brown plant-hopper	Green leaf-hopper	Head	Total		
											(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)		
Taichung (Native) ¹	7158	4227	120	112	104	103	18.4	3	42	93	MR	S	S	S	S	S	59	72	L	30.2
Peta	4603	2073	137	144	171	165	12.4	100	100	24	S	S	S	S	S	R	66	72	L	31.8
C4-63	6888	5226	123	130	122	125	14.7	3	100	60	S	MR	S	S	S	R	62	70	H/Hi	29.3
BPI-76-1	5554	3576	125	130	134	141	11.2	87	100	75	S	S	MR	S	S	R	64	69	Hi/I	26.2
IR5	6309	4598	135	137	128	129	13.8	91	77	75	S	S	MR	S	R	R	64	71	I	33.0
IR5-81-3-2-3 ^f	6449	3716	129	132	130	127	13.3	40	67	45	S	R	S	S	MS	R	48	70	I	29.9
IR8	7161	5445	129	132	97	97	13.6	0	71	5	S	S	S	S	R	R	52	72	L	30.0
IR20	6894	4641	119	130	102	113	15.9	0	67	52	MR	MR	R	R	MS	MS	50	71	I	30.0
IR532-1-218-1 ^g	4832	4504	104	110	116	91	15.8	0	0	93	MR	MS	MR	MS	MS	MS	63	73	I	31.6
IR532E239 ^g	7778	3650	121	116	100	100	17.6	16	100	38	MS	MS	MR	MS	S	S	61	70	I	32.1
IR22	7370	5946	114	127	97	104	16.4	0	0	79	MR	MS	MR	MS	S	S	50	74	L	30.4
IR579-48-1-2 ^h	7436	5039	114	118	89	95	20.0	0	0	76	R	MS	R	MS	MS	MS	58	72	L	30.0
IR262-43-8-11 ⁱ	6660	5077	123	120	90	89	16.5	3	33	44	S	S	S	R	S	S	42	72	L	31.9
IR400-5-12-10-2 ⁱ	6262	4826	118	114	87	88	17.8	0	8	41	S	S	R	R	S	S	58	72	L	29.3
IR127-80-1-10 ^k	6922	4932	119	118	105	112	10.8	0	0	17	R	HR	MR	MS	MS	MS	21	68	Hi	22.2
IR140-136 ^l	5310	4875	116	115	121	121	14.2	63	25	34	S	R	MR	MR	S	S	62	70	Hi	21.6
IR305-3-17-1-3 ^m	6777	5294	129	130	89	98	18.1	0	55	33	MR	S	R	MR	MR	R	46	73	L	28.4
IR661-140-3 ⁿ	7875	6012	129	123	94	94	14.4	0	0	41	MS	MR	MS	MR	MR	R	40	61	L	19.3
IR874B ₂ -87-1 ^o	7907	6130	125	130	92	97	16.7	0	0	57	S	MR	MS	MS	S	S	56	73	I/L	29.9
IR878B ₂ -62-2 ^o	7143	5758	129	134	92	97	14.3	0	0	88	MR	MS	S	S	S	S	48	71	L	29.3
IR878B ₂ -122-1 ^o	6031	4713	124	125	86	89	16.1	0	0	80	MR	S	R	S	S	S	8	49	L	29.3
IR506-1-36 ^p	6677	6290	116	121	100	100	14.6	0	3	59	R	MS	MS	S	S	R	44	49	L	29.3
RD-1 (Thailand)	7187	3975	135	130	121	118	13.8	10	91	65	S	S	S	S	S	S	62	69	L	31.6
RD-3 (Thailand)	5014	5014	130	130	98	98	15.1	0	0	34	MS	S	S	MS	S	R	61	73	I/L	31.0
IR665-40-1 ^q	6512	5438	129	134	99	109	13.7	2	0	34	MS	MR	MS	MS	S	R	55	70	I/L	31.0

^a Seeding to harvest.

^b S = susceptible, R = resistant, M = moderately.

^c Gelatinization temperature based on alkali digestion. L = low.

^d H = high, I = intermediate.

^e Bacterial leaf blight.

^f Bacterial leaf streak.

^g Peta x Tangkai Rotan.

^h IR262-24-3 x TKM-6.

ⁱ IR8 x Tadukan

^j Peta/3 x TN1

^k CP-SLO x Sigadis

^l CP-SLO x Mas

^m Sigadis/2 x TN1

ⁿ IR8/2 x IR127-2-2

^o IR8/2 x [(CP-SLO) x Nahng Mon S-4]

^p IR8 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x TN1)

^q IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)

purposes. It provides seed for the widescale testing of promising new lines that would otherwise be delayed until the next crop season and it allows the lines to be observed under field conditions. A portion of each plot of each line is left standing for 2 or more weeks after maturity so that information on stiffness of straw, senescence, and disease reaction can be obtained in the post-ripening stage. The area planted to each line varied from one-sixtieth to one-fourth hectare, depending upon the projected demand for seed.

The yields obtained were reduced by a serious attack of brown planthoppers. Only one entry yielded over 8,000 kg/ha. Yield data on crosses and check varieties (IR8 and IR20) are shown in Table 6. Valuable information on uniformity, reaction to insects and diseases, lodging resistance, and grain quality was obtained. The superior qualities of IR22 were first revealed in a seed-increase plot grown during the dry season.

During the wet season, 16 promising lines were grown in ¼-ha fields. Two lines (IR661-140-3-2 and IR22) were multiplied on a large scale (several hectares).

Seed purification

Breeder seed of IR8 was produced during the dry season and that of IR5 in the wet season. Seed purification of IR20 was started during the 1968 wet season and that of IR22 in the 1969 wet season. Thus, when IR20 and IR22 were

named as varieties, pure seed was available for growing breeder seed. Breeder seed of both varieties will be grown during the 1970 dry season.

Seed purification plots of several outstanding new lines were grown so that pure seed for growing breeder seed would be available should any of them be named as varieties. A total of 33 lines was grown in 1969. During the purification process, the lines are checked for uniformity of visible traits such as time of heading, plant height, growth habit, grain size, etc., for disease and insect reaction, and for grain characteristics such as amylose content and gelatinization temperature. When extreme variability is found, as it was in IR661-1-140-3, new selections are made from single plant lines grown in purification rows.

International cooperative variety testing

Cooperative testing is an integral part of the rice breeding program. Promising selections and varieties from the Institute are sent to various cooperators and rice breeders in the major rice-growing countries of Southeast Asia and Latin America. Rice breeders in the cooperating countries thus have the opportunity to acquire new breeding materials, and IRRI breeders profit from the information obtained on the performance of these selections under different environmental conditions. During the year breeding lines were sent to cooperators in

Table 6. Yield data on selections and varieties grown in the seed-increase program, 1969 dry season.

IRRI cross no.	Parents	No. of entries	Yield range (kg/ha)		
			High	Low	Mean
IR594	IR8 x (CP-SLO x BPI-76)	4	5227	3909	4613
IR661	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	13	7932	4090	5992
IR874	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4)	2	7829	5450	6639
IR878	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	3	6408	4746	5764
IR593	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	5	7036	3625	5427
IR930	IR8 x IR12-178-2-3	4	5718	5455	5639
IR880	IR8 x (81B-25 x Dawn)	4	6420	5439	6073
IR442	(Peta/2 x TN1) x Leb Mue Nahng	3	6200	3836	5122
IR578	IR8 x (Sigadis x TN1)	3	6859	6583	6742
IR589	IR8 x (H-105 x Dgwg)	8	6980	4983	6317
IR662	IR8 x [IR4-253-3 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x TN1)]	4	6514	4461	5359
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	9	7751	3443	5725
IR580	IR8 x TKM-6	8	7555	4640	6336
IR844	IR262 x Puang Nahk 16	5	6406	5351	5748
IR579	IR8 x Tadukan	17	8483	5120	7129
IR781	IR8/2 x (Yukara x TN1)	4	7614	4554	6458
IR8 (Check plots)		12	7406	5765	6854
IR20 (Check plots)		8	7475	6504	7045

Australia, Burma, Brazil, Ceylon, Colombia, India, Indonesia, Korea, Laos, Malaysia, Mexico, Nepal, Pakistan, Peru, Taiwan, United Arab Republic (Egypt), U.S.A., and Vietnam.

At the end of the 1969 dry season, an international nursery of 95 promising selections was sent to most of the cooperating countries for testing and at the end of the wet season, a nursery of 41 selections was sent out. Special nurseries, such as a tungro nursery, bacterial leaf blight nursery, blast nursery, and a cold-resistance nursery, were sent to the cooperating countries, as described elsewhere in this report.

In a varietal testing project started in cooperation with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, a replicated yield trial of 44 promising selections was sent to Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Nigeria, Sudan, and UAR (Egypt) for growing during the wet season. The results of this trial are still awaited.

During the year, 15,998 samples of Institute breeding lines were sent to 185 organizations and individuals in 50 countries.

Several promising selections were given to IRRI agronomists to be tested for their response to nitrogen at IRRI and at three other locations in the Philippines. The results of these trials are given in the Agronomy section of this report.

A varietal testing program in cooperation with the Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) was also continued. Thirty seven varieties and promising selections were grown in a replicated yield trial during the dry season at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and at the Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur. The wet-season trial consisted of 50 entries at Maligaya and of 40 entries at Pili.

Several promising selections from the IRRI breeding program were entered in the Cooperative Lowland Rice Performance Tests conducted by University of the Philippines College of Agriculture and BPI during the dry and wet seasons. Minikit testing, a cooperative project of BPI and the Rice Production Training and Research Office of IRRI, included two selections from the IRRI breeding materials. Farmers' Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial (Fensart), a similar project for "on-the-

farm testing," included four IRRI entries, IR8, IR20, IR22, and IR661-1-140-3-2.

New varieties

Two new rice varieties, IR20 and IR22, were named by the Institute on November 24. They are the third and fourth varieties to be named. The first was IR8, named in 1966; the second was IR5, named in 1967. The experimental line IR532E576 was named IR20 and IR579-160-2 was named IR22. The new varieties represent a considerable improvement over IR8 and IR5, but they are just steps on the way to even better varieties for the tropics.

IR20 was selected from an F_4 bulk hybrid population of the cross IR262-24-3 x TKM-6 made in 1965. IR262-24-3 was a line selection from the second backcross of Peta and Taichung (Native)1. The TKM-6 variety was used as a parent because of its resistance to stem borers. The F_2 population was seeded March 1966 and F_2 panicles were saved from selected dwarf plants in the population for growing in an F_3 bulk hybrid plot (seeded October 1966). Selected panicles were again saved for growing a bulk hybrid F_4 plot (seeded March 1967) which was evaluated for resistance to stem borers by the entomologists. Some 600 plant selections were made by entomologists on the basis of resistance to stem borers. These line selections were grown in pedigree rows (seeded August 1967) and evaluated for resistance to stem borers for agronomic and grain characteristics.

Sixteen pedigree lines of good plant type and low incidence of stem borers were bulk-harvested and each line was grown in a seed-increase plot during the 1968 dry season (F_6). IR532E576 was one of the most promising lines, so plant selections were made for growing in head-row purification plots during the 1968 wet season and the 1969 dry season. Breeder seed was grown during the 1969 wet season. IR20 was added to the Philippine Seed Board list of approved lowland rice varieties in December.

IR22 was selected from an F_4 bulk hybrid population of the cross IR8 x Tadukan made in September 1965. The F_2 population of the cross was seeded in June 1966 and panicles from selected dwarf plants were saved for seeding an F_3 bulk population sown in December 1966.

Panicles from many F_3 plants were harvested for seeding an F_4 bulk hybrid population sown in June 1967. Plant selections were made from the F_4 bulk hybrid population and grown in F_5 pedigree rows sown in December 1967. Plant selections were made from promising pedigree rows and again grown in F_6 pedigree rows sown in June 1968.

The F_6 pedigree row of IR579-160-2 was bulk-harvested and during the 1969 dry season it was grown in a single observational yield trial plot as well as in a seed-increase plot. Due primarily to outstanding performance in the seed-increase plot, line IR579-160-2 was advanced during the 1969 wet season to replicated yield trials and seed was distributed to other departments of IRRI and to agencies in the Philippines and elsewhere for extensive testing. A head row purification plot was also grown.

The grain of IR20 is of medium length while that of IR22 is long. The grains of both varieties are slender, translucent, and free of white belly. Thus, they are acceptable to Asian consumers because of their attractive appearance and high recovery of head rice and total milled rice. Because of a high amylose content (about 30 percent) they are dry and fluffy when cooked. IR20 has an intermediate and IR22 a low gelatinization temperature of grain starch.

Both varieties have vigorous seedlings, erect leaves, and a high tillering capacity. They are similar to IR8 in plant height. Compared with IR8 and IR22, IR20 has smaller and weaker stems. Its leaf sheath ages and disintegrates more rapidly. Consequently, IR20 is likely to lodge. Usually IR20 lodges only a few days before harvest, so yield reductions are not great, but when rainy, windy weather occurs shortly after heading, early lodging is likely to occur and may reduce yield significantly.

The new varieties are as resistant to most diseases as IR8, but more resistant to blast and bacterial leaf blight. IR20 is more resistant than IR8 to bacterial leaf streak. IR22 may be more susceptible to tungro virus than IR8 because in the Philippines it is not resistant to the green leafhopper, the vector of the virus. IR20 in the Philippines is not as resistant to the green leafhopper as IR8, but in greenhouse tests it usually shows a lower percentage of tungro-infected

plants. In East Pakistan, under field conditions, IR20 is more resistant than IR8 to a tungro-like virus. Different strains of the virus or different biotypes of the green leafhopper, or both, may be involved. Like IR8, both IR20 and IR22 are susceptible to brown planthoppers.

Compared with IR8, the growth durations of IR20 and IR22 are more sensitive to day length than IR8. In the wet season at the IRRI farm (14°N), IR20 usually is harvested 135 days after seeding in the seedbed, or about a week later than IR8. In the dry season it matures in about 120 days, or almost a week earlier than IR8. During the dry season IR22 has a shorter growth duration (115 days) than either IR20 or IR8. It matures in 130 days in the wet season. In rice-growing regions farther from the equator, the growth duration of both new varieties is longer. IR20 requires 160 to 165 days to mature in north India and northwest Pakistan.

IR22 has moderate grain dormancy which is similar to IR8 while IR20 has relatively strong dormancy.

Genetic and cytogenetic studies

Component characters of plant type

The plant characters related to a physiologically efficient plant type in the tropics may be narrowed down to four: Vegetative growth vigor in the juvenile stage; a short plant stature (about 100 cm); dark, erect, and relatively short leaves; and a growth duration from seeding to heading of 80 to 100 days. The inheritance of plant stature and growth duration has been investigated in detail at the Institute, but genetic information on the other traits is rather meager.

Three crosses were made to analyze the component traits of an improved plant type. Bengawan and BJ-1 were selected to represent the tropical type: they produce long and drooping leaves when grown on fertile soil, but are relatively early in maturity and are photoperiod insensitive. Two semi-dwarf lines, IR160-27-3-1-3-2 and IR400-5-12-10-2, were chosen because they have very erect leaves and other essential attributes of an efficient plant type. However, the IR400 line had earlier maturity and a higher tillering ability than the IR160 line.

Fig. 1. Differences in the leaf angle (of openness) among tall and short parents and their F_1 hybrids.

F_1 hybrids of the IR400 line x BJ-1, Bengawan x the IR400 line, and the IR160 line x Bengawan were grown in the wet season together with their parents. Data was taken on plants surrounded on four sides by competing plants. The degree of dominance exhibited by the F_1 hybrids is indicated by the potence ratio (hp) between [F_1 - midparent value] and [high parent - midparent value].

Two of the F_1 populations produced a larger mean tiller number than the high parent at 40 days after seeding. The higher tillering ability of the F_1 plants was maintained in the overdominance range in two crosses up to the 70th day after seeding. In the other cross, the hybrid and the high parent produced the same number of tillers and the potence value indicated a complete dominance of high tillering over low tillering. However, when the panicle numbers were compared, only the BJ-1 x IR400 cross remained in the overdominance range, while in the other two crosses, the panicle number of the F_1 plants was intermediate between the high parent and the midparent value, indicating a partial dominance of high panicle number.

To obtain the angle of leaf openness, the leaf angle of the uppermost fully exerted leaf from the vertical axis of the plant to the tip of the blade was measured. At three sampling dates,

the hybrids and parents alike showed a gradual change from larger to smaller angles (Fig. 1). The F_1 hybrids generally had more drooping leaves than the erect-leaved parent at different growth stages. On the 70th day, the potence value of all three crosses were in the range of partial dominance for larger leaf angles.

When the semi-dwarf parent had nearly horizontal flagleaves, the F_1 hybrids were intermediate between the parents. When the semi-dwarf parent had very erect flagleaves, erectness was partially dominant over nearly horizontal angles in the F_1 hybrids.

Leaf length and width were markedly variable among F_1 plants of the same cross at any given date of sampling. The F_1 hybrids generally produced slightly shorter blades than the long-leaved parent, but the potence ratio did not show a consistent pattern. Hybrids produced from the cross between narrow-leaved BJ-1 and the broad-leaved IR400 line indicated a partial dominance of broad leaves. In the two crosses involving Bengawan, the hybrids produced narrower leaves than the mean of the two parents.

When leaf area was estimated from the product of length and width with different weighted factors, the estimates were considerably greater in the hybrids involving the IR400 line, indicating overdominance or true heterotic vigor. In

Table 7. Average percentages of F_1 performance compared with the midparent (MP) and high parent (HP) values and percentages of F_2 depression from F_1 for seven agronomic traits.

Trait	$(F_1-MP)/MP$		$(F_1-HP)/HP$		$(F_1-F_2)/F_1$
	1966 (%)	1967 (%)	1966 (%)	1967 (%)	1967 (%)
Days to heading	-11.14**	-9.60**	-19.77**	-16.55**	-5.49**
Plant height	10.57**	9.93**	-2.34**	-1.89**	1.71*
Panicles/plant	19.39**	17.11**	-10.95**	-11.99**	3.38*
Panicle length	3.46**	5.09**	-6.33**	-5.83**	2.16**
Panicle weight	-14.51**	—	-32.10**	—	—
Spikelet no./panicle	-2.93	—	-16.56**	—	—
Grain yield/plant	8.05**	—	-5.06**	—	—

* Significant difference from zero at 5% level.

** Significant difference from zero at 1% level.

the other cross involving the short and narrow-leaved IR160 line, the potence ratio indicated a partial dominance of smaller leaf areas.

The number of leaves on the main culm varied from 13 to 16 in the four parents. The hybrids showed intermediate counts.

The data on plant height again showed the incomplete dominance of tall stature. The number of days from seeding to heading of F_1 plants was related to the growth duration of the parents. When both parents were early maturing, the F_1 hybrids flowered a few days later, but when the two parents differed markedly in heading date, the potence ratios were in the partial dominance range, either on the upper or lower side of the midparent value. An early parent, like the IR400 line, produced a negative potence ratio, indicating the partial dominance of earliness.

Comparison of parents and F_1 and F_2 hybrids in diallel cross

Additional data obtained from the six sets of F_1 hybrids and F_2 progenies of the four-parent diallel cross (1966 and 1967 Annual Reports) were used to explore the possibility of using F_1 hybrids in improving yield levels and related agronomic characteristics. The four parents, Sukhwel-20, H-4, Dawn, and Sigadis, were selected on the basis of extreme differences in one or more agronomic traits. The single recessive gene for semi-dwarfism and its related effects was not involved in this series of crosses.

The traits we analyzed were plant height, number of days from seeding to heading, number of panicles per plant, panicle length, weight of five panicles from each plant, number of

spikelets per panicle, and percentage of fertile spikelets (grains). The sample sizes were 64 plants each for the parents and the F_1 's in 1966 and 60 parent plants, 20 F_1 plants, and 560 F_2 plants per cross in the 1967 dry season.

The mean heading date of the F_1 plants was earlier than the mean midparent value (Table 7). Similarly, the mean of F_1 populations was smaller than the mean of F_2 populations. When compared with the early parent in different crosses, only one F_1 population was later than the early parent of that cross. These comparisons suggest the feasibility of reducing growth duration through the use of F_1 hybrids. This observation is consistent with previous findings based on the basic vegetative phase.

All F_1 values for plant height were greater than the midparent values. The incomplete dominance of tallness had previously been indicated in a number of crosses.

The means of the F_1 values for both panicle length and panicle number per plant exceeded the midparent values, but were lower than those of the high parents when all crosses were compared. Among the six crosses, however, one F_1 population exceeded the high parent in panicle number. Four F_1 populations exceeded the F_2 means in panicle number and panicle length, while the other two F_1 populations were inferior to the F_2 means.

For panicle weight and number of spikelets per panicle, both F_1 means were lower than the midparent values (significantly lower for panicle weight). Only in one cross did the F_1 hybrids produce heavier panicles than the midparent value. For spikelet number, one cross exceeded the high parent and two others exceeded the

midparent values. Among the three F_1 populations having higher spikelet number, the two crosses involving Dawn showed partial sterility (about 40 percent fertility), and therefore, had low panicle weight.

The mean grain yield per plant of F_1 hybrids was 8 percent higher than the mean midparent value, but was 5 percent below the mean of the high parents. Only in two crosses did the F_1 plants exceed the midparent values, but none surpassed those of the high parent. Thus, the F_1 populations failed to show true heterosis for grain yield. The higher percentage of sterility of most hybrids is in part responsible for the failure of F_1 plants to surpass the high parents in grain production.

Inheritance of grain dormancy

In a series of crosses involving moderately dormant, weakly dormant, and non-dormant varieties, we found in 1967 that grain dormancy

has a complex mode of inheritance, that environment greatly affects the expression of dormancy, and that the relative moderately dormant genotypes can be easily identified by conducting germination tests 2 to 3 weeks after grain maturation (1967 Annual Report). Additional crosses were made to include the strongly dormant x non-dormant, strongly dormant x moderately dormant, and moderately dormant x non-dormant combinations.

Seven populations of F_2 plants, representing F_2 genotypes, were grown during the dry season along with the parents. Germination tests of air-dried panicles were made on the 7th, 21st, and 60th day after harvest. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution by germination percentage at three dates of 320 F_2 plants and of the two parents in a strongly dormant x non-dormant cross. Although two-thirds of the F_2 plants in the first germination test were dormant, the remaining plants were distributed over the

Fig. 2. Distributions and means of parents and F_2 plants by germination percentage classes in the cross of Taichung (Native)1 x Mayang Ebos 80 at 7, 21, and 60 days after harvest. Horizontal lines show the range of parents about the means (dotted circles).

Fig. 3. Distributions and means of parents and F₂ plants by germination percentage classes in the cross of Binato x Peta at 7, 21, and 60 days after harvest. Horizontal lines show the range of parents about the means (dotted circles).

entire range of the two parents. During the second germination test, about one-third of the F₂ progeny were as dormant as the parent, Mayang Ebos 80. By 60 days after harvest, the dormant parent had practically lost all of its dormancy. Only a few of the F₂ progeny showed weak dormancy; the remaining plants were no longer dormant. The F₂ distribution in the Mayang Ebos 80 x Taichung (Native)1 cross is very similar to that of the moderately dormant Peta x non-dormant I-geo-tze cross obtained in the 1966 wet season. Both crosses indicated multigenic control of a multiplicative type of gene action in the initial germination test.

The distribution of F₂ plants in the strongly dormant by moderately dormant cross of Mayang Ebos 80 x Peta was similar to that of Mayang Ebos 80 x Taichung (Native)1, even though most Peta plants showed distinct dormancy on the seventh day after harvest. Dor-

mancy in the F₂ progeny diminished nearly as rapidly as that in the Mayang Ebos 80 x Taichung (Native)1 cross in the subsequent germination tests.

In the Peta x non-dormant Binato cross, 183 F₂ plants out of 289 showed dormancy in the first germination test. By the third week, the F₂ plants were almost equally distributed over all 10 class intervals (Fig. 3). On the 60th day, only a few plants indicated any dormancy. The distribution of F₂ plants in this cross during the first germination test is similar to that obtained in the 1966 wet season from the cross of CP-SLO x PI 215936 which involved two weakly dormant parents.

The expression of short-duration dormancy in the strongly dormant Mayang Ebos 80 parent and its hybrid progeny in two crosses grown in the dry season could be attributed to a lack of rain from heading to maturity. Thus, without

rain, the strongly dormant genotypes behaved like the moderately dormant genotypes in a wet season.

Additional crosses involving strongly dormant parents that were also photoperiod-sensitive were planted in the wet season to determine the mode of segregation among F_2 plants. This series of crosses was made to broaden the spectrum of genetic diversity among intensely dormant genotypes.

Agronomic traits of Peta x T(N)1 backcrosses

During the 1964-65 growing seasons, when [Peta x Taichung (Native)1] hybrids were repeatedly backcrossed to Peta, tall and semi-dwarf segregates from randomly sampled backcross progenies were saved. These tall and semi-dwarf lines were grown in subsequent seasons until a high degree of homozygosity in plant height and heading date was reached within a line. Progenies from different backcross populations were grown in staggered plantings so they would reach a similar stage of selfing (F_5 or F_6) when yield trials were conducted in the 1968 dry season.

The comparative trial was divided into two groups by height. In the tall group, the 81 entries consisted of the Peta parent and 20 lines each of Peta/3, Peta/4, Peta/5, and Peta/6 backcross populations. In the semi-dwarf group, in addition to Taichung (Native)1, 16 lines each from the Peta/2, Peta/3, Peta/4, Peta/5, and Peta/6 populations were included. The yield trials were conducted as a simple lattice (9^2) design, replicated twice and containing four-row plots, 5 meters long. Single-seedling hills were spaced at 30 x 25 cm and given a basal application of 40 kg/ha N. Data were taken on tiller number (60 days after seeding), leaf color (in code number), date of heading, plant height, angle of openness of the leaf below the flagleaf, angle of the flagleaf, 100-grain weight, ratio of panicles to tillers, and grain yield.

In the semi-dwarf group, 80 lines of the five backcross populations and the T(N)1 parent gave grain yields ranging from 3,954 to 6,781 kg/ha. The differences among the 81 entries were highly significant. However, the mean yields of the dwarf parent and the five backcross populations were similar (range: 5,600 to 5,960

kg/ha) and the differences among lines within a backcross were not significant except in the Peta/5 x T(N)1 population.

Among the six agronomic traits, highly significant differences among lines were obtained for heading date, plant height, tiller number, leaf angle, and 100-grain weight. The mean heading date was appreciably delayed after one backcross to Peta. It was further delayed by repeated backcrossing except in the Peta/4 x T(N)1 population. Plant height decreased after three backcrosses, probably due to an unconscious selection of the modifying genes for shorter plant stature carried by T(N)1 (1966 Annual Report, p. 68) in the backcrossing process. The backcrossed lines generally had larger leaf angles and greater 100-grain weights than the T(N)1 parent. Tiller number did not show a consistent trend. The ratio of panicles to tillers decreased slightly after the backcrossing to Peta, but the percentage values, after square-root transformation, did not indicate significant differences among or within lines of a backcross population. The flagleaf angle of the 81 entries showed significant variation and ranged from very erect to horizontal. But the different populations and the T(N)1 parent did not differ significantly in their mean values. About 60 percent of the lines showed erect flagleaves (less than 45°). Much of the variability was traceable to variation among lines in the Peta/2, Peta/3, and Peta/4 backcrosses.

Practically all tall lines showed varying degrees of lodging before harvest. Though strings and stakes were installed to separate some of the very tall lines, a number of the plots that lodged early produced patches of rotten culms and soiled panicles. For such entries, grain samples were taken from normal plants, many of which had partly benefited from support of stakes and strings. The yield estimates were undoubtedly inflated when the harvested samples were converted to a hectare basis. Thus yield estimates ranging between 1,520 kg/ha and 4,960 kg/ha were obtained from the 81 tall entries.

The difference among all tall entries was significant, but the comparisons between Peta and the mean of different backcross populations and those among lines within a backcross population

were not significant. The mean yields of four backcross populations differed at a highly significant level, and showed an upward trend with repeated backcrossing.

Heading dates were generally earlier in the tall lines than in the short lines in the same backcross population. They showed pronounced variation among and within lines of the same population. Backcrossing tended to lengthen the period from seeding to heading. Plant height also increased with the number of backcrosses, but the proportional increases were less consistent. The 100-grain weight and tiller number varied appreciably among the 81 entries and among the backcross populations, but no consistent trend was shown by different populations. The tall lines in general produced more droopy leaves than the short lines, but the variation among tall lines and the difference between Peta and the backcross populations were not significant. The mean ratio of panicles to tillers was high in the tall lines, probably because the tillers of the tall lines were counted on the same day as those of the short lines. At this time, many tall lines were still producing late tillers. An interesting feature was that the flagleaves of all tall lines showed horizontal angles.

Partitioning the variance components of traits of the semi-dwarf lines showed that the component due to different numbers of backcrosses was smaller than most variance components within backcrosses. The tall lines generally produced larger backcross variance components for various traits than the short lines. But the backcross components in the tall lines were generally greater than the within-population components. The general trend in both semi-dwarf and tall lines was a proportional decrease of the variance components within-backcross as the number of backcrosses increased. This trend might not entirely reflect the increase in homogeneity among lines within a backcross population with repeated backcrossing, since the number of plants used in the backcrossing program varied from one generation to another.

Simple and partial correlation analysis indicated that among semi-dwarf lines in the first backcross population, grain yield was positively correlated with plant height and 100-grain

weight. When plant height was held constant, grain yield and heading date showed a negative association. In the fifth backcross population, grain yield was positively associated with plant height and tiller number. The association between yield and height was highly significant when any other agronomic trait was held constant.

Plant height and heading date were positively associated in the dwarf lines of three backcross populations. Plant height and tiller number were negatively correlated in two backcrosses.

Since the yield figures were biased in the tall lines, correlation coefficients obtained between grain yield and any of the plant characters were not valid. Among the plant characters, heading date and plant height were positively correlated in the Peta/3 and Peta/4 populations. Plant height and 100-grain weight also were positively correlated in these two populations. Plant height and tiller number were positively correlated in all backcross populations.

Multiple regression analysis indicated that when plant height, tiller number, leaf angle, and 100-grain weight were jointly considered, their variations could account for 27 to 46 percent of the variation in grain yield within a backcross population in the semi-dwarf lines. The multiple correlation coefficients were greater in the Peta/5 and Peta/6 populations than in the other three. When all eight agronomic traits were jointly considered, their contributions to the variation in grain yield were increased to a range of 35 to 68 percent.

Leaf structure and wind damage

During the early part of a wet season when strong winds prevail, varieties or selections usually show visible differences in the extent and mode of wind damage. In some lines, particularly at maximum tillering stage, the leaf breaks across the blade. In many other lines, the wind breaks the leaf tips along the veins, shredding the upper portion of the blade. Rice selections differ greatly in their resistance to these two types of wind damage.

Dawn and IR456-18-4-1-1-2 (Dawn x CP-SLO) were taken as representatives of selections resistant to wind damage. No shredding or tearing was noted after typhoons. On the

other hand, severe shredding and lacerations were observed in such lines as IR630-1-53-3 (IR8 x IR5) and IR580E162-325 (IR8 x TKM-6).

Histological examination of the cross-section taken within the upper one-third of the leaf blade revealed three important differences between lines resistant to leaf breakage and non-resistant lines.

First, the mechanical tissues of the sub-epidermal layer on both sides of the blade were 36 to 66 percent thicker and the sclerenchyma cells were 39 to 130 percent wider in the resistant lines than in the susceptible lines. The difference was particularly noticeable at the cluster of lignified cells (fibers) flanking the vascular bundles near the leaf margins.

Second, in the resistant lines, the leaf margins contained two to three layers of sclerenchyma cells, while in the susceptible lines they generally had a single layer.

Third, along the ridged veins of the blade where the bundle sheaths and vascular bundles are found, the fibers flanking the bundle sheath in the resistant lines were wider and thick-walled. The cell wall often was 20 to 150 percent thicker in the resistant lines.

Thus the higher degree of lignification found in the resistant lines protected them from the shearing stress of strong winds.

Cytology of sterility in indica x indica hybrids

An investigation of the cytogenetic nature of F_1 sterility in crosses among tropical and subtropical varieties done in cooperation with the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines was completed in 1969. In addition to the 21 reciprocal crosses studied in 1968, 44 cross-combinations were examined this year. The indica varieties used and their countries of origin were Peta, Sigadis, and Untung (Indonesia); TKM-6, Pankhari 203, Basmati 370, and MTU-15 (India); Milfor-6(2) and IR8 (Philippines); and T(N)1 (Taiwan). Two bulu's, Boegi Imba and Rodjolele, which originated in Indonesia were also used.

The hybrids were usually sterile whenever one of the three Indian indicas (TKM-6, Basmati 370, and the Pankhari 203) or the two bulu's was used as one of the parent varieties. The most sterile hybrids came from crosses of Pankhari

203 with IR8, Peta, T(N)1, MTU-15, Boegi Imba, and Rodjolele. Among the four Indian indicas, MTU-15 appeared to be the most cross-fertile variety. Yet, it produced low pollen fertility (26%) when crossed with Pankhari 203.

Five of the 65 cross-combinations showed reciprocal differences in spikelet fertility at the 5-percent level of significance and 16 at the 1-percent level. Only two cross-combinations, MTU-15 x Sigadis and Boegi Imba x Peta, showed differences in pollen fertility, however. The differences were significant at the 1-percent level.

Taking all the parents and F_1 plants together, a highly significant correlation coefficient of 0.65 was obtained for pollen and spikelet fertility.

At pachynema, chromosome pairing in all parents was normal except for some degree of "loose pairing" (5.0 to 46.7%). "Loose pairing" was notably high in Boegi Imba (46.7%). Average "loose pairing" for all the parents was 20.3 percent. One cell in Milfor-6(2) showed two unpaired chromosomes.

Most hybrids also showed normal pachytene pairing. In six of 45 hybrids, the percentage of normal cells was as high as that found in Basmati 370 which had the highest proportion of normal cells (95.0%) among the parents at pachynema. Eight cross-combinations exhibited structural aberrations (1.4 to 10.0%) in the form of bivalents with unequal length. Such bivalents may be heterozygous for terminal or small interstitial deletions. The presence of unequal bivalents was not associated with the sterile hybrids. Fertile hybrids like Boegi Imba x Rodjolele, Pankhari 203 x Basmati 370, and TKM-6 x Sigadis also exhibited unequal bivalents. "Loose pairing" similar to that observed in the parents was also noted in most of the hybrids at a frequency ranging from 2.9 to 57.1 percent. Average "loose pairing" in the hybrids was 21.3 percent. Such "loose pairing" may also be due to dissociation of the homologous chromosomes at very early diplonema since they were not morphologically different from those observed in the parents.

At diakinesis through telophase I, the abnormalities did not differ appreciably in kind and frequency from those previously reported in the 21 cross-combinations (1968 Annual Report).

Table 8. Selected sources of resistance to the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper.

Variety	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Reaction ^a	
			Brown plant-hopper	Green plant-hopper
Mudgo	India	6663	HR	S
Pankhari 203	India	5999	S	HR
Manavari CO22	India	6400	R	MR
Karsamba Red ASD7	India	6303	HR	HR
Kayama MGL 2	India	6218	R	MR
Dalwa Sannam MTU15	India	6365	R	MR
PTB 18	India	11052	R	HR
H 105	Ceylon	158	R	MS
Muthumanikam	Ceylon	8960	R	MR
Vellanlangalayan	Ceylon	8958	R	MR
DK1	E. Pakistan	8574	S	HR
DV139	E. Pakistan	8870	S	R
Su-Yai 20	China	7299	S	R
Bir-tsan No. 3	China	4335	S	R
AC 435	China	45	S	HR
Sigadis	Indonesia	611	MS	R
IR8	Philippines	9925	MS	R

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

In all the 65 hybrid combinations together, the abnormalities observed and their frequency at diakinesis and metaphase I were: two univalents (0.2 to 6.0%); four univalents (0.5 to 1.4%); one quadrivalent (0.3 to 4.2%); two quadrivalents (0.2%); one ring-of-four (0.3 to 0.7%); one trivalent and one univalent (0.2 to 1.0%); one hexavalent (0.2%); and two trivalents (0.8%). The frequency of normal cells ranged from 92 percent in Pankhari 203 x Boegi Imba to 100% in 14 hybrid combinations, or an average of 98.1 percent.

At anaphase I and telophase I, there were bridges without accompanying fragments (0.2 to 5.3%) in 12 cross-combinations, bridges with acentric fragments (0.5 to 1.4%) in six cross-combinations, and laggards which were mostly univalents (0.4 to 4.8%) in 18 hybrids. All abnormalities were obviously not directly associated with the incidence of pollen or spikelet fertility in the different cross-combinations. For example, the most sterile hybrids, Pankhari 203 x IR8 and Pankhari 203 x T(N)1, had averages of 93.5 to 94.7 percent normal cells for all stages of meiosis.

The hybrid populations generally exhibited a slightly wider range of meiotic abnormalities and a higher frequency of each compared with the parents. These differences suggest that a small portion of the sterility may be chromo-

somal. The frequency of the abnormalities is too low however to account for the very high sterility in some of the hybrids. Furthermore, when the percentage of normal cells for all stages of meiosis in the hybrids was compared to the mean of the two parents, the percentage of normal cells in the hybrid was often similar to that observed in the parents. Sometimes it was even higher than that in one parent or the average of the two parents.

Although sterility was often associated with the three Indian indicas and the two bulu varieties, the hybrids could not be grouped according to the type or frequency of meiotic abnormalities. For example, the incidence of sterility was higher when Indian indicas were crossed with the indicas of other regions (IR8, T(N)1, and Peta) while the observed meiotic abnormalities were not confined to these particular hybrids.

Repeated crossing and backcrossing is needed to determine whether the differences detected in some reciprocal crosses were due to a purely cytoplasmic cause or to a cytoplasmic-gene interaction. The difference observed may have been due to environment since they appeared only in the spikelet. Furthermore, the array of data from a particular female parent was not consistent. In some crosses the hybrid showed higher fertility than its reciprocal when used as a female parent and, at other times, when used as the male parent.

Therefore, sterility in indica x indica and indica x bulu hybrids of rice is probably due to complex genic interactions rather than to cytoplasmic causes, cytoplasmic-gene interaction, or chromosomal differences at the microscopic level.

Genetics of resistance to insects

Breeding for resistance to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*, and the green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, is becoming increasingly important. Studies on the inheritance of the resistance of Mudgo to brown planthopper and of Pankhari to green leafhopper (see the Entomology section) showed that the resistance of each depends on a single dominant factor. The current breeding program aims at incorporating these factors in future varieties. The natural variability of the insect populations could lead to the build-up of insects that may

attack the resistant varieties. To insure against the variability in the two insects, genetic studies, in cooperation with the entomologists, have been undertaken to identify diverse factors for resistance.

Table 8 lists the sources of resistance selected from different geographical areas which are being utilized in the genetic studies. As these studies have progressed we have found that some insect-resistant varieties are not pure: occasionally one of their seedlings is susceptible. Single-plant selections from these varieties have been made to build up pure stocks of seed.

An efficient technique for testing hybrid material is basic to genetic studies. Two testing techniques have been developed and used. One, the "bulk seedling test," involves planting the hybrid material in wooden flats, infesting the seedlings with insects at the one-leaf stage, and classifying the reaction on the basis of damage suffered as a result of insect infestation.

The second technique consists of infesting individual plants by caging a known number of insects on each plant and classifying the plant reaction on the basis of insect survival. Seedlings of varying age have been tried. Caging young seedlings for infestation interfered with their normal development primarily because sunlight was cut off. Lack of sunlight encouraged lanky growth and lowered the resistance of seedlings to the insects. The best results were obtained by infesting a tiller of a 6- to 7-week-old plant. This technique will be referred to as the "tiller test."

For the tiller test, single F_2 plants and the parent varieties are grown in 15-cm pots under insect-free conditions. When the plants are about 6-weeks old, one tiller is placed in a cage and 15 second- or third-instar nymphs are introduced into the cage. A cylindrical cage of mylar plastic, 53-cm long and 8 cm in diameter, is used to enclose the entire tiller for the green leafhopper test and a smaller cage, 13-cm long and 4 cm in diameter, is used to enclose the stem of a tiller for the brown planthopper test. Nylon mesh ventilators are provided to aerate the cages. The comparative survival of the insects on individual plants is determined by counting the living insects about 10 days after infestation. The frequency distribution based on insect

survival is used for genetic interpretation of the data.

The chief advantage of the tiller test is that an F_2 plant with known reaction can be grown to maturity and its phenotypic reaction confirmed by studying the breeding behavior of its F_3 progeny with the bulk seedling test. Also, two separate tillers of the same plant can be used to determine its reaction to the two insects simultaneously. The tiller test, however, is more successful for determining reaction to green leafhoppers than for brown planthoppers—the contrast it shows between insect survival on resistant and susceptible plants is clearer for leafhoppers than for planthoppers.

As described in the Entomology section, the seedling reaction in the bulk seedling test was classified into six grades from 0 to 5. The reaction of the resistant parents generally ranged from 0 to 2 and the susceptible parents from 4 to 5. In the segregating generations of crosses between susceptible and resistant varieties, a small percentage of seedlings with an intermediate reaction (type 3) was often observed in addition to the typical resistant and susceptible reactions. The intermediate plants were grouped with the dominant class because some heterozygous plants were expected to vary in reaction type due to incomplete dominance and the effect of modifying factors. Occasionally, a seedling of a resistant variety showed a susceptible reaction which might have resulted from lack of absolute seed purity or from an unusually heavy concentration of the insects. Because the soil was not sterilized, the susceptible reaction could also have been due to an infection by a soil fungus. However, the susceptibility of seedlings due to similar causes in the segregating populations of crosses between susceptible and resistant varieties should not influence the segregation ratios and the interpretation of results because it occurs with a very low frequency.

Using the bulk seedling test, F_2 populations of crosses of Karsamba Red ASD7, Manavari CO22, and Dalwa Sannam MTU15 (all resistant to brown planthoppers) with T(N)1 (susceptible) were tested for their reactions to the brown planthoppers. The F_2 segregation indicated that ASD7 possesses a single recessive gene and CO22 and MTU15, a single dominant gene for

Table 9. Classification of F₂ seedlings of susceptible x resistant crosses and their parents for reaction to the brown planthopper.

Variety or cross	No. of seedlings					Total	R ^a	S ^a	P value for 3:1 or 1:3
	Reaction type								
	0 & 1	2	3	4	5				
T(N)1	—	—	2	2	131	135			
ASD7	109	24	—	—	1	134			
T(N)1 x ASD7 F ₂	158	48	40	27	554	827	206	621	0.99–1.00
T(N)1	—	—	—	7	128	135			
CO22	36	54	14	—	1	105			
T(N)1 x CO22 F ₂	141	358	80	13	188	780	579	201	0.65–0.70
T(N)1	—	—	—	—	45	45			
MTU15	—	44	—	—	—	44			
T(N)1 x MTU15 F ₂	—	204	23	21	52	299	227	73	0.80–0.85

^a R = resistant group, S = susceptible group.

resistance to the brown planthopper (Table 9).

The F₂ populations of crosses among the varieties resistant to brown planthoppers, Mudgo, ASD7, CO22, and MTU15, were also tested. In crosses involving two resistant varieties, about 30 seedlings of a susceptible check were grown at two different sites in wooden flats in addition to the parents. The final reaction was recorded only after all seedlings of the susceptible check showed a type 4 or 5 reaction. Of the 1,364 F₂ seedlings of the Mudgo x MTU15 cross, 0.3 percent were susceptible, while of the 1,039 seedlings of the Mudgo x CO22 cross, 1.5 percent were susceptible (Table 10). Since such a small percentage of susceptible seedlings was

also observed among resistant parents, the resistance factors in Mudgo, CO22, and MTU15 could be allelomorphous and perhaps identical. Additional data are needed, however, before a definite conclusion can be drawn. About 1 percent of the 767 F₂ seedlings of the ASD7 x CO22 cross and 3.5 percent of the 1,071 F₂ seedlings of the Mudgo x ASD7 cross were susceptible (Table 10). Again the percentage of the susceptible seedlings is much lower than would be expected on the basis of independent assortment, i.e., 18.75 percent. Since the genetic factor for resistance in ASD7 is clearly recessive, it can be tentatively assumed to be different from the factor for resistance in Mudgo, but only further studies will show whether it is allelomorphous or closely linked to the latter.

Table 10. Classification of F₂ seedlings of resistant x resistant crosses according to their reaction to the brown planthopper.

Variety or cross	No. of seedlings ^a					Total
	Reaction type					
	0 & 1	2	3	4	5	
ASD7	122	—	—	—	—	122
CO22	113	15	—	—	1	129
ASD7 x CO22 F ₂	726	32	1	2	6	767
Mudgo	193	19	—	—	—	212
MTU15	171	14	—	1	—	186
Mudgo x MTU15 F ₂	1194	148	18	3	1	1364
Mudgo	135	2	3	—	—	140
CO22	111	52	2	—	1	166
Mudgo x CO22 F ₂	914	105	4	6	10	1039
Mudgo	123	3	1	6	2	135
ASD7	165	1	—	—	2	168
Mudgo x ASD7 F ₂	983	45	6	16	21	1071

^a Data were recorded after susceptible checks grown among F₂ populations were showing "4" or "5" type reaction.

Studies on the inheritance of the resistance of ASD7 and IR8 to green leafhoppers were carried out using F₂ populations of crosses between these varieties and susceptible T(N)1. The F₂ segregation pattern indicated that each resistant parent possesses one major dominant gene for resistance (Table 11). Additional data were obtained by the tiller test using a sample of 90 F₂ plants of each of the two crosses and five plants of each parent. The number of insects surviving on each plant was counted 9 or 10 days after infestation, when all of the 15 insects caged on plants of the resistant parent had died and, on the average, about 10 insects had survived on plants of the susceptible parent. The frequency distribution showing insect survival,

Table 11. Classification of F₂ seedlings of susceptible x resistant crosses according to their reaction to the green leafhopper.

Variety or cross	No. of seedlings					Total	R	S	P value for 3:1
	Reaction type								
	0 & 1	2	3	4	5				
T(N)1	—	—	—	3	42	45			
ASD7	39	5	—	—	—	44			
T(N)1 x ASD7 F ₂	171	53	7	35	31	297	231	66	0.20–0.25
T(N)1	1	2	5	13	69	90			
IR8	3	85	1	1	—	90			
T(N)1 x IR8 F ₂	45	317	52	74	80	568	414	154	0.20–0.25

Table 12. Classification of F₂ plants of different crosses based on survival of green leafhopper nymphs.

Variety or cross	No. of plants							Total	R	S ^b	P value for 3:1
	No. of insects ^a										
	0	1–2	3–4	5–6	7–8	9–10	Over 10				
T(N)1	—	—	—	—	1	—	4	5			
IR8	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	5			
T(N)1 x IR8 F ₂	54	11	5	2	2	8	8	90	70	20	0.40–0.45
T(N)1	—	—	—	—	—	2	3	5			
ASD7	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	5			
T(N)1 x ASD7 F ₂	54	6	3	5	4	8	10	90	63	27	0.20–0.25

^a Nine to 12 days after infesting plants about 1½ months old with 15 nymphs.

^b Plants on which five or more insects survived were considered as susceptible.

Table 13. Classification of F₂ seedlings of resistant x resistant crosses according to their reaction to the green leafhopper.

Variety or cross	No. of seedlings					Total	R	S
	Reaction type							
	0 & 1	2	3	4	5			
Mudgo ^a	—	6	8	18	28	60		
Pankhari	30	38	3	—	4	75		
ASD7	88	16	—	—	—	104		
Pankhari x ASD7 F ₂	368	130	5	12	9	524	503	21
Mudgo ^a	1	14	14	6	24	59		
IR8	10	78	2	—	—	90		
Pankhari	27	63	—	—	—	90		
IR8 x Pankhari F ₂	215	289	11	15	9	539	515	24

^a Used as a susceptible check.

as presented in Table 12, appears to support the single-factor hypothesis. This will be further confirmed by a study of the F₃ breeding behavior.

Bulk F₂ populations of crosses among the varieties resistant to green leafhoppers—Pankhari, ASD7, and IR8—were also studied. Although the susceptible check, Mudgo, grown among F₂ populations of the Pankhari x ASD7 and IR8 x Pankhari crosses, was not completely killed (because the insect populations

used were inadequate), 4.0 percent of the 524 F₂ seedlings of the Pankhari x ASD7 cross and 4.7 percent of the 539 F₂ seedlings of the IR8 x Pankhari cross were fully susceptible (Table 13). This indicates that the genetic factors for green leafhopper resistance in ASD7 and IR8 are non-allelic to the resistance factor in Pankhari. The results of the tiller test with 90 F₂ plants of the Pankhari x ASD7 cross also showed that some plants were as susceptible as T(N)1, confirming

Fig. 4. Effect of planting time on the spikelet sterility of three lines.

the hypothesis that the resistance factors in the two parents are non-allelic.

Genetic sterility

About 2 years ago, work was begun to develop male-sterile lines for possible use in the breeding programs. Since environment, particularly temperature, greatly influences spikelet sterility, tests were made to determine if different genotypes reacted differently.

Single rows of about 1 dozen lines differing in spikelet sterility were planted on the first day of each month from June 1968 to May 1969. The rows were 3-m long and spaced 60-cm apart. Ten seedlings were planted in each row. The data on IR8 x PTB10 F₁, IR8, and IR142-60-40-

3-10-1-1 have been selected to show the effect of planting time on sterility. Sterility was measured by taking a sample of five plants from each line and calculating the percentage of unfilled grains on two representative panicles of each plant.

The spikelet sterility of IR8 x PTB10 F₁ was drastically influenced by planting time. It ranged from about 62 percent in the November planting to about 6 percent in the April planting (Fig. 4). IR8, a standard variety, and IR142-60-40-3-10-1-1, a pure-breeding, partially sterile line, did not show any strong influence of planting time on spikelet sterility. These results indicate that developing sterile lines that are not greatly influenced by environment is possible.

In the 1967 wet season, many plants showing a high degree of spikelet sterility were selected. Further selection for spikelet and pollen sterility was made in their progeny for four generations. Four sterile lines, designated as D356, D362, D320, and D388, were identified. The meiotic behavior of these lines and of the standard variety IR8 was determined by an examination of the pollen mother cells. The results obtained are summarized in Table 14 which also includes the pedigree of crosses from which these lines were derived, as well as information on their pollen and spikelet sterility. The pollen sterility was determined by the degree of staining in a weak KI-I solution. None of the sterile lines showed significantly greater meiotic irregularities than IR8. Among the parents of crosses from which the sterile lines were developed, T(N)1, Mas, IR400-28-4-5, and Pankhari are indicas, and CP231 x SLO17, B581A6-545, and Zenith are indica-like lines of U.S. origin containing some japonica germplasm.

Table 14. Meiotic behavior^a and pollen and spikelet sterility of the sterile lines.

Line	Pedigree	Diakinesis		Metaphase I		Anaphase I		Telophase I		Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)
		T	%a ^b	T	%a ^c	T	%a ^d	T	%a ^e		
D356	[(CP231 x SLO-17)/2 x T(N)1] x Zenith	165	3.1	227	4.6	57	14.0	203	0.0	10-20	85-95
D362	B581A6-545 x Mas	347	2.6	227	5.7	55	20.0	193	0.5	40-60	80-90
D320	B581A6-545/2 x 81B-25	52	0.0	110	9.0	31	6.5	100	3.0	80-95	85-95
D388	IR400-28-4-5 x Pankhari	364	0.8	405	6.2	116	7.8	342	0.6	80-95	85-95
IR8	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen	169	5.9	663	6.2	131	6.9	377	1.1	5-10	10-15

^a T = No. of cells examined; %a = Percent cells with aberrations.

^b 13 bivalents or two univalents.

^c Early disjunction (two, four, or six univalents).

^d Late disjunction, laggards, or bridges.

^e One or two laggards or a bridge. In one cell a laggard and a bridge were observed.

D356 is a pure-breeding, female-sterile line with a range of 5 to 15 percent in seed setting. Its sterility is primarily caused by a deformity of the stigma. Instead of the normal bifurcated structure, the stigma is divided into many parts. Some stigmas are normal and the percentage of seed setting roughly coincides with the percentage of normal stigmas. D362 also breeds pure for about 85 percent spikelet sterility. A large proportion of its pollen (40 to 60%) was observed to be sterile, but some ovule sterility may also be involved because when used in crosses as a female parent, the line did not give normal seed setting.

Both D320 and D338 appear to be male-sterile lines since they give normal seed setting when hand-pollinated. Unlike the other two sterile lines, however, they show outcrossing and it has been a problem to maintain them as pure-breeding, male-sterile lines. If the panicles are bagged, little or no seed forms. The highly sterile plants in these lines usually have about 90 percent or higher pollen sterility and may produce 5 to 15 percent seed without bagging. These lines have been maintained by vegetative propagation and by selection of highly sterile plants resembling the parent plant in each generation. Both D320 and D388 have been crossed and backcrossed with IR8 and it seems possible to transfer the male-sterility mechanism to IR8. Most probably cytoplasm is not involved in this male-sterility mechanism because both Pankhari and B581A6-545 which appear to have transmitted this character to these lines, give

Table 15. Segregation for sterility in F_2 generation of crosses involving D362.

Classes of spikelet sterility	No. of plants			
	D362	D361	D362 x D361 F_2	D202-2* x IR8 F_2
0-20%	—	9	34	27
20-30%	—	1	65	26
30-40%	—	—	19	32
40-50%	—	—	5	34
50-60%	—	—	2	13
60-70%	—	—	—	10
70-80%	1	—	7	6
80-100%	9	—	28	12
Total	10	10	160	160

* A sister line of D362 with about the same level of spikelet sterility.

highly sterile F_1 progeny in crosses with other varieties whether used as a male or as a female parent. Basmati 370, Nahng Mon S-4, and Manavari CO22 are the other varieties which give highly sterile F_1 progeny in indica x indica crosses.

The segregation for sterility was studied in the F_2 generation of crosses of D362 with D361, a nearly isogene-fertile line, and with IR8. The frequency distribution in Table 15 indicates that segregation for sterility could be greatly influenced by modifying factors contributed by the fertile parent. Although in the F_2 of the cross involving the isogenic fertile line, the sterility appears to be simply inherited, the segregation in the cross involving IR8 is complex and difficult to interpret. The F_1 generation plants of the cross D362 x D361 were partially sterile and spikelet fertility showed incomplete dominance.

Agronomy

Research in agronomy aims to develop new cultural practices that reduce the cost and the time required by the rice farmer's field operations.

Among the significant results in the Institute's research in agronomy in 1969 was a world record for annual production of rice. Three continuous crops of transplanted IR593-3-17 produced 23,553 kg/ha in 315 days in cooperative experiments in Mindanao, in the Philippines. However, based on the best-treatment combination, the highest three-crop total was 24,279 kg/ha. Fifty days were available to prepare the land for the three crops. A new annual production record was also achieved at the Institute farm where three crops of broadcast IR8 produced 21,083 kg/ha in 365 days.

Cooperative experiments on sources of rock phosphate for flooded soils were started in three countries—Philippines, Thailand, and Ceylon. At the Institute farm, agronomists began to mechanize anhydrous ammonia application in puddled soils with an applicator mounted on a hand tractor.

To compare broadcast seeding and transplanting, agronomists began experiments measuring tiller number, leaf area index, and grain yield under these two planting methods.

As new high-yielding lines were developed, agronomists collected additional information on the optimum time of harvest.

During the wet season, the rainfall distribution was good. This made it possible to collect information on varieties and cultural practices for upland rice.

The most significant results came from research on weed control in transplanted rice. Agronomists found that the granular isopropyl ester of 2, 4-D, when applied before weeds emerge, controls grasses and other weeds. The granular formulation of isopropyl ester of 2, 4-D is now being sold in the Philippines at less than half the cost of one hand-weeding of 1 hectare of transplanted rice. This low-cost herbicide should have a profound influence on weed control in transplanted rice. Agronomists also collected information on the effects of drought at various physiological growth stages of the rice crop.

Continuous-cropping experiments

Studies of the continuous growing of rice on the same land are made every year at the Institute farm. In 1969, land preparation for the first crop started on January 3 and harvesting (for the third crop of IR8) was done on January 2, 1970. The highest three-crop total production, 21,083 kg/ha, was obtained from a broadcast IR8 in 365 days (Table 1). This is the highest three-crop total ever obtained from a single variety or line at the Institute farm. The growth-duration total for three crops of IR8 was 344 days. Therefore, 21 days were available for preparing the land for the three crops.

The other varieties or lines included in the same experiment were IR480-5-9-3-3, Taichung (Native)1, and Binato. The highest three-crop total for IR480-5-9-3-3, 21,020 kg/ha, was obtained from the broadcast method of planting in 355 days; for Taichung (Native)1, 16,407 kg/ha was obtained from the broadcast method in 355 days; and for Binato, 11,193 kg/ha, from the transplanting method in 351 days.

In another experiment in which rice has been grown continuously since 1963, a three-crop total yield of 23,041 kg/ha on a best-treatment basis during 1968-69 was obtained from broadcast IR8 (8,124 kg/ha), broadcast IR593-3-17 (7,858 kg/ha), and transplanted IR661-1-140-3 (7,059 kg/ha) in 350 days. These three crops were the 19th, 20th, and 21st grown successively in this experiment.

A cooperative field experiment similar to those mentioned was conducted at the Central Mindanao State University, at Musuan, in Mindanao, Philippines. The highest three-crop total production—23,553 kg/ha—was obtained

Table 2. Yields of five varieties or lines in a continuous-rice-cropping experiment. IRRI-CMSU* cooperative experiment, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines, 1969 crop season.

Crop number	Field duration † (days)	Grain yield ‡ (kg/ha)
IR8		
1 (Jan. 16 to May 6)	110	10081
2 (May 21 to Sept. 3)	105	6133
3 (Sept. 11 to Dec. 21)	101	6612
Total	316	22826
Production/day		72
IR20		
1 (Jan. 16 to Apr. 25)	99	9392
2 (May 21 to Sept. 4)	106	6828¶
3 (Sept. 11 to Dec. 15)	95	7006
Total	300	23226
Production/day		77
IR400-5-12-10-2		
1 (Jan. 16 to Apr. 25)	99	9761
2 (May 21 to Aug. 19)	90	3561
3 (Sept. 11 to Dec. 10)	90	6421
Total	279	19743
Production/day		71
IR593-3-17		
1 (Jan. 16 to May 4)	108	10274¶
2 (May 21 to Sept. 3)	105	6102
3 (Sept. 11 to Dec. 22)	102	7177¶
Total	315	23553
Production/day		75
C4-63		
1 (Jan. 16 to May 1)	105	9171
2 (May 21 to Sept. 4)	106	5436
3 (Sept. 11 to Dec. 18)	98	5526
Total	309	20133
Production/day		65

* Central Mindanao State University.

† Land preparation per crop took 5 to 7 days.

‡ Rough rice at 14% moisture (average of four replications).

¶ Three-crop total from best-treatment combinations (24,279 kg/ha).

from transplanted IR593-3-17 in 315 days (Table 2). This is the highest three-crop total ever obtained from a single rice variety or line anywhere in the world. In the same experiment, IR20 and IR8 also had very high yields. Three crops of IR20 produced 23,226 kg/ha in 300 days while three crops of IR8 produced 22,826 kg/ha in 316 days. When the three-crop total was computed on the basis of best-treatment combinations, the annual production was 24,279 kg/ha (Table 2); the previous record was 20,174 kg/ha (1966 Annual Report).

Results from this experiment demonstrate that three crops of rice can be grown on the same

Table 1. Three-crop production of broadcast IR8*. IRRI, 1969-70.

Crop number	Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
1 † (Jan. 8 to May 7)	119	8840
2 (May 13 to Sept. 2)	112	5525
3 ‡ (Sept. 11 to Jan. 2)	113	6718
Total	344	21083

* Best treatment; other varieties or lines included in the experiment were IR480-5-9-3-3, Taichung (Native)1, and Binato (data not presented).

† Land preparation was started on January 3, 1969.

‡ Harvesting was completed on January 2, 1970.

Fig. 1. Nitrogen response of IR8, IR5, and H-4 by harvest month plotted with solar radiation (IRR1 pyrliometer) total for 45 days before harvest. Date-of-planting experiment, IRR1, 1969.

land within a year with high yields. For any variety or line grown in this experiment, at least 49 days were available to prepare the land for three crops. This period should be sufficient to prepare the land for three crops even under farm conditions. However, a supply of water must be available throughout the year.

Date-of-planting experiment

The date-of-planting experiment, in which crops are planted in every month, was continued. Figure 1 shows the nitrogen response of IR8, IR5, and H-4 plotted with the solar radiation total for 45 days before harvest. Unlike previous years, solar radiation (Fig. 1) was measured by the pyrliometer installed at the Institute. In the dry season, as the solar radiation received during the 45-day period before harvest increased from about 16,000 cal/sq cm for the January harvest to about 25,000 cal/sq cm for the May harvest, the nitrogen response of IR8 and

IR5 increased. Figure 2 shows the nitrogen response from 10 harvest months of the newly named variety, IR20, which was planted across the date-of-planting experiment. It lodged at all harvest months, from 7 to 12 days before harvest, particularly at high levels of added nitrogen. Nevertheless, it reached 5,000 kg/ha in each of the 10 harvests, indicating its high yielding ability.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Nitrogen response of promising lines

Experiments were conducted at the IRR1 farm, in farmers' fields, and at various experiment stations in the Philippines to study the nitrogen response and growth characteristics of new lines that have better grain qualities and better disease or insect resistance than IR8. The tall tropical variety, Peta, was used for comparison in most of these experiments.

Wet season. Among the 14 varieties or promis-

Fig. 2. Nitrogen response of IR20 by harvest month plotted with solar radiation (IRR1 pyrliometer) total for 45 days before harvest. Date-of-planting experiment, IRR1, 1969.

ing lines tested in an experiment at the IRRI farm, the highest grain yield, 6,162 kg/ha, was obtained from IR22 (formerly IR579-160-2). IR22 has most of the desirable characters of IR8, such as short stature, lodging resistance, and high grain yield (Table 3). Both IR22 and IR8 matured within 121 days. The data indicate that IR22 had more tillers and panicles than IR8. Although IR8 had slightly heavier grains, it also had a higher percentage of unfilled grains. The grain-to-straw ratios for both IR8 and IR22 were similar. Field observations indicated that IR22 was more resistant to bacterial leaf blight than IR8. IR22 was shorter than C4-63 (Fig. 3) and was also superior in lodging resistance. These two growth characteristics of IR22 are highly desirable for a monsoon crop. The IR22 crop appeared dark green until maturity, indicating slow leaf senescence.

In the same experiment, IR773A1-36-2-1 matured 10 days earlier than IR8 and appeared extremely promising. Figure 4 shows the relative heights of Peta and IR773A1-36-2-1 at 100 kg/ha N. IR773A1-36-2-1 was even shorter than IR8 and was highly resistant to lodging. The milling data indicate that it produced a very high yield of head rice and should compare favorably with other good-milling rice (Table 4).

In another location at the IRRI farm, three lines from the Thai breeding program and the variety Jaya from India were compared with some promising IRRI lines. IR844-86-1 produced the highest grain yield (7,199 kg/ha). Jaya yielded about the same as IR8. The lines from Thailand, developed from a cross between Leuang Tawng and IR8, produced lower grain yields than IR8 at all nitrogen levels (Table 5). They were taller and more susceptible to lodging

Table 3. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the grain yield components of IR8 and IR22. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Plant height at harvest (cm)	Tillers (No./sq m)	Panicles (No./sq m)	Weight of 100 grains (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain: straw ratio	Grain yield* (kg/ha)	Weight of straw (kg/ha)	Total dry matter (kg/ha)
IR8†									
0	85	176	174	3.1	17	1.1	4648	4225	7631
25	91	212	206	3.1	21	1.2	5165	3404	8143
50	91	222	216	3.0	24	1.1	5491	4992	9015
75	91	216	208	2.9	29	1.1	5534	5031	9086
100	98	264	258	3.0	31	0.8	5824	7280	11269
Mean	91	218	212	3.0	24	1.0	5332	5166	9029
IR22‡									
0	89	206	202	2.4	10	1.1	4887	4443	8024
25	95	244	240	2.5	15	1.0	5172	5172	8896
50	98	248	242	2.4	16	1.0	5337	5337	9180
75	100	278	276	2.4	11	0.9	5506	6118	9997
100	106	344	340	2.5	10	0.9	6162	6847	11188
Mean	98	264	260	2.4	12	1.0	5413	5583	9457

* At 14% moisture.

† Growth duration: 121 days.

‡ Growth duration: 120 days.

at high levels of fertility than IR8. Figure 5 shows the relative performance of another new Institute variety, IR20 (formerly IR532E576), compared with IR8 and Peta. Although IR20 and IR22 were not included in the same fertilizer experiment at IRRI, the superiority of IR22 over IR20 in terms of nitrogen response was apparent when IR8 was used as a standard high-yielding variety (Fig. 5).

One outstanding characteristic of IR22 is its excellent grain which looks and mills better than that of IR8 and IR20. IR22 gave 10 percentage points more head rice than IR8. On the other hand, IR20 gave about the same percentage of head rice as IR8 (Table 6a and 6b). The protein

Table 4. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the grain yield and milling characteristics of IR773A1-36-2-1. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)
0	3765	70	65
25	4149	71	66
50	4633	71	66
75	4977	71	67
100	5399	72	66
Mean	4583	71	66

contents of IR8, IR20, and IR22 were similar (Table 7a and 7b). Results from these two experiments strongly indicate the superiority of IR22 over IR8 and IR20 in growth characteristics, grain yield, and milling qualities.

Fig. 3. Relative heights of IR22 and C4-63 at 100 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Fig. 4. A stand of a short and early maturing line, IR773A1-36-2-1, and Peta at 100 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Table 5. Effect of levels of nitrogen on the grain yield of rice. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Variety or line	Grain yield* (kg/ha)					Mean	Growth duration (days)
	0	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)					
		25	50	75	100		
IR8	5561	5927	6100	6069	5969	5925	126
IR20	5232	4955	5347	4869	4003	4881	126
56-1-63†	5005	5839	5711	4831	5321	5341	129
IR844-86-1	6166	6402	7199	7199	7153	6824	133
IR662-2-7-2-2	5267	5236	5772	5600	5601	5495	133
KN-9†	4250	4849	5170	5306	5115	4938	123
17-2-1†	4598	4587	4605	4629	4347	4553	123
Jaya	5468	6261	6171	5873	6136	5982	122
IR661-1-140-3	5371	5803	5944	5948	5754	5764	118
IR579-14-1-3	4924	5286	5441	5177	5388	5243	118
IR127-80-1-10	4363	4823	4753	4893	4991	4765	116
Peta	2994	2303	2523	2493	2738	2610	139

* At 14% moisture—average of four replications.

† Selection from Leuang Tawng x IR8.

Experiments in farmers' fields

Studies on varietal reaction to nitrogen fertilization continued during 1969.

Dry season. The nitrogen levels used were 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg/ha. The entire amount applied, except 20 kg, was incorporated during the last harrowing. Figure 6 shows the relative grain yields of IR8, IR20, and C4-63 at various levels of nitrogen. Nitrogen response was linear for IR8 which yielded the most (9,537 kg/ha) at 150 kg/ha N.

Wet season. The highest grain yield, 7,382 kg/ha, was obtained with IR8 at 75 kg/ha N. The

differences in grain yields between IR20 and C4-63 were greater during the wet season than in the dry season.

The two-crop total of 16,919 kg/ha for IR8 was 2,900 kg/ha higher than the two-crop total of 14,070 kg/ha for IR20.

Cooperative fertility experiment

Field experiments were conducted at three locations in the Philippines to study varietal reactions to nitrogen levels. The experiments

Fig. 5. Relative performances of IR20 and IR22, compared with IR8 and Peta. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Table 6a. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the milling characteristics of IR8 and IR22. IRRI, Location I, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	IR8		IR22	
	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)
0	69	52	72	67
25	69	53	71	66
50	70	54	72	65
75	70	55	71	60
100	70	56	72	61
Mean	70	54	72	64

Table 6b. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the milling characteristics of IR8 and IR20. IRRI, Location II, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	IR8		IR20	
	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)
0	70	59	69	59
25	69	56	69	59
50	69	58	69	58
75	70	56	69	57
100	70	58	69	52
Mean	70	57	69	57

Fig. 6. Effects of nitrogen levels on the grain yield of three varieties in farmers' fields, 1969 wet season.

reported here were conducted during the 1969 wet season in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and the Visayas Rice Experiment Station.

Table 8 shows the comparative performances of IR8, IR20, IR22, IR661-1-140-3-2, and Peta. Among the yields of improved varieties with good grain qualities, the highest were those of IR22—at least 6,000 kg/ha in the three locations. IR22 showed a higher resistance to bacterial leaf blight than IR8. IR20 had excellent resistance to bacterial leaf blight and yielded most at Visayas. It lodged severely at Bicol and moder-

ately at Visayas, particularly at high levels of added nitrogen. IR661-1-140-3-2 yielded the most in two out of three locations and showed moderate resistance to bacterial leaf blight.

Slow-release nitrogen fertilizers

In flooded soil, the efficiency of applied nitrogen is low unless it is placed in the reduced soil layer. Our efforts to identify a suitable nitrogen fertilizer more efficient than urea or ammonium sulfate were continued. If a slow-release material is found which provides nitrogen according to the crop requirement, it may be possible to increase the efficiency of nitrogen.

Two sulfur-coated urea materials developed

Table 7a. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the protein contents of the brown rice of IR8 and IR22. IRR1, Location I, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Protein content (%)	
	IR8	IR22
0	7.5	7.9
25	8.0	8.0
50	8.5	8.7
75	8.1	9.3
100	9.3	9.6
Mean	8.3	8.7

Table 7b. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the protein content of the brown rice of IR8 and IR20. IRR1, Location II, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Protein content (%)	
	IR8	IR20
0	8.1	9.0
25	8.8	9.4
50	8.6	9.2
75	8.7	9.6
100	10.0	10.1
Mean	8.8	9.5

Table 8. Grain yields of IR20 and IR22 at various nitrogen levels compared with those of other varieties (or lines) grown at three Bureau of Plant Industry stations in the Philippines—Maligaya (M), Bicol (B), and Visayas (V). IRRRI-BPI cooperative nitrogen-response experiments, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen ^a applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^b (kg/ha)														
	IR8			IR20			IR22			IR661-1-140-3-2			Peta		
	M	B	V	M	B	V	M	B	V	M	B	V	M	B	V
0	5180	4550	4024	4384	3985	5177	4048	3772	4480	5008	5114	4011	3849	3418	4140
10 + 20	5234	5851	4711	5173	4566	6021	4546	4838	5505	5402	6287	4507	3809	3294	4646
40 + 20	5809	5988	4340	5236	5005	7317	5267	5645	4903	5883	6367	5197	3519	3489	3578
70 + 20	5934	6260	4576	5741	5217	7976	5692	6226	6024	6074	6370	4759	2716	3631	3119
100 + 20	6274	6141	5265	5958	5829	7538	6070	5881	6708	6661	6407	4490	2205	3871	3212
130 + 20	5964	5204	4013	6092	4101	6760	5524	6242	6560	6282	5571	5146	3074	3695	3125
Mean ^c		5295			5671			5441			5530			3466	
Duration (days)	123	125– 133	126	119– 123	114– 131	127	119	114– 116	126	119	117– 132	127	131– 136	131– 136	142

^a Basal application plus application at panicle initiation.

^b At 14% moisture—average of three replications.

^c Of yields at the three locations.

by the Tennessee Valley Authority (U.S.A.), which have different rates of solubility, and two organic nitrogen compounds from Japan of relatively low solubility were compared with prilled urea and ammonium sulfate in an experiment at the Institute farm during the 1969 wet season. The nitrogen levels used are shown in Table 9. Grain yield increased significantly with added nitrogen. All sources of nitrogen, except prilled urea and crotonylidene diurea, gave significant increases in grain yields at 25 kg/ha N compared with the control (no fertilizer). The crotonylidene diurea compound released nitrogen very slowly and caused poor growth compared with other sources of nitrogen. Response to nitrogen from crotonylidene diurea was, therefore, significant only at 75 kg/ha N or more.

Fertilizing with anhydrous ammonia under two methods of planting

An experiment was conducted during the dry and wet seasons to study the effects of different tillering capacities on the nitrogen response of flooded broadcast and transplanted rice. IR8, a relatively high tillering variety, and IR127-80-1-10, a low-tillering line, were used in a strip plot design with variety and nitrogen level as the main plots and methods of planting as the subplots. Nitrogen was applied as anhydrous ammonia with an applicator mounted on a hand tractor designed and built by the IRRRI Engineering Department (Fig. 7). Transplanting was done at a 20 x 25 cm spacing. For the broadcast treatment, the seeds were broadcast on puddled soil at 100 kg/ha.

Table 9. Effect of some slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on the grain yield of IR8 at different nitrogen levels. IRRRI, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen source	Grain yield (kg/ha)				
	Nitrogen rate (kg/ha)				Mean
	25	50	75	100	
Ammonium sulfate	5940**	5438	6123**	6258**	5940
Prilled urea	5584	6186**	6484**	6247**	6126
Sulfur-coated urea No. 1 ^a	5908*	5879*	6545**	6229**	6140
Sulfur-coated urea No. 2 ^b	6024**	4850	6267**	6000**	5785
Isobutylidene diurea	5874*	5954**	5930*	6247**	6001
Crotonylidene diurea	5463	5486	6161**	6135**	5811
Unfertilized control			5151		
Mean	5799	5632	6252	6186	

* Significant (based on comparison with the control mean) at the 5% level.

** Significant at the 1% level.

^a Dissolution rate = 5.5% in 10 days.

^b Dissolution rate = 40.8% in 10 days.

Dry season. The grain yields of both broadcast and transplanted IR8 and IR127-80-1-10 in the dry season responded linearly up to 160 kg/ha N (Fig. 8). The yield differences due to nitrogen level were highly significant. Although IR8 and IR127-80-1-10 yields were statistically similar, the grain yields obtained from the two methods of planting were significantly different. The yields from broadcast plots were better than those from transplanted ones. The yields of IR8 from both methods of planting, however, were not significantly different from each other. Unlike IR8, broadcast plots of IR127-80-1-10 produced a significantly higher grain yield than transplanted plots. In both broadcast and trans-

Fig. 7. Land preparation combined with fertilizer application using an anhydrous ammonia applicator mounted on a hand tractor. IRRI, 1969.

Fig. 8. Effect of levels of nitrogen as anhydrous ammonia (applied 15-cm deep) and methods of planting on the grain yield of flooded rice. IRRI, 1969 dry and wet seasons.

Fig. 9. Stand of broadcast IR127-80-1-10 compared with stand of transplanted IR8 at 80 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

planted IR8 and IR127-80-1-10, the responses to added nitrogen were similar.

Wet season. Figure 9 shows that in the wet season the stand of broadcast IR127-80-1-10 was as good as that of transplanted IR8 at

80 kg/ha N. As in the dry season, the grain yield response of either variety or line was not significant at various levels of nitrogen (Fig. 8). Between planting methods, broadcasting proved to be better than transplanting. Unlike the dry-

Table 10a. Effects of time of nitrogen application on the grain yields of IR8 and IR5. Farmer's field, Bay, Laguna, Philippines. 1969 dry season.

Time of application ^a					Grain yield (kg/ha)				Mean ^b	
					Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)					
					80		120			
LP	MT	PI	B	H	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5		
0	0	0	0	0	4475	5383	4434	4949	4810	d
all	0	0	0	0	6603	7191	7144	7265	7051	c
½	½	0	0	0	6919	8120	7146	7421	7469	ab
½	0	½	0	0	7189	7444	7517	7558	7426	ab
½	0	0	½	0	6890	7569	6842	7799	7275	bc
¾	0	¼	0	0	7411	7622	7662	7854	7637	a
0	¾	0	0	¼	6597	7512	6692	7832	7158	bc

^a LP = during land preparation; MT = at maximum tillering stage; PI = at panicle initiation stage; B = at booting stage; H = at heading stage.

^b Treatment means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 10b. Effects of time of nitrogen application on the grain yields of IR8 and IR5. Farmer's field, Bay, Laguna, Philippines. 1969 wet season.

Time of application ^a					Grain yield (kg/ha)				Mean ^b	
					Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)					
					30		60			
LP	MT	PI	B	H	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5		
0	0	0	0	0	5189	5405	5252	4769	5154	c
all	0	0	0	0	5593	5185	6069	5399	5561	bc
½	½	0	0	0	5945	5701	6468	6364	6120	a
½	0	½	0	0	5625	5658	6806	5637	5932	ab
½	0	0	½	0	6164	5373	6468	5892	5932	ab
¾	0	¼	0	0	6025	5771	6739	5752	6070	ab
0	¾	0	0	¼	5979	5377	6573	5931	5965	ab

^a LP = during land preparation stage; MT = at maximum tillering stage; PI = at panicle initiation stage; H = at heading stage; B = at booting stage.

^b Treatment means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 11. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yields of IR8, C4-63, and IR305-4-12-1-3. IRRI, 1969 dry season (Long-term fertility experiment, 10th crop).

Fertilizer treatment (kg/ha)			Grain yield ^b (kg/ha)			
N ^a	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	C4-63	IR305-4-12-1-3	Mean
0	0	0	4026	3876	4353	4085
100 + 40	0	0	8614	7386	8694	8223
0	30	0	4132	3940	4612	4228
0	0	30	4158	3752	4208	4039
100 + 40	30	0	8681	7091	8364	8045
100 + 40	0	30	9010	7746	8815	8524
100 + 40	30	30	8660	7517	9068	8415
100 + 40 ^c	30	30	8346	7024	8336	7902
Mean			6953	6038	7056	
Duration (days)			130	127	132	

^a Basal application + application at panicle initiation.

^b At 14% moisture—average of four replications.

^c Compost plus inorganic.

season results, broadcast IR127-80-1-10 had a significantly higher grain yield than broadcast IR8. This was because half the broadcast IR8 plots lodged at 60 kg/ha N and all of them lodged at 80 kg/ha N. Under either method of planting, IR127-80-1-10 did not lodge at any level of nitrogen. For IR8, lodging was generally more serious when it was broadcast than when it was transplanted. A different result was obtained in the transplanted method. The grain yields of IR127-80-1-10 were lower than those of IR8; thus, a highly significant interaction between varieties and planting methods was obtained.

Thus higher grain yields can be obtained with low-tillering lines, such as IR127-80-1-10, by broadcasting seeds on puddled soil rather than by transplanting. With a heavy-tillering variety, such as IR8, high grain yields can be obtained by either method of planting. However, the high grain yields from broadcast IR127-80-1-10 were obtained with carefully controlled water management, which most farmers in the monsoon-rice-growing regions of Asia cannot achieve.

Time of nitrogen application

In farmers' fields, water control is not as good as it is in experimental plots. So for farmers it is often better to apply nitrogen in split doses than to incorporate all of it into the soil during land preparation. During the dry and wet seasons, field experiments were conducted in farmers' fields in Bay, Laguna, to study the optimum time of nitrogen application.

Dry season. At 80 and 120 kg/ha N, grain yields were about the same in the dry season. Averaging two varieties and two nitrogen levels, the highest grain yield was obtained when the nitrogen was applied in split doses: three-fourths during land preparation and one-fourth during the panicle initiation stage (Table 10a). Among the nitrogen-treated plots, a single application at planting gave the lowest grain yield.

Wet season. The grain yields of IR5 in the wet season were much higher when nitrogen was applied in split applications at planting and at the maximum tillering stage than when the entire amount was applied at planting. There were no apparent differences among the other split application treatments (Table 10b).

Data for the two seasons indicate that a split application of nitrogen, in which most of the nitrogen was applied during land preparation and the remainder applied not later than panicle initiation, resulted in higher grain yield than a single-dose application during land preparation. The difference was more marked during the dry than during the wet season.

Long-term fertility experiment

The long-term fertility experiment started in 1964 was continued during 1969. The results reported here are from the tenth and eleventh crop in a series. In both the dry and wet seasons this year none of the three indicas showed significant response to phosphorus or potassium, or both (Tables 11 and 12).

Table 12. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yields of IR8, C4-63, and IR305-4-12-1-3. IRRI, 1969 wet season (Long-term fertility experiment, 11th crop).

Fertilizer treatment (kg/ha)			Grain yield ^a (kg/ha)			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	C4-63	IR305-4-12-1-3	Mean
0	0	0	4290	3992	4512	4265
60	0	0	5342	4751	5834	5309
0	30	0	4966	4254	5542	4921
0	0	30	4660	4138	4792	4530
60	30	0	5584	4397	5598	5193
60	0	30	5378	4423	5656	5152
60	30	30	5358	5472	4278	5036
60	30	30 ^b	5163	4637	5210	5003
Mean			5093	5327	4359	
Duration (days)			125	125	125	

^a At 14% moisture—average of four replications.

^b Compost plus inorganic.

Growth characteristics and yield

Field experiments were conducted to study the effects of plant density and nitrogen levels on the tiller number, leaf area index, and grain yield of rice.

Dry season. The highest tiller number per

Table 13. Effects of plant density and nitrogen level on the tiller number per square meter of four varieties at harvest. 1969 dry season.

Planting density ^a	Tillers (no./sq m)		
	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)		
	0	60	120
		IR8	
Broadcast	463	617	717
20 x 20	146	212	277
30 x 30	122	172	203
40 x 40	101	171	161
50 x 50	86	133	150
100 x 100	38	63	59
		IR127-80-1-10	
Broadcast	420	447	440
20 x 20	103	148	191
30 x 30	90	125	138
40 x 40	75	84	99
50 x 50	59	71	88
100 x 100	21	32	37
		IR305-4-12-1-3	
Broadcast	705	842	735
20 x 20	236	410	378
30 x 30	215	246	288
40 x 40	181	230	254
50 x 50	175	220	218
100 x 100	69	87	106
		Peta	
Broadcast	390	447	431
20 x 20	182	232	240
30 x 30	136	164	136
40 x 40	108	161	163
50 x 50	116	148	141
100 x 100	55	65	82

^a Spacings are in centimeters.

square meter in the dry season was obtained with IR305-4-12-1-3 and the lowest with IR127-80-1-10. With all varieties or lines, the maximum tiller numbers were obtained from the broadcast method of planting (Table 13). Measurements taken at the flowering stage of the crop indicated that leaf area index values increased as plant density increased. Like maximum tiller production, the highest leaf area index values were obtained from the broadcast plots. The lowest leaf area index values were recorded from the low-tillering line, IR127-80-1-10, and the highest, from Peta, a medium-tillering, leafy variety. The highest leaf area index for broadcast IR127-80-1-10 was 7.0 as against Peta's 14.6 at 120 kg/ha N (Fig. 10). Except for Peta, grain yields generally increased with increased plant density and increased leaf area index. The grain yields of Peta did not reflect its high leaf area index because it lodged heavily.

Wet season. The highest leaf area index (10.2) in the wet season was obtained with broadcast IR8 at 80 kg/ha N (Fig. 11), but grain yields were higher with transplanted IR8 at close spacing. For the low-tillering line, IR127-80-1-10, or the medium-tillering variety, IR8, the leaf area index values obtained were higher in the wet season than in the dry season. However, for the medium-tillering Peta, or the heavy-tillering line, IR305-4-12-1-3, the leaf area index values recorded were lower in the wet than in the dry season. The high leaf area indices obtained from the broadcast plots were not associated with high grain yield. Excessive vegetative growth by

broadcast plants caused lodging and reduced grain yields.

Time-of-harvest experiments

To obtain a high return from investment in inputs, the farmer needs high-yielding rice varieties with good grain qualities. For each variety, cultural requirements such as the optimum rate of nitrogen application and optimum time of harvest should be known.

A field experiment was conducted during the dry season with IR8, IR20, IR305-4-12-1-3, and C4-63. The highest grain yield of IR8 was 8,528 kg/ha; of IR20, 7,975 kg/ha; of IR305-4-12-1-3, 8,602 kg/ha; and of C4-63, 6,790 kg/ha. These yields were obtained when the crops, fertilized at 120 kg/ha N, were harvested between 32 and 38 days after heading. Figure 12 shows the grain yield data plotted against time of harvest. C4-63 a variety from the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, had a higher percentage of head rice than either IR8 or IR20 (Fig. 13). The time of harvest that resulted in the maximum percentage of head rice was 30 days after heading for C4-63 and IR20, 28 days after heading for IR8, and 24 days after heading for IR304-4-12-1-3. Each variety, however, could have been harvested several days before or after the optimum time without reducing the yield of head rice significantly.

The effect of the interaction between nitrogen and time of harvest on the percentage of head rice was highly significant. The optimum period for harvesting the crop without fertilizer was narrower (from 24 to 30 days after heading) than that for the crop fertilized with 60 and 120 kg/ha N (from 20 to 34 days after heading).

Upland rice experiments

Upland rice yield trial

Large areas of rice grow under upland conditions in Asia, Africa, and South America. It is not known whether a special type of variety is needed for upland rice culture. The results from previous experiments at the Institute indicated that rainfall distribution is the most critical factor for obtaining high yields with upland rice. The varieties or lines generally considered as

Fig. 10. Relationship between leaf area index at flowering and grain yield of rice at 120 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Fig. 11. Relationship between leaf area index at flowering and grain yield at 80 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

high yielding for lowland rice culture also performed well under upland rice culture.

An experiment was conducted during the 1969 wet season to screen varieties for upland rice culture. Forty new lines including a few

Fig. 12. Effect of time of harvest on the grain yield of IR8, C4-63, IR305-4-12-1-3, and IR20 (average of three nitrogen levels). IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Fig. 13. Effect of time of harvest on percentages of head rice in IR8, C4-63, IR305-4-12-1-3, and IR20 (average of three nitrogen levels). IRRI, 1969 dry season.

high-yielding, lowland varieties were planted under a randomized complete block design with four replications. An upland variety, M1-48, developed by the Maligaya Rice Research and

Table 14. Upland rice yield trial. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Variety or line	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Duration (days)
IR5	5196	134
IR442-2-58-2-1-2	4618	121
IR8	4329	122
IR661-1-140-3	4235	122
IR293-3-6-2-1	4140	118
IR430-373-1-3	4130	129
IR661-1-170-1-3	4090	120
IR20	3974	120
IR589-66-2-1	3890	116
IR478-68-2	3796	112
IR773A1-36-2-1	3778	120
IR667-142-2-3	3745	116
IR586-16-1-3	3700	115
IR580-15-3	3621	112
IR573-33-3-2	3614	113
IR593-1-19-3-1	3545	136
IR293-6-1	3536	114
IR293-6-2-1	3521	114
IR435-7-3-1	3451	141
IR781-133-2-3	3282	118
IR1154-243-1	3085	112
IR81-105-2-3	3047	116
IR332-2-10-1-2-1-2	2979	137
IR140-136-2-3-1-2	2960	116
IR661-127-3-3	2930	116
IR579-14-1-3	2806	114
IR583-14-1-2-1	2669	113
IR586-117-2	2411	113
IR181-2-2-2-5-3-2	2408	122
IR239-134-2-1-3	2303	132
M1-48	2240	112
IR334-7-6-2-2	2222	114
IR452-21-3-3	2218	117
IR441-6-2-1-1	2152	132
IR781-144-1	2136	114
IR117-21-2-1-1-1-2	1920	113
IR239-39-3-3-1	1916	118
IR478-26-2-2	1888	112
IR474-109-2-3	1813	120
IR586-13-2-1	1699	112

Training Center of the Philippines Bureau of Plant Industry, was included for comparison. Table 14 shows the grain yield data together with the growth durations of the varieties or lines. IR5 which matured in 134 days gave the highest yield, 5,196 kg/ha. It is apparent that the high-yielding varieties meant primarily for lowland conditions outperformed the upland variety, M1-48. These results also suggest that when rainfall distribution is as good as it was during 1969 wet season, high grain yields can be obtained under upland rice culture if high-yielding varieties and improved cultural practices are used.

Time of nitrogen application for upland rice

Fertilizer management practices for lowland rice are better understood than are those for

Table 15. Effects of time of nitrogen application on the grain yield of upland rice. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

L	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)				Grain yield ^b (kg/ha)				
	Time of application ^a				IR661-1-140-3	IR5	IR480-5-9-3-3	IR20	Mean
	MT	PI	B	H					
0	0	0	0	0	3865	3817	2772	2069	3131
60	0	0	0	0	4996	4381	3629	2314	3830
0	30	30	0	0	5137	4010	4091	2826	4016
0	0	30	30	0	4238	3748	3452	2093	3383
0	20	20	20	0	4975	4757	3964	3396	4273
0	0	20	20	20	4226	4045	3637	2471	3595
90	0	0	0	0	4363	4630	3845	2037	3719
0	45	45	0	0	4403	3877	3688	1913	3470
0	0	45	45	0	4199	4359	4038	2803	3850
0	30	30	30	0	4920	4059	4190	2758	3982
0	0	30	30	30	4287	3960	3599	2038	3471
Mean					4510	4149	3719	2429	
Duration (days)					123	137	123	123	

^a L = during land preparation; MT = at maximum tillering; PI = at panicle initiation; B = at booting; H = at heading.

^b At 14% moisture—average of three replications.

upland rice. Therefore, a field experiment was conducted to study the optimum time of nitrogen application for upland rice. The nitrogen levels used were 0, 60, and 90 kg/ha, applied in split doses (Table 15). IR661-1-140-3 produced the highest grain yield, 5,137 kg/ha, when a total of 60 kg/ha N was applied in two split doses, at maximum tillering and at panicle initiation. The differences in grain yields between the varieties were highly significant except between IR5 and IR661-1-140-3. The grain yield differences from applying nitrogen at different times were not significant, so there was a considerable leeway on the time of nitrogen application. In addition the differences in grain yield between 60 and 90 kg/ha were not significant, suggesting that 60 kg/ha N was adequate for an optimum yield of upland rice grown on fertile Maahas clay soil.

Weed control experiments

Screening herbicides for transplanted rice

In the last 2 years, new herbicides have improved the prospects for chemical weed control in transplanted rice in the tropics. Several new granular herbicides are currently being sold in the Philippine market. Nevertheless, our efforts to identify new chemicals which would cost less or have a wider latitude in their time of application have continued. Table 16 presents the results of using a few outstanding herbicides and herbicide combinations.

A new chemical, Saturn, provided excellent weed control (Fig. 14) when the grasses were at the one- to three-leaf stage (Table 16). Other promising chemicals include granular formulations of MV 45360, FO 201, the ethyl ester of 2,4-D, MBR 3356, and the combination, molinate/2,4-D isopropyl ester. The combination, Saturn-M, appeared to have no advantage over Saturn alone. The granular formulation of CP 53619 continued to look promising even at half of the rate used in previous experiments (Table 16). Table 17 shows the chemistry of some herbicides not described in previous IRRI Annual Reports.

Promising new herbicides for transplanted rice

In tests conducted at the Institute farm, several new herbicides, particularly CP 57177 and CP 56250, gave excellent weed control and showed low toxicity to transplanted IR8 plants, when applied in granular or liquid formulation before the weeds had emerged or at the one- to two-leaf stage of the grasses. The results obtained from the 1969 wet-season experiments are summarized in Tables 18 and 19. The previously evaluated herbicide CP 53619 continued to look promising.

As in other experiments, the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D in the granular form at 0.8 kg/ha active ingredient gave outstanding performance when applied shortly after transplanting. Doubling the rate of application to 1.6 kg/ha active ingredient did not cause any noticeable toxicity to

Fig. 14. A significant difference in grain yield was observed when granular formulation of Saturn was applied at the one- to three-leaf stage of grasses. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Table 16. Promising granular herbicides for transplanted IR8. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Grain yield		Weed weight ^c		Control rating ^d		Toxicity rating ^e	
		D ^f (kg/ha)	F ^g (kg/ha)	D (g/sq m)	F	D	F	D	F
Early application ^h									
Nitrofen/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.4	5402	5929	123	78	8	9	1	0
2,4-D EE	0.8		5527		101		8		0
MBR 3356	1.5	5195	5528	156	155	8	8	4	3
CP 53619	1.5		5878		0		10		0
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE ⁱ	0.75/0.5		5329		106		9		0
Late application ^j									
Saturn	3.0	6050	5241	45	31	9	9	0	0
MV 45360	2.0/1.0		5831		75		9		0
FO 201	2.0/1.0		5705		81		8		0
Saturn-M	2.1/1.8	5817	5129	33	168	9	8	0	0
2,4-D EE	0.8		5152		150		7		0
Molinate/2,4-D IPE	1.5/0.6		5444		162		8		0
Controls									
MCPA-K ^k fb hand-weeding	0.8		5815		38		9		0
Hand-weeded twice	—		6226		0		9		0
Nonweeded	—		0		1325		1		0

^a IPE = isopropyl ester; EE = ethyl ester.

^b Of active ingredient.

^c At heading stage of grasses.

^d Scale: 0 = no control; 10 = complete control.

^e Scale: 0 = no toxicity; 10 = complete kill.

^f Drained.

^g Flooded.

^h At 4 days after transplanting.

ⁱ Standard for comparison.

^j At the one- to three-leaf stage of grasses.

^k Water-soluble liquid.

transplanted rice plants (Table 18). This indicates that the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D has a wide latitude in the rate of application.

The results also confirmed that MSMA alone is not able to control grasses and is weak in

controlling broadleaved weeds. Granular dacthal appeared to control grasses adequately and also contributed substantially to control of broadleaved weeds, but it was weak in controlling sedges (Table 18).

Granular herbicides for transplanted rice

Results from the cooperative experiments conducted at three locations in the Philippines indicate that the application of granular herbicides before weed emergence provided excellent weed control in transplanted rice, resulting in significantly higher grain yield. The most outstanding result was obtained with the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D. This phenoxy acid herbicide normally has been used for controlling broad-leaved weeds and sedges 2 to 3 weeks after their emergence in rice fields.

In our experiments the application of the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D before the emergence of all three kinds of weeds, i.e., grasses, broad-leaved weeds, and sedges, provided adequate weed control in transplanted rice (Table 20). The granular formulation of the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D is now being sold in the Philippines at less than half the cost of one hand-weeding of 1 hectare of transplanted rice. This low-cost herbicide normally provides grain yields statistically similar to but numerically lower than other successful rice herbicides currently marketed in the Philippines. These granular herbicides (Table 20) have been tested in at least 11 different countries, mostly in Asia.

The results of some of the tests conducted in Asian countries have been reported by the

Table 17. Common or trade names and chemical formulas of seven new herbicides. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Common or trade name	Source	Chemical name
CP 53619	Monsanto Chemicals (USA)	N-(2-butoxymethyl)-2-chloro-2',6'-diethylacetanilide
CP 56250	Monsanto Chemicals (USA)	2-chloro-N-(2-ethoxyethyl)-N-(2-methyl-6-propyl-1-cyclohexen-1-yl)-acetamide
CP 57177	Monsanto Chemicals (USA)	N-(2-butoxyethyl)-2-chloro-N-(2,6-dimethyl-1-cyclohexen-1-yl)-acetamide
DCPA (Dacthal)	Diamond Alkali (USA)	Dimethyl-2,3,4,6-tetra chloroterephthalate
MSMA	Chapman Chem. Co. (USA)	Monosodium methane arsonate
Saturn	Kumiai Chemicals (Japan)	S-(4-chlorobenzyl)-N,N-diethylthiocarbamate
Saturn-M	Kumiai Chemicals (Japan)	Saturn + 2,4,6-trichlorophenyl-4-nitrophenyl ether

scientists cooperating in the experiments. The isopropyl ester of 2,4-D performed as well as other rice herbicides in Korea and as well as

Table 18. Grain yield of transplanted IR8 and weed weight as affected by applying granular herbicides before emergence of grasses (4 days after transplanting). IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Weed weight ^c				Grain yield ^d (kg/ha)
		EC	S	B	P	
CP 53619	3.0	0	0	0	0 6283 a	
CP 53619	6.0	0	0	0	1 6455 a	
CP 56250	0.4	0	0	0	3 6354 a	
CP 56250	0.8	0	0	0	8 6392 a	
CP 57177	0.4	0	0	3	31 6112 a	
CP 57177 (liquid)	0.8	0	0	0	0 6001 a	
CP 29036 (liquid)	2.0	0	0	0	11 6063 a	
CP 29037	1.0	0	0	0	11 6149 a	
CP 29037	2.0	0	0	3	0 6059 a	
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.75/0.5	0	1	—	8 6096 a	
Nitralin/MCPA (sodium salt)	1.5/0.6	0	0	0	9 5971 a	
EPTC/MCPA (on limestone)	1.75/0.7	60	5	5	0 6128 a	
EPTC/MCPA (on clay)	1.75/0.7	0	1	3	0 6240 a	
EPTC/MCPA (on extruded Bentonite)	1.75/0.7	0	0	0	7 5865 a	
EPTC/2,4-D (on limestone)	1.75/0.7	0	3	3	3 6254 a	
2,4-D IPE	0.8	38	4	4	5 6088 a	
2,4-D IPE	1.6	0	0	0	4 5679 a	
DCPA	7.0	0	13	9	3 5872 a	
DCPA & 2,4-D IPE	7.0 & 0.8	0	0	0	0 6057 a	
MSMA	5.0	244	1	78	0 3828 c	
MSMA & 2,4-D IPE	5.0 & 0.8	26	3	3	3 6182 a	
Trifluralin/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.8	4	0	9	0 6168 a	
Control	—	443	4	216	0 4055 bc	

^a IPE = isopropyl ester; + = chemicals applied in immediate succession.

^b Of active ingredient.

^c Taken at heading stage of grasses: EC = *Echinochloa crusgalli* and similar species; S = sedges; B = broadleaved weeds; P = *Paspalum spp.*

^d Average of four replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 19. Grain yield of transplanted IR8 and weed weight as affected by applying granular herbicides after emergence of grasses (15 days after transplanting). IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Herbicide	Rate ^a (kg/ha)	Weed weight ^b				Grain yield ^c (kg/ha)
		EC	S	B	P	
CP 53619	3.0	3	0	6	0 6080 a	
CP 53619	6.0	0	0	26	1 5664 a	
CP 56250	0.4	0	0	23	0 6133 a	
CP 56250	0.8	0	0	1	3 6021 a	
CP 57177	0.4	90	0	76	3 5446 a	
CP 57177 (liquid)	0.8	1	38	3	3 5875 a	
CP 29036 (liquid)	2.0	57	1	45	0 5209 ab	
CP 29037	1.0	379	4	0	0 4023 b	
CP 29037	2.0	36	0	18	0 5843 a	
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE ^d	0.75/0.5	0	0	18	3 5984 a	
Untreated control	—	443	4	216	0 4055 b	

^a Of active ingredient.

^b Taken at heading stage of grasses: EC = *Echinochloa crusgalli* and similar species; S = sedges; B = broadleaved weeds; P = *Paspalum spp.*

^c Average of four replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^d IPE = isopropyl ester.

Table 20. Grain yields of transplanted IR8 at three locations in the Philippines as affected by granular herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting. IRR cooperative weed control experiments, 1969 dry season.^a

Herbicide ^b	Rate ^c (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^d (kg/ha)		
		Maligaya	Bicol	Mindanao
TCE-styrene	0.75	5945 ab	7192 a	9388 a
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.75/0.5	6378 ab	7416 a	10303 a
Nitralin + 2,4-D IPE	1.5 + 0.8	6782 a	7383 a	10417 a
Propachlor/2,4-D IPE	2.5/0.5	6249 ab	6495 a	9440 a
Nitrofen + 2,4-D IPE	2.0 + 0.8	5828 ab	6823 a	9890 a
2,4-D IPE	0.8	6052 ab	6534 a	8893 a
EPTC/MCPA	1.75/0.7	5631 bc	6490 a	9710 a
Trifluralin/MCPA	0.7/0.4	6086 ab	7491 a	9609 a
MCPA-K ^e fb handweeding ^f	0.8	4779 c	7246 a	9935 a
Control	—	2251 d	4301 b	6079 b

^a With Bureau of Plant Industry in Maligaya and Bicol; with Central Mindanao State University in Mindanao.

^b IPE = isopropyl ester; + = chemicals applied in immediate succession; fb = followed by.

^c Of active ingredient.

^d Rough rice at 14% moisture; any two means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^e Water-soluble liquid applied 25 days after transplanting.

^f Thirty-five days after transplanting.

other herbicides for the first crop in Taiwan. The cooperative experiment in Korea was conducted at the Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Milyang, from May through October 1969. The experiment in Taiwan was conducted at the Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station from February through June 1969.

Preliminary results from Taiwan indicate that low temperatures during the first 2 months following transplanting of the first crop caused very little toxicity to the rice crop, and provided excellent weed control and significantly higher grain yield than the untreated control (Table 21).

Varietal effects of herbicide application

With the gradual increase in the availability of granular herbicides for transplanted rice, the varietal reaction to herbicide application is important. A field experiment was conducted during the wet season to investigate this problem. The varieties used were IR8, C4-63, and a promising selection, IR773A1-36-2-1. Eleven-

day-old dapog seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 20 x 20 cm. The herbicides used are listed in Table 22. C4-63 lodged heavily; the grain yield data obtained were erratic and therefore are not reported here.

The Monsanto herbicide CP 53619 showed high toxicity to the test varieties at the early stage of crop growth (this kind of toxicity was not noticed during the dry season). A heavy shower of rain occurred shortly after the herbicide was applied. The increased water depth may have exposed additional surface area at the base of the rice crop to the chemical, thus causing high crop injury. Heavy tillering indicas, however, recovered from the injury within 2 months after transplanting and produced a normal crop and high grain yields. Formulations of 2,4-D isopropyl ester on either limestone chips or on clay provided adequate control of weeds and showed no toxicity to either variety (or line).

Water management for granular herbicides

Certain water management practices must be strictly observed if granular herbicides are to be effective against weeds in transplanted rice.

In monsoon Asia, most rice is grown in fields where the water level cannot be controlled. It is therefore important to know how granular herbicides perform under variable water levels. A field experiment was conducted during the 1969 dry season to study the water management requirements for two granular herbicides for transplanted IR8. Table 23 shows the water

Table 21. Grain yields of transplanted rice in Korea and Taiwan as affected by the granular isopropyl ester of 2,4-D applied 4 days after transplanting. IRR cooperative weed control experiments, 1969.

Herbicide	Rate ^a (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha)		
		Korea		Taiwan
		Palkweng	T(N)1	Chianung 242
2,4-D IPE	0.8	5286	5789	5382
Control	—	4119	4572	4361

^a Of active ingredient.

management treatments used in the experiment. Granular formulations of EPTC/MCPA and TCE-styrene/2,4-D were applied before weeds emerged and after weeds emerged. Although the highest yield in this experiment was obtained with TCE-styrene/2,4-D under continuous flooding with 5 cm water, only 5 to 10 days of flooding were necessary to obtain adequate weed control by the two herbicides.

Without continuous flooding and weed control, the grain yield was less than 250 kg/ha. On the other hand, with continuous flooding with 5 cm water and without weed control, the grain yields varied from 3,000 to 4,000 kg/ha. These data suggest that a water depth of 5 cm helped weed control substantially although it did not eliminate the weeds completely.

The superiority of TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE over EPTC/MCPA in controlling weeds (average of all water management treatments) after their emergence is apparent from the grain yield data in Table 24. This additional quality of TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE may prove to be an advantage in many areas where farmers may decide to control weeds chemically just after the weeds have emerged.

Chemicals in place of land preparation

In recent years, attempts have been made in many countries to use chemicals in place of some tillage operations to control weeds before planting rice.

During the 1969 dry season, a study on the use of chemicals in place of land preparation was continued. Before planting, herbicides were applied to weedy plots infested with sedges such as *Cyperus difformis* L., grasses, and rice stubbles from the previous crop. Five days after herbicide spraying, pre-germinated seeds of IR8 were broadcast into 1 to 2 cm of water.

The grain yield data for IR8 are shown in Figure 15. The combination of dalapon/2,4-D amine followed by paraquat gave the highest grain yield, 7,281 kg/ha. Chemicals such as PCP with diesel oil or amitrole-T/2,4-D amine followed by PCP with diesel oil, or dalapon/2,4-D amine followed by paraquat gave grain yields similar to those from the plots which were plowed and harrowed. Paraquat applied alone resulted in grain yields significantly lower than

Table 22. Varietal response of transplanted rice to granular herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^c (kg/ha)	
		IR8	IR773A1-36-2-1
TCE-styrene	0.75	5454 c	5299a
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.75/0.5	6670 a	5799 a
Nitralin/MCPA-Na	1.5/0.6	5610 bc	5662 a
CP 53619	3.0	6300 ab	5787 a
Nitrofen/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.8	6698 a	5916 a
2,4-D IPE ^d (on limestone)	0.8	6136 abc	5743 a
2,4-D IPE ^e (on clay)	0.8	6191 abc	5758 a
2,4-D IPE ^e (on limestone)	0.8	6162 abc	5652 a
EPTC/MCPA	1.75/0.7	6041 abc	5820 a
Trifluralin/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.8	6600 a	5687 a
MCPA-K salt ^f			
fb handweeding ^g	0.8	6772 a	5454 a
Untreated control	—	4088 d	4000 b

^a IPE = isopropyl ester; fb = followed by

^b Of active ingredient.

^c Any two treatment means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^d From Bayer Philippines, Inc.

^e From Union Carbide Philippines, Inc.

^f Applied 25 days after transplanting.

^g Thirty days after transplanting.

Table 23. Effects of water management practices on weed control by two granular herbicides applied before weeds emerge^a (early) and after weeds emerge^b (late) for transplanted IR8. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Water management ^c	Grain yield (kg/ha)			
	EPTC/MCPA ^d		TCE-styrene/ 2,4-D	
	Early	Late	Early	Late
1 cm + 5 cm (0-20) (21-m)	6255	1831	6061	4936
2.5 cm + 5 cm (0-20) (21-m)	7460	3107	8250	5859
5 cm (0-m)	8098	5097	8791	8094
2.5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (0-10) (11-20) (21-m)	7786	3763	7224	6663
5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (0-10) (11-20) (21-m)	8241	5719	8305	7059
2.5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (0-5) (6-20) (21-m)	7582	5200	7833	3780
5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (0-5) (6-20) (21-m)	6630	6374	7638	6592
2-3 cm ^f (0-m)	7922	—	7895	—
Untreated controls				
1 cm + 5 cm (0-20) (21-m)		239		233
2.5 cm + 5 cm (0-20) (21-m)		605		694
5 cm (0-m)		3248		4452

^a 4 days after transplanting.

^b 10 days after transplanting.

^c For each water management treatment, the first line indicates the depth of water and the second line in parentheses indicates the corresponding period of flooding in days; m = maturity.

^d 1.75/0.7 kg/ha active ingredient.

^e 0.75/0.5 kg/ha active ingredient.

^f Standard practice at IRRI.

Fig. 15 Grain yield of IR8 (55 days after seeding) from plots receiving various herbicide treatments. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Table 24. Weed control (measured by yields of transplanted IR8) by two granular herbicides applied before weeds emerged^a (early) and after weeds emerged^b (late).

Herbicide	Rate ^c (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	
		Early	Late
EPTC/MCPA	1.75/0.7	7436	4447
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE ^d	0.75/0.5	7730	6140
Untreated control		1578	
Statistical analysis		s.e. LSD 5% (kg/ha)	
Two herbicide means at the same time of application		302	603
Two time-of-application means of the same herbicide		399	797

^a 4 days after transplanting.
^b 10 days after transplanting.
^c Of active ingredient.
^d IPE = isopropyl ester.

dalapon followed by paraquat.

These data suggest that zero tillage techniques may become useful in areas where the cost of land preparation is high or the implement used in preparing the land is not efficient.

Water management experiment

Moisture stress and growth and yield of rice

During past years, several experiments were conducted to study the effects of various water depths and periods of drainage on the water use and grain yield of rice. In monsoon Asia, dis-

Fig. 16. A stand of IR8 grown on montmorillonitic Maahas clay when the crop was subjected to moisture stress from transplanting to maximum tillering. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Fig. 17. When IR8 was subjected to moisture stress during the ripening period (from heading to maturity), growth was normal. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

tribution rather than amount of rainfall is critical for rice production. In many areas a period of drought occasionally occurs which substantially reduces grain yield. To study the effects of a drought period at various physiological growth stages of the rice crop, a field experiment was conducted during the dry season. In each plot, tensiometers were installed in the soil 6 inches deep to measure soil moisture tension.

For treatments receiving a stress period, irrigation was cut off a week before the stress period. The soil moisture tension was allowed to reach 50 centibars, after which adequate moisture was provided to compensate for losses through evapotranspiration. Table 25 shows that in tanks without bottoms, increasing the stress period during the vegetative growth stages increased the growth duration and decreased the grain yields. Figure 16 shows that when the crop was subjected to moisture stress from transplanting to maximum tillering, growth was retarded—the plants were shorter and had fewer tillers. The crop also produced low grain yield. The yield, however, was not significantly lower than that of the best treatment, continuous flooding with 2.5 cm water (Table 25). When the crop was subjected to moisture stress during the ripening period (from heading to maturity), growth was normal (Fig. 17) and the grain yield was statistically similar to the crop yield under continuous flooding (Table 25). The reason was that when the water was cut off after flooding,

the Maahas soil, which is a heavy clay, held enough moisture to carry the crop through the harvest.

Grain yields were reduced when the crop was subjected to moisture stress during the reproductive and ripening periods but not as much as when it was subjected to moisture stress during the early stages of its growth. These data suggest that grain yield will be reduced unless adequate moisture is available during the early stages of crop growth. If the crop is subjected to moisture stress during the reproductive and ripening stages of its growth, the grain yield will also be reduced, but if the stress period is preceded by continuous flooding, the reduction in grain yield

Table 25. Grain yields of IR8 and water-use patterns under various water management practices in tanks without bottoms. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Water management ^a		Maturity (days)	Grain yield ^b (kg/ha)	Water use (mm)
T	MT PI H M			
f	————→	123	7161 a	1147
f	→s————→	127	6314 ab	1178
f	————→s	124	6096 ab	904
f	————→s	124	5874 ab	730
s	→f————→	131	5842 ab	1435
s	————→f	133	4682 bc	1438
s	————→f	145	3758 cd	1121
Irrigation at moisture stress		152	1841 d	432

^a T = transplanting; MT = maximum tillering; PI = panicle initiation; H = heading; M = maturity; f = flooded to 2.5 cm; s = stress (50 centibars).

^b Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Fig. 18. The growth of IR8 was extremely poor when water was provided each time the crop exhibited moisture stress symptoms. IIRI, 1969 dry season.

Table 26. Grain yields of IR8 and water-use patterns under various water management practices in tanks with bottoms. IIRI, 1969 dry season.

Water management ^a					Maturity (days)	Grain yield ^b (g/sq m)	Water use (mm)
T	MT	PI	H	M			
f	→				123	908 a	618
f	→s			f	127	882 a	593
f	→		s		123	838 b	544
s	→f				131	768 bc	653
f	→		s		123	762 c	528
s	→		f		133	732 c	632
s	→		f		135	717 d	558
Irrigation at moisture stress					145	172 d	257

^a T = transplanting; MT = maximum tillering; PI = panicle initiation; H = heading; M = maturity; f = flooded to 2.5 cm; s = stress (50 centibars).

^b Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

may not be significant. These data were collected from a crop grown on a heavy clay soil with high

Table 27. Grain yields of IR8 and H-4 under various water management practices in large paddies. IIRI, 1969 dry season.

Water management ^a					Grain yield ^b (kg/ha)	
					IR8	H-4
T	MT	PI	H	M		
f	→				6562 a	5842 abc
f	→s			f	6398 ab	6366 ab
f	→		s		5880 abc	6668 a
f	→		s		5692 abc	5202 bc
s	→f				5207 bcd	5635 abc
s	→		f		4902 cd	5720 abc
s	→		f		4780 cd	4830 c
Irrigation at moisture stress					3969	2893 d

^a T = transplanting; MT = maximum tillering; PI = panicle initiation; H = heading; M = maturity; f = flooded to 2.5 cm; s = stress (50 centibars).

^b Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

moisture-holding capacity. If the crop suffered from moisture stress before adequate water was provided, the growth was extremely poor (Fig. 18) and the grain yield was considerably reduced (Table 25). Water-use data indicate that deep cracks which formed during stress periods caused increased use of water (Table 25).

When the same series of treatments were imposed in tanks with bottoms (Table 26) and under natural paddy condition (Table 27), the grain yield data obtained were similar to those obtained from the treatments in tanks without bottoms. The water-use data from tanks with bottoms indicate that evapotranspiration values from treatments varying in moisture stress periods were similar to those from the continuous-flooding treatment (Table 26).

Soil Chemistry

In 1969, emphasis shifted from basic studies of the chemistry of flooded soils to investigations of a more practical nature. Among these were soil factors retarding the growth of rice at low temperature, management of water in rice soils, chemical criteria of suitability of rice varieties for upland soils, and assay of carbon dioxide and organic acids in flooded soils.

Low-temperature injury to rice was more severe in acid soils than in neutral soils largely because of the persistence of harmful concentrations of carbon dioxide, organic acids, and water-soluble iron. Drying the soil between rice crops led to a substantial loss of nitrogen without compensating advantages; midseason soil drying aggravated the loss and also depressed yield. Internal drainage benefited rice on two soils which tended to build up salinity and alkalinity. In sharp contrast to the reactions of 15 lowland rice varieties or lines, four Philippine upland varieties showed marked resistance to manganese toxicity in an aerobic acid soil and to iron deficiency in an aerobic calcareous soil, but succumbed to the toxins in a strongly reduced soil. Differential titration was found to be a rapid and accurate method for simultaneously determining the concentration of bicarbonate and organic acids in the solutions of flooded soils.

Temperature of flooded soils and the growth of rice

In recent years there have been reports that the new high-yielding, photoperiod-insensitive, tropical rice varieties developed by the Institute at Los Baños (latitude: $14^{\circ} 10'N$; altitude: 39 m above mean sea level; mean daily temperature range: 25 to 29 C) were not doing well in northern latitudes and at high elevations in the tropics, especially in the cool season. This poor performance has been attributed to the influence of low temperature *per se* on the growth and reproduction processes of the plant. Because earlier experiments (1967 and 1968 Annual Reports) strongly suggested that the chemical environment of rice roots produced by low soil temperatures was an important cause of the poor growth of rice, studies on the influence of different soil temperature regimes on the

chemical kinetics (quantitative chemical changes with time) of flooded soils and the growth of rice were continued with further refinements. The main objectives were to identify the chemical factors retarding the growth of rice and to devise means of countering them.

The experimental procedure was the same as for the previous experiment (1968 Annual Report), but extra precautions were taken to insure that the temperature of both the soil and the supernatant water did not deviate more than 1 C from the desired levels. The temperature regimes are shown in Figure 1. The soils were the same as in the previous experiment (1968 Annual Report) except for the substitution of Korean sandy loam limed to pH 6.2 for the Korean silt loam.

Temperature regime markedly affected the chemical and electrochemical kinetics of the soils and the growth of IR20. The rates of

Fig. 1. The four temperature regimes used in the study of the effect of soil temperature on the growth of rice.

chemical and electrochemical changes during the first 4 weeks almost invariably corresponded with the temperature regimes in the order: 38 — 20 C > 30 C > 20 C > 15 — 31 — 18 C. The 38 — 20 C and the constant 30 C regimes quickly produced small concentrations of such substances as Fe⁺⁺, carbon dioxide, and organic acids which harm rice if present in excess. The constant 20 C regime gave the highest and most persistent concentrations of these substances. The temperature rise in the 15 — 31 — 18 C regime partially counteracted the effect of early low temperature on the concentrations of these substances. Growth and yield of rice followed the chemical pattern exactly. The adverse effects of low temperature were most acute in the acid soils and least in Maahas clay, a good lowland rice soil. These changes and their influence on the growth and yield of rice are discussed below.

Redox potential

The rate and magnitude of the decrease in redox potential (Eh) during the first 4 weeks generally corresponded with the temperature regimes in the order: 38 — 20 C > 30 C >> 20 C > 15 — 31 — 18 C. The differences were most pronounced in Louisiana clay (Fig. 2). The rapid fall in Eh in the 38 — 20 C regime in this acid soil is advantageous because of the reciprocal increase in pH.

Fig. 2. Influence of temperature on the kinetics of redox potential in Louisiana clay.

Soil pH

The spontaneous increase in pH that occurs when soil is submerged is one benefit of flooding acid soils. And the sooner this happens the better it is for rice because the pH rise eliminates aluminum toxicity and minimizes iron and carbon dioxide injury in acid soils. Figure 3 shows that low temperature retarded pH in-

Fig. 3. Influence of temperature on changes in pH in three soils.

Fig. 4. Influence of temperature on the kinetics of P_{CO_2} .

crease most in Casiguran sandy loam (pH 4.9; 0.M. ^a 5.3%), least in Albay sandy loam (pH 5.9; 0.M. 4.0%), and intermediately in Louisiana clay (pH 4.8; 0.M. 3.2%). The marked retardation of growth of rice at low temperatures in Casiguran sandy loam and in Louisiana clay can be partially correlated with the secondary effects of low pH.

Partial pressure of carbon dioxide

Carbon dioxide is an important chemical in flooded soils. Its partial pressure (P_{CO_2}) determines the pH, redox potential, and the solubility of iron, manganese, and calcium in flooded soils. If the P_{CO_2} is too large, the concentration of Fe^{++} may reach toxic levels and, in addition, carbonic acid may directly poison the plant; if it is too low the pH increases and this causes the solubility of iron to decrease, so the plant may suffer from iron deficiency. The kinetics of P_{CO_2} are, therefore, ecologically important.

Temperature regime markedly affected P_{CO_2} kinetics. In all soils, the 38 — 20 C regime produced the lowest peaks and the smallest overall P_{CO_2} values during the 14 weeks of submergence. With the single exception of Louisiana clay, no soil gave a P_{CO_2} value exceeding 0.4 atm at any sampling time. In the 30 C regime in almost all soils at all times, P_{CO_2} values

followed a course roughly parallel to, but higher than, the values in the 38 — 20 C regime. The peak values in the 30 C regime ranged from 0.77 atm in Louisiana clay to 0.23 in Maahas clay (pH 6.6; 0.M. 2.0%); the highest mean concentration (0.34 atm) was in Casiguran sandy loam, the lowest concentration (0.18 atm), in Maahas clay. The 20 C and 15 — 31 — 18 C regimes gave higher P_{CO_2} values than the two high-temperature regimes after 2 weeks submergence in almost all soils. The differential effect of temperature regimes (Fig. 4) was most pronounced in the sandy loam from Korea and least in Maahas clay. Liming the sandy loam from Korea markedly depressed the P_{CO_2} values in the low-temperature treatments.

These results indicate that the concentrations of carbon dioxide were least in the 38 — 20 C regime, intermediate in the 30 C regime, and highest in the early low-temperature regimes. A high temperature during the first 2 weeks of submergence prevented the build-up of high concentrations of carbon dioxide, a low initial temperature favored it.

Volatile organic acids

Volatile organic acids are found as intermediate products of the decomposition of organic matter

^aOrganic matter

in flooded soils. Their composition, concentration, and persistence depend on such environmental conditions as the nature and content of organic matter, kind and amount of oxidized soil components, pH, and temperature. The eight soils and the four temperature regimes used in this study provided a wide range of these environmental conditions. The kinetics of volatile organic acids reflected the conditions and indicated that low temperature led to a strong accumulation of these acids.

The volatile organic acids were determined by

a method which estimates formic, acetic, propionic, and butyric acids. Earlier gas chromatographic studies showed that acetic acid made up the largest portion of the volatile organic acid (1965 Annual Report). If acetic acid at a concentration of 10 meq/liter is toxic to rice, the kinetics of volatile organic acids may influence the growth of rice.

The kinetics of water-soluble organic acids in all soils at all temperature regimes (Fig. 5) followed the same pattern: when the soil was flooded the concentration increased, reached a

Fig. 5. Influence of temperature on the kinetics of volatile organic acids in six soils.

Fig. 6. Influence of temperature on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe^{++} in three soils.

peak, and then decreased to practically nothing. But the height of the peaks and the area under them varied with temperature regime and soil. In other words, the rate of acid production and the rate of acid destruction were determined by temperature and by soil properties.

In all soils, the 38 — 20 C regime produced the quickest and the smallest peaks. Concentrations ranging from 29 meq/liter in Casiguran sandy loam to 5 meq/liter in Maahas clay were reached within a week of flooding and were reduced to practically zero 2 to 4 weeks later. In the 30 C regime, the pattern was almost a replica of that in the 38 — 20 C regime, except that the peaks were higher and broader. Concentrations of organic acids reached a maximum of 10 to 36 meq/liter 1 to 3 weeks after flooding and dropped to nothing within 3 to 6 weeks. The heights and breadths of the peaks were generally greatest under the 20 C regime in all soils.

Casiguran sandy loam with its high content of organic matter produced the highest concentration of organic acids at all temperatures. The high concentrations were short-lived in the 38 — 20 C regime and in the 30 C regime, but they were persistent in the 20 C regime and in the 15 — 31 — 18 C regime (Fig. 5). The Korean sandy loam, which had a much lower content of organic matter than the other soils, had smaller concentrations of organic acids. The silt loam from Texas (pH 6.2; O.M. 1.5%), despite its

low content of organic matter gave high concentrations of organic acids at low temperature. The most dramatic differences due to temperature were in Keelung silt loam (pH 7.9; O.M. 6.9%). Organic acids persisted longest at all temperatures in Luisiana clay. Because the pH increase in this soil was markedly retarded by low temperature, organic acid injury may have been more severe than in the other soils. In Maahas clay, the concentrations were low.

As with P_{CO_2} , high temperatures accelerated both the initial increase in concentration and the subsequent decrease. Low initial temperature retarded the formation of organic acids in the first 2 to 3 weeks of flooding, but did not prevent a build-up of a high concentration later. In the 15 — 31 — 18 C regime, in most soils, the peaks were lower and the decline in concentrations more rapid than in the 20 C regime. These observations support the theory that the disappearance of volatile organic acids (chiefly acetic acid) is due to the breakdown of acetic acid into methane and carbon dioxide and that the bacteria that bring about this change do not function well at low temperatures.

From the ecological standpoint, at low temperatures toxic concentrations of organic acids may be present in acid soils high in organic matter for most of the growing season. Low temperature aggravates the harmful effects by retarding pH increase in the soil. The lower the pH is, the higher the proportion of the injurious

undissociated acid. The adverse effects are further compounded by high P_{CO_2} values at low temperature. Thus three easily recognizable harmful effects of low temperature on rice are low pH, high P_{CO_2} , and high concentrations of organic acids.

Water-soluble Fe^{++}

The concentration of Fe^{++} in the solution of a flooded soil represents a balance between the reduction process that renders iron soluble and the precipitation reactions that remove iron from solution. Reduction is favored by factors that enhance bacterial activity, while precipitation is favored by an increase in pH. This is clearly seen in the influence of temperature on the kinetics of iron in different soils. In the first week the rate of solubilization in the various temperature regimes was in the order: 38 — 20 C > 30 C > 20 C > 15 — 31 — 18 C. But the spontaneous and rapid increase in pH that accompanied reduction made the concentration decline rapidly in the same order. Thus high concentrations of Fe^{++} were short-lived in the 38 — 20 C regime and the 30 C regime.

Low temperature retarded but did not prevent the build-up of high concentrations of Fe^{++} . The concentrations were highest and most persistent at 20 C. The subsequent increase in temperature in the 15 — 31 — 18 C regime hastened the decrease in Fe^{++} concentration. Although the general patterns were similar, Figure 6 shows some differences due to soil. The differential response to temperature regimes was most pronounced in Luisiana clay and least in Maahas clay (Fig. 6). In Luisiana clay, harmful concentrations of Fe^{++} were present in the 20 C regime from the fifth to the 14th week after submergence.

Thus harmful concentrations of Fe^{++} may be present in acid soils during two critical stages of plant development: tillering and initiation of panicle primordia. Further, low temperature favors the absorption of iron as seen in Table 1.

Manganese

The influence of temperature on the kinetics of manganese concentration was generally similar

Table 1. Influence of temperature on the absorption of iron by a 3-week-old IR20 seedling placed in a 100-ppm iron solution for 24 hours.

Temperature (C)	Iron concentration (ppm)	
	Root	Shoot
20	7,780	2660
25	5,950	602
30	7,060	529

to that of iron but with notable exceptions. In Maahas clay, temperature regimes caused striking differences in manganese concentration, but not in pH, P_{CO_2} , and Fe (Fig. 7).

From the ecological standpoint, concentrations of manganese in the range encountered may not be important. So manganese may not be involved in chemical injury to rice plants at low temperatures.

Growth and yield of rice

Soil temperature profoundly influenced the growth and yield of IR20, but the effect varied with the soil (Fig. 8). The 38 — 20 C regime gave the highest weight of straw, the largest

Fig. 7. Influence of temperature on the kinetics of water-soluble Mn^{++} in Maahas clay.

Fig. 8. Influence of soil temperature regime on the growth of rice (9 weeks after transplanting) in Casiguran sandy loam (top), Korean sandy loam (center), and Maahas clay (bottom).

number of panicles, and the highest yield of grain (Table 2).

The 30 C regime was generally quite inferior to the 38 — 20 C regime in all soils except Maahas clay. The 15 — 31 — 18 C regime was more favorable than the 20 C regime, but markedly inferior to the 30 C regime. The influence of temperature was most pronounced

Table 2. Growth and yield of IR20 (averaged for eight soils) as affected by soil temperature regime.

Temperature regime	Straw (g/pot)	Panicles (no./pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Grain index
15—31—18 C	40	28	29	66
20 C	27	22	24	56
30 C	57	38	43	100
38—20 C	46	45	60	129

in Casiguran sandy loam and least in Maahas clay (Table 3).

Some chemical factors associated with poor performance at low soil temperatures are low pH, high P_{CO_2} , and high concentrations of organic acids and Fe^{++} .

Conclusions

(1) Soil is an important factor retarding the growth of rice at low temperatures. (2) Low-temperature injury to rice was more severe in acid soils than in neutral soils. (3) High concentrations of carbon dioxide, Fe^{++} , and organic acids in the soil solution appeared to be injurious. (4) Internal drainage, midseason soil drying, liming, or continuous submergence seem to be promising methods of minimizing the harmful effects of low temperature on the growth of rice.

Water regime in rice soils

Water management in lowland rice fields is a controversial subject. The Japanese dry the soil between crops and in midseason; they also stress the benefits of percolation in flooded rice fields. The chemical kinetics of flooded soils, however, suggests that in tropical lowlands these practices are neither necessary nor desirable. To solve this conflict, two long-term experiments were started in 1967 to examine the influence of soil drying and of internal drainage on the chemical changes in the soil and on the growth of rice.

After growing seven successive crops on three soils, we found that soil drying causes a heavy loss of nitrogen without compensating advantages and that internal drainage may benefit rice on soils that tend to be saline and

Table 3. Influence of four temperature regimes on the concentration of carbon dioxide, organic acids and iron in the soil solutions, and on the yield of IR20 in two flooded soils.

Temperature regime	P_{CO_2} (atm)		Organic acids (mmole/liter)		Fe (ppm)		Yield (g/pot)		Grain index
	Peak	Mean ^a	Peak	Mean ^a	Peak	Mean ^a	Straw	Grain	
Casiguran sandy loam (pH 4.9; O.M. 5.3%)									
15—31—18 C	0.42	0.31	39.3	18.6	290	150	17	9.3	28
20 C	0.45	0.30	37.7	22.5	320	233	12	10.6	32
30 C	0.50	0.36	35.7	8.0	335	129	67	33.0	100
38—20 C	0.29	0.26	28.6	4.8	244	84	59	65.9	200
Maahas clay (pH 6.6; O.M. 2.0%)									
15—31—18 C	0.22	0.16	14.6	4.3	66	45	71	46.3	71
20 C	0.20	0.15	17.7	4.0	73	56	60	53.5	82
30 C	0.23	0.19	14.4	2.8	60	60	83	64.9	100
38—20 C	0.28	0.18	5.5	0.8	63	63	63	78.1	120

^aDuring 1 to 14 weeks after transplanting.

alkaline at the cost of a heavy loss of nutrients.

Flood fallow vs. dry fallow with and without midseason soil drying

The rationale and the experimental details of this investigation are described in the 1967 Annual Report. Answers to the questions posed are in Tables 4 and 5.

Averaged for three soils, eight seasons, and the two midseason treatments, flood fallowing between crops was slightly better than dry fallowing and omitting midseason soil drying was clearly better than midseason soil drying (Table 4). Midseason soil drying combined with dry fallow was the worst treatment in all soils in almost all seasons (Table 5).

Midseason soil drying depressed yield while soil drying between crops (i.e. dry fallow) conferred no benefit. In addition, the chemical analysis of the soils after seven successive crops, clearly revealed the striking benefits of continuous flooding (i.e. flood fallowing without midseason soil drying) and the adverse effects of soil drying between or during crop seasons. Table 6 shows that continuous flooding for 32 months brought about a substantial increase in

the content of organic matter and nitrogen, and a slight but consistent increase in the cation exchange capacity and the content of active iron and exchangeable bases, relative to the dry fallow with no midseason soil drying—the standard practice on the Institute farm. Table 7 shows the tremendous loss of nitrogen caused by soil drying between or during the crops and highlights the need for a fresh look at the management of water in lowland rice fields.

Table 5. Influence of four water regimes on the yield of rice^a on three soils in eight successive plantings^b, outdoors in large drum.

Water regime ^c	Grain yield (g/drum of four hills)					
	2/67	6/67	1/68	6/68	8/69	Mean
Luisiana clay (pH 4.7; O.M. 2.9%)						
Dry fallow						
no m.s.d.	405	261	362	333	165	305
with m.s.d.	316	228	326	301	178	270
Flood fallow						
no m.s.d.	368	298	355	274	186	296
with m.s.d.	344	277	328	345	190	297
Maahas clay (pH 6.6; O.M. 2.3%)						
Dry fallow						
no m.s.d.	353	254	383	320	203	303
with m.s.d.	306	297	331	316	200	290
Flood fallow						
no m.s.d.	370	282	409	302	167	306
with m.s.d.	299	346	322	331	202	300
Pila clay loam (pH 7.6; O.M. 1.5%)						
Dry fallow						
no m.s.d.	342	303	360	285	201	298
with m.s.d.	308	238	306	279	187	264
Flood fallow						
no m.s.d.	372	259	366	281	154	286
with m.s.d.	287	272	332	293	162	273

Table 4. Influence of water management on the yield of rice averaged for three soils and eight seasons.

Treatment	Grain (g/drum of four hills)		
	m.s.d. ^a	No m.s.d.	Mean
Dry fallow	275	302	288
Flood fallow	290	296	293
Mean	282	298	

^am.s.d. = midseason soil drying.

^aVarieties: IR8 at 2/67 and 6/67; IR5 at 1/68; IR532-293 at 6/68; and IR20 at 8/69.

^bNo yields are reported for the crop planted 10/67 because of damage by a typhoon and grassy stunt disease, for the crop planted 11/68 because of heavy stem borer damage, and for the crop planted 4/69 because of a heavy attack of grassy stunt disease.

^cm.s.d. = midseason soil drying.

Table 6. Comparison of the influence of four water regimes on the chemical composition of the top 20 cm of three soils after seven crops of rice.

Water regime ^a	pH	Organic matter (%)	N (%)	Active Fe (%)	Cation exchange capacity (meq/100g)	Exchangeable bases (meq/100g)	Carbon: nitrogen ratio
Luisiana clay (pH 4.8; O.M. 2.9%)							
Dry fallow							
no m.s.d.	6.2	2.66	0.151	3.95	29.5	19.3	10.2
with m.s.d.	6.4	2.63	0.150	4.04	29.7	18.4	10.2
Flood fallow							
no m.s.d.	6.5	3.66	0.197	4.17	30.6	21.6	10.8
with m.s.d.	6.3	3.13	0.181	3.85	30.9	19.5	10.0
LSD 0.05		0.24	0.006				
0.01		0.35	0.009				
Maahas clay (pH 6.6; O.M. 2.3%)							
Dry fallow							
no m.s.d.	7.0	2.22	0.125	2.58	40.5	32.5	10.3
with m.s.d.	7.0	2.07	0.123	2.48	40.5	32.2	9.8
Flood fallow							
no m.s.d.	7.1	3.24	0.170	2.73	40.7	35.2	11.0
with m.s.d.	7.1	2.64	0.148	2.67	39.6	32.4	10.3
LSD 0.05		0.35	0.010				
0.01		0.52	0.016				
Pila clay loam (pH 7.6; O.M. 1.5%)							
Dry fallow							
no m.s.d.	7.7	1.92	0.102	0.95	34.1	34.3	11.4
with m.s.d.	7.6	1.89	0.099	0.95	34.6	33.2	11.1
Flood fallow							
no m.s.d.	7.7	2.22	0.138	1.00	35.0	37.9	9.5
with m.s.d.	7.5	2.16	0.132	1.05	35.7	36.1	9.5
LSD 0.05		0.14	0.010				
0.01		0.21	0.016				

^am.s.d. = midseason soil drying.

Flood following without midseason soil drying (i.e. continuous submergence) prevented the loss of 720 to 920 kg/ha N in 32 months. Since the average loss of nitrate nitrogen per season when the aerobic soils were relooded was 40 to 80 kg/ha N, there must have been an accretion of about 400 kg/ha, presumably by algal fixation, during the 32 months of the experiment.

Table 7. Influence of water management on the loss of nitrogen from three flooded soils after seven crops of rice, each fertilized with 100 kg/ha of N.

Water regime ^a	Relative nitrogen loss ^b (kg/ha)		
	Luisiana clay	Maahas clay	Pila clay loam
Dry fallow			
no m.s.d.	920	900	720
with m.s.d.	940	940	760
Flood fallow			
no m.s.d.	0	0	0
with m.s.d.	320	440	120

^am.s.d. = midseason soil drying.

^bRelative to flood fallow with no midseason soil drying.

Continuous submergence of the soil conserves and adds nitrogen without depressing rice yields. Therefore, we recommend year-long flooding where the aim is to produce the maximum amount of rice per hectare per year.

Internal drainage in flooded soils

An experiment was conducted to study the effects of drainage at 1 cm/day on the yield of rice and on the chemical changes in three soils. Experimental details are described in the 1967 Annual Report.

Contrary to expectation, drainage improved the yield of rice (Table 8) not in the acid soil (Luisiana clay), where it was expected to depress the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ and carbon dioxide, but in the nearly neutral soil (Maahas clay) and in the calcareous soil (Pila clay loam). All three soils had been irrigated with alkaline water (pH 7.8) for 4 years prior to this experiment. Drainage prevented the build-up of salt and

Table 8. Influence of internal drainage at 1 cm/day on the yield of rice^a on three flooded soils in six successive plantings.

Drained	Grain yield (g/drum of four hills)						Mean
	9/67 ^b	1/68	9/68	12/68	4/69 ^c	8/69	
	Luisiana clay (pH 4.6; O.M. 2.9%)						
yes	122	437	265	242	243	242	259 ^{n.s.}
no	135	435	320	214	266	228	266 ^{n.s.}
	Maahas clay (pH 6.6; O.M. 2.3%)						
yes	162	415	326	227	285	274	273 ^{**}
no	148	378	286	228	257	224	253 ^{**}
	Pila clay loam (pH 7.6; O.M. 1.5%)						
yes	135	405	308	253	298	258	276 ^{**}
no	142	383	268	233	250	226	250 ^{**}

^a Varieties IR8 at 9/67; IR5 at 1/68, 9/68 and 12/68; and IR20 at 4/69 and 8/69.

^b Low yields due to typhoon damage.

^c Experimental area heavily screened to keep out insects.

n.s. = Difference in drainage means within a soil not significant.

** Difference in drainage means within a soil significant at the 1% level.

alkali which benefited rice (Table 9). But the slight increase in yield was at the cost of an average of 40 kg/ha N per season which was lost in the drainage water from these two soils.

Criteria for upland and lowland rice

Although 90 percent of the world's rice is grown on flooded soils, the physiological reasons for the benefits of this practice are not fully understood. Previous experiments (1963-1966 Annual Reports) suggested that prevention of iron deficiency in neutral and alkaline soils and suppression of manganese toxicity in acid soils are two important chemical benefits of flooding rice soils. In view of the current interest in improving the yield of upland rice, an experiment was begun to determine whether resistance to iron deficiency in an aerobic calcareous soil and resistance to manganese toxicity in an aerobic acid soil, in the absence of water stress, could be used in selecting varieties physiologically suited for upland aerobic conditions.

Twenty-one rice varieties or selections, including four Philippine upland varieties, were grown on three soils (Luisiana clay, pH 4.6; Maahas clay, pH 6.6; and Pila clay loam, pH 7.6), maintained at field capacity in 15-liter pots in the greenhouse.

During the first 6 weeks after dibbling the germinated seeds in the soil, growth and tillering were best in the acid soil and worst in the calcareous soil. The younger leaves of some varieties on the calcareous soil had interveinal chlorosis. But by flowering, the plants on the

acid soil had suffered a setback. Many were showing varying degrees of manganese toxicity (brown spots and streaks between the veins of the older leaves, followed by yellowing and death of the leaves). On the calcareous soil, all plants were suffering from iron deficiency. These observations, along with data on the reactions of the varieties to suffocation disease, a disorder of rice associated with certain harmful substances in flooded soils, are in Table 10.

It is remarkable that the four Philippine upland varieties (Dinalaga, Azucena, Palawan, and Azmil 26) showed the highest resistance to manganese toxicity as well as to iron deficiency in aerobic soils, but succumbed to suffocation disease in a highly reduced soil.

Table 9. Influence of internal drainage at 1 cm/day for eight consecutive seasons on the pH and salt content of the saturation extract of three flooded soils.

Soil	Drainage	pH	Specific conductance (mhos/cm)
Luisiana clay	No	6.68	1.33
	Yes	6.30	0.74
Maahas clay	No	7.45	1.60
	Yes	6.87	1.16
Pila clay loam	No	7.62	2.44
	Yes	7.54	1.66

Table 10. Rating^a of 21 rice varieties according to susceptibility to manganese toxicity on an aerobic acid soil, iron deficiency on an aerobic calcareous soil, and suffocation disease on a flooded soil, based on leaf symptoms.

Selection or variety	Mn toxicity	Fe deficiency	Suffocation disease
IR5	2	5	1
IR8	1	4	2
IR20	1	1	0
IR127-80-1-10	5	3	—
IR305	3	5	2
IR332-2-10-1-2-1-2	4	0	2
IR408-2-1-11-1-1-3	1	2	3
IR408-2-1-4-3-6	4	5	3
IR435-7-3-1-1	3	5	1
IR661-1-170-1-3	4	2	—
IR661-1-140-3	5	—	3
Peta	1	4	1
Chianung 242	3	1	3
Taichung (N)1	0	3	—
PI 215936	0	2	0
Bluebonnet 50	0	0	4
Century Patna 231	0	0	1
Dinalaga	0	1	4
Azucena	0	0	4
Palawan	1	1	5
Azmil	1	0	5

^a 0: leaf symptoms absent; 5: leaf symptoms most pronounced.

Table 11. Comparison of four methods of determining the partial pressure of carbon dioxide, in eight flooded soils kept submerged for 4 weeks.

Soil	Partial pressure of carbon dioxide (atm)				
	pH	Differential titration	Gas chromatography	Titration	P_{CO_2} electrode
Casiguran sandy loam	4.9	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.13
Korean sandy loam	4.8	0.25	0.22	1.38	0.11
Korean sandy loam ^a	6.2	0.20	0.18	0.21	0.14
Albay sandy loam	5.9	0.30	0.25	0.29	0.13
Texas silt loam	6.2	0.21	0.19	0.21	0.13
Maahas clay	6.6	0.14	0.12	0.13	0.09
Keelung silt loam	7.9	0.28	0.22	0.28	0.13
Luisiana clay	4.8	0.31	0.24	0.31	0.24

^a Limed.

This study, though still incomplete, may have implications for rice taxonomists and breeders. First, upland varieties appear to differ physiologically from the lowland varieties. Second, these differences pertain to important chemical conditions associated with water regime. Third, if resistance to manganese toxicity and iron deficiency is genetic, it may be possible to combine these traits with good plant type to produce varieties better suited to upland soils. And fourth, breeding may provide a simple method of avoiding iron deficiency on flooded alkali soils.

Chemical analysis of flooded soils

During the study of the chemical kinetics of flooded soils an urgent need arose for a rapid and accurate way to determine the partial pressure of carbon dioxide and the concentration of organic acids in the solutions of flooded soils. Because the earlier methods were either too laborious or not sufficiently accurate, we investigated the possibility of determining carbon dioxide and organic acids by the method

Table 12. Comparison of two methods of determining volatile organic acids in the solutions of flooded soils, 3 weeks after submergence.

Soil	Differential titration	Colorimetric (meq/liter)
Casiguran sandy loam	37.1	36.7
Albay sandy loam	20.0	21.2
Texas silt loam	41.9	40.1
Keelung silt loam	33.8	34.2
Korean sandy loam	17.9	15.7
Korean sandy loam ^a	7.2	8.8

^a Limed.

of Di Lallo *et al.* With this method bicarbonate and organic acids can be simultaneously assayed by successive titration of the same sample.

Partial pressure of carbon dioxide

Calculation of P_{CO_2} from pH and alkalinity determined by titration with methyl orange as indicator is often vitiated by the pressure of organic acids (1967 Annual Report). The use of pH and total carbon dioxide measured by gas chromatography to calculate P_{CO_2} is more reliable (1967 and 1968 Annual Reports) but inconvenient. Because we believed the potentiometric method using the P_{CO_2} electrode to be rapid and accurate and because it could be combined with the determination of pH, Eh, and specific conductance in the same electro-metric cell, we re-examined its suitability. The defect of slow response of the potentiometric method (1967 Annual Report) was partly overcome by adding carbonic anhydrase and raising the temperature to 35 C. But the P_{CO_2} values were considerably lower than those produced by other methods (Table 11). Therefore, the titration method of Di Lallo *et al.* was modified for use with the solution of submerged soils.

Twenty milliliters of soil solution were titrated electrometrically to pH 3.9, carbon dioxide was expelled by gentle boiling for 3 minutes, a few drops of *o*-phenanthroline were added to prevent the precipitation of iron, and finally the solution was titrated to pH 7.0. The difference between the first titer and the second one gave the concentration of HCO_3^- in solutions whose pH was 7.0 or less. The P_{CO_2} values obtained by this method are compared with those from other methods in Table 10. The

second titer is a measure of the content of total organic acids.

Volatile organic acids

The gas chromatographic method of determining volatile organic acids used earlier (1965

Annual Report) was not rapid enough to analyze large numbers of samples. Because of the simplicity of the method of Di Lallo *et al.* it was modified to suit submerged soil solutions. This method compared favorably with the colorimetric method of Sedlacek (Table 12).

Plant Physiology

Studies on the relationship of leaf area index to dry matter production and grain yield showed that IR8 has no optimum leaf area index, but it does have a critical leaf area index for maximum crop growth rate. Thus, unless the crop lodges, vigorous vegetative growth or high leaf area index associated with high nitrogen levels and close spacings is not detrimental to dry matter production or grain yield in IR8.

The effects of mineral nutrition on the cyclic photo-phosphorylation rate of chloroplasts isolated from rice leaves were studied in relation to the photosynthetic rate of single leaves. Both cyclic photophosphorylation rate and photosynthetic efficiency remained fairly constant when nitrogen supply was varied, but they decreased markedly when phosphorus and potassium deficiencies occurred.

In studies of zinc deficiency in rice, the following were found to affect zinc uptake and zinc deficiency: available zinc content of the soil, soil pH, submergence, high concentration of bicarbonate ion, addition of organic matter, and alternate drainage and manganese dioxide treatment.

In a series of experiments, two different varieties, when grown on zinc-deficient soils, responded differently to zinc application. The differences could not be explained by any of the plants' measured responses or capabilities.

Among promising IRRI selections tested for their response to photoperiod, IR12-178 had the longest basic vegetative phase and the shortest photoperiod-sensitive phase.

Laboratory experiments on the effects of low temperature on anthesis revealed that the minimum temperature at which anthesis occurs in IR8 is 22 C; the optimum, 33 C.

Experiments on the effects of applying simazine to flooded soil at flowering time on the protein content of the rice grain showed that simazine application decreased growth or reduced total grain and protein yields.

Total submergence of rice at early growth stages was found to affect the number of tillers and, at later stages, the number of spikelets, in both cases reducing grain yields.

Leaf area index, dry matter production, and grain yield

Most researchers believe that in rice there is an optimum leaf area index (LAI) for maximum dry matter production under a given amount of solar energy. Last year, an attempt was made to determine optimum leaf area indices for IR8, an improved dwarf indica variety, and for Peta, a tall indica. However, because of a lack of data at high leaf area indices, we estimated the optimum leaf area indices, assuming that a parabolic equation would fit the relationship between leaf area index and dry matter pro-

Fig. 1. Relationship between mean LAI and crop growth rate of IR8 under different amounts of solar radiation.

Fig. 2. Relationship between mean LAI and crop growth rate of Peta under different amounts of solar energy.

Fig. 3. Comparison of IR8 with Peta in dry matter production at different LAI values.

duction (1968 Annual Report).

Optimum LAI does not exist in other plants, such as pasture crops, but a critical one exists beyond which dry matter production remains constant with increasing LAI.

Since the relationship of LAI to dry matter production and to grain yield is very important, further attempts were made to clarify whether an optimum LAI exists.

One reason, it is difficult to determine the above-mentioned relationships is that at high populations, rice plants that have high LAI values tend to lodge. IR8 is naturally resistant to lodging so nonlodged plots with high LAI values can usually be obtained. But Peta tends to lodge. To get data from nonlodged Peta, the plants were supported with bamboo stakes.

LAI and crop growth rate

In IR8 crop growth rate increased with increasing LAI and then reached a plateau (Fig. 1), indicating that there was no optimum LAI but that there was a critical LAI for maximum crop growth rate. Both critical LAI and maximum crop growth rate increased as solar radiation increased. At the plateau crop growth rate, 100 cal cm⁻² day⁻¹ of solar radiation could produce about 60 g dry matter m⁻² week⁻¹. Peta, unlike IR8, had an optimum LAI above which crop growth rate decreased with increasing LAI (Fig. 2). In both varieties, the

Fig. 4. Relation of grain yield and LAI of IR8 at flowering in wet and dry seasons (1966-1969).

crop growth rate was not affected by the level of solar radiation when LAI was small. The crop growth rates of the two varieties were similar at low LAI values; but at a high LAI the crop growth rate of IR8 exceeded that of Peta (Fig. 3).

LAI and grain yields

As shown in Figures 4 to 7, the relationship between LAI at flowering and grain yields of the two varieties is similar to that observed between LAI and crop growth rate. In IR8, grain yield increased almost linearly with increasing LAI and reached the plateau at about LAI 6. This indicates that when LAI is below 6, grain yield of IR8 is largely determined by LAI. In Peta, however, there was an optimum LAI for maximum grain yield. Excessive vegetative growth resulted in decreased grain yield. The efficiency of low LAI values in grain production is about the same for both varieties but that of high LAI values is quite different.

Critical LAI and critical light transmission ratio

In IR8, the grain yield reaches the plateau at LAI 6 at flowering. Figure 8 shows the relationship between LAI and light transmission ratio in IR8. At LAI 6 the light transmission ratio becomes about 10 per cent, which may be considered critical. Either critical LAI or critical light transmission ratio may be used to test whether the vegetative growth of IR8, or of any

Fig. 5. Relation of grain yield and LAI of Peta at flowering in wet and dry seasons (1966-1969).

Fig. 6. Relation of LAI and grain yield of IR8 and Peta in the wet season (1966-1969).

Fig. 7. Relation of LAI and grain yield of IR8 and Peta in the dry season (1966-1969).

Fig. 8. Relationship between LAI and light transmission ratio of IR8.

Fig. 9. Development of LAI of IR8 at close spacings and high nitrogen levels.

variety of similar plant type, is limiting to grain yield.

Growth of IR8 at high nitrogen levels and close spacings

The relationship between LAI and crop growth rate or grain yields obtained for IR8 indicates that unless the crop lodges, vigorous vegetative growth or high LAI is not detrimental to dry matter production or to grain yields. To confirm whether a high LAI could be detrimental to

grain yields, an experiment was conducted in the wet season in which close spacings were combined with high nitrogen levels (150 and 200 kg/ha N).

As shown in Figure 9, LAI ranged from about 7 to 12 at flowering. Plants grown in a 10 x 10 cm spacing, with 200 kg/ha N, reached LAI 6 about 40 days before flowering, and about LAI 12 about 20 days before flowering. Partial lodging or slight bending occurred about a week before harvest at 10 x 10 cm spacing at the two nitrogen levels.

Table 1 shows the growth status of the crops at flowering. The plant height was about the same for all crops, but there were large differences in LAI, total dry weight, and number of green leaves per shoot. It appears that the tendency of the crops spaced 10 x 10 cm apart to lodge was related to low numbers of green leaves. The grain yields in this experiment, as shown in Table 2, ranged from 6,674 kg/ha to 7,112 kg/ha, and can be considered practically the same. The panicle-to-straw ratio was higher, the wider the spacing. The data on yield components (Table 3) underscore the similarity of the grain yields from all treatments. Apparently, a high LAI is not detrimental to the grain yield of IR8 unless the crop lodges, but a LAI higher than 6 is not beneficial either.

Grain yields of supported Peta

As shown in Figure 10, the grain yield of Peta, when not supported, decreased with increasing nitrogen application. Supported Peta gave its highest grain yield at 50 kg/ha N; above this level its grain yield decreased. A comparison between supported and unsupported Peta plants indicated that lodging was largely responsible for decreased grain yield at high nitrogen levels. At 150 kg/ha N, the grain yield of supported Peta approached that of the unsupported Peta. This could be attributed, at least partly, to serious mutual shading caused by more droopy leaves at higher nitrogen levels. The maximum grain yield of supported Peta was lower than that of IR8. Thus IR8 has not only improved lodging resistance but also better photosynthetic activity, as shown in the relation of LAI to crop growth rate (Fig. 3).

Table 1. Growth status at flowering of IR8 planted at close spacings with high nitrogen levels, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Spacing (cm)	Height (cm)	LAI	Total dry weight (g/sq m)	Green leaves (no./shoot)	Nitrogen content of leaf blade (%)
150	10 x 10	115	10.4	1,132	4.5	2.65
	20 x 20	113	8.1	1,090	5.5	2.81
	30 x 30	113	7.2	834	5.7	3.10
200	10 x 10	116	11.8	1,192	4.0	2.85
	20 x 20	115	9.7	1,091	5.5	2.90
	30 x 30	115	7.5	838	5.7	3.04

Weight composition of plant parts at different LAI values

Figure 11 shows the proportion of vegetative plant parts of IR8 and Peta at flowering. The largest difference between IR8 and Peta was in the culm. This may partly account for the difference in starch accumulation between the two varieties (1967 Annual Report). The culms of IR8 weighed about the same beyond LAI 6 while the leaf blades and leaf sheaths weighed more with increasing LAI (Fig. 12). The rice culm respire but its photosynthesis is negligible. Presumably, therefore, respiratory loss by the culm would remain about the same beyond LAI 6. On the other hand, since IR8 leaves remain erect even at high LAI values, they can utilize incident light efficiently and maintain a good balance between photosynthesis and respiration at high LAI values. This may explain why high LAI in IR8 does not have any detrimental effects on crop growth rate and grain yields unless the crop lodges.

A comparison of Figure 11 with Figures 3, 6, and 7 suggests that the tall plant stature or the large proportion of culms in Peta is not necessarily unfavorable for dry matter production or grain yields at low LAI values when leaves are relatively erect and the crop does not lodge,

Table 2. Dry weight, grain yield, and panicle: straw ratio of IR8 planted at close spacings with high nitrogen levels, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Spacing (cm)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Total dry weight (g/sq m)	Panicle: straw ratio
150	10 x 10	7,112	1,448	0.97
	20 x 20	6,939	1,462	1.07
	30 x 30	6,816	1,324	1.22
200	10 x 10	6,876	1,460	0.93
	20 x 20	6,674	1,403	0.95
	30 x 30	6,906	1,354	1.09

Fig. 10. Grain yield of supported and unsupported Peta compared with grain yield of IR8.

presumably because a greater penetration of incident light compensates for the greater respiratory loss caused by a larger proportion of culm. At high LAI values, however, the balance between photosynthesis and respiration becomes unfavorable for net assimilation because the leaves tend to be more droopy and the shoot axis tends to bend, thereby decreasing light penetration.

The above data and previous results (1966-68 Annual Reports) seem to indicate that the

Table 3. Yield components of IR8 planted at close spacings with high nitrogen levels, 1969 wet season.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Spacing (cm)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Grains (no./panicle)	Filled grains (%)	1000-grain weight (g)
150	10 x 10	341	83	85.2	28.6
	20 x 20	295	103	85.0	28.4
	30 x 30	262	108	86.6	28.7
200	10 x 10	359	84	82.5	28.2
	20 x 20	298	101	84.1	28.0
	30 x 30	280	108	84.9	28.7

Fig. 11. Weight composition of vegetative parts of IR8 and Peta at flowering.

improvement of IR8 directly results from an erect leaf habit at high nitrogen levels, and at later stages of growth, and from short and stiff culms and high tillering ability. The erect leaf habit permits efficient light penetration, which increases the crop's photosynthetic potential and establishes a wide plateau range in the relation of LAI to crop growth rate and to grain yield. The short and stiff culms increase lodging resistance which helps the variety achieve its yield potential. The high tillering ability permits vigorous growth under sub-normal management by compensating for the insufficient number of hills per unit area and for missing hills. This attribute contributes to high average yields in farmers' fields.

Photosynthesis

Mineral nutrition, photophosphorylation rate, and photosynthetic rate

In a preliminary attempt to examine the use of chloroplast activity to characterize varietal differences biochemically, the effects of mineral nutrition on the cyclic photophosphorylation rate of isolated chloroplasts were studied in relation to the photosynthetic rate of single leaves.

The photosynthetic rate of single leaves was closely correlated with the nitrogen and chlorophyll contents of leaves when the nitrogen supply was varied (Table 4). The leaves deficient in phosphorus and potassium had very low photosynthetic rates, although they looked green and appeared to have high chlorophyll contents.

To examine the effects of nutritional conditions on the photosynthetic rate per unit of chlorophyll, the photosynthetic rate per hundred square centimeters per hour was converted into micromoles of carbon dioxide per milligram of chlorophyll per hour. The photosynthetic efficiency per unit of chlorophyll remained fairly constant when the nitrogen supply was varied. Phosphorus and potassium deficiencies, however, caused a remarkable decrease in the photosynthetic efficiency per unit of chlorophyll. Thus nitrogen nutrition affects the photosynthetic rate per unit of leaf area through chlorophyll content. In addition phosphorus and potassium deficiencies must affect the rate mainly through the photosynthetic efficiency per unit of chlorophyll.

Fig. 12. Weights of culm, leaf blade, and leaf sheath of IR8 at flowering.

Table 4. Effects of mineral nutrition on the cyclic photophosphorylation rate of the chloroplast and the photosynthetic rate of single leaves.

Mineral nutrition level	Composition of sample leaves			
	Chlorophyll (mg/100sqcm)	N (%)	P (%)	K (%)
Low N	2.07	2.43	0.55	2.20
Medium N	3.33	3.54	0.45	1.90
High N	3.66	4.00	0.27	1.50
Very high N	4.41	6.16	0.31	2.35
Low P	4.96	4.35	0.07	2.35
Low K	3.83	4.31	0.51	0.50

Mineral nutrition level	Photosynthetic rate of single leaves (mg CO ₂ 100 cm ⁻² hr ⁻¹)	Photosynthetic efficiency (μmole CO ₂ mg chlorophyll ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)	Cyclic photophosphorylation rate (μmole ATP/mg chlorophyll)
Low N	25	272	548
Medium N	34	227	508
High N	37	227	497
Very high N	48	245	515
Low P	22	102	315
Low K	13	77	273

Cyclic photophosphorylation remained fairly constant when the nitrogen supply was varied. But phosphorus and potassium deficiencies brought about large decreases in both cyclic photophosphorylation and photosynthetic efficiency. These results indicate that phosphorus and potassium deficiencies affect chloroplast activity in a different way than nitrogen nutrition.

The total cyclic photophosphorylation per unit of leaf area correlated well with the photosynthetic rate per unit of leaf area (Fig. 13). Although the conversion of radiant energy into chemical energy is only part of the photosynthetic process of single leaves, the results seem to indicate that the photosynthetic rate of single leaves is closely correlated with the cyclic photophosphorylation rate of isolated chloroplasts when expressed per unit of leaf area. The data also suggest that the photosynthetic rate of single leaves and the cyclic photophosphorylation rate of isolated chloroplasts expressed per unit of chlorophyll may be a reasonable measure for comparing plants at different levels of nitrogen nutrition.

Photorespiration

In a preliminary study of the possible use of photorespiration to compare the photosynthetic rates of rice varieties, the ¹⁴C-assay method was

Fig. 13. Relation of cyclic photophosphorylation rate of the isolated chloroplasts to photosynthetic rate of single leaves (ATP = adenosine triphosphate: V.H.N. = very high nitrogen; H.N. = high nitrogen; M.N. = medium nitrogen; L.N. = low nitrogen; L.P. = low phosphorus; L.K. = low potassium).

examined. We fed ¹⁴CO₂ on leaf disks in a Warburg vessel in the light and the amount of the radioactive compound released into air from which carbon dioxide had been removed was measured in the light and in the dark. The ratio of ¹⁴CO₂ release in the light to that in the dark was considered a measure of photorespiration. To minimize changes in the specific activity of the released ¹⁴CO₂, measurement of ¹⁴CO₂ was done within the linear range during the time course of ¹⁴CO₂ release. Figure 14 shows examples of ¹⁴CO₂ release in the light and in the dark for rice and sorghum.

As shown in Table 5, corn and sorghum have low light-to-dark ratios—about 0.1 to 0.2. Rice varieties, however, show ratios of about 1.0 to 1.7. These results agree with those reported for the compensation point for carbon dioxide. Rice varieties with high light-to-dark ratios have high compensation points for carbon dioxide.

Although the interpretation of light-to-dark ratio is not simple, these results suggest that the rice plant shows photorespiration.

Fig. 14. Comparison of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ released from rice and sorghum leaf disks in the light and in the dark.

Table 5. Release of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ from rice, corn, and sorghum leaf disks in the light and dark.

Leaf disk	Temperature (C)	Flow rate (ml/min)	Light intensity ^a (klx)	$^{14}\text{CO}_2$ release (light:dark ratio)
Rice	35	500	20	1.0-1.7
Corn	34	500	40	0.1
Sorghum	35	500	20	0.2

^a When $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ release was measured in the light.

Nutritional disorders of the rice plant in Asia

Besides nitrogen, other nutritional problems hold rice yields down. These problems are the so-called nutritional disorders or physiological diseases. Huge areas devoted to rice have nutritional disorders that limit plant growth. Twenty-five physiological disorders of rice have been reported from different rice-growing countries (Table 6). Some, like Penyakit Merah in Malaysia and suffocating disease in Taiwan, have recently been identified as virus diseases.

For the past 7 years, we have investigated nutritional disorders of rice in Asia. We visited 76 sites in 10 countries and made observations on symptoms of affected plants, on the soils, and on the physiography. In addition plant and

Table 6. Physiological disorders of rice reported in various rice-growing countries.

Country	Physiological disease
Burma	Amyit-Po Myit-Po Yellow leaf
Ceylon	Bronzing
Columbia	Espiga Erecta
Hungary	Bruzone
India	Khaira disease Bronzing Yellowing
Indonesia	Mentek
Japan	Akiochi Akagare I Akagare II Akagare III Aodachi Hideri-Aodachi Straighthead
Korea	Akiochi
Malaysia	Penyakit Merah
Pakistan	Pansukh Hadda
Portugal	Branca
Taiwan	Suffocating disease
U.S.A.	Straighthead Alkali disease

soil samples were collected and analyzed in the laboratory. The investigations were completed in 1969 and the results will be published in 1970 as an Institute bulletin (some findings were published in the 1965 Annual Report).

Diagnostic technique

A major part of the study was devoted to identifying the disorders found at the problem sites. To do so, plants had to be grown in culture solutions so that the symptoms caused by deficiencies and toxicities of the various elements could be systematically recorded. (Color plates of the symptoms will appear in the bulletin).

To supplement visual examination of the disorders, plant and soil analyses and simple greenhouse experiments were conducted when necessary. Table 7 lists tentative critical contents of various elements for deficiencies and toxicities. The data should be used only as a guide because they are subject to modification according to the criteria by which the disorders are defined, the status of other elements or substances in the soil, the growth stages of the plant, the varieties, the climatic conditions, etc.

Major nutritional disorders and conclusions

Figure 15 summarizes our observations of nutritional disorders of rice in Asian countries. It also includes information collected from the literature.

Deficiencies of phosphorus, potassium, and zinc, as well as iron toxicity and salinity, appear to be major problems. Iron deficiency was found occasionally in alkaline soils.

Phosphorus deficiency. Phosphorus deficiency is commonly observed on lateritic, black cotton (regur), red (chalka), Ando, and some acid soils.

This deficiency is primarily caused by soils that do not supply enough phosphorus to plants. The high phosphorus-absorption coefficient of Ando also is important because it affects the availability of applied phosphates.

Phosphorus-deficient plants have dark-green and erect leaves, and reduced tillering. When the deficiency is combined with nitrogen deficiency, the leaves become pale green. Most phosphorus-deficient plants observed during the survey were also nitrogen-deficient. Under these circumstances, plant tissue analysis gives a more definite answer. When the phosphorus content of plant tissues during vegetative growth is less than 0.2 percent, phosphorus deficiency may be merely suspected, but when it is less than 0.1 percent, a deficiency is very probable.

Since phosphorus deficiency occurs in soils of low or high pH, it is frequently associated with other kinds of disorders, such as iron toxicity on acid soils and iron deficiency or salinity in alkaline soils.

Potassium deficiency. Low potassium content was frequently found in plants growing on lateritic soils, calcareous soils, and some sandy soils. It was also associated with iron toxicity which was frequently observed on acid lateritic soils and acid-sulfate soils. *Helminthosporium* leaf spots frequently accompanied potassium deficiency.

The incidence of *Helminthosporium* leaf spots is closely associated with Akiochi in Japan and Korea. Akiochi occurs mainly on sandy soils with excessive internal drainage. However, a visual indication of a nutritional disorder observed on a calcareous soil with poor internal drainage was a severe incidence of *Helminthosporium* leaf spots in Bohol, Philippines.

porium leaf spots in Bohol, Philippines.

A major cause of potassium deficiency is soil that does not supply enough potassium to plants. Exchangeable potassium content appears to be a good measure of the soil's capacity to supply potassium. This may be particularly true in rain-fed fields where the soil is the only source of potassium, although it may not always be true for irrigated fields where some potassium comes from the irrigation water.

Zinc deficiency. Until very recently, field deficiencies of zinc in rice were unknown, although such deficiencies are common in up-land crops, such as corn, citrus, and cauliflower.

Khaira disease in Pant Nagar, Uttar Pradesh, India; Hadda in Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, West Pakistan; Taya-Taya in Cebu, Philippines; and Akagare Type II in Chiba, Japan, have been identified as zinc deficiencies.

Our investigations showed that the incidence of zinc deficiency is observed on calcareous soils of high pH. The main cause of zinc deficiency in rice appears to be low solubility of zinc in the soil at high pH values, low available zinc content, submergence, and nitrogen application (which increases growth, raising the plant's requirement for zinc). These causes are discussed later in this report.

The symptoms of zinc deficiency are some-

Table 7. Critical contents of various elements for deficiency and toxicity in the rice plant.

Element	Deficiency (D) or toxicity (T)	Critical content	Plant part analyzed	Growth stage ^a
N	D	2.5%	Leaf blade	Til
P	D	0.1%	Leaf blade	Til
	T	1.0%	Straw	Mat
K	D	1.0%	Straw	Mat
	D	1.0%	Leaf blade	Til
Ca	D	0.15%	Straw	Mat
Mg	D	0.10%	Straw	Mat
S	D	0.10%	Straw	Mat
Si	D	5.0%	Straw	Mat
Fe	D	70 ppm	Leaf blade	Til
	T	300 ppm	Leaf blade	Til
Zn	D	10 ppm	Shoot	Til
	T	>1,500 ppm	Straw	Mat
Mn	D	20 ppm	Shoot	Til
	T	2,500 ppm	Shoot	Til
B	D	<3.4 ppm	Straw	Mat
	T	100 ppm	Straw	Mat
Cu	D	6 ppm	Straw	Mat
	T	30 ppm	Straw	Mat
Al	T	300 ppm	Shoot	Til

^aMat = maturity; til = tillering.

what similar to those of iron toxicity. However, since iron toxicity occurs on acid soils and zinc deficiency on alkaline soils, these two disorders cannot be confused if the soil pH is examined.

Plant tissue analysis for zinc is quite reliable. If the zinc content of the shoot at the early growth stages is less than 10 to 15 ppm, zinc deficiency is likely.

Iron toxicity. Bronzing was first reported from Ceylon. It is associated with high concentrations of ferrous iron in soil solution.

The symptoms of bronzing are the same as those of iron toxicity developed in water culture by increasing the iron level in the culture solution at certain stages of growth, especially at the later ones. Bronzing is therefore considered to be caused by iron toxicity. Iron toxicity was frequently observed and associated with phosphorus and potassium deficiencies in acid, sandy, lateritic soils, in peaty or boggy soils, and in acid-sulfate soils. An interaction between iron and potassium is quite apparent.

Plants that have bronzing are often low in potassium. Potassium deficiency in plants appears to accelerate the development of bronzing symptoms. Akagare Type I in Japan has been considered to be caused by potassium deficiency. It can be remedied by the application of potash. However, the symptoms of Akagare Type I appear similar to those of iron toxicity, and plants suffering from Akagare Type I generally have a high iron content. Therefore, the disorder seems to be caused by an imbalance between iron and potassium.

Diagnosing iron toxicity by plant tissue analysis is difficult. The iron content of the plant is not necessarily well correlated with the development of iron toxicity symptoms. Examination of symptoms and soil analysis are more dependable ways to identify iron toxicity.

Salinity. During the survey, injury due to salinity was observed on sodic soils in the northern part of India, on calcareous soils in the southern part of West Pakistan, and on

Fig. 15. Nutritional disorders of rice in Asia.

Table 8. Relationship between soil properties and incidence of iron deficiency of rice^a

Locality	Iron deficiency ^b	Soil condition	pH ^c	Organic matter (%)
Umerha, India	+	Flooded	9.7	0.24
Manga, Pakistan	+	Flooded	8.6	0.43
Kimberley, Australia	+	Flooded	8.3	0.34
Bhai Pheru, Pakistan	+	Flooded	8.6	0.68
Rajendranagar, India	+	Upland	7.6–8.2	0.68–0.85
Pila, Philippines	+	Flooded	7.5	1.5
Eagle Lake, U.S.A.	–	Flooded	8.1	1.2
Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan	–	Flooded	7.9	1.7
Pant Nagar, India	–	Flooded	8.3	2.2
Cebu, Philippines	–	Flooded	8.2	3.6
Bohol, Philippines	–	Flooded	7.4	15.0

^aAll soils were calcareous, except the one from Umerha.

^b+ = Fe deficiency; – = no Fe deficiency.

^cAir-dried soil.

acid sandy soils in the Korat region of Thailand. Acid-sulfate soils also are potentially saline soils.

Salinity is generally associated with alkalinity in inland areas where evaporation exceeds precipitation. In coastal areas, however, salinity is usually associated with acidity. Their common problem is the high salt concentrations of the soil solution.

The most effective treatment is to wash the salts away with irrigation and drainage. This requires a heavy investment in the construction of an irrigation system and drainage canals.

During the survey, the plant samples frequently showed rather high sodium content (about 1–2%). Our greenhouse study indicated that under weakly saline conditions sodium may help rice growth by partially replacing potassium in the plant if sodium is the major cation and if potassium is deficient.

Varieties differ in resistance to salinity. In India, Jhona 349, Pokhali, and SR26-B are known as salt-resistant varieties. IR8 also is salt resistant. The salt resistance of a rice variety is important in determining its adaptability to a wide range of environments.

Iron deficiency. Iron chlorosis was frequently observed on submerged sodic soils and on upland or submerged calcareous soils. Iron chlorosis usually occurs in the early stages of plant growth, but it disappears in the later stages in submerged soils. Table 8 summarizes the relation of iron deficiency to the amount of organic matter in alkaline soils. Iron deficiency

seems related to the low organic matter content of the soil. In the greenhouse, iron deficiency in submerged soils can be corrected by applying cellulose or other organic matter.

Zinc nutrition of rice

Zinc availability and zinc absorption

Zinc deficiency has usually been found in rice grown on calcareous soils. To find out why, we studied the relation of absorption of zinc by the rice plant to the incidence of zinc deficiency.

Available zinc content of the soil. In the previous study (1968 Annual Report) neither total zinc nor 0.1 N HCl-extractable zinc of the soils appeared to be correlated with zinc content of the plant or incidence of zinc deficiency. Another attempt was made to characterize the zinc status of the soil by extracting soil zinc (available zinc) with a solution of EDTA and ammonium carbonate.

Zinc deficiency apparently occurs when the available zinc in the soil is less than 1.5 ppm and the soil is alkaline (Table 9).

Soil pH. In submerged soils, the pH of acid soils increases and that of alkaline soils tends to decrease, both reaching values near neutral. Therefore, the range of pH that affects the availability of zinc in submerged soils would be from the pH of the air-dried soil to about neutral.

To simulate this condition, the fate of ⁶⁵Zn in the soil was studied in the presence of 1 N KCl

Table 9. Soil pH, available zinc content, plant zinc content and incidence of zinc deficiency of rice.

Soil	Country	pH	Available Zn (ppm)	Zn content of shoot ^a (ppm)	Zn deficiency ^b
Luisiana	Philippines	5.8	18.2	83	-
Udonrthani	Thailand	5.8	17.5	34	-
Pila	Philippines	7.5	14.5	c	-
Maahas	Philippines	5.8	8.29	23	-
Bohol	Philippines	7.6	6.80	c	-
Eagle Lake	U.S.A.	8.7	4.78	15	+
Vatanakhurissi	India	5.1	1.76	20	-
Libon	Philippines	7.0	1.75	c	-
Minglanilla	Philippines	8.2	1.49	13	+
Kuntuni	India	5.3	1.04	46	-
Kala Shah Kaku	Pakistan	7.9	0.71	10	+
Bhai Pheru	Pakistan	8.6	0.58	12	+
Manga	Pakistan	8.6	0.53	11	+
Pant Nagar	India	8.3	0.42	8	+
Manohapur	India	10.4	0.39	12	?

^aFrom pot experiment, except Luisiana and Eagle Lake soils, which were grown in the field.

^b+ = Zn deficiency; - = no Zn deficiency.

^cNot determined.

and 1 N NH₄AcO solution. As shown in Table 10, a higher percentage of ⁶⁵Zn remained in the 1 N KCl extract in low-pH soils, indicating that the availability of added ⁶⁵Zn was high. Only a small fraction of added ⁶⁵Zn was left in solution in the 1 N KCl extract for alkaline soils, indicating the low availability of added ⁶⁵Zn. But when the soil was treated with 1 N NH₄AcO adjusted to pH 7.0, the availability of added ⁶⁵Zn increased in alkaline soils and decreased in acid soils. Thus the pH change caused by submergence could affect zinc availability in the soil.

Submergence. To study the effects of submergence on zinc uptake by the rice plant, a pot experiment was conducted under upland and submerged conditions using Luisiana soil (Philippines) as an acid soil and Eagle Lake soil (U.S.A.) as a calcareous soil. Zinc deficiency symptoms were observed in plants in Eagle Lake soil under submerged conditions 3 weeks after transplanting.

When Luisiana soil was submerged, the zinc content in plant shoots decreased sharply (Table 11). This may be explained by an increase in pH upon submergence. Submergence also caused a decrease in the amount of zinc taken up by plant shoots. This indicates that the sharp decrease in zinc content in plant shoots under submerged conditions was not caused by better growth but by decreased zinc availability

Table 10. Partition of added ⁶⁵Zn between solution and solid phase.

Soil	pH	1 N KCl extraction		1 N NH ₄ AcO extraction	
		Solution (%)	pH	Solution (%)	pH
Luisiana	5.3	66.9	6.9	18.9	
Udonrthani	5.1	97.7	7.0	67.3	
Maahas clay	5.1	56.9	7.0	14.8	
Eagle Lake	7.7	1.1	7.5	16.0	
Kala Shah Kaku	8.3	0.2	7.7	20.3	

or by something in the submerged soil that retarded zinc absorption by the plant, or by both.

In the Eagle Lake soil, submergence also resulted in decreased zinc content in plant shoots which produced symptoms of zinc deficiency, even though the pH of the soil upon submergence was expected to drop. The decreased zinc content in the plant might be partly caused by better growth in submerged soil. Other factors, such as bicarbonate ion, are also considered responsible for decreased zinc content.

Bicarbonate ion and zinc uptake. We have observed that zinc deficiency occurs in calcareous soils where drainage is poor or the water table is high. Adding cellulose to the soil aggravates zinc deficiency of rice in the greenhouse. In addition a high concentration of bicarbonate ion in culture solution retards zinc absorption by the rice plant (1968 Annual Report).

To confirm the effects of bicarbonate ion on zinc uptake, the effects of sodium bicarbonate and sodium chloride on ⁶⁵Zn uptake by the rice plant were compared, using IR8 as the test variety.

As seen in Figure 16, the bicarbonate ion itself markedly retarded ⁶⁵Zn uptake by the rice plant, as distinguished from the sodium ion and osmotic effects. That indicates that the effects of cellulose or other organic matter on

Table 11. Effects of submergence on growth and zinc uptake of the rice plant grown on Luisiana and Eagle Lake soils.

Soil	Soil condition	Dry weight (g/pot)	Nutrient content of shoot (ppm)			Total Zn uptake (mg/pot)
			Zn	Mn	Fe	
Luisiana	Upland	30	578	1,162	515	17
	Flooded	51	83	725	385	4
Eagle Lake	Upland	2	41	225	203	0.07
	Flooded	14	15	337	166	0.21

zinc deficiency can be attributed, at least in part, to the bicarbonate ion produced in submerged soils.

Organic matter and zinc uptake. A pot experiment was conducted to determine if different kinds of organic matter had different effects on zinc uptake by the rice plant in submerged soils.

Symptoms of zinc deficiency appeared about 3 weeks after transplanting in all the plants grown in pots treated with organic matter. The symptoms were clearer in plants grown in pots with added cellulose. However, rice straw and soybean leaves retarded dry weight more than cellulose (Table 12). The decreased growth was associated with decreased zinc content in the plants.

Effects of alternate drainage and addition of manganese dioxide on growth and zinc uptake. The addition of organic matter to the soil aggravates zinc deficiency; so zinc deficiency is somehow related to soil reduction. Under strongly reduced conditions, soil zinc could become unavailable to the rice plant by forming zinc sulfide which is very insoluble. To test this possibility, the effects on the incidence of zinc deficiency of continuous flooding, alternate drainage (two times a week), and addition of manganese dioxide and zinc sulfate were studied in the greenhouse.

About 2 weeks after transplanting, zinc deficiency symptoms started to appear in the plants subjected to continuous flooding, alternate drainage, and manganese dioxide treatments. Only the addition of zinc sulfate gave normal plant growth.

Table 13 clearly shows that the addition of manganese dioxide or drainage was no better than continuous flooding in increasing the zinc uptake or in alleviating zinc deficiency. Since

Fig. 16. Effects of NaHCO_3 and NaCl on the uptake of ^{65}Zn by IR8.

the addition of manganese dioxide was expected to keep the redox potential of the soil relatively high, it seems unlikely that the formation of insoluble zinc sulfide is the cause of zinc deficiency in this soil when it is submerged.

Effects of phosphate application on the uptake of zinc and phosphorus under upland and submerged conditions. A heavy application of phosphate is one cause of zinc deficiency in many upland crops. A pot experiment was conducted to test whether heavy application of phosphate aggravates zinc deficiency of rice under submerged and upland soil conditions.

In Louisiana soil, phosphate application resulted in decreased zinc content in the plants grown under upland conditions, but it increased

Table 12. Effects of different kinds of organic matter on growth and zinc content of the rice plant (Kala Shah Kaku soil).

Material added	Dry weight (g/pot)	Nutrient content of shoot (ppm)		
		Zn	Mn	Fe
Added cellulose (0.5%)	5.3	19	686	200
Added rice straw (0.5%)	3.4	19	555	170
Added soybeans (0.5%)	3.8	19	437	172
Added ZnSO_4 (40 ppm Zn)	8.4	51	437	202

Table 13. Effects of continuous flooding, alternate drainage, and addition of manganese dioxide under flooded condition on growth and zinc content of the rice plant (Cebu soil).

Treatment	Dry weight (g/pot)	Zinc content (ppm)
Continuous flooding	0.59	17
Alternate drainage	0.64	15
Added MnO_2 (0.5%)	0.66	15
Added ZnSO_4 (100 ppm Zn)	2.56	53

Table 14. Effects of phosphate application on growth and on zinc and phosphorus contents of the rice plant under upland and submerged conditions.

Phosphate added (ppm)	Upland			Flooded		
	Dry weight (g/pot)	Zn (ppm)	P (%)	Dry weight (g/pot)	Zn (ppm)	P (%)
	Luisiana soil					
0	4.0	1,324	0.18	2.2	55	0.08
200	5.3	581	0.26	4.8	55	0.19
800	6.4	558	0.43	9.4	74	0.27
3,200	6.9	562	0.64	10.1	113	0.33
12,400	3.3	481	1.05	4.9	119	0.54
	Eagle Lake soil					
0	0.1	75	ND ^a	1.3	12	0.31
200	0.5	59	0.34	1.5	10	0.32
800	1.4	71	0.56	1.9	13	0.34
3,200	1.3	87	1.27	D	D	D
12,400	D ^b	D	D	D	D	D

^a Not determined.
^b D = Plants died.

the zinc content of the plants grown under submerged conditions (Table 14). In Eagle Lake soil, phosphate application did not change the zinc concentration of the plant shoots, but it increased the total uptake of zinc by the plant.

Apparently a heavy application of phosphate does not cause zinc deficiency in submerged soil.

Varietal differences under zinc-deficient conditions

At Kala Shah Kaku Rice Station, West Pakistan, scientists have observed that some varieties and lines are more susceptible to zinc deficiency than others, as judged by growth performance. The line IR184-67-1-3-2 was among those which performed very poorly compared with varieties such as IR8. A study was therefore started to gain an understanding of varietal differences in plant nutrition.

Since both soil environment and climatic

Table 15. Seedling growth and zinc and manganese content of IR8 and three selections on Kala Shah Kaku soil and Maahas clay^a

Variety or selection	Dry weight of shoot (g/pot)	Zn content (ppm)	Mn content (ppm)
	Kala Shah Kaku soil		
PD17	0.42	14	315
PD19	0.56	14	287
PD23	0.52	11	332
IR8	0.77	12	292
	Maahas clay		
PD17	3.68	63	1,463
PD19	3.83	57	1,263
PD23	4.23	61	1,500
IR8	6.00	54	1,600

^a Data collected 26 days after germination.

environment affect the growth of rice varieties, two preliminary experiments were conducted to determine if a varietal difference similar to that observed in West Pakistan could be found in the Philippines. Table 15 shows the results of seedling growth on Kala Shah Kaku and Maahas clay soils in the Institute greenhouse. Because some evidence indicates that zinc and manganese may interact, the manganese content of the plant was also analyzed. We found that the three selections of IR184-67-1-3-2 (PD17, PD19, PD23) apparently are less vigorous than IR8 and that not much difference exists in zinc or manganese content of the shoot among the four varieties.

To compare the growth performance of IR8 as a resistant variety and of PD17 as a susceptible variety under zinc-deficient field conditions, an experiment was conducted in a farmer's field at Minglanilla, Cebu, Philippines in the 1969 wet season. At early stages of growth, both varieties showed very severe zinc deficiency symptoms when zinc was not added. At later stages, however, IR8 recovered rapidly but PD17 continued to have extremely poor vegetative growth and subsequent reproductive growth. These differences in recovery rate were reflected in grain yield as shown in Table 16. The ratio of relative grain yield of "with" to "without zinc" was about 3 for IR8 and about 10 for PD17. This indicates that IR8 and PD17 grown on a zinc-deficient soil differ in grain yield in response to zinc application. The following experiments attempted to determine the cause of the difference between the two varieties.

Difference in symptoms. When grown in culture solutions, different symptoms were observed. In IR8, a large number of brown spots appeared in the lower leaves. The basal portions of the young, emerging leaves became chlorotic and quickly developed brown spots. The brown spots were small (about 1 mm), discrete and circular, and, when severe deficiency occurred, were combined, forming brown streaks and blotches.

In PD17, only a few brown spots appeared on old leaves. The spots were larger (2-3 mm) than on IR8, quite diffuse, and ovate in shape. A purplish discoloration was observed on the leaf sheaths and leaf margins. The leaf angle

Table 16. Varietal difference in yield performance on a zinc-deficient soil, Cebu, Philippines.

Treatment	PD17		IR8	
	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Index	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Index
NPK	281	100	1,777	100
NPK plus ZnCl ₂ ^a	2,845	1,012	5,621	316

^a100 kg/ha Zn.

became large, giving the plant an umbrella-like appearance.

Clearly, the symptoms on the two varieties were different. Those on IR8 were easier to identify.

Critical zinc content. A culture solution experiment was conducted to determine the difference, if any, in the critical zinc content of the plant for zinc deficiency.

When the zinc content of the shoot was around 10 to 11 ppm, both IR8 and PD17 showed deficiency symptoms and their dry weights were reduced remarkably (Table 17). It appears that there was little difference in the critical zinc content.

Interactions between zinc, manganese, and copper were quite apparent. Zinc-deficient plants tended to accumulate more manganese and copper in the shoot.

Zinc absorption from dilute solutions. Difference in plant nutrition between varieties is usually related to the ability of roots to accumulate elements selectively. Therefore, a study was made to determine any difference in the ability of the two varieties to absorb zinc from dilute solutions. Both IR8 and PD17 were found to have about the same ability to absorb zinc from dilute solutions (Fig. 17).

Effects of bicarbonate ion on zinc absorption. As mentioned earlier, the presence of bicarbonate in the culture solution retards zinc absorption by the rice plant. Therefore, an experiment was conducted to study if there was any difference in bicarbonate retardation of zinc absorption between the two varieties. We found almost no difference between the two varieties in bicarbonate retardation of zinc absorption (Fig. 18).

A series of such experiments showed that IR8 and PD17 have greatly different responses

Fig. 17. Absorption of ⁶⁵Zn by IR8 and PD17 from low concentrations of Zn in culture solution.

to zinc application on zinc-deficient soils, that the symptoms of zinc deficiency in the two varieties are different, and that the varietal difference cannot be explained by any measured plant response or capability, such as critical zinc content for deficiency, capability to accumulate zinc from dilute solution, or bicarbonate retardation of zinc absorption. No varietal difference seemed to exist in the absorption of zinc from solution when zinc deficiency was induced, but there was a difference in the rate of recovery from zinc deficiency

Table 17. Dry weight and zinc, manganese, and copper content of rice plants (IR8 and PD17) grown at low concentrations of zinc in culture solutions^a

Added zinc (ppm)	Dry weight (g/pot)		Nutrient content of shoot (ppm)		
	Shoot	Root	Zn	Mn	Cu
	IR8				
0	1.4	0.4	11	3,628	51
10 ⁻⁴	1.5	0.5	12	2,696	50
10 ⁻³	2.5	0.7	11	1,843	34
10 ⁻²	8.9	2.3	14	473	15
	PD17				
0	1.0	0.4	10	4,075	56
10 ⁻⁴	1.4	0.5	11	3,487	48
10 ⁻³	2.4	0.8	9	2,096	30
10 ⁻²	5.0	0.9	22	997	21

^aData collected 37 days after germination.

Fig. 18. Effect of NaHCO₃ on the uptake of ⁶⁵Zn by IR8 and PD17.

under field condition. It therefore seems important to determine what internal activity or activities are related to faster recovery of growth. This subject appears to be related to "vigor."

Zinc toxicity in rice

Although small amounts of zinc are indispensable for plants, high levels of zinc can stunt plants. Annual applications of zinc to zinc-deficient soils must be made cautiously so that

levels of zinc in the soil are not raised to toxic levels. As mentioned earlier, the rice plant had very high zinc content when grown on Louisiana soil under upland condition.

Within the range of concentrations tested, symptoms of zinc toxicity were not clear. The lower leaves of plants grown in culture solution containing 56 ppm of added zinc had interveinal chlorosis (Table 18). When the zinc content of the shoot exceeds about 2,000 ppm, zinc toxicity may be suspected.

Interactions between zinc and manganese are quite apparent from Table 18. Unlike the results obtained with zinc-deficient plants, no zinc-copper interactions seemed to occur in the tops of normal and zinc-toxic plants. The data indicate that rice is quite resistant to zinc toxicity.

Zinc deficiency of rice in the Philippines

In some fields in Minglanilla, Cebu, Philippines, a disorder of rice, locally known as Taya-Taya, has been known to exist since 1945. Several attempts to cure the disorder with insecticides and fungicides have been unsuccessful.

In March we inspected the disorder at the site. The symptoms and soil properties suggested that the disorder might have been caused by zinc deficiency. Subsequent greenhouse studies and field experiments have confirmed this diagnosis.

Symptoms and soil properties. The disorder is characterized by stunting and yellowing which occurs about 2 weeks after transplanting, followed by the formation of rusty brown spots on the lower leaves. Growth usually recovers to some extent at later stages.

The soil has a pH of 8.2 in water and is calcareous. The exchangeable potassium of the soil is 0.13 meq/100 g soil, suggesting the possibility of potassium deficiency.

Table 18. Dry weight and zinc, manganese, and copper content of the rice plant grown at high concentrations of zinc in culture solutions.*

Added zinc (ppm)	Dry weight (g/pot)		Nutrient content of shoot (ppm)		
	Shoot	Root	Zn	Mn	Cu
	IR8				
10 ⁻²	18.8	7.3	44	216	8
10 ⁻¹	19.7	7.2	55	219	8
1	19.8	7.5	223	191	8
10	20.2	7.3	758	119	10
31	18.7	6.6	1,516	44	8
56	17.7	5.8	2,219	31	8
	PD17				
10 ⁻²	15.5	5.5	34	233	10
10 ⁻¹	15.9	5.2	90	263	14
1	17.7	6.4	234	206	12
10	16.7	5.9	836	119	10
21	15.5	4.9	1,672	47	10
56	13.8	9.0	2,250	31	13

* Data collected 40 days after germination.

Table 19. Effect of added zinc on IR8 grown in zinc-deficient soil in the greenhouse.*

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Dry weight (g)	Zn content (ppm)
No Zn	26	0.53	19
With zinc sulfate	47	1.73	33

* Plants harvested 4 weeks after transplanting.

Greenhouse experiment. A greenhouse experiment was conducted using the problem soil to determine if the addition of zinc could alleviate the disorder.

About 3 weeks after transplanting, the rice plants without added zinc developed chlorosis along the midrib and brown spots and blotches, and were very stunted. The addition of zinc resulted in a remarkable increase in dry weight which was associated with an increase in zinc content (Table 19). Later in the experiment, some indications of potassium deficiency were observed in the plants with added zinc.

Field experiment. A field experiment was conducted in the wet season at the problem site in Minglanilla, Cebu.

At early stages of growth, plants without zinc application had extremely reduced plant height, tiller number, and dry weight, and zinc content was very low (Table 20). The zinc chloride treatment was more effective than the 1-percent zinc oxide treatment. The dry weight of the plants treated with 1-percent zinc oxide was only half that of the plants treated with zinc chloride.

Without potassium application, the plant's potassium content was relatively low, but still within the range for normal growth.

Data on grain yield show that applying zinc chloride or dipping seedlings in a 1-percent suspension of zinc oxide before transplanting increased rice yield by 300 percent. Although there was a large difference in dry weight between the two treatments at early stages of growth, the plants treated with 1-percent zinc oxide showed greater recovery at subsequent stages of growth and gave about the same grain yield as those treated with zinc chloride.

Application of potassium did not have any beneficial effect on grain yield at the yield level obtained.

This field experiment also indicates that early growth status is not necessarily related to grain yield in zinc-deficient plants and that grain yield should be measured to obtain a proper assessment of the effectiveness of the zinc source.

Photoperiod

Review of literature

A comprehensive review of the literature on the flowering effects of photoperiod on the rice plant was completed in 1969 and will be published in 1970.

The following general statements may be drawn from the papers reviewed which consisted of almost 400 articles:

1. Rice is a short-day plant. Nearly all varieties mature within a shorter time under a short photoperiod (about 10 hours) than under a long one (14 hours), but the degree of sensitivity varies greatly among varieties.
2. Younger leaves are more receptive to the photoperiodic stimulus than older leaves. Leaf sheaths may also receive the stimulus.
3. The photoperiodic stimulus is not translocated from one tiller to another in the same plant.
4. The minimum number of photoinductive cycles necessary to initiate the panicle primordium varies from five to 24. It differs not only with varieties, but also with the photoperiod being used.
5. The response of the rice plant to photoperiod is governed by the length of the longest

Table 20. Effects of zinc application on growth, yield, and zinc content of the rice plant on a calcareous soil, Cebu, Philippines.

Treatment	35 days after transplanting						Relative yield
	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Dry weight (g/hill)	Nutrient content of shoot		Grain yield (kg/ha)	
				K (%)	Zn (ppm)		
NPK	31	8	1.0	2.0	15	1,777	100
NPK plus dipping in 1% ZnO	52	16	5.4	3.1	22	5,346	301
NPK plus ZnCl ₂ ^a	62	17	11.5	2.1	55	5,621	316
NP plus ZnCl ₂ ^a	58	18	10.8	1.7	60	5,122	288

^a100 kg/ha Zn.

Table 21. Days from treatment to visible emergence of panicle primordium (1 mm) in eight varieties.

No. of photoinductive cycles	Raminad Str. 3	Podiwi A-8	Radin China 4	Engkatek	Serendah Kuning 23 (days)	Siam 48	Gow Ruang 88	BPI-76
0	+ ^a	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
6	+	+	+	+	+	+	b	c
8	+	+	+	30	36	30	16	18
10	b	c	b	26	21	16	14	15
12	36	24	26	20	18	14	14	14
14	26	18	19	17	16	14	14	14
18	18	18	18	—	—	—	—	—
Control	18	18	18	16	15	14	14	14

^a + = no panicle initiation.

^b Some plants had visible panicle primordia.

^c No visible panicle initiation, degeneration of shoot apex.

continuous dark period. Very short light periods (3-15 minutes) during the dark period may markedly affect the time of heading in some varieties.

6. For supplementary illumination or light breaks, red light is the most effective.

7. Varieties very sensitive to photoperiod may react to very low light intensities (1-100 lux). Twilight may contribute significantly to photoperiod length under natural daylength.

8. In addition to panicle initiation, the developmental processes between initiation and anthesis may also be affected by the prevailing photoperiod.

9. The duration of the basic vegetative phase ranges from 15 to 60 days, while the photoperiod-sensitive phase can be extended to as long as 12 years (actually recorded). For photoperiod-sensitive varieties, the optimum photoperiod is about 10 hours while the critical photoperiod ranges from 12 to 14 hours.

10. The basic vegetative phase, photoperiod-sensitive phase, critical photoperiod, and

optimum photoperiod differ among varieties. The variations in each are largely responsible for the differences in flowering response to photoperiod among varieties.

11. High photoperiod sensitivity is controlled by one or two dominant genes; the basic vegetative phase is controlled by two or three genes of cumulative, but unequal effect. A short basic vegetative phase is dominant to a long one.

Photoinductive cycles needed for panicle initiation

The reported minimum number of photoinductive cycles needed to initiate the panicle primordium in rice ranges from five to 24 cycles. Since only one or two varieties were used in the reported experiments and a comparison of the results is not possible, the reported range may not be accurate. The minimum requirement may vary not only with the photoperiod being used but also with the variety.

An experiment was conducted on eight photoperiod-sensitive varieties primarily to determine if the minimum number of photo-

Table 22. Days from treatment to flowering of eight photoperiod-sensitive varieties under different photoinductive cycles.

No. of photoinductive cycles	Raminad Str. 3	Podiwi A-8	Radin China 4	Engkatek	Serendah Kuning 23 (days)	Siam 48	Gow Ruang 88	BPI-76
0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6	—	—	—	—	—	—	b	b
8	—	—	—	a	a	a	72	74
10	a	—	a	a	58	58	47	50
12	a	—	a	62	52	46	42	43
14	104	70	60	59	44	42	39	42
18	56	54	48	—	—	—	—	—
Control	38	39	39	38	35	32	32	35

^a Panicles formed, but no exertion.

^b Panicles initiated, new branch formed.

Table 23. Leaf numbers of eight photoperiod-sensitive varieties given different photoinductive treatments.

No. of photoinductive cycles	Raminad Str. 3	Podiwi A-8	Radin China 4	Engkatek (no. of leaves)	Serendah Kuning 23	Siam 48	Gow Ruang 88	BPI-76
0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
8	—	—	—	—	—	15	15	14
10	—	—	17	16	15	15	15	14
12	—	15	16	15	15	14	14	14
14	15	14	16	16	15	15	15	14
18	15	14	16	—	—	—	—	—
Control	15	14	16	16	15	15	15	14

inductive cycles needed for panicle initiation and panicle emergence differs with varieties.

Plants were grown for 40 days under a 24-hour photoperiod, after which they were divided into seven groups. The following treatments were then given: 0, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, and 18 photoinductive cycles of 10 hours each, after which the plants were returned to a 24-hour photoperiod. The control received continuous photoinductive cycles of 10 hours each.

The minimum number of photoinductive cycles needed for panicle initiation ranges from eight to 12 (Table 21).

Based on flowering, rather than panicle initiation, varieties show greater differences in the number of photoinductive cycles required (Table 22). The greater the sensitivity to photoperiod of a variety, the more photoinductive cycles it needs to flower. A difference of two photoinductive cycles could determine whether the panicle exerted or not. The data show that panicle initiation, as influenced by photoinductive cycles, is a separate phenomenon from internode elongation.

The leaf number of a variety was more or less the same in all the photoinductive treatments that resulted in flowering (Table 23). The delay in flowering of plants that received fewer photoinductive cycles was the result of slower leaf development and slower internode elongation since the treatments were all started at the same leaf number or time.

Response of Korean varieties

Since the growing season in Korea is short, rice varieties there must either be relatively insensitive to daylength to prevent any delay in growth durations or highly sensitive to

daylength with a long critical photoperiod. Although temperature and daylength have a wide range in Korea, the rice varieties being planted there are obviously adapted to such conditions. Since an understanding of the growth duration of Korean varieties would help in selecting new varieties for Korea, a study was made on the effect of these factors on growth duration and on the characters of the rice varieties responsible for such adaptation.

Fifteen Korean varieties representing early, medium, and late types were used in the photoperiod studies. The plants were grown for 8 hours in natural light in the greenhouse and then transferred to darkrooms with different photoperiods: 8, 10, 12, 13, 14, and 16 hours of light, using artificial light of low intensity to extend the photoperiod. The temperature in the darkrooms was maintained at 21 C.

All varieties flowered at all the photoperiods used, indicating that the Korean varieties are relatively insensitive to photoperiod (Table 24). A delay can be expected in these varieties if the daylength is beyond 14 hours, however.

At photoperiods of 14 and 16 hours the early varieties generally flowered before the medium and late varieties. But there seemed to be no distinct difference between the medium and late varieties.

The basic vegetative phase, determined by subtracting 35 days from the minimum growth duration, was longer in the early than in the late varieties. The photoperiod-sensitive phase, determined by subtracting the minimum growth duration from the maximum growth duration, was shorter in the early than in the late varieties. The optimum photoperiod for the Korean varieties was around 10 hours, which is about

Table 24. Flowering response of Korean varieties to different photoperiods.

Variety	Photoperiod (hr)						BVP ^a (days)	PSP ^b (days)
	8	10	12 (days to flowering)	13	14	16		
Early								
Suwon 118	78	71	71	72	80	91	36	20
Norin 17	78	69	70	73	79	89	34	20
Fujisaka 5	67	60	60	60	69	79	25	19
Yuku-132	73	66	68	71	80	91	31	25
Suwon 82	68	62	63	63	81	131	27	69
Medium								
Sunson	64	55	64	59	81	127	19	73
Paltal	69	60	59	67	80	121	24	62
Shirogame	66	59	60	63	80	124	24	65
Pungok	69	64	64	73	87	128	29	64
Jinhung	67	56	56	60	81	136	21	80
Late								
Norin 29	63	56	56	60	88	118	21	62
Chonbunok	67	59	59	65	65	117	24	58
Palkwoeng	67	60	60	65	89	125	25	65
Umbangju	63	57	57	63	89	122	22	65
Nongkwang	65	54	55	62	86	137	19	83

^a Basic vegetative phase.

^b Photosensitive phase.

the same for most rice varieties.

When planted in the warm tropical regions, the growth duration of Korean varieties is short. There will be no problem of plants not flowering because of daylength. On the other hand, varieties to be developed for Korea should be relatively insensitive to photoperiod, based on the general photoperiod characteristic of the Korean varieties. Since most photoperiod-sensitive varieties have short critical photoperiods (around 12 hours), it would be difficult to introduce them to Korea because their flowering would be greatly delayed. A variety with a critical photoperiod of around 13 hours might be able to adapt to Korean conditions; however, no such variety is known to exist.

Response of promising IRR1 selections

Of the five promising IRR1 selections tested, IR532-1-218 showed the shortest growth duration (Table 25). At optimum photoperiod, it flowered in 66 days after soaking. Its photoperiod sensitivity is similar to that of IR8. It has a shorter growth duration than IR8 because of its shorter basic vegetative phase.

IR12-178 had the longest basic vegetative phase and the shortest photoperiod-sensitive phase. It also has the shortest photoperiod-sensitive phase recorded in all the tests so far conducted at IRR1, which have included more

than 120 varieties and selections. Norin 20 and Milfor(6)2 are the only varieties that come close to this selection. Under tropical conditions, however, Norin 20 has an extremely short growth duration—48 days from sowing to flowering under optimum photoperiod. Milfor(6)2, on the other hand, has a long growth duration—106 days from sowing to flowering under optimum photoperiod. IR12-178 should be a good source of photoperiod-insensitive genes. Aside from the effect of temperature, this selection can be planted at any latitude.

All selections tested flowered at all photoperiod treatments. IR410-1-16-9-1 showed the greatest photoperiod sensitivity, followed by IR20 (formerly IR532E576). Although IR20 is not as sensitive as IR5, it is more sensitive than IR8.

Temperature

In the tropics, temperature is more or less constant and, within safe limits, causes little concern. When varieties are introduced from one latitude to another, daylength is a primary concern. But with the use of new varieties that are almost insensitive to photoperiods, low temperature can become a limiting factor and its effects are now apparent. A common example is the extended

Fig. 19. Temperature pattern during the rice cropping season at Hokkaido, Japan; Katmandu, Nepal; and Los Baños and La Trinidad, Philippines.

growth duration resulting from low temperature in subtropical regions. The introduction of new photoperiod-insensitive varieties, like IR8, to subtropical regions and high-altitude areas has caused problems which were not apparent during testing under tropical conditions.

Generally temperature problems involve only the low temperatures since the rice plant tolerates high temperatures. The temperature patterns of subtropical and temperate regions

are different from those of high-altitude areas, however. Figure 19 shows that low temperature is a serious problem during the seedling and early growth stage in temperate areas such as Hokkaido (Japan). During active tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering, low temperature is not usually a problem.

In high-altitude areas, like La Trinidad (Philippines), the temperature is almost uniformly low throughout the growing season. The

Table 25. Responses of four IRRI selections, IR20, and TKM-6 to photoperiod.

Variety or selection	Photoperiod (hr)				BVP ^a (days)	PSP ^b (days)	Photoperiod (hr)			
	10	12 (days to flowering)	16	24			10	12 (no. of leaves)	16	24
IR20	78	81	115	126	43	48	11	11	13	13
IR532-1-218 [Peta/3 x T(N)1] x TKM-6	66	68	87	101	31	35	10	10	12	13
IR127-70-3-1 CP-SLO x Sigadis	83	82	108	119	47	37	12	11	14	15
IR410-1-16-4-1 Dawn x Sigadis/2	85	99	126	141	50	56	12	11	15	15
IR12-178 (MCVA x lgt)	89	89	91	—	54	2	11	11	12	—
TKM-6	69	68	118	132	33	64	9	9	13	13
IR8 ^c	88	86	118	—	51	32	—	—	—	—

^aBasic vegetative phase.

^bPhotosensitive phase.

^cData for IR8 response were obtained from a different set of tests.

Fig. 20. Anthesis of IR8 subjected to different temperatures on the second day after panicle emergence.

temperature pattern is very different from other high-altitude areas. For example, the temperature during panicle emergence at La Trinidad is lower than at Hokkaido, which is the northernmost area under rice cultivation in Japan. High temperatures from panicle initiation to flowering are possible, however, even at high altitudes, as in Katmandu (Nepal).

With the introduction of varieties like IR8, and with the use of these varieties as parents of new varieties, a knowledge of their temperature responses is important.

Field experiments were set up this year at La Trinidad and several laboratory and greenhouse experiments were undertaken at the Institute. The results of some laboratory experiments are presented here.

Blooming

Blooming or the opening of the spikelets depends primarily on the prevailing atmospheric temperature, the light intensity, and other climatic conditions. If the temperature is high, the spikelets start to bloom early in the day. Blooming slows down when the sky is cloudy and when the temperature drops.

The reported optimum maximum daily tem-

perature for blooming under natural conditions is between 27.5 and 32.5 C; the reported minimum is 22.2 C.

Growth chambers were used to test the effect of temperatures on the anthesis of IR8. Two-day-old panicles were sampled early in the morning and placed individually in test tubes containing water to prevent them from drying. To determine anthesis, the panicles were tapped by hand for the presence of pollen grains. Ten panicles were used per treatment and the treatments were replicated.

The minimum temperature at which anthesis occurred in IR8 was 22 C (Fig. 20). The optimum temperature was 33 C. At all the temperatures used, maximum anther dehiscence occurred at 2 PM, except at 33 C, when maximum dehiscence took place earlier and was sustained for a longer time. Higher temperature treatments were not possible with the growth chambers available at IIRRI.

At La Trinidad, the maximum and minimum temperatures during the regular flowering season are much below the optimum temperatures. No observations were made there on the blooming of IR8. However, laboratory tests indicate that blooming would be hindered or completely inhibited by the low temperatures common at La Trinidad. The high incidence of sterility in IR8 at La Trinidad (82% as opposed to 8% at Los Baños during the dry season) indicates that the temperatures are too low for anthesis.

Figure 21 shows the two temperature patterns at La Trinidad during the flowering period. The pattern on July 25 is the normal one; however, at Los Baños it has a higher temperature range. This pattern shows that by noon the temperature is high enough for blooming to occur. The pattern from July 26 to July 28 is of a type in which the temperature is low and more or less constant during the day and night. In this temperature pattern, IR8 may not bloom at all. Such temperature patterns may last for 5 or more days.

One aspect of blooming that needs further study is the temperature pattern in which the base temperature is below the minimum required for anthesis (as on July 26 through July 28) but it increases above the minimum for only

Fig. 21. Temperature and relative humidity patterns at La Trinidad, Benguet, Philippines.

a short period of the day. How many hours of high temperature is needed to induce a spikelet to open?

To answer this question, IR8 panicles were sampled as in the previous experiment and placed in growth chambers with a temperature of 21 C. This temperature prevents the anthesis of cut panicles. Several sets of panicles were placed for varying periods of time in a chamber at 32 C and then returned to the chamber at 21 C. A similar experiment was conducted using 27 C and longer periods of time.

Figure 22 shows that anthesis at 32 C occurred only after 20 minutes of exposure. Maximum anthesis in all treatments occurred 2 hours after treatment. The longer the panicles were subjected to 32 C, the greater the number of panicles with anthesis. Three hours after treatment, anthesis declined, while 4 hours after treatment it was almost nil. To obtain at least 50 percent anthesis, the panicles must be exposed to 32 C for 40 minutes.

At lower temperatures, such as 27 C, the minimum period of exposure required to obtain 50 percent anthesis is 60 minutes (Fig. 23). As in the 32 C treatments, maximum anthesis

occurred 2 hours after treatment and hardly any occurred 4 hours after treatment.

At La Trinidad, temperatures of 27 C and above sometimes occur for short durations during the regular flowering season. Generally, however, the temperatures are far too low for optimum anthesis. In fact, the temperatures are often not higher than the minimum requirement level. This problem is compounded by the high relative humidity at La Trinidad which may also inhibit anthesis.

Simazine and the protein content of the rice grain

The protein content of the milled rice grain is low, ranging from 5 to 14 percent. Various projects are underway in several institutions to increase, as well as improve, protein content.

Increases in the protein content of several crops as a result of applying low rates of simazine (2-chloro-4,6-bis ethylamino-s-triazine) have been reported. Simazine is generally used as a herbicide at rates of 1 to 4 kg/ha active ingredient.

An experiment was conducted to determine the effect of simazine on the protein content of the rice grain when applied to flooded soil at flowering time.

Seeds of Earlirose, a California rice variety, were grown in pots containing 4 kg soil and a sufficient amount of phosphorus and potassium. Three nitrogen levels were used: 0, 2, and 4 g ammonium sulfate per pot. When the panicles emerged, active simazine was applied at rates of 0, 1.25, 2.50, and 5.00 mg/pot.

Figure 24 shows that simazine at all four rates increased the protein content of the brown rice. Generally the increase in protein content was higher at lower soil nitrogen levels.

Simazine increased the amino acid contents of the brown rice without favoring or inhibiting any particular amino acid except lysine (Table 26). The decrease in lysine content with an increase in protein content had been reported

Fig. 22. Effect of short temperature treatments (32 C) on anthesis of IR8 panicles.

Fig. 23. Effect of short temperature treatments (27 C) on the anthesis of IR8 panicles.

previously under a different situation.

Although simazine increased the nitrogen content of the rice grains, it also increased the sterility of the plants, thus lowering grain yields (Table 27).

The increase in protein content has been attributed to the action of simazine in the reduction of nitrate to ammonia, or perhaps earlier, in the uptake of nitrate. The action of simazine in rice plants seems different, however, since the rice plant under flooded conditions usually absorbs nitrogen in the form of ammonium rather than nitrate ions. Also, preliminary data indicate that simazine ap-

Table 26. Amino acid content of brown rice treated with simazine at 5 mg/pot.

Amino Acid	Control (%)	Treated (%)
Lysine	4.2	3.5
Histidine	2.4	2.6
Ammonia	2.6	2.8
Arginine	9.0	9.4
Aspartic acid	9.8	10.2
Threonine	3.8	3.5
Serine	5.0	5.1
Glutamic acid	17.6	19.7
Proline	3.8	4.1
Half cystine	1.7	1.2
Glycine	5.2	4.7
Alanine	6.2	5.8
Valine	6.5	6.1
Methionine	2.2	1.9
Isoleucine	4.2	4.2
Leucine	7.8	8.3
Tyrosine	4.6	5.0
Phenylalanine	5.5	6.2
Protein	7.4	18.2

plication does not increase the total nitrogen uptake at all.

In an experiment using a culture solution, simazine was applied at the rate of 1.0 mg/pot 40 days after sowing. The application of simazine to young rice plants increased the nitrogen content of the blades, sheaths plus culms, and roots (Table 28). The increase of nitrogen in the leaves and straw became apparent as early as the second day after application, while the increase in the roots became apparent only on the eighth day after treatment.

The increase in nitrogen content, however, did not result from an increase in nitrogen uptake. In fact, the control plants had more nitrogen than the treated ones. Nitrogen uptake was not affected by simazine application.

In additional treatments, the nitrogen source of the culture solution was varied at the start of the treatment. If simazine increased the activity of the nitrate reductase, the plants grown

Table 27. Percentage of unfilled spikelets of variety Earlirose given simazine at flowering.

Nitrogen ^a applied (g/pot)	Unfilled spikelets (%)			
	Simazine (mg/pot)			
	0	1.25	2.50	5.00
0	37	57	89	100
2	21	40	52	92
4	26	33	47	68

^a (NH₄)₂SO₄.

in nitrate-nitrogen solution should have had a higher percentage of nitrogen and a higher total nitrogen uptake (Table 29).

Simazine, at herbicidal levels, reportedly inhibits photosynthesis, causing a decrease in the weight of the dry matter produced. At low simazine levels, we found that the apparent increase in the percentage of nitrogen of the treated plants was also the result of a decrease in the amount of dry matter produced (Fig. 25). The total sugar and starch contents of the plants were drastically reduced by simazine treatment. The decrease in total carbohydrates in the culm

Fig. 24. Protein content of brown rice from different levels of nitrogen and simazine treatments. LSD (.01) = 0.946.

Table 28. Percentages and amounts of nitrogen in control (C) and treated (T) plants and total accumulated carbohydrate (CHO) in the plants.

Days after treatment	Nitrogen content (%)						Total N in plants		Total CHO ^a accumulated	
	Blades		Sheaths & culms		Roots		(g/pot)		(g/pot)	
	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T
0	3.06	3.06	1.27	1.27	1.22	1.22	0.37	0.37	0.62	0.62
1	—	3.70	—	1.80	—	1.30	—	0.47	—	1.00
2	3.25	3.33	1.39	1.75	1.67	1.58	0.53	0.48	0.82	0.75
4	3.01	3.58	1.25	1.56	1.21	1.04	0.54	0.52	1.30	0.44
8	2.99	3.53	1.06	1.31	1.18	1.26	0.56	0.57	1.96	0.65
10	2.59	3.30	0.91	1.27	0.89	1.15	0.63	0.64	4.28	1.12
13	2.36	2.71	1.06	1.23	0.92	1.13	0.73	0.68	5.40	3.06
14	2.57	3.21	0.95	1.22	1.02	1.23	0.80	0.74	5.87	2.43

^a Accumulated carbohydrate is total sugar and starch.

and leaf sheath reduced the dry matter weight of these plant parts without correspondingly reducing their protein or nitrogen content. That accounted for the higher percentage of nitrogen in the plant.

Field experiments were also conducted to test the possibility of increasing the protein content of the grain and the protein yield of the crop. Simazine was applied to the irrigation water at flowering.

Table 30 shows the decrease in protein yield as a result of simazine application. This decrease resulted from the high sterility of the plants,

which in turn lowered grain yield. Although the percentage of nitrogen was high, the resulting protein yield per unit area decreased. IR532-1-218 gave the highest protein yield at 120 kg/ha nitrogen without simazine. It also had the highest protein production per unit area per day.

The application of simazine to increase the percentage of protein of the rice grains resulted in decreased growth or reduction in the total grain and protein yields.

Submergence and survival of rice

In many monsoon areas, the rice plant is subjected to inundation lasting for a day to a week.

Fig. 25. Changes in the dry matter production of simazine-treated and untreated plants.

Table 29. Percentages and amounts of nitrogen in different parts of plants grown with different nitrogen sources and treated with simazine. Data taken 4 days after treatment?

Nitrogen source	Dry weight (g/pot)	Nitrogen (%)	Total nitrogen (g/pot)
Leaf blades			
NH ₄ NO ₃ (control)	10.0	3.0	0.30
NH ₄ NO ₃	9.3	3.6	0.34
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	9.2	3.7	0.34
NaNO ₃	9.7	3.4	0.33
No nitrogen	8.1	2.8	0.23
Culms & leaf sheaths			
NH ₄ NO ₃ (control)	13.1	1.3	0.17
NH ₄ NO ₃	9.2	1.6	0.15
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	9.7	1.6	0.16
NaNO ₃	9.4	1.5	0.14
No nitrogen	10.3	1.1	0.11
Roots			
NH ₄ NO ₃ (control)	6.3	1.2	0.08
NH ₄ NO ₃	5.3	1.0	0.05
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	5.2	1.2	0.06
NaNO ₃	5.1	1.2	0.06
No nitrogen	5.1	0.6	0.03

^a The nitrate-nitrogen content of the plant was also determined but the values were low and the differences insignificant.

Table 30. Percentages of nitrogen in the grain, and protein yields of varieties planted under field conditions and given simazine at flowering.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Simazine level (kg/ha)	Nitrogen in grain (%)				Protein yield (kg/ha)			
		Chianung 242	T(N)1	IR532-1-218	IR8	Chianung 242	T(N)1	IR532-1-218	IR8
0	0	1.22	1.29	1.11	1.21	214	274	298	238
	0.5	1.25	1.50	1.24	1.33	208	220	256	244
	1.0	1.27	1.56	1.32	1.47	137	143	202	232
30	0	1.12	1.22	1.11	1.18	214	303	345	298
	0.5	1.20	1.34	1.24	1.30	196	238	303	232
	1.0	1.25	1.66	1.34	1.48	179	232	262	238
60	0	1.10	1.24	1.14	1.20	303	333	405	345
	0.5	1.24	1.52	1.18	1.31	262	315	333	345
	1.0	1.32	1.47	1.30	1.34	226	196	286	292
90	0	1.22	1.32	1.18	1.18	363	411	434	412
	0.5	1.28	1.52	1.32	1.24	327	309	422	363
	1.0	1.28	1.54	1.40	1.37	250	280	357	363
120	0	1.20	1.29	1.30	1.22	417	440	583	530
	0.5	1.30	1.60	1.33	1.31	333	399	434	446
	1.0	1.35	1.84	1.54	1.38	315	381	399	446

Sometimes it is submerged at different stages of growth.

The effects of inundation on the growth of the rice plant, especially the new short, stiff-strawed varieties, are not well understood. A series of experiments was started to determine the tolerance of rice plants to total submergence as influenced by water temperature, light intensity, nitrogen fertilization, stage of growth, length of submergence, and variety.

To study the effect of submergence at different growth stages, early-short and early-tall lines of Peta were grown in pots containing 6 kg soil and added fertilizer. One set of plants was submerged 20 days after sowing—the seedling establishment period. Another set was treated at 40 days after sowing—the active tillering period. A third set was treated at 60 days after sowing—the panicle initiation period. The plants were completely submerged for 6 days, a period preliminary experiments have shown to be near critical for survival.

Figures 26 and 27 show the survival of tall and short Peta lines. Tall Peta is more susceptible to submergence than short Peta. Submergence at panicle initiation did not result in the death of the plants as a whole, while submergence at active tillering not only killed some of the plants but also caused a large decrease in the number of tillers of the plants that survived.

Submergence reduced the grain yield of short Peta (Table 31). When short Peta was

Fig. 26. Percentage survival of tall Peta submerged for 6 days at different stages of growth.

Fig. 27. Percentage survival of short Peta submerged for 6 days at different stages of growth.

Table 31. Yield components of early-tall and early-short Peta submerged for 6 days at different stages of growth. Average of 10 plants.

Submerged at	Panicles (no./hill)	Weight (g/panicle)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (% of control)
Short Peta					
20 days	4.4	0.52	126.0	22.74	62.3
40 days	10.4	0.91	71.4	22.31	91.6
60 days	11.6	0.49	32.4	18.86	43.6
Unsubmerged (control)	12.5	1.25	106.2	20.28	100.0
Tall Peta					
20 days	D ^a	D	D	D	D
40 days	2.8	0.73	101.8	21.78	44.7
60 days	8.9	0.95	75.5	17.84	65.5
Unsubmerged (control)	11.1	1.41	106.6	19.73	100.0

^a All plants died.

submerged at the seedling stage, most tillers died and the low panicle number decreased grain yield. Submergence at panicle initiation caused the greatest yield reduction mainly because the number of spikelets per panicle was low and the spikelets degenerated. Submergence at active tillering affected only the number of spikelets.

No yield was obtained from tall Peta submerged at the seedling stage since all the plants

died. Yield reduction in plants submerged at active tillering resulted mainly from the low panicle number per plant, while yield decrease in plants submerged at panicle initiation resulted from the low spikelet number per panicle.

In short, submergence at an early stage affected the tiller number while at later stages it affected the spikelet number. These effects are clearly shown in the grain yields.

Agricultural Economics

The major emphasis in research continued to be related to economic problems associated with the adoption of new varieties and the use of inputs at the farm level. However, increased attention was given to the analysis of the impact of the new high-yielding varieties on the production and marketing of rice in Asia.

This report deals with trends in the production and export of rice in Asia; quality, demand, and price relationships; productivity and efficiency in the use of farm inputs; the diffusion of high-yielding varieties.

Production and export of rice in Asia

The spread of the new high-yielding varieties of rice throughout Asia was discussed in the 1968 Annual Report. Table 1 presents the most recent figures showing the area planted to the new varieties. The first part of this section examines the apparent causes of the more rapid spread of the new varieties of wheat as compared with those of rice. This discussion is followed by an analysis of the possible impact of increased rice production on the export market.

Environment and the spread of new high-yielding varieties.

In both absolute and relative terms, the new wheat varieties have been spreading more rapidly than rice. The dwarf wheat varieties have been concentrated in India, Pakistan, and Turkey. From their introduction in 1965/66, they have spread to more than 7 million hectares, or over 20 percent, of the Asian wheat area. This can be compared with the 4.7 million hectares, or 6 percent, of the Asian rice area planted to new varieties.

Many reasons are given for this difference. For example, some observers say that the new rice varieties require a higher level of management skill from farmers. Available data suggest, however, that the difference results mainly from the environmental conditions under which the two crops are grown and not from the cultivation

problems. Environment refers not only to climate and soil, but also to irrigation facilities, factors over which farmers have very little control. Although the influence of physical environment cannot easily be separated from social and cultural conditions, we contend that the major obstacle to the spread of the new rice varieties has not been poor farm management, lack of farmer knowledge, nor inadequate extension. Under favorable environmental conditions, the potential of the new rice varieties equals or exceeds that of wheat, but most farmers grow rice under typical monsoon Asian conditions. Thus they face a more variable yield response to inputs and a higher risk.

Environment: wheat vs. rice. The new Mexican wheat varieties are grown mainly in the relatively homogenous area of northern India and West Pakistan. This area has a dry climate, fertile soils, and adequate underground water supplies. Before the new varieties were introduced, regions such as the Punjab were already showing marked growth in agricultural production. The new varieties are concentrated on irrigated lands, which make up approximately two-thirds of the wheat area. In these areas, farmers have often doubled their yields.

West Pakistan is the most favorable rice-growing area in Asia. Here, rice, like wheat, is grown under a dry climate with adequate underground water supplies close to the surface. The 1.5 million hectares of rice in West Pakistan (only one-eighth of the area of Pakistan), however, represents a tiny fraction of the rice area of Asia.

In Asia, rice is usually grown in regions with high seasonal rainfall where good water control is absent and water supply is uncertain. Figure 1 shows our estimate of the percentage of the rice crop area under a specified water resource situation. Only 20 percent of the rice area is irrigated. Much of the irrigation is done with diversion dam systems, so even the irrigated area is not free from floods and droughts.

The new varieties are not suited to the deep-water conditions in the large flood plains of South Vietnam, central Thailand, East Pakistan, and lower Burma. In rainfed and upland areas, the new varieties perform at least as well as

Table 1. Estimated area of new rice varieties in South and Southeast Asia^a

Country	Rice crop area 1968/69	Planted to new varieties ^c		
		1966/67	1967/68	1968/69
(1000 ha)				
Burma	4,978	b	3	190
Ceylon	663	—	b	7
India	36,981	867	1,785	2,632
Indonesia	8,482	—	—	168
Laos	628	b	1	2
Malaysia (West)	478	42	63	91
Nepal	1,119	—	—	42
Pakistan (East)	8,588	b	67	121
Pakistan (West)	1,515	4	4	308
Philippines	3,200	83	447	1,060
Vietnam (South)	2,238	—	b	44
Total	68,870	996	2,370	4,654

^a Principal source: D. G. Dalrymple, "Imports and Plantings of High Yielding Varieties of Wheat and Rice in the Less Developed Nations," Foreign Agricultural Service, USDA, Nov. 1969.

^b Less than 1,000 ha.

^c Principally IRR1 varieties, plus ADT-27 and Taichung (Native)1 in India, Mahsuri in Malaysia, and C4-63 in the Philippines and Indonesia.

Fig. 1. Estimate of percent rice crop area and production by specified land type in South and Southeast Asia.

local varieties. The potential differences in yield are far less, however. In much of this area, uncertain rainfall conditions cause farmers to limit the use of fertilizer and other cash inputs.

The high humidity during the main growing season is another environmental problem for rice. Humidity increases the severity of attacks by insects and diseases. The susceptibility of IR8 to insects and diseases has been largely responsible for the lack of success in attempts to introduce it into East Pakistan, Malaysia, and Indonesia. The search continues in these countries for a resistant variety with the yield potential of IR8. By contrast, in 1970 a major portion of the rice area in the dry climate of West Pakistan will be planted to the IRRI selection, IR6-156-2-1 (known in Pakistan as Mehran 69), which has not been named a variety by IRRI because of its high disease susceptibility in most of the tropics.

Physical production functions. The yield response of new and local varieties of rice and wheat to nitrogen is shown in Figures 2, 3, and 4. These functions are based upon experimental results obtained under irrigated conditions.

Figures 2 and 3 compare wheat and rice in India. Although the potential yield is greatest for dry-season IR8 rice, the slopes of the functions for dry-season rice and for the Mexican wheats are comparable over a wide range (from 0 to 120 kg/ha N). The rate of yield

increase resulting from nitrogen fertilization of wet-season IR8 is decidedly less pronounced. Both wheat and dry-season rice are grown under high sunlight or solar energy. The poorer response of wet-season rice can be attributed to the heavier cloud cover during the growing season which sharply reduces available solar energy.

Figure 4 compares the Indian rice response functions with those for the Philippines to show the general similarity in yield response and production potential in these two widely different geographic areas. (The response functions for IR8 in India shown in Fig. 4 are the same as those in Fig. 3.)

The Philippine response functions were discussed in detail in the 1968 Annual Report. The individual annual functions were estimated separately. The analysis showed a considerably higher year-to-year variability in the functions for the wet season than in those for the dry season. The uncertainty of response for a major portion of the Asian rice-growing area, as reflected in the wet-season functions, is clearly an important reason for the comparatively slow rate of adoption of new varieties and of the fertilizers to grow them. By contrast, one would expect to find rapid adoption of inputs and resulting production increases under response conditions like those in the dry season at the Maligaya experiment station in the Philippines.

Fig. 2. Variability in yield response of wheat to nitrogen by variety. India, 1967. Based on experiments of All India Coordinated Wheat Improvement Project.

Fig. 3. Variability in yield response of rice to nitrogen by variety and season. India, 1968. Based on experiments of All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project.

Fig. 4. Variability in yield response of IR8 variety to nitrogen by location and season. India, 1968 (19 locations) and Maligaya Rice Experiment Station in Central Luzon, Philippines (average of 1966, 1967, and 1968).

This appears to be the situation for the high-yielding wheat varieties in northern India and for the high-yielding wheat and rice varieties in West Pakistan.

Along with the production functions, the

relationship between the prices of grain and of fertilizer is important in establishing the optimum economic levels of nitrogen input and of grain yield. In both India and Pakistan, the price of wheat is supported well above the world market. The ratios of paddy prices to fertilizer prices have been lower than those for wheat. Of course, these ratios vary from location to location throughout Asia. Grain price supports have encouraged production, and the more rapid gains in wheat production can be attributed in part to a more favorable price relationship.

Production achievements. The reasons for production changes are often difficult to determine. In the short run, the increase in production caused by the new varieties and by additional inputs rarely can be separated from the increase caused by favorable weather. Particularly in India, which experienced severe drought when the monsoons failed in the 1965/66 and 1966/67 crop years, much of the recent increase in production can be attributed to better weather.

Table 2 shows the changes in production in the areas with the largest plantings of new varieties. The first crop year in which a substantial area was planted to new high-yielding varieties was 1968/69. Early reports suggest that the 1969/70 production levels for both wheat and rice will equal or exceed those of 1968/69.

As noted previously, the percentage of the area planted to new wheat varieties in Asia is considerably greater than that planted to new rice varieties. The production gains in wheat have been remarkable, and are matched only by the performance of rice in West Pakistan.

Implications. The acceptance of the hypothesis concerning environmental differences has important implications for policy-makers in Asian countries. Sustained gains in rice production can be achieved principally by reducing the risk and uncertainty which farmers face. To do so, irrigation and drainage facilities must be improved and expanded. At the same time, more attention should be given to raising the production potential of rainfed and upland rice. Also, adequate research funds must be invested in the development of insect- and disease-

Table 2. Changes in production of wheat and rice for selected Asian countries, 1960/61 to 1968/69*

Country	Year					Increase 1960-64 to 1968 (%)
	1960-64	1965	1966 (1000 metric tons)	1967	1968	
Wheat						
India	10,809	12,290	10,424	11,393	16,540	53
W. Pakistan	4,065	4,625	3,916	4,334	6,477	58
Asia	52,247	56,388	51,904	58,370	64,239	23
World	231,758	247,500	285,500	277,190	308,012	33
Rough rice (paddy)						
India	53,105	46,500	45,707	59,300	59,701	12
E. Pakistan	14,754	15,718	14,308	16,698	16,958	15
W. Pakistan	1,783	2,026	2,100	2,306	3,126	75
Philippines	3,883	4,033	4,165	4,560	4,583	18
Asia	141,787	138,060	138,355	159,053	162,209	14
World	161,000	159,000	161,000	183,000	186,620	16

* Source: U.S. Department of Agriculture and Government of Pakistan.

resistant varieties. For the long run, resistant varieties offer a more fruitful approach than emphasis on insecticides which, for the individual farmer, are expensive and have uncertain benefits. Some form of crop insurance scheme, coupled with the above programs, would be desirable, but would be difficult to administer in most Asian countries.

Impact of new rice varieties on world trade

The amount of rice traded internationally since 1956 has varied from 6 to 7.5 million metric tons. That is less than 5 percent of the world's total production. No pronounced trend has occurred. During the same period, however, world wheat trade doubled, reaching a peak of 51 million metric tons, or approximately 20 percent of world production. The growth in wheat trade up to the mid-1960's resulted primarily from the increasing imports of the developing countries and the increasing exports of the leading exporters (Argentina, Australia, Canada, and U.S.A.). The expanding wheat production in the developing countries, due to the introduction of the dwarf Mexican varieties, has already reversed this trend, resulting in a decline in the world wheat trade in the last 2 to 3 years.

Most observers believe that the spread of the new high-yielding rice varieties will also lead to a decline in the world rice trade. World trade in 1968 was 12 percent below the 1967 level of 7.1 million metric tons. Reports available for the first half of 1969 indicate a further decline. Export prices which declined from their

peak levels in 1968 have remained fairly steady throughout 1969 (Fig. 5).

The impact of the new varieties on rice trade within South and Southeast Asia was analyzed on the basis of a projection of national trends in annual production and consumption of rice to 1972, with 1966-68 as the base period. Estimates of rice imports and exports in 1972 were computed for South and Southeast Asia—the area bordered by the Philippines and Indonesia on the east and Pakistan on the west. Cambodia, Laos, and South Vietnam were excluded, but the rice-consuming centers of Singapore and Hong Kong were included.

Fig. 5. Prices of four export grades of Thai rice, f.o.b. Bangkok.

Rice imports and exports in this region exceeded 3 million metric tons, or approximately one-half of the world total, in 1960-62 and 1963-65 (Table 3). However, in 1966-68, both imports and exports fell sharply, with the decline in Burmese and Thai exports exceeding the decline in Indonesian and Philippine imports. Internal trade among countries within the region which remained rather steady at 2 to 2.5 million metric tons for 1956-65 also declined—to below 2 million metric tons—in 1966-68. The increased production due to new varieties could cause a further decline in trade by 1972.

The projected trends in imports and exports were determined as follows.

The trends in consumption are based upon the formula:

$$C = P + YI \quad (1)$$

where:

- C = annual per capita consumption
- P = annual growth in population
- Y = annual growth in per capita income
- I = income elasticity of demand

The major cause of increased consumption is population growth, which is most rapid in the Philippines and Thailand. The income elasticity of demand for rice based upon estimates available from studies in India, Malaysia, Pakistan, and the Philippines is relatively low, varying from 0.1 to 0.4, and is assumed to be -0.1 in Hong Kong and Singapore.

Domestic disappearance (domestic production adjusted for imports or exports) in the 3-

year period, 1966-68, was used as the base consumption requirement. The demand for rice in 1972 was determined by compounding the growth in rice consumption over a 5-year period using the estimated annual growth rate

Annual growth in rice output was determined for 1960-63 to 1967-68 for each country. These figures were used to project the 1966-68 production to 1972 (low estimate). They were then revised upward to provide a basis for projecting the impact of the high-yielding varieties on production (high estimate). This produced two sets of production figures, one based on the assumption of no high-yielding varieties and one making allowance for the impact of high-yielding varieties (Table 3).

Estimating production growth rates resulting from the introduction of high-yielding varieties is hazardous. No two research workers would arrive at the same set of values. Based upon the projected production targets of most governments, however, the growth rate figures used here are conservative. In fact, many importing countries are predicting self-sufficiency by 1972.

Assuming that the annual growth in output continued at the rate that prevailed throughout most of the 1960's, by 1972 the potential import demand in the region would exceed potential export supplies by 2.5 million metric tons (3.9 million minus 1.4 million), indicating a substantial regional deficit. Making allowance for higher production growth rate due to new varieties and other complementary factors re-

Table 3. Import and export trends for 10 rice-producing and -consuming countries in South and Southeast Asia with projections to 1972 (in 1,000 metric tons).

Country	1960-62 ^a		1963-65 ^a		1966-68 ^a		1972-low production ^b		1972-high production ^c	
	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export
Burma	—	1,659	—	1,455	—	643	—	96	—	575
Ceylon	462	—	440	—	524	—	537	—	356	—
India	387	—	534	—	562	—	1,310	—	427	—
Indonesia	1,038	—	726	—	516	—	919	—	540	—
W. Malaysia	—	—	—	—	227	—	246	—	170	—
Pakistan	251	105	131	132	184	142	—	92	—	788
Philippines	623	1	372	—	133	30	320	—	—	13
Thailand	—	1,336	—	1,696	—	1,330	—	1,196	—	1,543
Hong Kong	347	41	356	35	380	17	407	—	386	—
Singapore	—	—	—	—	268	87	205	—	197	—
W. Malaysia/Singapore	563	80	660	128	—	—	—	—	—	—
Total	3,671	3,222	3,219	3,446	2,794	2,249	3,944	1,384	2,076	2,919

^a Source: Commonwealth Economic Committee Reports. Annual average of 3 years.

^b Based on rice production trends 1960-64 to 1967-68.

^c Based on allowance for increased output due to high-yielding varieties.

verses the situation, however: potential exports for the region exceed imports by 0.8 million metric tons (2.9 million minus 2.1 million).

These results reflect the extreme sensitivity of the export market to potential shifts in production trend. In several countries, the future trend in rice production is highly uncertain because of political and economic rather than agronomic factors. Burmese rice exports still give no signs of recovery. In Indonesia, the Bimus Gotong Royong, which provided for the mass distribution of inputs (amounting to US\$50/ha) on more than a million hectares of rice land, has shown little success. Expansion of internal trade within Pakistan and development of the market facilities needed for export of rice from West Pakistan appear to be stymied by political uncertainties. Fiscal and monetary problems within the Philippine economy could significantly reduce rice production.

In short, world rice production and trade face many uncertainties in the near future. Nevertheless, the trends and projections in Table 3 indicate a declining international rice trade among Asian countries that is likely to extend into the early 1970's.

Quality, demand, and price relationships

With higher rice production now being achieved in many regions of Asia, increasing attention is being given to problems of marketing and consumption. The foremost marketing problem is rice quality. A study was begun this year to investigate the relation of rice quality and prices to domestic and export markets. The latter part of this section presents results showing the changes in the quantity of rice that will be consumed as income levels change in the various regions of the Philippines.

Rice quality and price

Factors, such as appearance, taste, and cooking quality, determine the price consumers will pay for a given quantity of rice. Not only the variety of rice, but also the way in which the rice is handled from the farm through the entire marketing and milling channel, determines the

final quality of the rice purchased by consumers.

Quality preferences tend to differ from country to country. However, the quality standards for international trade are almost uniform and are based mostly upon appearance. For example, the Thai and U.S. grading standards and the recently adopted Philippine standards classify rice into basic categories by such intrinsic characters as size and shape (e.g. long grain, medium grain, short grain, glutinous) and by degree of processing (e.g. parboiled, undermilled, fully milled).

Within these basic categories, rice is graded by specifying allowable tolerances for acquired characteristics, such as percentage of brokens, chalkiness, percentage of yellow damaged or red rice, and percentage of foreign matter.

Samples of Philippine wholesale rice were collected and classified to determine the relationship between specific quality characteristics (appearance, percentage of brokens, etc.) and the domestic wholesale price at the mill; to compare the domestic wholesale with export quality by grading the domestic samples against the Philippine export standard; and to compare, through regression analysis, the factors which influence domestic and export quality and price.

Quality characteristics and domestic price. From February through April 1969, milled rice samples were obtained from miller-wholesalers in 10 regions throughout the Philippines.

The prevailing wholesale price reported at the mill was obtained for each sample. Of the 37 samples, 15 were IR8, with an average wholesale price of 55.2 centavos per kilogram; the remaining samples were local varieties with an average wholesale price of 61.2 centavos per kilogram (Table 4).

The samples were analyzed to determine the content of acquired quality characteristics (Table 4). Compared with the ordinary grades, the fancy and special grades, on the average, differed very slightly in acquired quality characteristics. For example, the content of brokens, a very important quality factor in international standards, is between 31 and 32 percent on the average for the domestic samples and does not differ significantly in fancy and special grades as compared with ordinary grades.

Grading domestic samples. All samples were

Table 4. Average wholesale price and percentages of broken grains, red rice, yellows, and damaged grains of IR8 and local varieties.

Grain characteristics	IR8	Local	All varieties
Average broken grains (%)	34.1	29.9	31.6
Fancy and special	—	31.2	31.2
Ordinary	34.1	27.2	31.9
Average brewer (%)	1.87	1.51	1.63
Fancy and special	—	1.42	1.42
Ordinary	1.87	1.69	1.82
Average chalky kernels (%)	1.76	1.18	1.41
Fancy and special	—	1.24	1.24
Ordinary	1.76	1.05	1.53
Average red rice, yellows, and damaged grains (%)	3.14	2.48	2.75
Fancy and special	—	2.19	2.19
Ordinary	3.14	3.09	3.13
Philippine grade (no. of samples)			
Grade 4	3	4	7
Grade 5	8	11	19
Sub-standard	4	7	11
Average price (P/kg)	0.552	0.612	0.588
Fancy and special	—	0.622	0.622
Ordinary	0.552	0.590	0.564

graded after their acquired characteristics had been analyzed. The Philippine standard grades range from Grade 1 (the best) to Grade 5. Thailand *White Rice 5%* is almost comparable to *Philippine Grade 1* and to *United States Grade 2*. The maximum broken grain tolerance for *Philippine Grade 1* is 10 percent; for Thai *White Rice 5%*, 5 to 7 percent; and for *United States Grade 2*, 7 percent. About one-quarter of the rice exported by Thailand approximates or exceeds these quality levels.

Based on the Philippine standard the grades assigned to the domestic Philippine samples are summarized in Table 4. The highest grade given any sample was Grade 4, and 11 of the samples were considered sub-standard. The reason for these low grades appeared to be the generally high percentages of broken, brewers or "binlids," and yellow and damaged grains.

Regressions of price and quality factors. Among the 37 rice samples collected, variety was highly correlated with grade. All 16 IR8 samples fell into the grade category of ordinary rice. Two sets of regression equations were run. In the first set, samples were divided by variety. One equation was fitted to the observations for local varieties, and a second equation to the observations for IR8 (see equations 2a and 2b). In the second set, samples were divided by grade. One equation was fitted for fancy and special

grades, and a second equation for ordinary grade (see equations 3a and 3b below):

$$\hat{Y} = 73.03 - 0.177X_1 + 0.040X_2 - 0.0587X_3 - 1.581X_4 \quad (2a)$$

(0.098) (1.203) (0.496) (0.931)
R² = 0.26 (local)

$$\hat{Y} = 61.70 - 0.185X_1 + 0.052X_2 - 0.355X_3 + 0.653X_4 \quad (2b)$$

(0.095) (0.621) (0.244) (0.898)
R² = 0.43 (IR8)

$$\hat{Y} = 74.06 - 0.214X_1 + 0.747X_2 + 0.486X_3 - 1.638X_4 \quad (3a)$$

(0.141) (1.622) (0.648) (1.118)
R² = 0.30 (fancy and special)

$$\hat{Y} = 70.78 - 0.264X_1 - 0.348X_2 - 0.111X_3 - 2.329X_4 \quad (3b)$$

(0.090) (0.876) (0.341) (1.052)
R² = 0.50 (ordinary)

where:

- $\hat{Y}$ = The wholesale price or the selling price reported at the mill in centavos per kilogram adjusted for location by an index of transportation differential.
- X_1 = Percent broken where broken are milled rice grains whose sizes range from three-fourths to one-half of a whole grain.
- X_2 = Percent brewers or "binlids" which are milled rice grains whose size ranges from one-half to one-fourth of a head rice or whole grain.
- X_3 = Percent red rice, yellow, and damaged grain where red rice is rice with any degree of redness, and yellow or damaged kernels are grains damaged by fermentation or heat, by water, by insects, or by mechanical means.
- X_4 = Percent chalky grains or milled rice kernels with 25 percent or more white portion.

Before fitting the regression equations, the wholesale rice price was adjusted by a transportation index, using central Luzon as the basing point, and lowering the price per unit for samples collected in other regions by the transportation cost from central Luzon to the region in question. This procedure, while not an entirely satisfactory correction for differences in price due to location, improved the regression fit in all equations.

The two most important quality variables explaining differences in price are the percentage of broken (X₁) and the percentage of chalky grains (X₄). For IR8, of course, the percentage of chalky grains is not a significant factor since essentially all grains of this variety are chalky.

The relationship between price and percentage of broken is graphed in Figures 6 and 7. All independent variables other than percentage of

Fig. 6. Functional relationship between wholesale price and percent broken with variety as a dependent variable.

Fig. 7. Functional relationship between wholesale price and percent broken with milled rice appearance as a dependent variable.

brokens have been held constant at the arithmetic mean. The original unadjusted observations of wholesale price and percentage of brokens are plotted. All lines taper gradually to the right, with the price difference between 20-percent brokens and 40-percent brokens being a little over 5 centavos per kilogram, or 10 percent. There is no significant statistical difference between the slopes of the lines in each figure.

At 25-percent brokens the computed prices are 65 centavos for the local variety compared with 57 centavos for IR8; for the fancy and special grades the prices are 65 centavos compared with 60 centavos for the ordinary grade. The difference in price for variety is 12 percent; for grade, it is 8 percent.

Figure 8 shows the relationship between price and percentage of brokens for Thai export varieties and for the two Philippine domestic grades. The line representing Thai exports is based upon a simple correlation between percentage of brokens and the f.o.b. export price, as quoted by the Rice Committee Board of Trade from January through April, 1969 (the period that coincides with the collection of the domestic Philippine samples). This figure again emphasizes the contrast between the quality standards for export and for domestic rice.

Implications. Both the process of grading samples and the regression analysis conducted in this study indicate clearly that factors which are extremely important in determining export quality have little importance in determining domestic quality or grade. Consequently, a

discussion of modernization of rice milling and marketing must clearly distinguish domestic from export markets. Domestic markets generally will require less sophisticated milling equipment. On the other hand, equipment now satisfactory for domestic marketing cannot be used without major modifications to produce export quality rice.

Incomes and demand for rice in the Philippines

The initial results of a study of the income elasticity of demand for rice in the Philippines were reported in the 1968 Annual Report. This study has been conducted with the help of the Bureau of Census.

Table 5 shows the average income, rice expenditure, and household size for each of the

Fig. 8. Comparison of Thailand export price with Philippine domestic wholesale price.

Table 5. Average income per year, rice expenditure per week, and size of household, by region. Philippines, 1965^a

Region	Income (P)	Weekly rice expenditure (P)	Household size (persons)	Yearly per-capita income (P)	Weekly per-capita rice expenditure (P)
Manila	6,639	9.05	6.7	998	1.36
Ilocos and Mt. Province	2,029	9.79	5.4	374	1.80
Cagayan Valley and Batanes	1,686	6.77	6.4	262	1.05
Central Luzon	2,858	11.77	6.2	463	1.91
Southern Luzon and Islands	3,705	10.27	6.4	581	1.61
Bicol	2,269	9.20	6.3	363	1.47
Western Visayas	2,451	10.11	5.9	417	1.72
Eastern Visayas	2,700	8.74	5.9	461	1.49
Northern Mindanao	2,776	10.45	6.3	444	1.67
Southern Mindanao and Sulu	2,630	11.00	6.0	439	1.83

^a Source: Bureau of Census, Philippine Statistical Survey of Households, May 1966.

10 Bureau of Census regions. The rice expenditure is in pesos per household for the week in which the survey was conducted. The lowest expenditure is in the Cagayan Valley and the highest in central Luzon. The low expenditure in the Cagayan Valley appears associated with low purchasing power.

Income elasticity estimates for each of the 10 regions includes separate estimates for rice producers and non-rice producers (Table 6). The general form of the equation was:

$$C = f(I, S) \quad (4)$$

where:

C = Rice expenditure per capita or rice expenditure per household divided by the size of household. Rice expenditure per household is the value of the rice, including glutinous rice, used by members of the family including servants. The value includes purchases, own produce, and those obtained from other sources by the household. The value excludes the amount taken by boarders and guests.

I = Income per capita or income per household divided by the size of household. Income per household refers to the net income before taxes. This excludes the earnings of the servants and other boarders living in the sample household.

S = Size of household or number of persons living in the household regardless of age. The data, however, exclude the number of servants.

The equation was fitted in both the log and semi-log form. With the exception of the Cagayan Valley and Batanes, the semi-log

equations gave the better fit, with the R^2 values being somewhat higher than for the log form of the equation. R^2 values were generally low (40 or less), which is not unusual for this type of survey data. About half the coefficients for elasticity were significant at the 5- or 1-percent level.

The values in Table 6 reconfirm the earlier finding that income elasticity of demand for rice in the Philippines generally is very low. For example, an income elasticity estimate of 0.13 was found for rice consumers in Manila. This figure indicates that a 1-percent increase in per-capita income would be accompanied by approximately one-eighth of 1-percent increase in rice expenditure.

The highest income elasticities appear to be associated with rice producers in areas where resources for rice production are poor and incomes of rice farm are low. The Cagayan Valley shows the lowest average income among all 10 regions and the highest income elasticity of demand, approximately 0.45. In northern Mindanao, the income elasticity of demand for

Table 6. The estimated income elasticity of demand for rice in regions of the Philippines based upon rice expenditure.

Region	Form of equation	
	Log	Semi-log
Manila	0.132*	—
Ilocos and Mt. Province		
Rice producers	0.058	0.043
Non-rice producers	0.060	0.103
Cagayan Valley and Batanes		
Rice producers	0.467*	0.443*
Non-rice producers	-0.057	0.008
Central Luzon		
Rice producers	0.039	0.041
Non-rice producers	0.059*	0.067*
Southern Luzon and Islands		
Rice producers	0.040	0.044
Non-rice producers	0.044	0.055*
Bicol		
Rice producers	0.058	0.061
Non-rice producers	0.120*	0.140*
Western Visayas		
Rice producers	0.138*	0.144*
Non-rice producers	0.085*	0.069*
Eastern Visayas		
Rice producers	0.171*	0.118
Non-rice producers	0.168*	0.157*
Northern Mindanao		
Rice producers	0.271*	0.279*
Non-rice producers	0.038*	0.050
Southern Mindanao and Sulu		
Rice producers	NA	NA
Non-rice producers	0.108*	0.112*

* At least significant at the 5% level.
NA = matrix nearly singular. Estimates not available.

rice producers is about 0.27. More than a third of this area is in upland rice, and only one-eighth is irrigated. Income elasticities not significantly different from zero were estimated for non-rice producers in a number of regions and for rice producers throughout most of Luzon.

Productivity and efficiency in rice production

Two of the most important and least understood areas in the economics of rice production are water distribution and management and insecticide use. For the past 2 years, the Department has undertaken experiments in both areas.

Economics of water distribution

The initial experiments were designed to establish the relationship between the quantity of water applied and the rice yield. The hypothesis was that as the level of water applied diminishes, the level of yield will drop very sharply, reflecting the extreme sensitivity of puddled rice to drought conditions, and that the general nature of the response will take the shape of a sigmoid or logistic curve.

During the 1968 dry season, all experimental plots were kept flooded to a depth of 5 cm until panicle initiation (60 days after transplanting). Then water was applied at 5-day intervals at five levels ranging from 2 mm/day to 6 mm/day in 1-mm intervals plus a flooded

control. The soil moisture content never fell below 50 percent or approximate field capacity. At the lower water application levels, yields were reduced only slightly.

The 1969 dry-season experiment was re-designed with the assistance of Dr. Gilbert Levine, Visiting Professor, U.P. College of Agriculture. The experiment was moved to one of the highest points in the Institute farm, a location which is also somewhat isolated from other plots, to minimize the effect of underground water movement on soil moisture conditions.

Nine 12 x 12 m plots were laid out and each plot was enclosed by a strip of gauge 26 corrugated galvanized iron sheet 45 cm high buried 30 cm deep. The objective was not to minimize or eliminate seepage or lateral water loss, but to hold the seepage at a level that would approximate field conditions.

Seven treatments (2-mm to 8-mm average daily application applied at 5-day intervals) plus two flooded controls were used. The treatments were started shortly after transplanting (as compared with panicle initiation in 1968). The soil moisture content was estimated at regular intervals. Readings of soil moisture tension were also taken on the four plots receiving the lowest levels of water application. The tensiometer used registered soil moisture tension at 10-cm intervals from 10 to 50 cm in depth. These readings indicated no apparent upward movement of soil moisture from underground water flow.

Table 7 shows the data on water application

Table 7. Effect of different water application treatments on rice yield. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Water treatment ^a (mm/day)	Soil moisture content ^b (%)	Water for land preparation ^c (mm)	Irrigation period ^d (days)	Crop maturity ^e (days)	Water for irrigation ^f (mm)	Total water applied (mm)	Grain yield (kg/ha)		
							Total	Per day	Per mm water
8	66	118	100	116	800	918	8,832	76	9.62
7	58	129	105	119	735	864	8,735	73	10.11
6	61	132	110	121	668	800	7,301	60	9.13
5	63	130	115	126	590	720	4,650	37	6.46
4	61	144	135	145	555	700	89	1	0.13
3	58	142	135	145	418	560	0	0	0
2	51	133	135	—	285	418	0	0	0

^a Irrigation treatments were made every 5 days.

^b Immediately before the water treatment (oven-dried basis).

^c Prior to the water treatment.

^d For experimental plots below soil-saturated conditions from flowering to maturity, irrigation was continued to about a week before expected harvest. For flooded to saturated plots, irrigation was ended about 2 weeks before expected harvest.

^e Measured from transplanting.

^f Total amount of water used after land preparation.

and crop yield. The treatments were begun 3 days after transplanting and carried out every 5 days for 100 to 135 days. Under the low levels of water input, the growing season and the irrigation period were extended by more than a month.

Both yield per hectare and yield per hectare per day were greatest at 8 mm of water per day. Maximum yield per millimeter of water was achieved at 7 mm/day, however. Thus where water payment or cost is based on the volume delivered, care should be taken both to minimize costs by not using too much water and to avoid reducing yields by applying too little water.

Figure 9 shows the response of rice yield to water application intensity. A curve was fitted to the plotted observations using an interpolation procedure and the sigmoid or logistic form of the function. The general shape of the curve seems to fit the original hypothesis (1968 Annual Report).

Below the water application level of 6 mm/day, yields dropped sharply and were almost zero at 4 mm/day. At 8 mm/day, the plot was maintained at a flooded to saturated level. At 7 mm/day, intermittent flooding to saturation was maintained before flowering. From flowering to

Fig. 9. Yield response of IR8 to different water application intensity treatments, 1969 dry season, IRRI.

Table 8. Plant characteristics under different water application treatments. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Water treatment (mm/day)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Tillers (no./sq m)	Pro-ductive tillers (%)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
8	96	377	401	94	8,832
7	93	388	403	96	8,735
6	83	413	425	97	7,301
5	70	403	489	82	4,650
4	50	441	676	4 ^a	89
3	40	165	753	0 ^b	0
2	—	—	—	0	0
Flooded	93	372	388	96	8,728

^a Only 29 of 441 exserted panicles bore limited grains.

^b None of the 165 exserted panicles produced grain.

maturity, the plot fell below saturation. At water application levels below 7 mm/day, all plots fell below saturation before flowering. The plants in the plot receiving 3 mm/day flowered but produced no grain; plants in the plot receiving 2 mm/day did not flower.

The change in the soil moisture level for each plot is graphed in Figure 10. Except for the 2-mm treatment, it took at least 60 days after transplanting for the soil moisture to fall below approximate field capacity (50 percent). These results explain why no severe yield decline occurred in the 1968 experiment when all plots were kept flooded until 60 days after transplanting (compare Fig. 10 with Fig. 5, 1968 Annual Report).

Table 8 shows plant characteristics for different treatment levels. At lower levels of water application, plant height decreased while tiller number increased. However, the number of productive tillers also declined.

Profitability of insecticide use

For the long run, undoubtedly, the most economical approach to disease and insect control involves the development of resistant varieties. But until appropriate resistant varieties become available, efforts must be continued to develop effective, low-cost insecticides. Determining the optimum level of application is considerably more difficult for an insecticide than for either a fertilizer or a herbicide because of the mobility and high degree of variability of the insect population.

Basically insects can be controlled in two ways. The first can be referred to as preventive

Fig. 10. Soil moisture content (oven-dry basis; 15-cm profile depth) at different water application treatments throughout crop growth.

or prophylactic. Insecticide is applied whether or not there is any sign of insect attack. The second approach involves the application of insecticides only in the event of imminent or actual infestation.

The first approach makes sense economically when the cost of the insecticide is very low relative to the potential savings as measured by the value of the crop.

Large-scale application of insecticides over a wide area may be economically justifiable if it lowers the cost per hectare. However, applications must be made at the proper growth stage of the plant. The small size of Asian rice farms coupled with the introduction of non-photo-period sensitive varieties is likely to reduce the uniformity in timing of planting and harvesting operations, thus reducing the effectiveness of blanket spraying over a large area.

In view of the shortage of capital, the relatively high cost of chemicals, and the uncertainty of the benefits, the typical rice farmer cannot afford the luxury of the prophylactic approach.

Our research has been undertaken with the

assumption that individual small farmers with limited capital resources will be responsible for deciding what insect control measures are used on their farms.

Experimental procedure. Experiments have been conducted for four crop seasons, the first ones on the Institute farm. The insect population at IRRI was so atypical of the surrounding area that the results obtained had little economic significance. In particular, brown planthopper attack was so severe that it caused hopper burn on control plots receiving no treatment, something rarely observed on farmers' fields.

During the 1968 wet season, the experimental site was changed to a farmer's field in Calauan, a town about 10 km from IRRI. The experiments were designed to determine the effect of alternative levels and timing of insecticide application on yields and profits from lowland rice. Experiments were conducted in both the dry and wet seasons of 1969 with three varieties, six treatment levels, and three replications. The fertilizer level was 75 kg/ha N for both seasons. This level approximated the rate most commonly used by farmers in the area. In addition, a case study was undertaken to determine the control practices followed by 11 other farmers in the town of Calauan near the experimental area.

Experimental results. The experimental results for the dry season are summarized in Table 9 and those for the wet season, in Table 10. Dead heart and white head percentages reflect the severity of stem borer attack.

Perhaps the most significant feature of the results is the high degree of variability not only by treatment, but also by variety and by season. In both the dry and the wet seasons, crop damage from stem borers and leafhoppers was low. Most of the dead heart and white head counts were less than 2 percent and often less than 1 percent. The dry-season crop in general suffered less total damage than the wet-season crop which was severely infested by whorl maggot (particularly IR20 and IR8, although the impact of this attack upon yields is difficult to isolate).

For IR20, all insecticide treatments in the dry season gave a negative return. In the wet season, a single application was most profitable. The

Table 9. Effectiveness and profitability of applying two insecticides at 2 kg/ha (active ingredient)^a: Calauan, Laguna, Philippines, 1969 dry season.

Chemical and application time (days after transplanting)	Dead hearts ^b (%)	White heads ^c (%)	Grain yield ^d (kg/ha)	Net return ^e (P/ha)
IR20				
Lindane				
50	0.81	0.01	4,564 a	(47)
booting	0.75	0.04	4,314 a	(47)
80	0.41	0.02	4,814 a	(22)
50 and 80	0.61	0.20	4,629 a	(1)
Diazinon				
50 and 80	0.41	0.16	4,907 a	(48)
Control				
No application	1.87	0.12	4,759 a	—
IR8				
Lindane				
50	0.66	0.22	5,224 cd	225
booting	1.27	0.08	4,896 abc	109
80	0.80	0.00	5,330 d	215
50 and 80	2.95	0.02	4,734 ab	52
Diazinon				
50 and 80	0.81	0.36	5,068 bcd	117
Control				
No application	2.04	0.32	4,454 a	—
Intan				
Lindane				
50	0.73	0.33	6,026 c	111
booting	1.27	0.19	5,964 bc	87
80	0.83	0.05	5,852 abc	(3)
50 and 80	1.16	0.19	5,659 ab	(31)
Diazinon				
50 and 80	0.55	0.40	5,864 abc	(5)
Control				
No application	0.79	0.28	5,618 a	—

^a The insecticide cost P25/kg of active ingredient and treatment cost P50/ha per application.

^b Sum of counts, at 54 and 64 days after transplanting.

^c 86 days after transplanting.

^d Average of three replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^e Increase in value of the yield above the control minus the cost of the insecticide. Values in parentheses indicate negative returns.

yield increases for two and for four applications did not differ significantly from that for one application. Two applications of lindane, however, had a significant advantage over diazinon.

For IR8, insecticide treatments were generally profitable in both the wet and the dry seasons. The highest profit was achieved with four applications of insecticide in the wet season. Lindane was significantly better than diazinon in the dry season, but showed no significant difference in the wet season.

With Intan (dry season), only the single application was profitable. With C4-63 (wet season), all treatments were profitable.

The yield difference between two applications of diazinon and the same number of applications of lindane, with the exception of IR8, in the dry season were not significant.

Table 10. Effectiveness and profitability of applying two insecticides at 2 kg/ha (active ingredient)^a: Calauan, Laguna, Philippines, 1969 wet season.

Chemical and application time (days after transplanting)	Dead hearts ^b (%)	White heads ^c (%)	Grain yield ^d (kg/ha)	Net return ^e (P/ha)
IR20				
Lindane				
50	1.31	1.15	5,165 b	189
booting	1.75	0.04	5,132 b	174
50 and 80	1.76	0.14	5,111 b	118
15, 35, 55 & 75	0	0.36	5,136 b	36
Diazinon				
50 and 80	1.31	0.47	4,679 a	(83)
Control				
No application	1.54	0.75	4,641 a	—
IR8				
Lindane				
50	1.67	1.01	5,050 a	126
booting	1.97	0.21	4,632 a	(24)
50 and 80	1.38	0.11	5,153 a	117
15, 35, 55 & 75	0	0.24	6,107 b	367
Diazinon				
50 and 80	0.76	0.76	4,844 a	(1)
Control				
No application	1.17	1.38	4,569 a	—
C4-63				
Lindane				
50	0.67	1.29	4,661 ab	69
booting	1.01	0.84	5,066 bc	244
50 and 80	1.12	0.42	5,044 bc	187
15, 35, 55 & 75	0.02	0.93	5,524 c	300
Diazinon				
50 and 80	1.28	0.65	4,940 b	136
Control				
No application	0.88	0.75	4,391 a	—

^a The insecticide cost P25/kg of active ingredient and treatment cost P50/ha per application.

^b Sum of two counts, at 55 and 65 days after transplanting.

^c Sum of two counts, at 95 and 105 days after transplanting.

^d Average of three replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^e Increase in value of the yield above the control minus the cost of the insecticide. Values in parentheses indicate negative returns.

Farmer experience. Observations were made of insect infestation, insecticide practices, and yields on 11 farms in Calauan. All farms used foliar spray, and nearly all made only one application. The level of application was generally lower in the dry season than in the wet season, with four farms applying no insecticide treatment during the dry season.

Stem borer infestation was measured on all farms during the wet season by a white head count at 95 days after transplanting. Two sample counts were taken on five paddies in each farm. The white head count ranged from 0.11 to 4.32 percent and averaged 1.02 percent. No farm encountered a severe stem borer attack. Analysis of variance for the eight farms growing IR8 showed that there was no significant difference in white head counts among barrios (villages)

or among farms at the 5-percent level, but a significant difference among paddy fields within barrios at the 1-percent level. This result agrees with our finding of significant differences among replications in the experiments conducted. The replications were located in separate paddy fields.

Implications. The results of experiments and farm observations represent an extremely small area. The high variability of these results indicates that with the information now available it is virtually impossible to give farmers economically sound recommendations about insecticide application. In the absence of adequate data, the farmer must rely largely on his previous experience regarding the likely degree of severity of insect attack in a given season. But previous experience may not be a reliable guide if higher levels of fertilizer application result in increased insect activity.

Economics of herbicide use

Until recently, farmers have had little interest in herbicides. A new granular herbicide for rice, isopropyl ester of 2,4-D, may change this picture. Economic analysis in this section explains why.

The economic advantage of using herbicides compared with hand weeding is principally decided by the cost of the herbicide, the cost of the labor for hand weeding, and the amount of labor saved by substituting herbicides for hand weeding. Figure 11 combines these three relationships graphically. Lines A, B, C, and D may be regarded as "break-even" lines. For example, assume that 175 hours can be saved by substituting the herbicide for hand weeding. If the point of intersection defined by the cost of the herbicide and the farm wage rate fell exactly on line B, then using herbicides would cost exactly the same as hand weeding.

The first step in using the figure is to decide whether the potential labor savings is large (175 to 225 hours for two hand weedings) or small (75 to 125 hours for one hand weeding). Then choose the appropriate herbicide and wage rate for the particular situation and determine where these two lines intersect.

For example, if the cost of a complete herbicide is ₱70 per hectare and if labor is

Fig. 11. Price map for use in deciding on herbicide versus hand weeding.

hired for weeding at ₱3.50 per day then, as the broken lines in Figure 11 show, the point of intersection is below line B. It would, therefore, be more profitable to use the herbicide than to hire 175 hours or more of labor to do the job. However, if only 125 hours are used for hand weeding, it would pay to continue hand weeding.

If the price of the herbicide falls to ₱30 per hectare and the wage rate remains the same, the new point of intersection lies below line D. It now pays to use herbicide even when the labor saved by hand weeding is comparatively small. The ₱30 value used for herbicide in this second example is the approximate cost per hectare of the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D. Thus Figure 11 illustrates the impact that the drop in herbicide price from ₱70 to ₱30 is likely to have on increased use of herbicides.

The cost per hectare for weeding is shown in Table 11 under several labor and wage rate assumptions. Of course, many farmers still do little, if any, weeding. Those who practice proper weed control, however, often spend ₱50/

Table 11. Cost per hectare of hand weeding at different weeding intensities and farm wage rates.

Daily farm wage rate (P)	Cost for weeding (P/ha)			
	Hours for hand weeding			
	75	125	175	225
2	19	31	44	56
3	28	47	66	84
4	38	62	88	112

ha or more for hand weeding. This table illustrates again the importance of decline in the price of herbicides. With the herbicides costing P70 per hectare, in all but three of the situations shown in Table 11 it would be more profitable to weed by hand. But with herbicide costing P30, hand weeding is more profitable in only two situations.

Cropping and income distribution in Bicol

As the new rice varieties have spread, a question frequently raised is how farmers will respond if increased production of rice leads to a surplus and a lower price. A study was started in 1969 to investigate the cropping and income patterns among farmers growing rice and competitive crops in Bicol, Philippines.

Preliminary investigation indicated that many farmers in the Province of Albay were growing rice in combination with other crops. An initial survey sample of 350 farms was drawn in April. The farmers were interviewed to establish the basic farm production patterns in the region. The percentages of effective crop area from 1964/65 to 1968/69 are summarized for specific

Table 12. Percentages of effective crop area utilization, 1964/65 to 1968/69, Albay, Bicol, Philippines^a

Crop ^b	1964/65	1965/66	1966/67	1967/68	1968/69
Palay (rice)	34	35	34	33	33
Coconut	16	16	16	17	17
Abaca	12	12	12	11	11
Corn	5	4	5	5	5
Root crops	15	15	14	15	15
Banana	6	6	6	6	6
Vegetables	8	8	9	10	10
Fruit crops	1	1	1	1	1
Peanuts	1	1	1	1	1
Coffee	1	1	1	1	1
Cocoa	1	1	1	1	1

^a Estimate is based on 350 sample farms from 19 sample barrios of five sample towns, with sampling units in all stages drawn with equal probability.

^b Crops planted to less than 0.50% of total area are excluded, e.g. sorghum.

crops in Table 12. All but a small portion of the lowland rice in this province is irrigated.

The initial survey identified three basic types of rice farms: Irrigated farms growing one or two crops of lowland rice, irrigated farms growing one or two crops of lowland rice in combination with other crops, and farms growing upland rice and other crops.

A second interview was conducted on several farms in each of these categories to obtain more information on income and resource use. Income initially was measured as the return above variable costs and the charge for land and for family labor was omitted. The payments made both in kind and in cash for such services as harvesting were included as a part of costs. Products consumed by the family as well as those marketed were considered as part of income. This income measure provides a crude yardstick of comparative efficiency with which the farm family uses fixed resources. Returns above variable costs on tenant-operated farms would be reduced by another 50 percent if allowance were made for the share rental of land.

Returns above variable costs averaged about the same for the two types of lowland farms—P1,140/farm and P840/ha for farms growing rice only, and P1,475/farm and P932/ha for farms growing rice in combination with other crops. However, the average income for upland farms was P225/farm and P205/ha or only one-fifth that of the lowland farms.

Distribution of incomes as measured by the returns above variable resources is shown for the three farm types in Figure 12. There was little difference in the income levels or income distribution patterns for the two types of lowland farm, whether measured on a per-farm or on a per-hectare basis.

A breakdown of income distribution by varieties indicated that those farms with incomes above P600 were all growing new varieties. Thus the introduction of new varieties may have widened the income distribution. But no evidence suggests that the impact of the new varieties on farm income distribution has had detrimental social or economic effects. This, however, is a subject that requires more detailed investigation by sociologists.

The relationship between farm income and

Table 13. Inputs and return above variable cost by farm size and type. Albay, Bicol, Philippines, 1968/69.

Farm size (ha)	No. of farms	Inputs		Return above variable costs	
		Capital (P/ha)	Work units (man-days/ha)	(P/ha)	(P/farm)
Lowland rice					
<1	22	1,743	296	939	481
1-1.9	15	1,314	203	673	880
2-2.9	4	617	138	589	1,325
3+	10	1,096	192	752	2,856
Lowland rice and other crops					
<1	7	1,154	207	432	277
1-1.9	6	1,588	235	676	902
2-2.9	7	1,350	153	450	1,061
3+	7	731	74	331	3,577
Upland rice and other crops					
<1	4	835	190	132	70
1-1.9	9	1,055	85	207	268
2-2.9	3	443	65	127	257
3+	7	471	61	76	351

resource inputs, such as land, labor, and capital is of considerable interest. In Table 13 farms have been sorted according to size. As farm size increases beyond the 1- to 2-hectare range, generally capital and labor input per hectare tend to decline, although this does not seem to be the trend in lowland rice farms above 3 hectares. Of the 10 farms in this category, eight were planted to new varieties and used capital and labor more intensively. Income per hectare also declines with farm size, but income per farm increases.

The lowland farms growing rice in combination with other crops were examined in detail. On these farms many combinations of crops were being grown and many different cropping patterns were being used. Farms showing the largest returns per hectare for 1968/69 were growing rice in combination with cabbage and tomatoes. The return above variable cost on these farms exceeded ₱1,300/ha. (compared with the average of ₱932 for the group). However, on most farms, alternative crops were being grown on land not suited to rice production. On these farms, no rotation or intercropping was being practiced.

Decision-making on Laguna farms

During 1969, landlords and tenants of 30 tenant-operated farms taken from the original 155 in our Laguna survey were interviewed to

learn about decisions with respect to the use of credit and farm inputs.

On these farms rice land owned by the landlords ranged from 0.33 to 50.0 hectares. Most landowners had less than 10 tenants, each of whom operated, typically, 1 to 3 hectares. Three tenants had less than 1 hectare each and another three tenants had more than 3 hectares each.

On 24 of the farms the tenant decided the kind and amount of fertilizer, insecticide, and herbicide used. The landowners normally visited their farms only three or four times during the crop season, except for a few who were actively engaged in the decision-making.

Fig. 12. Income distribution (return above variable costs) of three types of farm, Albay, 1968-1969.

Most crop production loans which tenants made were for the purchase of fertilizer, chemicals, and for transplanting. A smaller number were for land preparation, weeding, and fuel to run irrigation pumps. Twenty-seven of the 30 tenants received loans from the landowner. The landowner usually supplied the inputs, such as fertilizer, when needed, and the cash for hired labor. The tenant repaid him at harvest time with rice he set aside before the equal sharing of the harvest took place. Under this system, the rate of interest being charged was hidden. Many landowners said they charged no interest. Some based the repayment on the value of the rice at the time the input was purchased.

The landowner himself often did not need to borrow money to lend to the tenants. Eight landowners borrowed money from the banks for loans on cash operating expenses and almost as many borrowed to invest in pumps or other capital items. Many landowners were engaged in some form of business or profession outside of agriculture. Even those borrowing from banks frequently used borrowed funds for business activities not connected with the farm.

The combined impact of the new varieties and the higher rice prices on input use is shown by comparing the input levels for 1965 with those for 1969 (Table 14). The 20 landowners reporting indicated that the average loans to their tenants increased from ₱83/ha to ₱245/ha in this period. Only two of the 26 tenants borrowing from landowners indicated that the amount of credit extended in 1965 had not increased in 1969. Both the number of landowners extending credit and the amount of

credit increased for all items. Between 1965 and 1969, the amount of credit extended to tenants by landowners increased by more than five times to an average of ₱173/ha.

The increase in loans for contract labor exceeded that for fertilizer and chemicals. The most dramatic change was for land preparation. Custom hiring of tractors appears to be substituting for farm-owned carabao.

Capital investment in farm implements and farm power was also examined. The tenant made a large part of this investment without using credit. All except two of the 15 irrigation pumps belonged to the landowner, but the hand tractors and carabaos were owned by the tenant. Most farm operators had purchased one or more hand weeders from their own savings.

Both landowners and tenants were asked how they would spend additional funds for the farm operation. The answers suggested a continuing demand for more fertilizer, but less interest in insecticides and herbicides.

With respect to capital investment, the chief demand of the tenant is for a tractor, while the landowner is concerned more with the irrigation pump. This difference simply reflects the different responsibilities of the two in the farm-sharing arrangement.

Diffusion of high-yielding varieties

Spatial aspects of diffusion of high-yielding varieties

Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines (Fig. 13) is a municipality of 2,300 farmers. Seed of the new short-statured, high-yielding plant type was first introduced in July 1966 and 16 farmers planted at least part of their holdings in IR8. These original innovators were concentrated in the northwestern portion of the municipality close to the *poblacion* (town proper). This concentration (Fig. 14) was strongly influenced by the fact that nine of the 16 original planters were tenants of three large landowners who obtained seed through government channels. All three owners lived in the *poblacion* and the tenants were selected to grow the "miracle rice" partly because of the proximity of their land to the home of the owner.

Table 14. Credit extended by landlords to tenants. Laguna, Philippines, 1965 and 1969.

Item	1965		1969	
	Tenants reporting	Amount of credit (₱/ha)	Tenants reporting	Amount of credit (₱/ha)
Fertilizer	18	28.15	24	64.55
Chemicals	10	5.20	23	15.90
Land preparation	0	0	14	108.10
Transplanting	13	33.90	19	52.20
Weeding	4	15.30	10	54.55
Other ^a	1	39.00	9	73.55

^a Mostly fuel for irrigation pumps.

Fig. 13. Land use pattern, Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

In May 1967, the original 16 planters of IR8 were joined by 78 others. The new innovators (Fig. 15) were concentrated in two areas: the same barrios as in the previous year and along the National Road south to Malimba and Baluarte.

In 1967, less than 5 percent of Gapan's farmers planted high-yielding varieties, but a year later, the figure increased dramatically to over 30 percent. The map showing the pattern of

adoption for 1968 (Fig. 16) is striking not only because of the large number of farms involved, but also because its pattern was markedly similar to that of the previous year. A noticeable concentration of adopters was found in the barrios (villages) close to the poblacion and those along the national highway. But Santa Cruz, Kapalangán, and Mahipon, with a total of 40 percent of the farm population, had less than 8 percent of the 1968 adopters. Such a

Fig. 14. Concentration of 16 original adopters of high-yielding varieties 1966.

Fig. 15. Concentration of 78 new adopters of high-yielding varieties, 1967.

Fig. 16. Concentration of new adopters of high-yielding varieties, 1968.

Fig. 17. Concentration of new adopters of high-yielding varieties, 1969.

marked differential in the rate of adoption between these three barrios and the rest of the municipality appears too great to ascribe to distance and to the “neighbor effect” alone,

particularly because during this period every barrio had its own land reform fieldman operating as a “change agent” and extension worker. The map suggests a period of intensi-

fication of the earlier pattern and raises the question of why the adoption failed to spread farther outward from the center.

Figure 13 provides a clue to the apparent resistance of farmers to high-yielding varieties in Santa Cruz, Kapalangan, and Mahipon. In these three barrios, less than one-third of the land is irrigated. In the rest of the municipality, 95 percent is irrigated. The shift from traditional to high-yielding varieties of rice involves far more than the use of new seed. Investment in a variety of agricultural chemicals and in more costly methods of cultivation is necessary if improved yields are to be achieved. Such investments involve great risk on farms that depend on rainfall alone for their water supply. On irrigated land, a high rate of return on investment is relatively secure. At least early in the process of diffusion, farmers with little ready cash and inadequate credit facilities hesitate to invest in high-yielding varieties unless they have an assured water supply.

In 1969, the pattern of new adopters (Fig. 17) was strikingly different from that of previous years. In 1969 the barrios of Mangino, Santo Cristo Norte, Santo Cristo Sur, and San Nicolas, which have the closest contact with the poblacion, all showed a decrease in the number of new innovators, while Santa Cruz, Kapalangan, Pambuan, Malimba, Baluarte, and even Mahipon showed striking increases. The new adopters for this year were markedly concentrated in the barrios more remote from the center. In this year, 597 farmers, 25 percent of all farmers in the municipality, grew high-yielding varieties for the first time. The map shows a marked renewal of the outward spread of innovation from the original center. By the completion of the palagad (season starting in May) planting in 1969, 98 percent of the farms in Mangino and San Nicolas already had been planted, at least in part, to high-yielding varieties. In the more remote barrios served by irrigation, adoption in 1969 reached the levels achieved the previous year in the more central locations. Even in 1969 the proportion of farmers using high-yielding varieties in barrios that had little irrigated land remained far below that in barrios with irrigation. For example, in Mahipon, the most remote barrio and the one

least favored with irrigation, one in 10 farmers had been converted while elsewhere in the municipality, two out of three farmers were planting high-yielding varieties.

The maps of innovation suggest four stages in the spatial pattern: (1) a concentrated focus of early adoption, (2) a dramatic outward extension from this center, (3) a marked elaboration of the pattern set in the second stage, and (4) a renewed outward extension.

The mean center of the 1966 innovative farms was found by graphic means and the road distance from this "Center of Innovation" to all new innovators was measured for each year. The means of these measurements and the results of a test of the "comparison among means" appear in Table 15. They add to the evidence supporting the stages outlined above.

To measure the influence of several spatially variable patterns on the spread of high-yielding varieties in Gapan, a correlation matrix was developed and a stepwise multiple regression formula was determined for each year. Six independent variables were considered, with number of adopters as the dependent variable.

The results of the correlation matrix are presented in Table 16.

The results of the multiple regression analysis are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &1967 \text{ Adopters } (Y_1) \\ &\hat{Y}_1 = -3.794 + 0.044^*X_1 + 0.663 X_2 + 2.946 X_3 \\ &R^2 = 0.874 \end{aligned} \quad (5a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &1968 \text{ Adopters } (Y_2) \\ &\hat{Y}_2 = -25.746 + 0.297^*X_1 + 7.365^{**}X_2 + 20.150 X_3 \\ &R^2 = .955 \end{aligned} \quad (5b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &1969 \text{ Adopters } (Y_3) \\ &\hat{Y}_3 = -5.708 + 0.510^*X_1 + 26.136^*X_3 - 0.134 X_4 \\ &R^2 = .945 \end{aligned} \quad (5c)$$

where:

- X_1 = Percentage of land irrigated by barrio.
- X_2 = Number of original innovators in 1966 by barrio.
- X_3 = The settlement pattern, mapped as continuous or non-continuous. Based on the formula: $d = 1.1 A/N$, where: d = diameter of a circle drawn around each barrio; A = total area of all cultivated land in Gapan; and N = the number of settlements in the municipality.
- X_4 = The percentage of leaseholders by barrio.
- X_5 = Cost of transportation of fertilizer from the source in the poblacion to each barrio.
- X_6 = The percentage of owner-operators by barrio.

*Significant at the 5-percent level. **Significant at the 1-percent level.

Table 15. Mean distances from the center of innovation to all new innovators.

Year	Mean distance ^a (km)
1966	2.3 a
1967	3.8 b
1968	3.3 b
1969	5.1 c

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level.

In each of the three formulas for estimating Y, only three independent variables are included. In the stepwise regression analysis the variable explaining the greatest variance in Y is included first, the next greatest, second, and so on. When the addition of the next most important variable in the equation fails to explain a significant portion of the variance in Y, it is excluded and the formula is considered complete. This does not mean that such excluded variables are not important since their influence may be confounded with the included variables. In this case, the independent variables are themselves strongly correlated (Table 16).

For the 3 years taken together, the most important factor explaining the variation of percentage of adopters is "percent irrigation." The second factor is "continuous settlement," which again is represented in each of the three equations. The location and number of original innovators apparently had a strong influence in 1967 and 1968, but significantly diminished in importance by 1969. Transportation cost and percentage of owner-operators by barrio (X_5 and X_6) did not significantly help explain the number of adopters and are thus excluded in the equations. In all 3 years the coefficient of

determination (R^2) was large enough to warrant a high degree of confidence in the formula.

The diffusion followed a pattern quite similar in many ways to those identified in studies in the U.S.A. and Western Europe. In those studies, factors such as irrigation, the settlement pattern, and the cost of transportation, were found to have influenced the spread of improved varieties. By contrast, the conversion of half of the farmers in Gapan from share tenants to leaseholders during the period 1965-68 was not correlated significantly with the spread of high-yielding varieties. The most striking feature of the innovation in Gapan was that in irrigated barrios with as little as 4 years of contact with high-yielding varieties, the cumulative adoption was over 80 percent. For Gapan as a whole the figure was 59 percent at the end of 4 years. This rate of adoption exceeds the rate found by researchers dealing with similar innovations in the U.S.A. or Western Europe.

While Gapan is atypical of Central Luzon in that a very high percentage of its land is under irrigation, it is quite representative in other respects. With the same extension efforts, there is no obvious reason why the rates of conversion to high-yielding varieties for irrigated and for rainfed areas identified in Gapan should not be similar in other municipalities.

Diffusion of high-yielding varieties in Luzon

Another study dealing with the farmer acceptance of new varieties was conducted by Mahar Mangahas through a cooperative project with the U.P. School of Economics. The study

Table 16. Correlation matrix for three dependent variables, Y_1 to Y_3 , and six independent variables, X_1 to X_6 , as observed by barrio for 10 barrios in Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines ($n=10$).

Variable	X_1 Irrigated land	X_2 No. of inno- vators, '66	X_3 Continuous settlement	X_4 Leaseholders '69	X_5 Cost of trans- portation	X_6 Landowners '69
Y_1 Adopters, '67	0.765**	0.720*	0.845**	-0.170 ^{n.s.}	-0.745*	0.046 ^{n.s.}
Y_2 Adopters, '68	0.734*	0.817**	0.850**	-0.077 ^{n.s.}	-0.835**	-0.063 ^{n.s.}
Y_3 Adopters, '69	0.910**	0.453 ^{n.s.}	0.840**	-0.371 ^{n.s.}	-0.658*	-0.044 ^{n.s.}
X_1 Irrigated land		0.363 ^{n.s.}	0.647*	-0.334 ^{n.s.}	-0.634*	-0.294 ^{n.s.}
X_2 No. of innovators, '66			0.597 ^{n.s.}	-0.079 ^{n.s.}	-0.822**	-0.042 ^{n.s.}
X_3 Continuous settlement				-0.156 ^{n.s.}	-0.643*	0.228 ^{n.s.}
X_4 Leaseholds					0.132 ^{n.s.}	-0.315 ^{n.s.}
X_5 Cost of transportation						0.055 ^{n.s.}

* Significant at the 5% level.

** Significant at the 1% level.

n.s. Not significant.

Table 17. Linear probability functions^a for use of high-yielding varieties on specified farm types in Central Luzon, 1967/68.

Independent variable ^b	Rainfed		Irrigated wet season		Irrigated dry season	
	Non-cooperator	Cooperator	Non-cooperator	Cooperator	Non-cooperator	Cooperator
Expertise	0.114 (0.097)	0.469 (0.347)	0.689 (0.134)	0.720 (0.148)	0.780 (0.279)	0.985 —
Interest	-0.096 (0.093)	0.370 (0.494)	-0.001 (0.006)	-0.472 (0.349)	-1.531 (0.692)	-0.522 (0.377)
Tenure	0.013 (0.029)	-0.160 (0.116)	0.060 (0.052)	0.042 (0.073)	0.109 (0.109)	0.028 (0.104)
Size	0.005 (0.010)	0.074 (0.037)	-0.022 (0.013)	0.048 (0.016)	-0.083 (0.042)	0.003 (0.038)
Pump	—	—	0.124 (0.063)	0.123 (0.077)	-0.008 (0.192)	-0.103 (0.125)
Constant	0.053	0.001	0.066	0.048	0.471	0.295
R ²	0.009	0.157	0.130	0.161	0.161	0.183
Sample size	343	69	236	218	89	117

^a Numbers in parentheses indicate standard errors of the coefficients.

^b *Expertise* = the ratio of the number recommended of farm practices used the preceding year to seven recommended practices; *Interest* = annual interest rate on farm loans with minimum adjusted to 5%; *Tenure* = 1, if the farmer is an owner-operator; 0, if otherwise; *Size* = area planted to rice in hectares; *Pump* = 1, if pump irrigated; 0, if gravity irrigated; *Dependent variable* = 1, if planting high-yielding variety; 0, if otherwise.

covered six important rice-growing provinces in Luzon—Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, Pangasinan, Tarlac, and Laguna. Nearly 900 farm survey records collected for the crop year 1967/68 by the Philippine Bureau of Agricultural Economics were analyzed to determine factors which lead to the acceptance of the new varieties.

Farms were grouped into three crop types—rainfed, irrigated wet season, and irrigated dry season and then further separated into co-operators (those that participated in the government program) and non-cooperators. There were thus six categories or cells. Separate equations were estimated for each cell. The use of new varieties in 1967/68 was used as a dummy dependent variable. Regression results may be interpreted as linear probability functions.

Age and schooling contributed little to either “expertise” (the proportion of seven recommended production practices which the farmer had applied in the *preceding* crop year) or varietal-use. A two-equation model which would have allowed for intercorrelation among the age, schooling, and “expertise” variables did not appear to be of critical importance. The age and schooling variables were then omitted. Table 17 indicates that the most important of the remaining variables is “expertise.” “Expertise” has a high degree of complementarity with irrigation and participation in the government program (Table 17). The “expertise” coefficient for the farmer who is not a cooperator and who

grows rainfed rice is 0.114, in contrast with the coefficient of 0.985 for a farmer who is a cooperator and grows irrigated rice in the dry season. A coefficient as high as 0.9 implies that knowledge of one additional modern practice, out of seven, contributes about 13 percent ($0.9 \div 7$) to the probability of use of high-yielding varieties.

The signs obtained for coefficients of the other variables were generally in the “right” direction. None of the coefficients were comparable in size to that of “expertise,” however. The interest-rate coefficient was of modest size only for those strata identified with cooperators. The coefficient of the “pump” variable (pumps vs. gravity irrigation) was not positive for the dry season as it was for the wet; however, the results here are obscured by an apparent shift of pump-users to non-rice activities (excluded from the survey) in the dry season. The possible contributions to varietal diffusion of conversion to owner-operatorship and of expansion in farm size were not of large importance. Conversely, tenancy and smallness of farm—conditions

Table 18. Standardized probabilities of high-yielding variety use in Central Luzon, by crop type and cooperators, crop year 1968/69.

	Rainfed	Irrigated wet season	Irrigated dry season
Non-cooperators	0.074	0.198	0.232
Cooperators	0.264	0.253	0.402

ordinarily associated with initially low income levels—are not serious impediments to adoption of new rice varieties.

Using the information available in Table 17,

the probability of acceptance of the high-yielding varieties was computed for each of the six strata. The standardized probabilities are shown in Table 18.

Agricultural Engineering

A lighter table thresher was designed to facilitate moving it to fields with no access roads. An eight-row seeder for pre-germinated paddy seed was developed and tested. The machine can sow 1 hectare in 5 man-hours as compared to 120 man-hours required for transplanting.

The development of a stripper-harvester made satisfactory progress. The experimental machine was modified to insure complete harvesting of paddy grains directly from the field without cutting the plant.

Studies on the economics of mechanization were continued with increased emphasis on the economics of specific agricultural machines. A survey of small hand-tractor owners was made to develop specifications for hand tractors for tropical rice cultivation.

We assisted local manufacturers of the drum thresher in their manufacturing programs. Several drum threshers were sent to countries in Asia for evaluation and drawings and other technical information on the thresher were sent to Asian, South American, and African countries.

To develop basic information on accelerated rice drying, two research projects were started using sand and mechanical agitation to lessen the effects of localized grain heating. Preliminary results indicate that it is possible to dry paddy from 35 percent to 18 percent moisture in 15 seconds. The accelerated drying experiments, which had a parboiling effect on rough rice, increased head rice yields by up to 18 percentage points.

Research on grain processing was also begun. A rotary screen grain cleaner, which combines mechanical and pneumatic separation in a single rotating member, was designed and fabricated. This machine can clean over 1 ton of grain per man-hour. It is fairly simple in design and can be manufactured in the tropical countries.

Field machinery development

Paddy stripper combine

The introduction of conventional combines for rice harvesting has been slow in the tropical countries. A conventional combine cuts the rice plant and feeds it through the threshing mechanism. Because combines handle complete rice plants with large volumes of straw, these machines are bulky and heavy. Their weight is further increased by the need for high-flotation devices, such as crawler tracks, to support the machine in wet paddy fields.

A paddy harvester that could strip the grain from the panicles without cutting the plant would eliminate the need for machine components to handle straw. As a result, the machine would be compact, lightweight, and better suited for harvesting rice in the wet tropics. The stripping mechanism is our main concern, initially. Suitable screening, winnowing, and grain delivery components will be added in later designs.

During the operation of the stripper-harvester, plants immediately in front of the machine are gently bent and pressed against the upper portion of an inclined moving wire-loop threshing belt. The panicles move downward along the threshing belt as the machine moves forward and runs over the plants. During the forward motion of the machine, additional plants are continually bent toward the top portion of the threshing belt and subsequently threshed.

Fig. 1. Experimental paddy stripper combine being field-tested.

Fig. 2. Improved Ceylon-type lowland seeder for pre-germinated paddy.

An early problem was getting the plants to bend onto the threshing belt properly. In the original design, the horizontal velocity of the deflecting bar was equal to the ground speed. Field trials indicated that insufficient plant deflection at ground speed caused too many unthreshed panicles. Tests with different deflecting-bar velocities showed that the horizontal velocity of the deflecting bar must be considerably higher than the forward speed of the machine for satisfactory operation. In addition, the panicle must touch the top end of the threshing belt first to provide sufficient time for complete threshing.

The experimental machine (Fig. 1) can satisfactorily harvest all the grain from a standing paddy crop. It has been tried on non-lodging dwarf varieties. Lifting fingers are being installed to enable it to harvest a lodged crop. A four-row, self-propelled, stripper-harvester with a rotary screen cleaner will be developed as soon as tests on the present machine are completed.

Row seeder for lowland rice

The problem of direct seeding of rice in puddled soil was discussed in the last annual report. To gain some experience with the seeding of pre-germinated rice, a portable seeder, patterned after a simple six-row seeder from Ceylon, was fabricated. This seeder (Fig. 2) incorporated an improved manual seed metering arrangement and two additional seed tubes to sow eight rows at a time. It was equipped with a small hopper of 1/2-kg capacity. The manual seed metering arrangement consisted of a scraper and a set of eight rectangular openings in the hopper. These openings led to the individual seed tubes. A skid measuring 0.15 x 2m was fastened to the lower ends of the seed tubes to hold the openings above the surface of the mud.

The operator pulled the seeder while walking backwards, then paused momentarily to scrape some seeds into the rectangular openings. Tests were conducted under actual field conditions. The field was puddled and leveled the day before the test. When the surface of the field was uneven, the seeds were planted irregularly.

The skid provided enough flotation, but it bulldozed extremely soft areas. Some of the bulldozed mud was pushed around the ends and flowed behind the skid. This disturbed the seeds previously seeded in the adjacent rows and in the rows being sown by the two end tubes. The variations in seed placement and the seed disturbance caused by displacement of mud made it necessary to place the seeds in small furrows.

The simple device for metering the seeds by hand worked even for germinated seeds in an advanced stage of growth (up to a maximum root length of 2 cm). The rate of seeding and the accuracy of seed placement depended on the skill of the operator. Walking backward in deep mud was tiring for the operator.

The second experimental seeder was built to improve seed metering, seed placement, and handling. Figure 3 shows the second machine which was equipped with a ground-driven metering device. An adjustable handle permitted the seeder to be pulled by the operator as he walked forward. Two plates mounted on the ends of the skid reduced the flow of bulldozed mud behind the skid. Wedge-shaped furrow

Fig. 3. IRR I-developed, eight-row lowland seeder for pre-germinated paddy.

Fig. 4. Seed metering mechanism used with the IRR I seeder for pre-germinated paddy.

openers were attached to the underside of the skid to improve seed placement. A ground-driven wheel, 584 mm in diameter, provided the power to rotate the metering device in the puddled field and to support the weight of the machine as it was transported on hard ground and levees. Four lugs were welded to the wheel spokes to minimize slippage and maintain a uniform seed rate.

The ground-driven seed-metering device had two main components (Fig. 4), a fluted roller and a seed distributor with tapering seed

Fig. 5. Second prototype anhydrous ammonia applicator.

channels. The roller metered the seeds from the hopper while the seed distributor took the place of the rectangular openings in the first machine. A brush cut-off was used with the fluted roller to reduce damage to seeds as they were being separated from the hopper. The distributor with eight tapering channels was located beneath the fluted roller and funneled the seeds into the seed tubes. The excess seeds, those that did not drop into the seed channels, were collected in an overflow bag. A wide range of seeding rates was made possible by changing the position of the distributor in relation to that of the fluted roller. The capacity of the seed hopper was 5 kg of germinated seeds, enough for one-tenth of a hectare at 50 kg/ha.

The performance of the seeder was compared with transplanting in a field test. Three quarter-hectare plots were puddled and fertilized with 60 kg/ha N by mixing ammonium sulfate during the final leveling operation and 20 kg/ha N at panicle initiation. Each plot was split. In one half, 21-day-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted 25-cm apart at two to three seedlings per hill. The other half was seeded with the eight-row experimental seeder. Standard management and optimum pest and disease control were followed.

With the eight-row seeder, 4.9 man-hours were needed to seed 1 hectare. Transplanting required 199 man-hours. Researchers usually find that 100 to 120 man hours per hectare are required for transplanting. The higher labor requirement in our tests was probably the result of transplanting in rows. The test indicated that direct seeding with the experimental seeder was about 40 times faster than transplanting. The weight and number of tillers of the transplanted plots were significantly lower than those of the seeded plots. Possibly, the relatively high rate of seeding which increased the plant population in the direct-seeded plots caused the difference. The yield of the direct-seeded plots was not significantly different from that of the transplanted plots.

Applying NH_3 with small tractors

The development of a six-shank, anhydrous ammonia applicator for use with small tractors

Fig. 6. Set-up for measuring rotary tiller pushing force.

was reported in the 1968 Annual Report. It was used by the Agronomy Department for their experiments during the last two crop seasons. Results of tests on its use in flooded rice fields under transplanted and broadcast methods of planting for two varieties are presented in the Agronomy section of this report.

The first prototype applicator had a tank which held 8.5 kg of anhydrous ammonia. At an application rate of 80 kg/ha N, only 870 sq m could be covered on one tank-filling, so almost 12 refills per hectare were necessary.

The tank was subsequently replaced by two larger ones (Fig. 5) with a combined volume of 79.3 liters. The tanks have sufficient capacity to fertilize 2,500 sq m on one filling at an application rate of 80 kg/ha N. At the maximum application rate of 542 kg/min, these tanks maintain adequate discharge pressure.

A compact regulator-distributor was mounted with the new applicator. The shanks of the first prototype applicator were weak and tended to bend in puddled soil. Occasionally, weeds collected on the shanks and on the tubular shank frame. Stronger and longer applicator shanks (44.8 cm) were designed with a larger back-sweeping angle (45°). The applicator shanks performed better but they were still not completely self-shedding. Shanks further lengthened to allow a 30-degree back-swept angle with the horizontal are currently being tested.

Rotary tiller

Tests were conducted with the large-diameter, wetland rotary tiller (1968 Annual Report) to determine its pushing reaction on the tractor. We found that compared with conventional tillers, the experimental tiller reduced the wheel slippage of the tractor due to increased pushing force.

A new rotor with an adjustable blade was constructed and tested with the experimental tiller. The purpose of the tests was to determine the best blade angle for maximum pushing force. The blade angle of the new rotor could be set at 12.5, 32.5, 52.5, and 72.5 degrees from the radial line (Fig. 6). The position of the upper link of the three-point linkage of the tractor was rearranged to determine the pushing force and the power requirements of the tiller

with only a two-channel data recording system. The configuration, formed by the new arrangement of the tractor linkage, indicated that the horizontal force between the tiller and the tractor can be transmitted only through the two lower links. During the tests, the upper link was maintained in a vertical position by adjusting its length. The power requirements were measured by a torque transducer installed on the tiller input shaft (Fig. 7).

Figure 8 shows the relation between pushing force and pitch of cut for the four blade settings. The tilling depth was maintained at 10 cm. The blade angle of 12.5 degrees developed the maximum pushing force among the four angle settings. Although the 32.5 degree blade angle developed a pushing force which was not significantly lower than the 12.5 degree setting, it improved soil shedding and clogged less.

The power requirement as affected by the pitch of cut is shown in Figure 9. The 32.5 degree blade angle caused the highest power consumption. The 12.5 degree angle consumed

Fig. 7. Extension beam and PTO torque transducer for measuring rotary tiller pushing force.

Fig. 8. Pushing force versus pitch of cut at four blade angles.

Fig. 9. Horsepower versus pitch for four blade angles.

less power, although it developed more pushing force than the 32.5 degree angle.

Tractor rolling resistance

Tractors often bog down when used for land preparation in rice paddies. The rolling resistance of a tractor has an important bearing on its capacity to move under adverse soil conditions, but little information on the rolling resistance of standard tractors under lowland conditions in the tropics is available.

Experiments to determine the rolling resistance of a standard 55-hp tractor weighing 3,250 kg were conducted by towing the test tractor with a crawler tractor in flooded fields. Standard tractor tires without traction aids were used. A strain-gauge, load-cell transducer

was designed to measure the horizontal component of the towing force (Fig. 10).

Three test fields were selected. In field A the tractor encountered bogging within 5 m of travel. Fields B and C had different degrees of resistance, but in both the tractor could move without bogging (Fig. 11a). The results indicate that rolling resistance does not vary significantly with a change in speed (Fig. 11b). The coefficient of rolling resistance of the test tractor for the different test conditions: Field A $\phi = 0.378$; Field B $\phi = 0.147$; Field C $\phi = 0.128$; On concrete $\phi = 0.023$.

The power required to tow the tractor is also indicated in Figure 11b. In fields B and C, where the tractor could move without bogging with standard tires, about 12 hp was required while travelling at 1.8 m/sec. About 16 hp was required to tow the tractor in field A.

Differential cage-wheel slip

With a lightweight four-wheeled riding tractor which has independently driven front and rear cage wheels, land preparation could be achieved by inducing a speed differential between front and rear wheels. For maximum mobility, both the front and rear cage wheels could be driven at the same speed.

Since flooded soils have a low load-bearing capacity, weight was a major consideration in the design of the experimental machine. Two lightweight, 6-hp hand tractors were hitched together with an articulated chassis. Enough

Fig. 10. Load cell for measuring uni-directional tractor rolling resistance.

Fig. 11a. Penetrometer characteristics of fields A, B, and C for rolling resistance tests.

Fig. 11b. Rolling resistance and horsepower required to tow the tractor in three fields.

ground clearance was provided to avoid "bellying" and to make moving over dikes easy. In our tests, the machine, complete with an operator, weighed 331 kg: 181 kg on the front axle and 150 kg on the rear axle.

In irrigated fields with a relatively shallow hard pan, the experimental tiller (Fig. 12) could travel with ease, and tilling was achieved when the wheels were operated at unequal speeds. It could cross dikes which were higher than its wheel diameter without damaging the dikes. In softer fields, better tillage and steering control was achieved by operating the front wheels faster than the rear ones. Further studies are being made.

Fig. 12. Differential-slip lowland tillage using the experimental tiller with independently driven front and rear cage wheels.

Power table thresher

The table-type thresher has a flat, rotating surface which uses the available threshing surface more effectively than do cylinder-type threshers.

The first two prototype table threshers (1968 Annual Report) were designed to deliver the threshed straw all around the periphery of the machine. In these machines straw dropped on the operators' feet and was difficult to remove during operation. A third prototype thresher has been fabricated with a sheet metal housing to convey and deliver the threshed straw to a single location. This machine has two screens, one rotating and the other stationary. The straw and grain are separated on the rotating screen. The straw then drops onto a stationary screen where rubber flaps sweep it towards the straw outlet.

The third prototype had three major flaws. First, although it performed well with dry paddy, it did not deliver the straw properly when the crop was wet. Second, the machine had relatively complex sheet metal components which were difficult to fabricate by hand. Third, the machine was too heavy to be carried into the field by four persons.

The development of a fourth prototype thresher was started to eliminate the drawbacks of the earlier machines. The new machine (Fig. 13) is designed with detachable legs for compact packaging and will be considerably lighter than the third prototype.

Fig. 13. Fourth prototype table-type thresher.

Fig. 14. Tractor PTO-driven multicrop thresher with rotary screen separator.

Tractor PTO-driven thresher

The hold-on type of thresher, such as the IRRI drum thresher (1968 Annual Report), in which paddy is held by the operator during threshing, requires little power, but it has a low output. A tractor-mounted, PTO-driven throw-in type multicrop thresher for standard 30- to 60-hp tractors would be desirable since large tractors are becoming popular in the tropical countries. Such a machine would have good mobility, high output, and a reduced labor requirement—features preferred by custom thresher operators and farmers with larger holdings.

Drawings of a PTO-driven thresher were completed during the year. The thresher (Fig. 14) has a spike-toothed threshing drum. It is designed to deliver the threshed material along

the drum axis rather than at a right angle, as found in conventional threshers. A threshing cylinder velocity of 884 m/min will be achieved at the standard power take-off (PTO) speed of 540 rpm. A set of adjustable baffles inside the cylinder cover will control the duration of threshing in the cylinder. This feature should provide the controls necessary for threshing different crops and crops at various moisture levels.

The thresher has a rotary screen separator which has been successfully used with the IRRI drum thresher and the grain cleaner. The use of a rotary screen separator in threshers, seed cleaners, and stripper-harvesters at the Institute is new and has generated considerable interest among equipment manufacturers. The first prototype machine is being built.

Comparative performance of threshing cylinders

Proper threshing of freshly harvested paddy is important for maximum yields. Three types of threshing cylinders are generally used in rice threshing machines: Wire loop, peg tooth, and rasp bar. A study was undertaken to establish the differences among the three types of cylinders for threshing freshly harvested paddy.

Two series of tests were conducted. In the first, three test stands using the wire-loop, peg-tooth, and rasp-bar cylinders were constructed. The peg-tooth and the rasp-bar cylinders were equipped with concaves; the wire-loop cylinder had no concave, but was equipped with rubber flaps and a sheet-metal housing with a side opening (Fig. 15). During threshing, the rubber flaps moved the grain and straw in an axial direction toward the side opening. Paddy grain and straw that fell into the sheet metal housing during threshing rotated a few times before being discharged through the side opening.

Freshly harvested, mature IR8 paddy with straw 35 cm long (as measured, from the panicle neck) was used throughout the tests. The mean moisture content of the paddy was 24.8 percent (wet basis).

In the second series of tests, the same peg-tooth and rasp-bar test stands were used, but two new wire-loop cylinder test stands, one without concave and the other with a perforated, sheet-metal concave, were added (Fig. 15). In

Fig. 15. Threshing cylinder test stands for comparative performance tests.

wire-loop threshers, paddy is either fed on the topside or the underside of the threshing cylinder. The wire-loop test stand with the perforated, sheet-metal concave was fed from the underside of the cylinder. Freshly harvested IR20 paddy was used throughout the second series of tests. The moisture content of the paddy was 23.5 percent (wet basis).

The effect of the feeding method and the peripheral velocity of the cylinder on threshing performance and grain damage was investigated. Hold-on feeding and throw-in feeding were used in both series of tests. The cylinders were driven by a 55 hp, standard four-wheel tractor through the PTO shaft. Sixteen cylinder peripheral velocities were used in the tests ranging from 274 to 1,417 m/min.

With the throw-in feeding method, an untied bundle of 4 kg paddy with all panicles at the same end was fed evenly into the machine for 16 seconds. With the hold-on feeding method, a 4-kg sample was divided into four bundles of 1 kg each which were individually threshed by holding them onto the cylinders for 4 seconds. The completely threshed paddy (individually detached), the semi-threshed paddy (bunches of two or more kernels), and the unthreshed paddy (paddy retained on the panicles after threshing) were collected separately during each test. The visible seed damage was determined by inspection and by the percentage of paddy milled during threshing. Internal seed damage was determined by the yields of head rice and by a germination test.

Hold-on feeding. In the first series of tests using IR8 paddy (Fig. 16), the rasp-bar and peg-tooth cylinders performed relatively poorly at the slower velocities. At higher velocities, the rasp-bar cylinder and wire-loop, side-delivery cylinder performed slightly better than the peg-tooth cylinder. The performance of the peg-tooth cylinder was less affected by change in cylinder speeds than the other cylinders, but the peg-tooth cylinder gave slightly more semi-threshed paddy. The wire-loop cylinder gave the best overall performance with this method of feeding.

In the second series of tests, with IR20 (Fig. 16), the wire-loop cylinder without concave and the rasp-bar cylinder performed poorly at low

velocities. At intermediate velocities, the wire-loop cylinder with concave and the peg-tooth cylinder performed slightly better than the other two cylinders. At high velocities, all four were satisfactory. The peg-tooth cylinder had the best overall performance in these tests. Although poor in performance at low velocities, the wire-loop cylinder without concave produced the least semi-threshed paddy.

Throw-in feeding. In the first series of tests, the peg-tooth cylinder performed best throughout the range of velocities. The wire-loop, side-delivery cylinder and the rasp-bar cylinder performed poorly, especially below the 808 m/min. It can be concluded that for throw-in feeding, the peg-tooth cylinder is better suited especially at low cylinder velocities.

In the second series of tests, the peg-tooth cylinder again exhibited the best overall performance. The wire-loop cylinder without concave and the rasp-bar cylinder performed poorly. The wire-loop cylinder with concave, however, outperformed the peg-tooth cylinder at low velocities.

The results from both series of tests indicated that high cylinder velocities give less semi-threshed paddy. Except for the wire-loop cylinder without concave, throw-in feeding gave poorer performance than hold-on feeding at low cylinder velocities. It has generally been accepted that throw-in type threshers are better suited for high output than the hold-on types. These tests seem to indicate that users of throw-in type threshers are penalized by higher losses.

Grain damage. For the first series of tests, with IR8, at velocities of up to 655 m/min, none of the three cylinders showed significant milling with either hold-on or throw-in feeding. At 655 m/min, milling began with both feeding methods, but milling increased faster with hold-on feeding. This seems understandable. With hold-on feeding the paddy is stationary during threshing, so the magnitude of the impact is higher than with throw-in feeding at the same peripheral velocity.

At high velocities, the rasp-bar cylinder produced less milled paddy (1.323% at the maximum test velocity) than the other cylinders, possibly because it had a greater cushioning effect. The rasp-bar cylinder was not serrated

Fig. 16. Threshing performance of cylinder test stands with hold-on and throw-in feeding at various cylinder velocities.

Table 1. Performance of the different threshing cylinders tested at various velocities.

Cylinder type	Feed ^a	Cylinder peripheral velocity (m/min)	Unthreshed paddy (%)	Milled paddy at threshing (%)	Head rice yield (%)	Germination (%)
First series of tests (IR8)						
Wire-loop with side delivery	H	655	1.00	0.00	93.8	93.3
	T	1,036	2.4	0.71	80.0	74.2
Peg-tooth	H	884	0.90	0.40	91.5	88.0
	T	960	2.4	0.86	88.9	77.1
Rasp-bar	H	732	1.50	0.14	94.7	87.4
	T	884	2.60	0.70	82.5	65.5
Second series of tests (IR20)						
Wire-loop without concave	H	808	0.7	0.11	97.2	95.8
	T	1,113	20.1	0.64	78.9	88.5
Wire-loop with concave	H	655	1.7	0.22	96.0	93.5
	T	884	1.7	0.38	86.1	92.4
Peg-tooth	H	655	1.6	0.13	97.8	94.8
	T	884	1.1	0.30	93.3	92.7
Rasp-bar	H	808	1.6	0.17	95.0	93.8
	T	1,113	4.4	0.43	85.0	85.4

^a H = hold-on; T = throw-in.

deeply enough to penetrate into the paddy bundle, unlike the peg-tooth cylinder or the wire-loop, side-delivery cylinder.

In the second series of tests, although milling started at 503 m/min with both feeding methods, it did not become significant with any of the four test stands or with either of the feeding methods up to 732 m/min. Here again, the increase in milling with hold-on feeding was greater than with throw-in feeding as the cylinder velocity increased. The rasp-bar cylinder had the best overall performance, although at intermediate velocity the wire-loop cylinder without concave did a little better.

The head rice yield (unbroken grains) decreased as cylinder velocity increased in both series of tests. The differences among the three types of cylinders were not great up to a peripheral speed of 1,113 m/min. The head rice recovery was poorest from the wire-loop cylinder with concave, especially with the throw-in feeding method.

With hold-on feeding, seed germination in the first series of tests was higher with the wire-loop, side-delivery cylinder and the peg-tooth cylinder than with the rasp-bar from above 503 m/min. With throw-in feeding, however, the peg-tooth cylinder gave the poorest performance.

In the second series of tests with IR20 and hold-on feeding, the wire-loop cylinder without concave gave the best germination at all speeds

tested, while the wire-loop cylinder with concave gave the worst. The peg-tooth and rasp-bar cylinders were about even at the intermediate range. With throw-in feeding, the wire-loop cylinder without concave again performed best, while the other cylinders did not differ significantly in their performance at all speeds tested.

The limits set as the objective of the tests were 2.0% maximum unthreshed paddy, 1.0% maximum milled paddy, 85% minimum head grain yield, and 85% seed germination. The performance closest to the operational limits was found at the cylinder velocities indicated in Table 1.

There was a dramatic improvement in the performance of the wire-loop cylinder when a concave was provided for both the hold-on and the throw-in feedings. In the four test stands, the peg-tooth cylinder was outstanding even at relatively low velocities.

Drying and processing research

Accelerated drying of paddy

In the tropics, paddy is generally harvested at a moisture level of 20 to 35 percent and then dried to 14 percent (wet basis) for safe storage. Conventional driers blow hot air at about 38 to 54 C through a mass of stationary or moving grain. If the rate of moisture removal is not

carefully controlled, total milling recovery will drop drastically. Thus the rice must be dried slowly. In conventional driers the rice is dried and tempered alternately several times until it reaches the right moisture content. To reduce the cost of drying, ways must be found to speed it up.

Drying with infra-red heat and conductive methods has been tried in the U.S.A. and elsewhere with rice and other crops.

To find ways to accelerate rice drying, studies were begun to develop background information on drying of paddy with conducted heat. In the preliminary tests, heat was rapidly introduced into paddy kernels by submerging wet paddy in heated oil held for a controlled duration at slightly below the rice-popping temperature—the oil immersion method; by mixing wet paddy in heated sand at temperatures slightly below ones which would make the grains pop—the heated sand method; and by placing wet paddy on a shaking screen held directly over a flame—the mechanical agitation method.

The oil immersion method removed moisture rapidly—15 percent (dry basis) in 15 seconds. Some tests showed increased yields of head rice, too.

The oil absorbed by the husk and the rice kernel was also observed. It was hoped that the oil-soaked husk could be used as fuel for rice driers. Unfortunately, the kernel as well as the husk absorbed the oil.

Preliminary tests with the hot sand and the mechanical agitation methods did not indicate any adverse results and a few milling tests indicated very high head rice yield. The methods were further investigated in two experiments.

Heated sand method. In studies on the heated sand method, wet paddy was mixed with heated sand for periods ranging from 15 to 60 seconds. Subsequently the moisture removed from the paddy was measured. The paddy was mixed with sand in a ratio of 1:20 by weight. Freshly harvested paddy of four varieties, IR8, IR20, C4-63, and Malagkit, were tested.

The wet paddy was carefully cleaned and the initial moisture content was determined by the oven method. Control paddy samples were dried by spreading them on the floor of an air-conditioned room for 24 hours.

Drying tests were conducted by simultaneously pouring 200 g of wet paddy and 4,000 g of heated sand in a flask. The exposure time of the paddy to the sand was recorded after one-half of the paddy had been poured into the flask.

After the desired exposure time, the paddy was separated from the sand with a sieve and then immediately placed in sealed bottles for measurement of the grain temperature. Then the paddy was allowed to cool 10 minutes at ambient temperature before the final moisture content was determined. The treated samples were spread on the floor of an air-conditioned room for 24 hours and then milled.

Figure 17 shows the drying rates and milling recoveries of IR8 and IR20 paddy with a high initial moisture level (32% to 35%) at different initial sand temperatures. The maximum reduction in moisture (approximately 15%) occurred during the first 15 seconds of grain-sand exposure. A similar drying performance was observed with other varieties. During the first 15 seconds of exposure the head rice yield of IR8 increased by about 22 percentage points and that of IR20 by 18 percentage points. Treated IR20 grains became more translucent. IR8 grains changed a little in color and exhibited less white belly than the control samples. With a sand temperature of 220 C and above, the grain changed to a yellowish and finally brownish color depending on exposure time. Slight popping of the paddy was observed at 15 seconds exposure with a sand temperature of 240 C and at 30 seconds with a sand temperature of 200 C.

Exposures longer than 15 seconds resulted in a slight decline in milling recovery and head rice yield. Initial sand temperatures ranging from 195 C to 202 C seemed to give a fairly high rate of moisture removal plus good total milling yield and head rice yield from the two varieties. A similar test with the Malagkit, a glutinous variety, at a high moisture level (31%) indicated results similar to those obtained with IR8 and IR20, but the change in color was more significant with Malagkit.

The unexpected increase in the head rice yield was due to parboiling. This observed phenomenon opens possibilities for the development of a rapid parboiling process. We conclude

Fig. 17. Effect of accelerated drying rate on milling recovery of IR8 and IR20 with high initial moisture content.

that the brief exposure of paddy with a high initial moisture to a high temperature results in parboiling and drying.

Experiments were conducted on paddy with relatively low initial moisture to check if similar results could be obtained. Figure 18 shows that drying IR8 and IR20 with 25 to 26 percent initial moisture levels under similar conditions of time and temperature decreased head rice yield the longer the drying continued. To obtain higher head rice yields with the sand drying process, the paddy rice must contain sufficient moisture.

To further test the validity of these results, variety C4-63 was studied at 26 and 30 percent initial moisture levels. The data showed that a high initial moisture level is essential to increase head rice yield in C4-63, too (Fig. 19).

Paddy is not always harvested with a moisture level high enough for this process. The tests were repeated with pre-soaked paddy. Figure 20 shows the results of pre-soaking IR22 paddy rice at 22 percent initial moisture for 6, 12, and 24 hours at room temperature. Very high milling recovery and head yield were obtained by pre-soaking for 6 to 12 hours. Pre-soaking

Fig. 18. Effect of accelerated drying rate on milling recovery of IR8 and IR20 paddy with low initial moisture content.

for more than 12 hours did not further improve head rice yield.

Mechanical agitation method. Experiments on the mechanical agitation method were performed by placing wet paddy on a metal screen which was shaken over a flame. The shaking action reduced localized heating. At the end of the test the paddy samples were removed from the flame and exposed to ambient air to complete the drying process.

Figure 21 shows that the rate of moisture removal is high in the early stages and is gradually reduced with longer exposure time.

No sudden change in the rate of moisture removal was apparent between 20 to 150 seconds exposure.

The color of the milled rice did not show any change up to 85 C grain temperature. Occasionally, the appearance of the grain improved because it became more translucent. Above 85 C, some yellowing was observed and this intensified with exposure time.

The initial moisture content significantly affected the head rice yield of the three samples (Fig. 22). Paddy with a high initial moisture (34% to 36%) had a higher head rice yield than

Fig. 19. Effect of accelerated drying rate on milling recovery of C4-63 paddy with high and low initial moisture content.

the control for the whole range of exposure time. Paddy with a low initial moisture content, 22 percent, had considerably lower head rice yield than the control sample. An examination of paddy with the higher initial moisture revealed a parboiling effect and the grain was more translucent.

Heated sand vs. mechanical agitation. Moisture seems to be removed faster with the heated sand method than with the mechanical agitation method. Both methods prove that rapid drying and parboiling of paddy is possible if sufficient moisture is initially present in the grain.

Counterflow drying

The shallow-bed, batch-type farm drier has some basic limitations. The grain dries more quickly near the air inlet than near the outlet, and

during at least the latter part of the drying period, air leaves the drier unsaturated, thus the drier fails to use all the available heat. In the counterflow method, with grains other than paddy, the movement of the grain and of the drying air permits the use of an air temperature higher than that in batch drying. The counterflow method continuously removes a layer of grain nearest the air inlet and at the same time adds a fresh layer of wet grain at the air outlet. Thus a greater drying capacity per unit volume is achieved.

A laboratory model of a counterflow drier for paddy was constructed (1968 Annual Report) to evaluate the performance of the counterflow system. The heated air passes from a cone-shaped plenum chamber upwards through a descending grain layer. The grain moves against the drying air to a discharge mechanism located at the bottom of the drying chamber. The grain flow from the hopper maintains a constant grain depth above the plenum chamber.

The relationship of airflow rate, grain-flow rate, and drying air temperature, as expressed

Fig. 20. Effect of pre-soaking on head rice yield during accelerated drying of IR22 paddy.

in terms of moisture-content reduction, milling yield, thermal efficiency, and drying rate, were established. Airflow rates of 170, 255 and 340 m³/hr were blown against a descending grain mass which flowed at rates of 88, 132, and 176 kg/hr for each airflow rate. With these grain-flow or discharge rates, the descending grain was exposed to the drying air for approximately 18, 12, and 9 minutes, respectively. Drying air temperatures of 49, 60, 71, and 82 C were used for each discharge rate.

The total milled rice and head rice yields were significantly affected by the drying air temperature and discharge rate but not by airflow rate. The percentage of total milled rice (Fig. 23) was 69 to 70 percent (98% to 99% of the control) at drying air temperatures up to 60 C for 88 kg/hr, and 71 C for 132 and 176 kg/hr. The percentage of head rice (Fig. 23), based on the weight of total milled rice, did not decrease significantly with drying air temperatures up to 60 C at 88 kg/hr, 71 C at 132 kg/hr, and 82 C at 176 kg/hr. The significant decrease of 49 C with 176 kg/hr, resulted from the relatively longer time the paddy was stored at high moisture content as a result of the slow drying in this treatment.

Thermal efficiency varies inversely with drying air temperature up to 71 C and the number of kilocalories used to evaporate a kilogram of water (Fig. 24) varies directly with drying air temperature up to 71 C. Both were unaffected by airflow and discharge rates.

The heat utilization factor (HUF) was not affected by airflow rate, discharge rate, drying air temperature, or any interaction of these factors. The HUF grand mean was 98 percent; that is, 98 percent of the available heat was used either for drying or increasing the temperature of the paddy.

The 98 percent value and the almost saturated air condition at the exhaust of the drier proved that the drying zone was contained within the 30.5-cm grain layer maintained above the plenum chamber. The maximum drying rate period, which depends solely on the moisture-carrying capacity of the drying air, occurs at the drying zone. Using an equation which is applicable for counterflow drying, and which assumes maximum drying rate, we established the relationship of actual and theoretical drying

Fig. 21. Exposure time versus moisture content for three paddy samples with different initial moisture contents in conducted heat drying of agitated paddy.

Fig. 22. Head rice yield for three paddy samples with different initial moisture contents in conducted heat drying of agitated paddy.

rates for all treatments and passes through the drier. The actual drying rate was 70 to 72 percent of the maximum drying rate.

With an initial paddy moisture content of 22 to 27 percent (dry basis), the drier removed 5 percentage points per pass without reduction

Fig. 23. Total milled rice and head rice as affected by drying air temperature and grain discharge rate.

in head rice yield, with a thermal efficiency of 60 to 70 percent, and at a drying rate of 70 to 72 percent of the maximum drying rate. This indicates that paddy can be more effectively dried by counterflow methods than by conventional methods.

Rotary screen grain cleaner

Cleaners that satisfactorily separate mature paddy grain from immature grain, straw, chaff, dust, and other impurities and that are suitable for developing countries are generally not available. A simple winnower, popular in many Asian countries, consists of a paddle-type blower with a grain hopper mounted so that air from the blower is directed against the uncleaned grain falling from the hopper. The lighter impurities are blown away from the heavy mature grain. In practice, the grain is often recycled through the winnower to achieve satisfactory cleaning.

Such winnowers generally have an output of 200 to 300 kg/hr.

These simple winnowers use variation in the aerodynamic properties of the grain and impurities and depend on a short-duration exposure of grain to a high-velocity airflow. The drawbacks of such winnowers are that some larger-than-grain impurities are difficult to remove pneumatically and that the time that the grain is exposed to the airflow is extremely limited because of the grain's high free-fall velocity.

A simple machine is needed that could mechanically separate the larger-than-grain impurities before subjecting the grain to a pneumatic separation. This principle is widely used in large-capacity seed cleaners popular in the developed countries which are equipped with oscillating screens for mechanical separation. Oscillating screens do not function well when

high amounts of large impurities are present in the grains. Also, driving mechanisms for oscillating screens are expensive and subject to mechanical problems.

The use of a rotary screen offers many advantages over the oscillating screen for a simple grain cleaner for developing countries. The grain-air exposure time can be increased by blowing air on top of a tumbling mass of grain inside a rotary screen. During tumbling, the lighter impurities and empty kernels which tend to collect on top of the heavy, mature grains can be removed by pneumatic methods. A rotary screen grain cleaner being developed at the Institute incorporates mechanical and pneumatic separation in one rotating screen cylinder (Fig. 25).

The machine has a rotating cylindrical member with two concentric screens. An auger feeds dirty grain into the inner screen. The perforations of the inner screen are large enough to screen grain from the straw and other larger-than-grain impurities. The outer screen has perforations small enough to retain the grain while screening the smaller-than-grain impurities. Spiral baffles inside the inner screen move the larger-than-grain trash towards the impurity outlet.

Air is blown through the lower half portion of the annular space between the two screens. As the grain falls from the inner screen and when it is tumbled between the two screens it is pneumatically separated. The outer screen has sliding fins on its inner side which move the grain against the air. Another set of fins helps to tumble the grain properly.

The rate of axial grain movement and the degree of tumbling inside the outer screen cylinder are critical for satisfactory pneumatic cleaning. Too fast an axial grain movement or less tumbling of grain adversely affects the quality of cleaning. Many tests with the two kinds of fins were needed to find the right balance between tumbling and sliding for optimum operation.

The first prototype machine was equipped with a gravity feed arrangement, but bridging in the hopper caused an irregular feeding rate. A positive auger feed was installed to provide a

Fig. 24. Thermal efficiency and number of kilocalories necessary to evaporate a kilogram of water at different drying air temperatures.

Fig. 25. Schematic drawing of the rotary screen grain cleaner.

uniform feeding rate. The use of an axial fan caused the air to swirl, which resulted in uneven distribution of air velocity. Deflecting baffles were installed in the fan housing to minimize air-swirling and to restrict the flow of air in the screening and tumbling region.

The first prototype machine delivered the clean grain in a large can. Initial tests at maximum output revealed that one man had difficulty loading the hopper and putting the cleaned grain into the sacks from the can. The

Fig. 26. Rotary screen grain cleaner in operation.

cleaner was later equipped with a bagging attachment (Fig. 26) making it possible for one person to operate the machine.

Tests were conducted to determine the cleaning output and quality with two rice varieties at different moisture levels (Table 2). A maximum output of over 1,000 kg/hr of paddy was obtained for the Malagkit variety. Generally, the output decreased with an increase in grain moisture. Some bridging was observed when

excessive straw was present in the dirty grain. The mechanism removed all the straw and chaff and most empty grains in a single pass. Light, immature grains, ranging from 0.15 to 0.75 percent of the output, were blown out through the impurity outlet.

The degree of cleanliness and the amount of mature grain delivered with the impurities are interrelated and depend on the airflow. A comparison between test 10 (airflow control fully open) and test 13 (airflow control partially closed) indicates a reduction from 2 to 1 percent in the amount of mature grain delivered with impurities and an increase from 1 to 5 percent of impurities in the cleaned grain due to reduced airflow (Table 2). A similar trend is observed in tests 15 and 16.

A second test was conducted to compare the cleaning capacity and quality of a motorized native winnower with those of the experimental rotary grain cleaner (Table 3). The grain output of the experimental rotary grain cleaner (1,274 kg/hr) was about six times that of the motorized native winnower at comparable cleaning quality.

Work on a second prototype machine has started. The second machine will be equipped

Table 2. Performance data of the experimental rotary grain cleaner on wet paddy of two varieties.

Test no. ^a	rpm			Clean grain output (kg/hr)	Composition of feed materials (%)		Chaff and empty grain removed in 1 pass (%)	Grain in chaff (%)
	Engine	Auger	Drum		Grain	Chaff and empty grains		
Malagkit (23% moisture, wet basis)								
1	2,325	325	18	813	96	4	4	1.1
2	2,490	350	20	876	96	4	3	1.3
3	2,687	378	22	918	96	4	3	2.5
4	2,800	395	22	990	96	4	4	3.2
5	2,350	362	19	963	96	4	3	1.1
6	2,590	390	21	1,017	96	4	4	1.7
7	2,760	420	22	1,014	96	4	2	2.6
Malagkit (30% moisture, wet basis)								
8	2,300	380	18	879	91	9	8	1.1
9 ^b	2,580	430	21	819	91	9	9	2.5
10	2,580	430	21	1,038	91	9	8	1.7
11 ^b	2,780	475	22	849	91	9	N.D. ^d	3.1
12 ^b	2,780	475	22	1,017	91	9	9	3.1
13 ^c	2,580	440	21	1,119	91	9	4	0.8
C4-63 (30% moisture, wet basis)								
14 ^c	2,760	389	22	781	89	11	10	1.9
15 ^c	2,750	435	22	910	89	11	9	2.5
16	2,750	435	22	873	89	11	10	4.7

^a Duration of all tests was 1 min except No. 14: 11 min, No. 15: 10 min, No. 16: 8 min.

^b Bridging of wet paddy occurred at auger intake.

^c Air control partially closed (6 cm from rim's top); other tests (No. 1-12 and 16) with air control fully open.

^d No data taken.

Table 3. Comparative performance of a motorized native wooden winnower (hunkuyan) and the IRRRI experimental rotary grain cleaner on dry paddy seeds (IR662-2-2-7-2-2, 12% moisture).

Cleaner	Test duration (min)	Grain output (kg/hr)	Impurities (% of input)		Grain removed with impurities (% of input)
			Before cleaning	Removed by cleaner	
Native	60	215	7	5	1.7
Experimental ^a	12	1274	7	5	1.3

^a With fully open air control, engine rpm 2,750, auger rpm 430.

with a centrifugal blower to improve air distribution and control. The machine will have a 2 ton/hr cleaning output and would be simpler to fabricate than the first prototype machine. Philippine manufacturers are interested in this machine for use in conjunction with rice mills, grain driers, and threshers. On completion of the second prototype, the machine will be released for trial production in the Philippines.

Economics of mechanization

Survey of Central Luzon and Isabela and Cotabato Provinces

Surveys on mechanization were conducted in Central Luzon, Isabela, and Cotabato. These are among the largest rice-growing regions in the Philippines. Two areas in Cotabato were chosen: Midsayap, an irrigated district, and Tacurong, a rice-corn area.

Rainfall patterns vary from one area to another. The contrast between Central Luzon and Isabela is particularly distinct. While both have an average rainfall of 195 cm, the monsoon rainfall pattern is more pronounced in Central Luzon. In Isabela, annual rainfall has two peaks; thus with good early rain, farmers can grow two rainfed crops. Furthermore, the main harvest in Isabela is later than that of Central Luzon, so mechanized threshing teams from Central Luzon can be brought to the Isabela area. This is currently being done, to some extent, with large McCormick threshers. The rainfall pattern in Cotabato, on the other hand, is more evenly spread throughout the year. The period of relatively high rainfall, however, coincides with that of Central Luzon. Thus, rainfed sites in the

two areas are planted at about the same time.

Correlation of estimated yield with observations on growth of the crop. A number of regressions were run using data from the 1967-1968 surveys. The large number of variables and the limited number of observations made it difficult to draw definite conclusions. The results of the regressions, however, showed that a higher coefficient of determination, and hence a better correlation of variables to yield, was obtained for the irrigated fields. Water control showed up as a significant variable, especially in Laguna.

Weeding. In our first survey of Central Luzon farmers in 1966-1967, some data on weeding practices were collected. One-fourth of the farms were not weeded at all and about three-fourths were weeded only once. At the time of the survey, however, few improved varieties had been introduced. Farmers who have adopted new varieties probably also use the necessary inputs to obtain higher yields.

Table 4 presents a summary of weeding practices gathered from farmers in the 1967-1968 cropyear surveys. Most farmers in the survey practiced weeding. Indications are that the farmers planting improved varieties, especially in Laguna, do more weeding.

Farm labor. To understand the feasibility of mechanization, the demand and supply parameters of labor must be examined. Data

Table 4. Number of farmers who use various weeding methods. Survey of five areas in the Philippines, 1967-1968.

Area	Weeding method					No. of observations ^a
	None used	Hand, once	Rotary, once	Hand, once Rotary, once	Hand, twice	
Laguna	2	13	6	24	4	49 (21)
Central Luzon	28	18	3	5	7	61 (26)
Isabela	—	46	44	14	9	113 (18)
Midsayap (Cotabato)	1	4	37	—	—	42 (38)
Tacurong (Cotabato)	7	20	11	5	4	47 (31)
All areas						
Improved variety	10	4	20	20	3	57 (29)
Local variety	26	58	42	14	13	153 (68)
Mixed variety	2	39	39	14	8	102 (37)
All varieties	38	101	101	48	24	312 (134)

^a Numbers in parentheses refer to the number of farmers who used herbicide in addition to hand and rotary weeding.

Table 5. Average labor input (man-days/ha), irrigated two-crop sites using tractor and carabao, hand-threshed. Laguna, Philippines, wet season, 1967. (n = 20).

Operation	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Total
Seedbed preparation and care	0.3	0.2	1.5	0.2	—	—	—	2.2
Plow	0.2	1.7	1.6	0.2	—	—	—	3.7
Harrow	0.3	1.0	2.8	0.3	—	—	—	4.4
Repair and clean dikes	0.2	0.5	2.2	0.1	—	—	—	3.0
Pull seedlings and transplant	1.0	—	7.7	0.9	—	—	—	9.6
Care of crop	1.5	0.2	4.1	9.4	1.2	—	—	16.4
Harvest	—	—	—	—	—	5.1	12.9	18.0
Thresh	—	—	—	—	—	8.5	13.5	22.0
All operations	3.5	3.6	19.9	11.1	1.2	13.6	26.4	79.3
Operator	1.1	2.0	5.5	3.6	—	—	0.1	12.3
Family	0.7	0.1	2.2	—	—	—	—	3.0
Hired	1.6	1.3	11.0	7.5	1.2	13.6	25.1	61.3
Exchange	0.1	0.2	1.2	—	—	—	1.2	2.7

collected in the surveys show that the demand for labor in farm operations has seasonal peaks. During personal interviews, however, the farmers indicated a shortage of labor only for land preparation. Since hired labor is a cash cost, farmers may be willing to shift from manual to mechanized methods if production costs can be cut.

Table 5 presents data on average labor inputs for all farms in the wet season in Laguna. Out of the 79 man-days, 15 were contributed by the operator and his family. The remaining was hired or exchange labor. Thus there seems to be a great reliance on hired labor in Laguna. The operations requiring a high amount of labor are harvesting and threshing (mostly manual methods), weeding (crop care), transplanting, and, to some extent, land preparation.

Table 6 shows the wet-season labor distribution by category of farm worker for tractor-

prepared and machine-threshed rice farms in the Tacurong region. Of a total labor input of 56 man-days, 13 were contributed by the operator and his family. Transplanting and harvesting were the two operations using the largest amount of hired labor. The seasonal distribution of labor use for two-crop farms using carabao and tractor is shown in Figure 27. Figure 28 compares an irrigated two-crop farm use of labor with that of a rainfed farm. The labor requirement generally was higher in the irrigated farms.

Attitudes towards use of tractors for land preparation. The farmers in the survey areas were asked to indicate their opinion about hiring a tractor for land preparation. Of the 307 farmers interviewed, 75 percent indicated a desire to hire tractors, 12 percent did not want to hire tractors, and the remaining 13 percent did not give an answer. Timely operation was

Table 6. Labor input (man-days/ha), irrigated two-crop farms using tractor, machine-threshed, Tacurong, Cotabato, Philippines, 1967-1968. (n = 17).

Operation	1967								1968			Total	
	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.		Mar.
Seedbed preparation and care	—	1.31	0.58	0.58	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.08
Plow	0.02	0.21	1.24	—	—	0.04	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.51
Harrow	—	0.63	0.33	2.53	—	0.04	—	—	—	—	—	—	3.53
Repair and clean dikes	—	—	0.75	2.81	0.12	0.54	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.22
Pull seedlings and transplant	—	—	1.48	11.95	2.29	—	0.53	—	—	—	—	—	16.25
Care of crop	—	—	—	0.96	3.33	3.49	1.66	0.44	0.03	0.12	—	—	10.03
Harvest	—	—	—	—	—	0.36	0.43	7.93	6.99	—	0.44	—	16.15
Thresh	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.13	0.39	0.74	0.41	0.29	0.01	1.97
All operations	0.02	2.15	4.38	18.44	5.74	4.47	2.75	8.76	7.76	0.53	0.73	0.01	55.74
Operator	—	0.53	1.23	2.85	1.20	1.05	0.46	0.12	0.48	0.02	—	—	7.94
Family	—	0.54	0.52	1.81	0.46	1.50	0.32	—	—	—	—	—	5.15
Hired	0.02	0.65	1.81	13.09	2.36	1.82	1.97	8.29	3.80	0.51	0.73	0.01	35.06
Exchange	—	0.43	0.82	0.69	1.72	0.10	—	0.35	3.48	—	—	—	7.59

Fig. 27. Monthly labor distribution, 9 irrigated 2-crop farms using tractor and 5 using carabao, Laguna, 1967-1968.

Fig. 28. Monthly labor use per hectare, irrigated 2-crop farm sites using tractor and carabao, hand-threshed, compared with rainfed farms using carabao, machine-threshed, Central Luzon, 1967-1968.

the major reason farmers gave for hiring tractors. This observation is interesting since approximately one-third of the pre-harvest labor is associated with plowing and harrowing and usually a reduction in the labor requirement should be a significant reason for mechanizing land preparation. The labor required per hectare for preparing with hand tractors is about one-half of that for carabaos, but the total time required is about one-third to one-fourth. Two men are normally required to operate a hand tractor, however.

Farmers had several other reasons for hiring tractor for plowing and harrowing. Some indicated that they simply had no carabaos or that it was too tedious to use them. Others felt that it was easier to control weeds when tractors are used for land preparation because the weeds

are better incorporated into the soil.

The farmers who did not want to hire a tractor for land preparation gave the following main reasons: They still owned carabaos; they had sufficient supply of family and exchange labor; their farm was too small; the field was too hard and stony; and they lacked cash resources to pay for custom service. A response related to the last reason, and perhaps more significant than the rest, was the feeling that the custom rates for land preparation were too high to be profitable for the farmers. If custom tractor service is to gain acceptance, it seems that the rates must be kept in line with that of hiring a carabao to accomplish similar work. The study indicates that a good potential demand for tractor custom operation is present in the survey areas.

Entomology

Experiments were conducted during 1969 to investigate the ineffectiveness of Diazinon in controlling brown planthoppers at the IRRI farm. The ineffectiveness was found to be due to the biological degradation of the chemical when applied to the paddy water and possibly to the development of resistant strains of the insect. To find better insecticides, studies of several other compounds were continued. Carbofuran was found to be highly effective against stem borers, leafhoppers, and planthoppers. MIPC and Uden were highly effective against leafhoppers and planthoppers, but not against stem borers. Insecticide combinations, like the mixtures of lindane with the new carbamate compounds, such as MIPC and Uden, provided excellent control of stem borers, leafhoppers, and planthoppers. These compounds, when applied to the paddy water at 2 kg/ha at 20-day intervals, produced high yields.

A significant advance in the control of important rice pests is the development of high-yielding resistant varieties. The new variety IR20 possesses a high degree of resistance not only to rice stem borers, but also to several important diseases of the rice plants.

Using one or two insecticidal applications with resistant varieties gives more effective control of insect pests, because the additive effect of resistant varieties and of effective insecticides results in higher yield, and reduces the cost of pest control compared with previous practices. Extensive studies have shown that varieties resistant to one borer species are also resistant to other common species. This suggests that resistant varieties have a broad base of resistance to borers.

Several varieties, other than Mudgo and Pankhari 203, were identified as resistant to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers. Breeding studies revealed that resistance to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers is controlled by a single dominant factor. Most advanced progeny of selected lines of IR8 and of Mudgo have good plant type and other desirable agronomic features besides resistance to brown planthoppers.

Stem borers

The naming of the variety IR20, a progeny of [Peta/3 × Taichung (Native)1] × TKM-6, highlighted the project on varietal resistance to rice stem borers. IR20 (formerly selection IR532E576) possesses the resistance of TKM-6 to stem borers and the short and heavy-tillering plant type of Peta/3 × Taichung (Native)1. In addition, IR20 is highly resistant to the common races of blast in the Philippines, is resistant to bacterial blight, and has field resistance to the tungro virus.

IR20, when grown according to improved cultivation practices, yields about the same as

Table 1. Incidence of rice stem borers and yield of IR532 selections and five check varieties in treated and untreated plots. IRRI, January to April 1969.

Variety or selection	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Grain yield ^a (kg/ha)
No insecticide			
IR532E68	2.3	0.9	5,689 a
IR532E576 (IR20)	1.1	1.0	5,485 ab
IR532E230	1.3	0.4	5,432 ab
IR8	1.7	0.4	5,283 abc
IR532E369	1.5	0.5	5,242 abc
IR532E105	1.7	0.7	4,861 bc
IR532E117	1.7	0.6	4,774 bc
IR532E86	2.0	0.8	4,706 bc
TKM-6	1.7	0.4	4,509 c
T(N)1	3.1	1.3	3,645 d
CP-SLO	2.9	1.7	2,778 d
Rexoro	7.5	5.4	2,000 e
Diazinon at 40 and 80 days after transplanting ^b			
IR532E68	0.1	0.2	7,736 a
IR532E576 (IR20)	0.1	0.1	7,311 ab
IR532E230	0.2	0.0	6,846 bc
IR8	0.1	0.1	6,727 bc
IR532E369	0.1	0.3	6,778 bc
IR532E105	0.1	0.3	6,354 cd
IR532E117	0.1	0.2	6,887 bc
IR532E86	0.1	0.2	7,081 abc
TKM-6	0.2	0.1	5,361 e
T(N)1	0.2	0.1	5,691 de
CP-SLO	0.4	1.7	3,444 f
Rexoro	1.2	4.5	2,388 g
Diazinon at 20-day intervals ^b			
IR532E68	0.08	0.06	7,759 ab
IR532E576 (IR20)	0.08	0.02	7,488 ab
IR532E230	0.04	0.05	7,406 c
IR8	0.14	0.01	7,607 ab
IR532E369	0.17	0.18	7,724 ab
IR532E105	0.10	0.09	7,491 ab
IR532E117	0.04	0.08	8,241 a
IR532E86	0.03	0.10	7,866 a
TKM-6	0.09	0.04	5,455 e
T(N)1	0.14	0.00	6,296 d
CP-SLO	0.20	0.29	4,070 f
Rexoro	0.65	1.70	3,302 g

^a Yields followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level of significance.

^b Diazinon granules were broadcast to the paddy water at 2 kg/ha a.i.

IR8. Without insect control, however, IR20 frequently outyields IR8 by about 1 ton/ha.

The resistance of TKM-6 to stem borers and its incorporation in various hybrids have been discussed in previous annual reports. Screening about 10,000 rice varieties for their resistance to stem borers revealed only moderate levels of resistance, but such resistance has been highly consistent in repeated field experiments. TKM-6 was used in the breeding program because even under the severest insect infestations at the IRRI farm it has not suffered significant damage. In selecting its progeny, this quality of TKM-6 was given top priority. Only the lines which possessed it and, in addition, had field tolerance to common plant diseases at IRRI and improved plant type with better quality grain were selected. Thus IR20 carries a broad base of insect and disease resistance along with a potential for high yield and good-quality grain. These qualities should contribute significantly to increased rice production, particularly where insect pests have been major problems. Although the moderate level of IR20's resistance to borers must be supplemented with insecticides to ensure good control of pests, such varietal resistance should play a role in increasing grain yields at all levels of pest infestation.

Resistance of IR532 lines

From experiments conducted in 1968, seven IR532 lines (TKM-6 is one parent in the cross IR532) were selected and evaluated, along with some resistant and susceptible checks, for insect resistance and yielding ability under various levels of insect control: No insecticide, Diazinon applied at 40 and at 80 days after transplanting, and Diazinon applied every 20 days from transplanting to harvesting.

Although the infestation of stem borers was low, all lines including IR8 had significantly lower percentages of dead hearts and white heads than the susceptible check, Rexoro. IR20 had the lowest dead heart incidence, followed by IR532E576 (Table 1). IR20 and a few other lines produced the high grain yields in all the three treatments. Yields of the plots that received two Diazinon treatments were only slightly higher than the yields of plots treated every 20 days. Although TKM-6 and IR532E68 showed similar

Table 2. Rice stem borer and brown planthopper infestation of different varieties treated with two insecticides at 2 kg/ha a.i. IRRI, August to December 1969.

Variety	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Brown plant-hoppers (no./10 plants)	Virus (%)	Plant height (cm)	Yield (kg/ha)
No insecticide						
IR20	3.5	4.9	48.0	5.3	98.0	3,652
TKM-6	2.2	3.3	33.6	3.7	118.8	3,189
IR8	4.7	4.2	31.1	38.6	82.9	2,595
Mudgo	6.0	2.5	4.5	3.7	114.5	2,205
T(N)1	5.7	5.1	39.4	32.1	78.8	2,117
DV 139	6.1	1.9	^a	4.9	114.8	2,106
Taitung 16	8.4	15.6	20.0	66.2	90.3	607
Rexoro	29.9	16.6	14.5	35.3	124.0	80
MIPC						
IR20	3.5	6.9	33.9	4.9	99.6	3,729
TKM-6	3.5	1.6	24.9	3.4	104.5	2,999
IR8	5.2	4.4	34.7	33.1	84.2	2,687
Mudgo	4.6	2.8	6.5	15.0	114.6	1,879
T(N)1	5.4	7.5	33.4	49.3	81.1	1,899
DV 139	3.4	1.2	^a	1.8	113.5	2,744
Taitung 16	4.2	11.1	27.8	67.1	102.8	843
Rexoro	22.0	15.9	14.9	59.0	123.9	104
Lindane						
IR20	0.7	3.4	66.1	4.0	101.2	4,131
TKM-6	1.1	1.1	87.5	3.4	121.0	3,707
IR8	2.6	1.9	48.2	10.9	88.3	4,261
Mudgo	1.5	1.0	7.5	7.5	124.3	2,795
T(N)1	1.7	1.9	43.1	12.5	87.6	3,912
DV 139	3.6	1.2	^a	4.9	123.0	2,544
Taitung 16	2.1	2.5	37.2	64.0	103.4	1,454
Rexoro	3.5	20.2	18.9	41.8	134.3	317

^a Lodged severely before brown planthopper observation.

responses, most other test lines showed distinct yield increases as insecticide treatments were increased. This indicates differences in their levels of insect resistance.

In several experiments, under intense insect infestations, IR20 suffered less damage and produced higher yields than most of the other test varieties. The results of two such experiments are summarized in Figure 1. These experiments were aimed at studying the natural population dynamics of common pests on test varieties. No insecticidal treatment was made. There was a severe insect infestation and a high incidence of grassy stunt virus in both experiments. IR20 demonstrated its over-all resistance by yielding at least 1,000 kg/ha more than IR8 and the other test varieties.

The role of the varietal resistance of IR20 in insect pest control was further investigated by growing the variety along with seven other varieties under different levels of insect control. In one treatment, lindane (gamma-BHC), which

controls stem borers, but not brown planthoppers, was used, and in another treatment, MIPC, which controls brown planthoppers, but not stem borers, was used. Both insecticides were applied as granules to the paddy water at 2 kg/ha at 20-day intervals.

The resistant varieties consistently had low insect infestations and they gave higher yields on all plots than other varieties, whether treated with insecticides or not (Table 2).

In the untreated and MIPC-treated plots, IR20 yielded 3,600 kg/ha as a result of low percentages of dead hearts, white heads, and virus-infested plants, compared with the susceptible variety Rexoro which yielded 80 kg/ha. Lindane gave good control of rice stem borers in the field, but not of brown planthoppers. The hopper population was not high enough to cause hopper burn on the susceptible varieties, however. Generally, the yields of all varieties treated with lindane increased, but the yield increase of the resistant varieties was not significant.

These results illustrate the effectiveness of resistant varieties in reducing the insect infestation and in giving high yields at any level of insect population.

Fig. 1. Yields of four rice varieties in the dry season (February to June) and in the wet season (June to November) under natural insect infestation. IRRI, 1969.

Resistance of IR580 lines

Another line that has shown promise in combining resistance to stem borers with improved plant type is IR580 (IR8 × TKM-6). IR580 plant selections were tested in field experiments during the dry and wet seasons. Selections tested in the dry season were in the F₇ generation; those tested in the wet season were in the F₈ generation. Several possessed the same broad base of insect and disease resistance as that of TKM-6 and had excellent plant types, but all lacked good-quality grains. These will be turned over to the Varietal Improvement Department for use in their breeding program.

Cross-resistance to four species of stem borers

Field evaluations of rice varieties for their resistance to stem borers have yielded data primarily on striped stem borers, which constitute the major species of stem borers at IRRI. This species has been used in all re-evaluation greenhouse experiments. Resistant and susceptible varieties have been therefore selected

primarily on the basis of their reaction to striped rice borers.

To test the susceptibility of these varieties to several species of stem borers, field tests were conducted at three locations in the Philippines: IRRI, at which the major species is *Chilo suppressalis*; Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, at which the major species are *Sesamia inferens* in the dry season and *Tryporyza incertulas* in the wet season; and Iloilo City at which, in the dry season, the major species are *C. suppressalis* and *T. innotata*. All species were also evaluated in the greenhouse at IRRI except *T. innotata* which is not known to occur in Luzon. *T. innotata* was investigated in a greenhouse at Visayas Experimental Station, Iloilo City.

Plants of 16 varieties were transplanted at 25 x 25 cm. The incidence of dead hearts was recorded 20, 50, and 80 days after transplanting; white heads were counted at harvest. Individual tillers of 10 random hills selected from each plot 50 and 80 days after transplanting were dissected to determine populations of larvae and pupae.

Fig. 2. Cross-comparisons of resistance in rice varieties to four species of stem borers.

Table 3. Populations of stem borer larva and pupa in 16 rice varieties^a IRRI, 1968-69.

Variety	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	<i>Tryporyza innotata</i>	<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>	Composite grading for all species ^b
Pankhari 203	39.2	6.5	95.8	28.3	72.7
Mudgo	31.9	10.1	117.7	16.3	72.2
Paimat	45.4	2.6	119.5	22.1	65.9
DV 139	73.1	6.1	44.2	20.0	65.3
Milfor (6)2	41.9	11.4	69.4	9.2	61.2
RDR 2	40.1	4.9	111.7	12.1	58.5
Binolayangun	40.2	5.3	92.2	13.2	56.3
MTU 19	47.1	6.4	45.6	18.3	55.9
Rexoro	31.4	6.8	69.0	17.1	55.3
Su Yai 20	39.0	10.7	21.6	12.2	52.2
Muey Nawng 62 M	30.1	4.2	91.3	14.5	51.6
PTB 10	29.6	9.0	49.5	8.8	48.1
IR8	42.4	5.6	46.8	9.5	44.5
Chianan 2	29.8	6.7	42.0	10.9	43.4
Taitung 16	20.2	6.6	37.6	7.5	35.9
TKM-6	35.0	3.5	25.7	6.2	30.5

^a Each value is the total of five dissections and the mean of four replications. All are transformed values based on the relative damage potential of different larval size groups.

^b Sum of relative larval population of all species on a variety.

Based on these data, eight varieties were selected for greenhouse evaluations. Each was transplanted in pots at two to three seedlings per pot. About 40 days after transplanting, each pot was thinned to 10 tillers and infested with 10 newly hatched borer larvae. The borer damage to the tillers was recorded frequently. Twenty days after infestation all tillers were dissected to determine the number of surviving larvae and their weights.

Highly significant differences were found in the dead heart incidences of the varieties in experiments conducted at all three locations. The data from these experiments are summarized in Figure 2 which shows that varieties resistant to one species tended to be resistant to the other species of borers as well. The overall performances of the varieties at different locations had highly significant correlations. The varieties Rexoro, Milfor-6(2), Binaloyangun, Muey Nawng 62 M, Pankhari 203, and Paimat were susceptible to all borer species. The other 10 varieties were moderately to highly resistant. Some of the 10 showed differential susceptibility to borer species. Although MTU 19 and Mudgo were moderately susceptible to *T. innotata* and Taitung 16 and DV 139 to *S. inferens*, all four were resistant to other species. TKM-6, PTB 10, and Su Yai 20 had the lowest percentages of dead hearts in all experiments.

Generally the incidence of white heads in these

experiments was inconsistent and was not correlated with the incidence of dead hearts. Some varieties like TKM-6 and Su Yai 20 had low incidences of dead hearts and white heads. Others like Taitung 16 and Chianan 2 had low dead heart counts, but suffered heavily from white heads.

Except for *T. innotata* which was recorded only in Iloilo, all other species were recorded in all three locations. Therefore, the over-all population of a particular species on a variety was determined by adding all larvae and pupae of that species recovered from all five experiments. Also, because early-instar larvae generally suffer higher mortality than late-instar larvae, weighted values were assigned to different instar stages. These calculations revealed highly significant differences in the populations of different borer species on different varieties (Table 3). Again, varieties that were susceptible or resistant to one borer species generally reacted in the same way to other species (Fig. 2). Also, varieties that had fewer dead hearts harbored small larval populations (Table 4), except Mudgo, Pankhari 203 and DV 139, which, in spite of low dead-heart incidence, had large larval populations. These two varieties are tolerant to infestations of stem borers.

In greenhouse experiments, the different species of borer larvae varied significantly in

Table 4. Survival, larval weight, and damage caused by four species of stem borers on eight selected rice varieties (averages for four borer species):^a

Variety	Average larval weight (mg)	Insect survival (%)	Dead hearts ^b (%)	Index ^c
Rexoro	93.6	75.3	80.6	250
Pankhari 203	90.5	92.3	54.8	238
IR8	79.8	70.2	81.2	231
Mudgo	73.7	88.9	46.8	210
DV 139	66.7	84.8	52.0	204
Taitung 16	49.8	62.8	78.2	191
Chianan 2	47.5	55.4	83.4	187
TKM-6	50.9	67.8	53.5	172

^a Figures represent relative values calculated separately for each species based on the most susceptible variety whose value is considered as 100.

^b Caused by 10 introduced borers.

^c Sum of values for average larval weight, insect survival, and dead hearts.

their survival, larval weight, and damage to different varieties. Figure 3 shows the differences in their larval weights. These differences are comparable to differences in dead hearts caused by them or to differences in their larval populations on different varieties in field tests (Fig. 2 and Table 3). The over-all reaction of the test varieties in greenhouse experiments to all four borer species is presented in Table 4.

Thus varieties resistant to one species were also resistant to the other common borer species. This indicates that these varieties have a broad base of resistance to borers.

Brown planthopper studies

A high level of resistance to brown planthoppers was previously detected in Mudgo during the screening of about 1,000 selected rice varieties (1967 and 1968 Annual Reports). To identify additional sources of resistance, another 5,000 varieties were screened in field plots. These were planted in unreplicated 5-m rows, but a heavy insect infestation during the experiment led to the rejection of most of the susceptible varieties.

The varieties selected from this test were further evaluated for resistance by mass screening in the greenhouse. In the tests, about 30 varieties were observed to be almost as resistant to brown planthoppers as Mudgo. Subsequent experiments revealed that several of these varieties were distinctly non-preferred by the brown planthopper. Furthermore, the percentage of insects caged on them that died was significantly higher than the percentage on susceptible varieties (Table 5).

All 403 japonica rice varieties that were tested for resistance to brown planthoppers were highly susceptible. Of the 282 selections included in the Varietal Improvement Department's advanced yield trials, 11 were moderately resistant. In crosses specifically made for resistance to brown planthoppers, however, a large number of lines were identified as resistant. For example, from IR1330 (IR8 x [Leuang Twang x E K 1263]), 105 F₃ lines were resistant, 103 were intermediate, and 42 were susceptible. These figures can not be used for interpreting

Fig. 3. Weights of 20-day-old borer larvae on selected rice varieties.

inheritance of resistance because the lines were selected rather than random samples.

Causes of resistance in Mudgo

The 1968 Annual Report showed that the insects caged on Mudgo suffered high mortality, lost weight, secreted little honeydew, had underdeveloped ovaries (Fig. 4), and were unable to build up populations. They did not encounter mechanical barriers when feeding on Mudgo; moreover, a higher percentage of their stylet sheaths terminated in vascular bundles in Mudgo than in the susceptible variety, Taichung (Native)1. It was then suspected that the Mudgo plants either possess some feeding repellent for the brown planthopper or they lack a feeding stimulus (or stimuli) for this insect. This hypothesis was supported by data obtained during 1969.

Varietal preferences of planthoppers. Twenty potted plants each of IR8, Taichung (Native)1, and Mudgo were placed in a completely randomized design in a field plot spaced 80-cm apart. The plants were exposed to natural infestations of brown planthoppers 30 days after transplanting. On 10 random plants of each variety, the number of planthoppers present was recorded daily. On the other 10 plants, insects were counted at 5-day intervals. The insects were removed from all plants after each observation.

Daily observations revealed that significantly more (at the 5% level) brown planthoppers

Fig. 4. Differences in the ovary development of newly emerged brown planthoppers after being caged for 3 days on Taichung (Native)1 (top) and on Mudgo (bottom).

Table 5. Preference of female brown planthoppers for different rice varieties, IRRI, May 1969^a

IRRI acc. no.	Variety	Origin	Female brown plant-hoppers	
			(no./plant)	Freshly hatched nymphs ^b (no./plant)
6300	Thella Garikasannavari SLO 12	India	4.5	59.7
6365	Dalwa (Sannam) MTU 15	India	6.5	80.0
6400	Manavari CO22	India	9.5	107.8
6303	Karsamba Red ASD7	India	13.5	105.1
6663	Mudgo	India	15.5	97.4
6218	Kayama MGL2	India	36.0	112.7
105	Taichung (Native)1	Taiwan	77.5	210.7
10320	IR8	Philippines	99.5	363.1

^a Average of 20 plants per variety.

^b Seven days after exposing the plant to the brown planthopper.

migrated to IR8 than to Mudgo. Taichung (Native) 1 had more insects than Mudgo, but the differences were not significant. When sampled every 5 days (an interval which gives an indication of an insect's ability to locate a host and then stay on it), nearly 90 percent of all insects were found on IR8 or on Taichung (Native)1 plants. Only 7 percent of the females and 13 percent of the males were recovered from

Table 6. Number of brown planthoppers collected during 16 days on potted plants of different rice varieties.

Insects collected	Insects (%) collected on		
	Mudgo	IR8	Taichung (N)1
Daily ^a			
206 (females)	21	47	32
30 (males) ^b	30	53	17
At 5-day intervals ^c			
1034 (females)	7	49	45
309 (males)	12	48	40

^a Average of daily samples collected during 16 days.

^b Possibly the number of insects attracted is too small to show any trend for host preference.

^c Average of three samples collected during 15 days.

Mudgo plants (Table 6). So, although planthoppers did not differ much in their preference for plants on which to alight, they did not stay on Mudgo for sustained feeding.

Similarly, when adult planthoppers were introduced into a cage containing these varieties in a greenhouse, almost all females settled on either IR8 or Taichung (Native)1 within 24 hours after release (Fig. 5). Again, the differences in varietal preference were not apparent within the first 6 hours after release. Generally, the host preference exhibited by the male insects was similar to that of the female insects, but the males were more mobile. Thus both male and female planthoppers preferred IR8 and Taichung (Native)1 to Mudgo plants for sustained feeding. This further indicates a difference in the sap quality of Mudgo.

Sugar and amino acids in test varieties. One-month-old Mudgo, IR8, and Taichung (Native)1 plants were dried at room temperature and then ground to fine powder. Lipoidal materials were extracted first with chloroform and then with 80-percent ethanol. The ethanol extract was dried, redissolved in distilled water, and centrifuged to remove insoluble materials. The supernatant fluid was analyzed for sugars and amino acids by paper chromatography. A mixture of butanol, acetic acid, and water (4:1:2 v/v/v) was used as the solvent. Aniline-hydrochloride was used for detecting sugars, and ninhydrin for detecting amino acids. The relative concentration of these constituents in the different varieties was determined colorimetrically with anthrone for sugars and with ninhydrin stannous chloride for amino acids.

The main sugar in these varieties was sucrose,

with traces of glucose and fructose. Mudgo and IR8 had the same sugar content; Taichung (Native)1 had somewhat less (Table 7). Thus the differences in the susceptibility of these varieties to planthoppers were not related to their sugar contents. But the total amino acid concentration of these varieties varied widely, being particularly low in Mudgo plants. Although qualitatively all three varieties contained the same amino acids, the asparagine content of Mudgo plants was much lower than that of the others (Fig. 6).

Preference of planthoppers for sucrose and amino acids. The stimulatory feeding effect of sucrose and 10 amino acids was tested using the apparatus shown in Figure 7. The lower tip of one of the filter paper strips, inside a plastic cylinder, was dipped in the test compound while the tip of the other strip was dipped in distilled water. Through capillary action, the test materials kept the strips moist. Adult brown planthoppers (10 males and 10 females) were then placed in each cylinder and the number of insects on each filter paper was recorded periodically. A 5-percent sucrose solution and 1-percent solutions of the 10 amino acids were thus evaluated in separate experiments. Of the compounds tested, sucrose and asparagine had a distinct stimulatory effect on the insect's feeding.

Fig. 5. Distribution of brown planthoppers on resistant and susceptible hosts. Macropterous adults were released into a cage containing the three varieties.

Fig. 6. Amino acid composition of the three rice varieties, Mudgo, IR8, and Taichung (Native)1.

In separate tests the female planthoppers exhibited strong attraction to asparagine. This suggests that the brown planthopper's non-preference of Mudgo for feeding could be due to the variety's lower asparagine content, but this does not explain the non-preference of the males. The biochemical basis of insect resistance is often complex. Lower asparagine content in Mudgo may be just one aspect of resistance.

Green leafhopper studies

Studies on the green leafhopper (*Nephotettix impicticeps* Ishihara) revealed that unlike the brown planthopper which suffers high mortality and fails to complete its life cycle at 33 C or higher, the green leafhopper, despite its shorter life cycle span, completes its development even at 35 C. At this temperature, however, the durations of the egg and the nymphal stages were considerably prolonged (Fig. 8 and 9) and the adults had shorter life spans (Fig. 10). Nevertheless, these data reveal that this species can maintain populations at temperatures as high as 35 C.

Table 7. Relative concentrations of sugars and free amino acids in different rice varieties as determined by their light-absorbance in a spectrophotometer. IRRI, 1969.

Variety	Sugars		Free amino acids	
	Absorbance at 625m μ	Ratio	Absorbance at 570m μ	Ratio ^a
Mudgo	0.24	1.0	0.09	1.0
IR8	0.24	1.0	0.16	1.8
T(N)1	0.19	0.8	0.33	3.7

^a Of light absorbance with and without the sample.

Generally, the green leafhopper infests the upper parts of the plants while the brown planthopper remains near the base of the plant. The green leafhopper, however, lays most of its eggs on the leaf sheaths near the base of the plants rather than on the upper parts of the plant. In greenhouse experiments 65 percent of all the eggs laid were on the first leaf sheath, 11 percent on the second leaf sheath, and 24 percent on the third leaf sheath. Furthermore, 77 percent of the eggs laid on the first leaf sheath were within 4 cm

Fig. 7. Apparatus used to study the feeding preference of planthoppers for different solutions. A, test solutions; B, distilled water; C, filter paper; D, glass rod to suspend the filter papers; E, wire gauze; and F, translucent plastic cylinder.

Fig. 8. Duration of egg stage of *Nephotettix impicticeps* at different temperatures. IRR1, 1969.

of the water in the pot containing the test plants. Thus insecticide must reach the base of rice plants for effective control.

Varietal resistance

The population of green leafhoppers in fields at IRR1 is generally too low to evaluate varietal resistance to this pest effectively. Tests for resistance are made only in the greenhouse using mass screening techniques.

A thousand rice varieties were tested for their resistance to the green leafhopper. The varieties found resistant in these experiments were further evaluated for their antibiosis to the pest by caging a uniform number of insects on individual plants. This led to the identification of 25 varieties which possessed a level of resistance to green leafhoppers almost equal to that of IR8 and Pankhari 203. In a subsequent test, 20-day-old plants of a few selected varieties from these additional varieties and resistant and susceptible checks were caged individually with 100 second-instar green leafhopper nymphs. Such heavy infestations of seedlings seldom occur in nature. The insects caged on most of the varieties suffered very high mortality and caused barely noticeable damage symptoms, but they had high survival on susceptible plants which they eventually killed (Fig. 11).

The varieties causing high mortality of green leafhoppers were generally less preferred by the nymphs as well as by the adult insects.

Causes of resistance

The varieties Pankhari 203 and IR8, which are highly resistant to the green leafhopper, were used in a series of experiments on resistance. In one experiment, individual plants of IR8, Mudgo, and Taichung (Native) 1 (used as susceptible check) were planted in 25-cm diameter clay pots. When these plants were 10 days old, 30 green leafhopper nymphs were released in each pot and the presence of these insects on different plants was recorded periodically. All five nymphal instars were thus tested for their host preference.

In all tests, the insects showed a very strong preference for Taichung (Native) 1 plants. Few insects were recorded on the resistant varieties. Figure 12 shows the preferences of fifth-instar nymphs. The preferences of the first- through fourth-instar nymphs were similar. No mechanical barrier in resistant plants prevents the

Fig. 9. Duration of nymphal stage of *Nephotettix impicticeps* at different temperatures. (Sixty insects were observed at each temperature. Humidity: 70 to 100% R.H. Photoperiod: 16 hours/day.) IRR1, 1969.

Fig. 10. Life span of *Nephrotettix impicticeps* females at different constant temperatures. IRRI, 1969.

green leafhoppers' proboscises from reaching the proper feeding sites in Mudgo plants. This was determined by studying microtomic sections of the insects' salivary sheaths in reared and susceptible hosts. Furthermore, the green leafhoppers did feed on resistant plants—they gained weight (Fig. 13). In contrast, brown planthoppers lost weight on Mudgo, although the amounts of honeydew excretion were greater on susceptible hosts than on resistant hosts. Since the green leafhoppers gained weight, apparently they did more feeding on susceptible hosts than on resistant varieties. Whether this was due to lesser amounts of food ingested or due to differences in the plants' nutritive value is being further investigated.

Inheritance of resistance to planthoppers and leafhoppers

Studies begun in 1968 on the inheritance of the resistance of Mudgo to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*, and of Pankhari 203 to the

green leafhopper, *Nephrotettix impicticeps*, were continued in cooperation with one of the geneticists. Last year's results had indicated that the resistance of Mudgo to brown planthoppers might depend upon a single genetic factor.

The technique for testing hybrid populations against the two insects was standardized. It consists of planting the test material in rows about 5-cm apart in wooden flats 60 x 45 x 10 cm. Normally, a flat accommodates 12 or 13 rows, each 45-cm long. In F_2 tests, three rows (the second row from each end and the center row) are planted to the parent varieties with each parent occupying half the row. Because all test seedlings should be infested at the same stage of growth and development, the F_2 seeds and parental varieties are first germinated in petri dishes and 25 to 30 germinating seeds are spaced uniformly in rows in the wooden flat.

In F_3 tests, the hybrid lines and parental varieties are seeded directly in rows about 20-cm long and obtained by partitioning the 45-cm row length in the middle. Twenty-four lines are accommodated in a single flat. Each line has an

Fig. 11. Effect of infesting 20-day-old seedlings of some resistant and susceptible rice varieties with 100 second-instar *Nephotettix impicticeps*. IRRRI, July 1969.

average of about 25 seedlings. The number of lines per flat may be reduced to 20 to avoid overcrowding. One row of each of the susceptible and resistant parents is interspersed at random for each group of 8 or 10 rows of the hybrid material. The material is infested with insects at the one-leaf stage immediately after germination.

To find out if the insects at different stages of development are equally able to discriminate between resistant and susceptible seedlings, single seedlings of seven varieties were planted in pots. There were four treatments, corresponding with stages of insect development: first-instar and fifth-instar brown planthoppers and second-instar and fifth-instar green leafhoppers. Each treatment was replicated four times.

Before insect infestation, the 11-day-old seedlings in each pot were covered with a cylindrical plastic cage provided with nylon mesh ventilators. Seventy insects were introduced into each cage and the number of insects on each seedling was counted 2 or 3 days after infestation, before any seedling showed signs of wilting. Most fifth-instar insects had become adults by this time. The results (Table 8) show that the pattern of distribution of early-instar nymphs on resistant and susceptible seedlings was generally similar to the pattern of distribution of the fifth-instar nymphs and adult insects on those seedlings.

In our genetic studies, the seedlings were infested with insects about 7 days after seeding. The insect populations used for infestation generally consisted of third-instar to fifth-instar

Table 8. Distribution of green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers on seedlings of different rice varieties in a caged pot 3 days after infestation^a

Variety	Brown planthoppers (%)		Green leafhoppers (%)	
	1st instar	5th instar	2nd instar	5th instar
T(N)1	19	25	24	23
Mudgo	6	8	46	31
IR8	19	18	1	3
Pankhari	25	24	2	3
ASD 7	7	8	2	3
CO22	11	6	23	35
PTB 18	13	11	2	2

^a Except fifth-instar green leafhoppers which were counted 2 days after infestation.

nymphs, though sometimes a mixture of nymphs and adults was also used. Usually, seven to eight insects were enough to distinguish a resistant seedling from a susceptible one. If the test material is exposed to an adequate insect population, susceptible seedlings start yellowing and ultimately wilt and die in 1 to 2 weeks. The final reaction is recorded when the seedlings of the susceptible parent are either dead or wilted. A scale of 0 to 5 is used to record the reaction: 0 = No visible damage (highly resistant); 1 = Partial yellowing of the first leaf (resistant); 2 = Partial yellowing of the first and second leaves (moderately resistant); 3 = Pronounced yellowing and slight stunting (intermediate); 4 = Signs of wilting and severe stunting

Fig. 12. Preferences of fifth-instar *Nephotettix impicticeps* nymphs for three varieties.

(susceptible); 5 = Dead (highly susceptible).

When infested at the one-leaf stage, young, susceptible seedlings are markedly stunted.

Fig. 13. Range of increase in body weight of *Nephotettix impicticeps* after feeding on different rice varieties. (Nymphs fed for 4 hours; adults for 24 hours). IRRI, 1969.

Table 9. Classification of F₂ seedlings of crosses involving Mudgo and a susceptible variety for reaction to the brown planthopper.

Variety or cross	No. of seedlings					Total	R ^b	S ^c	P value for 3:1
	Reaction type ^a								
	0&1	2	3	4	5				
T(N)1	—	—	—	3	42	45			
Mudgo	43	1	—	—	1	45			
T(N)1 x Mudgo F ₂	198	6	23	38	49	314	227	87	0.25—0.30
Mudgo	44	—	1	—	—	45			
Pankhari	—	—	—	6	39	45			
Mudgo x Pankhari F ₂	166	35	28	35	35	299	229	70	0.50—0.55

^a 0 = highly resistant; 1 = resistant; 2 = moderately resistant; 3 = intermediate; 4 = susceptible; 5 = highly susceptible.
^b Resistant group: Reaction types 0 and 1, 2, 3.
^c Susceptible group: Reaction types 4, 5.

Many fail to develop a second leaf. Stunting is more apparent in infestations of brown planthoppers than in infestations of green leafhoppers, however.

Random F₂ populations of the crosses T(N)1 x Mudgo and Mudgo x Pankhari were tested for their reaction to brown planthoppers. T(N)1 and Pankhari are susceptible and Mudgo is resistant to the insects. The segregation for resistance and susceptibility for both crosses was in a 3:1 ratio (Table 9). Although resistance was dominant, seedlings with less resistance than that of Mudgo were observed in both crosses. This could be due to the combined effect of incomplete dominance and modifying factors. Some F₂ seedlings showed an intermediate type of reaction (type 3) and these were grouped with the resistant class for interpretation of results.

The F₂ results were confirmed by studying F₃ breeding behavior. In a random F₂ population of the Mudgo x T(N)1 cross grown in the field in

the 1968 wet season, 10 of 161 plants were killed by a severe infestation of brown planthoppers, so seed could be harvested from only 151 plants. Some seed was used for a field study of the F₃ progeny. Seed of only 92 plants remained available for inheritance studies in the greenhouse.

The breeding behavior of 92 F₃ progeny for brown planthopper reaction (Table 10) did not produce the expected 1:2:1 ratio apparently because this sample was no longer random after a part of the susceptible F₂ population was eliminated in the field. Consequently, the data on the 92 F₃ lines were supplemented by testing F₄ progenies of the 59 F₂ plants whose F₃ generation was grown in the field in the absence of a severe infestation of brown planthoppers. Also, the 10 F₂ plants that had been killed by brown planthoppers in the field were assumed to be homozygous susceptible. The combined data were close to a 1:2:1 ratio. A random sample of 105 F₃ lines of the Mudgo x Pankhari cross was also tested and the results confirmed that Mudgo possesses one major gene for resistance to brown planthoppers (Table 10).

Mudgo is susceptible to the green leafhopper. A sample of 664 F₂ seedlings of its cross with Pankhari, which is resistant to the green leafhopper, was tested for reaction to the insect in the greenhouse. The segregation for resistant and susceptible seedlings produced a 3:1 ratio (Table 11). This was supported by the breeding behavior of 92 F₃ lines of the same cross (20 homozygous resistant, 53 segregating, and 19 homozygous susceptible) which agreed with a 1:2:1 ratio (P = 0.30-0.35). Thus Pankhari's resistance to green leafhoppers also depends upon one major dominant genetic factor.

Table 10. Reaction to the brown planthopper of F₃ and F₄ lines of the cross Mudgo x T(N)1 and F₃ lines of Pankhari x Mudgo.

Cross	Gener-ation	No. of lines			Total	P value for 1:2:1
		Resist-ant	Segre-gating	Sus-ceptible		
Mudgo x T(N)1	F ₃	33	45	14	92	
	F ₄	9	35	15	59	
	F ₂ (s) ^a	—	—	10	10	
Total		42	80	39	161	0.90—0.95
Pankhari x Mudgo	F ₃	25	56	24	105	0.75—0.80

^a Susceptible F₂ plants that were so badly damaged by hopper burn in the field that no seed could be obtained from them.

Insecticides

Rice stem borers, leafhoppers, planthoppers, and the rice whorl maggot occur regularly at IRRI and must be controlled to get high rice yields. A major outbreak of brown planthoppers occurred this year at the IRRI farm. Diazinon which provided excellent control of this pest in the past was ineffective. Microorganisms which developed after previous Diazinon treatments appear to be degrading Diazinon rapidly in

Table 11. Reaction of F₂ seedlings of the cross Mudgo x Pankhari to the green leafhopper.

Variety or cross	No. of plants					Total	R ^b	S ^c	P value for 3:1
	Reaction type ^a								
	0&1	2	3	4	5				
Mudgo	—	—	1	17	72	90	1	89	
Pankhari	83	—	5	—	—	88	88	—	
Mudgo x Pankhari F ₂	427	34	25	27	131	644	486	158	0.80—0.85

^a 0 = highly resistant; 1 = resistant; 2 = moderately resistant; 3 = intermediate; 4 = susceptible; 5 = highly susceptible.
^b Resistant group: Reaction types 0 and 1, 2, 3.
^c Susceptible group: Reaction types 4, 5.

paddy fields. Studies to determine whether a Diazinon-resistant strain of brown planthoppers has developed are under way.

Many insecticides were evaluated in field and greenhouse experiments for their effectiveness in controlling these pests. Studies aimed at identifying compounds for brown planthopper control were emphasized. As foliar sprays in greenhouse tests, only MIPC and vamidothion killed more than 90 percent of the test insects; some commonly used insecticides, such as methyl parathion, EPN 300, endrin, and malathion, were rather ineffective (Table 12). MIPC in combination with lindane was highly effective in controlling stem borers as well as leafhoppers and planthoppers.

Field tests

In dry-season experiments, the insecticides, S-6626, Dursban, carbofuran, lindane + MIPC, and lindane + Uden, were further evaluated in

Table 12. Effectiveness of insecticides applied as 0.04 percent foliar spray on adult *Nilaparvata lugens* in the greenhouse. June to August 1969.

Insecticide	Formulation	Insect mortality ^a (%)				
		Days after treatment				
		1	5	10	15	20
Vamidothion ^b	40 EC	100	94	82	34	19
MIPC ^c	50 WP	100	71	16	5	0
Tsumacide	50 WP	77	15	2	8	0
S-6538	25 EC	74	27	16	12	0
SD 8447 ^d	50 WP	74	71	28	16	0
Bux 300	30 EC	72	10	1	8	0
K-57	25 EC	60	26	8	2	0
Telothion	25 EC	54	28	3	17	0
Phosalone ^e	35 EC	51	32	35	4	0

^a Mortality recorded at 48 hours after caging adult insects on treated plants. Values adjusted using Abbott's formula.
^b Trade name—Kival.
^c Trade name—Mipcin.
^d Trade name—Gardona.
^e Trade name—Zolone.

field experiments with IR8 (susceptible to brown planthoppers) and CP-SLO (highly susceptible to stem borers). Seedlings were transplanted at one seedling per hill 25 x 25 cm apart. Applications were made at 2 kg/ha at 17, 37, 58, and 78 days after transplanting.

All insecticides were highly effective against whorl maggot (Table 13 and 14). Although the incidence of stem borers was low, all treated plots had significantly lower percentages of dead hearts than the untreated controls. Both IR8 and CP-SLO were heavily infested with brown planthoppers. Even treated plots often suffered severe hopper burn. The plots treated with lindane + MIPC, lindane + Uden, or carbofuran suffered little from hopper burn. The populations of brown planthoppers in these plots are shown in Tables 15 and 16. These plots

Table 13. Effect of paddy water application of insecticides for pest control in IR8. IRR1, dry season 1969.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a		Dead hearts (%)		White heads (%)	Virus (%)	Hopper-burned area (%)	Grain ^c yield (kg/ha)
	36 ^b	48 ^b	43 ^b	57 ^b				
Diazinon	0.5	0	0.05	0.06	0.85	6	100	4,150 c
Lindane + MIPC	0.2	0	0.01	0	0.21	5	10	7,880 a
Dursban	1.2	0	0.07	0.21	0.54	5	68	5,843 b
S-6626	1.2	0.7	0.01	0.01	0.84	5	68	6,412 b
Carbofuran	0.5	0	0.03	0.16	0.01	5	0	8,271 a
Lindane + BPMC	0.7	0.5	0	0.01	0.36	4	18	7,174 ab
Lindane + Uden	0.7	0	0.70	0.12	0.04	8	3	8,048 a
Dolmix	0.5	0	0.30	0.01	0.52	6	26	7,071 ab
Lindane	0.7	0.5	0.09	0.48	0.56	6	85	4,373 c
Control	4.5	4.5	4.73	7.12	0.98	11	100	3,352 c

^a On a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage.
^b Days after transplanting.
^c Yields followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 14. Effect of paddy water application of insecticides for pest control in CP-SLO 17. IRRI, dry season 1969.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a		Dead hearts (%)		White heads (%) 104 ^b	Virus (%) 104 ^b	Hopper-burned area (%) 104 ^b	Grain yield (kg/ha) 106 ^b
	36 ^b	48 ^b	43 ^b	57 ^b				
Diazinon	0	0	0.14	0.04	1.3	12	50	3,721
Lindane + MIPC	0	0	0.11	0.06	0.82	16	7	4,779 ab
Dursban	0.25	0	0.03	0	2.09	12	48	3,420 bc
S-6626	1.0	0.2	0.02	0	2.29	8	61	4,140 ab
Carbofuran	0.5	0.0	0.28	0.18	0.43	15	0	4,967 a
Lindane + BPMC	0.2	0.5	0.03	0	1.09	11	0	4,563 b
Lindane + Uden	0.2	0.2	0.08	0	0.48	10	0	4,588 a
Dolmix	0	0.2	0.04	0.02	0.94	7	2	4,683 a
Lindane	0.2	0.5	0.11	0.02	0.88	10	30	3,680 b
Control	4.2	4.0	2.30	3.73	2.97	19	7	2,695 c

^a On a scale of 0 to 5. Larger numbers mean greater damage.

^b Days after transplanting.

^c Yields followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

produced the highest grain yields. In both varieties Diazinon did not control brown plant-hoppers effectively.

To confirm the results obtained in the dry-season experiments, the insecticidal combinations were again tested during the wet season. These combinations, together with the single formulations that were earlier found highly effective against stem borers, green leafhoppers, and brown planthoppers were applied at 2 kg/ha to the paddy water at 20-day intervals. The carbamates in combination with lindane were applied at 1.5 kg/ha.

The results (Table 17) confirmed the earlier trials. Although the incidence of dead hearts and white heads was generally low in all treatments, the percentages of damaged tillers and panicles in plots treated with combinations of lindane,

S-6626, or the carbamates were still significantly lower than in the untreated control. Plots treated with single formulations of carbofuran and Diazinon also had significantly lower percentages of dead hearts and white heads.

Populations of brown planthoppers were low in plots treated with any of the insecticide combinations and in plots treated with carbofuran (Table 18). The population of adult brown planthoppers in the Diazinon-treated plot was relatively higher than that of other treatments. Based on observations made at 60 days after transplanting, the difference, in terms of nymphal populations, was even greater than the rest of the treatments. The ineffectiveness of Diazinon was apparent from the population counts made at 78 days after transplanting, or 5 days after the fifth insecticide application. Here, even

Table 15. Effect of paddy water application of insecticides on brown planthopper population^a before^b and after^c the fourth insecticide application. Variety IR8. IRRI, dry season 1969.

Insecticide	Population per 10 hills					
	Before			After		
	Adults	Nymphs	Total	Adults	Nymphs	Total
Diazinon	132	656	788	182	814	996
Lindane + MIPC	33	43	76	12	29	41
Dursban	186	733	919	140	2,378	2,518
S-6626	65	155	220	54	492	546
Carbofuran	36	7	43	20	78	98
Lindane + BPMC	20	35	55	50	222	272
Lindane + Uden	46	33	79	26	232	258
Dolmix	27	47	74	18	135	153
Lindane	157	851	1,008	169	1,407	1,576
Control	296	1,652	1,948	91	1,078	1,169

^a Insects were collected using a portable insect suction machine.

^b Seventy-six days after transplanting.

^c Ninety days after transplanting.

Table 16. Effect of paddy water application of insecticides on brown planthopper population^a before^b and after^c the fourth insecticidal application. Variety CP-SLO. IRRI, dry season 1969.

Insecticide	Population per 10 hills					
	Before			After		
	Adults	Nymphs	Total	Adults	Nymphs	Total
Diazinon	121	680	801	53	633	606
Lindane + MIPC	28	69	97	9	65	74
Dursban	231	647	878	26	182	208
S-6626	53	201	254	13	271	284
Carbofuran	24	110	134	3	14	17
Lindane + BPMC	33	109	142	21	161	182
Lindane + Uden	63	219	282	22	80	102
Dolmix	38	62	100	8	23	31
Lindane	104	495	599	14	59	73
Control	176	631	807	14	29	43

^a Insects were collected using a portable insect suction machine.

^b Seventy-six days after transplanting.

^c Ninety days after transplanting.

Table 17. Effect of insecticidal combinations and single formulations applied to the paddy water for pest control in IR8. IRRI, wet season 1969.

Treatment ^a	Whorl maggot damage ^b 20 ^d	Dead hearts (%) 60 ^d	White heads (%) 104 ^d	Virus (%) 60 ^d	Hopper-burned area (%) 104 ^d	Crop stand ^c 104 ^d	Grain yield (kg/ha) 104 ^d
Carbofuran	0.1	0.11	0.1	5.3	0	1.5	5,215
Lindane + Uden	0.0	1.60	0.0	8.3	0	1.6	4,409
Lindane + MIPC	0.0	0.45	0.0	5.4	0	1.5	4,720
S-6626 + Uden	0.0	0.35	0.8	5.8	0	1.1	4,668
Diazinon (standard)	0.1	0.18	0.7	6.1	35 ^e	0.2	3,245
Meobal	4.5	0.83	0.5	12.5	0	2.8	3,727
Dolmix	0.0	0.33	0.0	7.3	0	1.6	4,988
S-4150	5.0	0.81	0.8	14.8	0	3.2	3,482
Landrin	1.0	1.00	0.6	13.7	0	2.8	4,375
Control	4.8	1.44	0.9	12.1	0	3.6	3,638
LSD (0.05)		0.34	0.27				2,923
Statistical transformation used		$\sqrt{x+0.5}$	$\sqrt{x+0.5}$				

^a Insecticides applied 7, 27, 47, 67, 72, and 79 days after transplanting.

^b On a scale of 0 to 5. Larger numbers mean greater damage.

^c On a scale of 1 to 5. Lower number indicates better stand.

^d Days after transplanting.

^e Two replications affected by hopper burn.

after insecticide application, the population of adult brown planthoppers increased sharply. Another indication of the ineffectiveness of Diazinon was the occurrence of hopper burn on these plots (Table 17). Plots treated with Landrin or Meobal had slightly higher populations of brown planthoppers but the increase came too late to cause significant damage.

Insecticide combinations and carbofuran were effective against stem borers and brown planthoppers and brought about significantly higher grain yields. Plots treated with S-4150, Landrin, and Meobal produced lower yields primarily because these chemicals were not effective against whorl maggots. This resulted in poor crop stand in these plots. The relatively high incidence of grassy stunt virus in these plots indicated that the chemicals were less effective against brown planthoppers. The low yields obtained in Diazinon-treated plots were due primarily to hopper burn.

Different rates and frequencies of carbofuran application

During previous planting seasons, screening tests showed that carbofuran was highly effective against stem borers, leafhoppers, and brown planthoppers when applied to the paddy water at 2 kg/ha active ingredient at 20-day intervals. To determine if applications at lower rates would also be effective, a trial was conducted

during the wet season with rates of 1, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 kg/ha. The frequency of application was tested, too, by making the applications at intervals of 20, 30, or 40 days.

At any of the rates, whorl maggot damage 38 days after transplanting was generally least in the 20-day-interval treatment. A noticeable increase in damage was observed in plots receiving 1 kg/ha at 30-day intervals or 1 and 1.5 kg/ha at 40-day intervals (Fig. 14). Thus, 1.0 kg/ha at 20-day intervals would control whorl maggots. Higher rates it seems are required at longer intervals.

The plots treated at 20-day or 30-day intervals

Table 18. Effect of insecticidal combinations and single formulations applied to the paddy water on brown planthopper population^a before^b and after^c the fifth insecticidal application. IRRI, wet season 1969.

Insecticide	Population per 10 hills					
	Before ^b			After		
	Adults	Nymphs	Total	Adults	Nymphs	Total
Carbofuran	6	15	21	9	12	21
Lindane + Uden	6	24	30	10	18	28
Lindane + Mipcin	7	29	36	7	13	20
S-6626 + Uden	9	80	89	3	0	3
Diazinon (Standard)	14	254	268	143	168	311
Meobal	8	24	32	20	43	63
Dolmix	8	20	28	5	6	11
S-4150	3	9	12	8	13	21
Landrin	11	30	41	35	78	113
Control	6	18	24	17	57	74

^a Insects were collected using a portable insect suction machine.

^b Sixty days after transplanting.

^c Seventy-eight days after transplanting.

had low incidence of dead hearts. Plots treated at 40-day intervals at any rate had significantly higher percentages of dead hearts (Fig. 14). So even at relatively high rates applied at 40-day intervals, the residual period of carbofuran was not long enough to affect the insects infesting the plots. The incidence of white heads, however, was low, indicating that these rates were nevertheless effective against stem borers later. Stem borers, which caused the dead hearts, were therefore affected by the subsequent insecticide application, but the effect was more apparent at 2 and 3 kg/ha.

The population of adult brown planthoppers in all treated plots, except those treated with Diazinon, was low. At 68 days after transplanting all the carbofuran-treated plots, regardless of rate and interval, had about two to three times fewer adults than the Diazinon-treated plots (Table 19). Populations increased significantly 10 days later, but the rates of increase in the Diazinon-treated and control plots were much higher.

In general, plots treated with carbofuran at 20-day intervals had fewer nymphs regardless of the rates used than plots treated at longer intervals. However, compared with the untreated check, all the rates, regardless of interval, had significantly lower populations.

Table 19. Effect of different rates and frequencies of carbofuran on brown planthopper population^a: IRR1, wet season 1969.

Treatment	Rate (kg/ha)	Population per 10 hills					
		68 ^b			78 ^b		
		Adults	Nymphs	Total	Adults	Nymphs	Total
Carbofuran (every 20 days)	1.0	7	5	12	18	29	47
	1.5	5	14	19	29	38	67
	2.0	4	15	19	12	14	26
	2.5	7	29	36	4	6	10
Carbofuran (every 30 days)	1.0	8	82	90	24	56	80
	1.5	8	38	46	17	25	42
	2.0	8	72	80	28	30	58
	2.5	6	43	49	9	22	31
Carbofuran (every 40 days)	1.0	5	59	64	29	58	87
	1.5	4	36	40	26	44	70
	2.0	3	24	27	23	48	71
	2.5	5	24	29	18	33	51
Diazinon (every 20 days)	2.0	21	411	432	123	114	237
Control		6	63	69	36	85	121

^a Insects were collected using a portable insect suction machine.

^b Days after transplanting.

The low populations of brown planthoppers, the relative absence of hopper burn in the carbofuran treatments, and the excellent control of stem borers resulted in high yields. Yields were about 1 to 1.5 times greater than the yield of the untreated check. The Diazinon-treated plot had a low yield because of the high population of brown planthoppers which caused hopper burn in these plots. Based on the yield increases resulting from the application of carbofuran at different rates and frequencies, it appeared that 1.5 kg/ha at an interval of 20 days was optimum. The rates of 2 kg/ha at 30-day intervals and 2.5 kg/ha at 40-day intervals were also appropriate.

Foliar sprays

Several insecticides were evaluated in field experiments during the wet season to determine their effectiveness against stem borers and planthoppers when applied as foliar sprays. The compounds were selected from among those found promising in greenhouse screening tests. They were applied at 900 to 1,300 liters/ha at a toxicant concentration of 0.05 percent. The first insecticide application was made 13 days after transplanting IR8 seedlings. Subsequent treatments were made at 14-day intervals until crop maturity.

Sixty days after transplanting, the percentages of dead hearts in plots treated with C-17018, carbofuran, and Azodrin were lower than in the untreated control (Table 20). The effectiveness of these compounds against stem borers was further confirmed by the significantly lower percentages of white heads in these plots before harvest than in the untreated control. However, Azodrin and carbofuran were more effective in reducing the incidence of white heads than the compound C-17018.

The observations on brown planthoppers were made 1 day before and 10 days after the fourth application (79 and 90 days after transplanting). Just before the fourth spraying, high populations of nymphs were observed on plots treated with C-10015, C-8353, R-5092, Azodrin, and vamidothion (Table 21). An average of more than 50 nymphs per 10 hills was recorded on these plots except for the plots treated with C-10015 and vamidothion where the average population was over 100 per 10 hills. Since the

Fig. 14. Effect of different rates and frequencies of carbofuran application on stem borer and leaf whorl maggot control on variety IR8. IRRI, July-November 1969.

first count was made 14 days after the third application, the residual effect of the compounds was wearing off and the newly emerging nymphs were not being affected. The significant decrease in the nymphal population on these plots at the count made 10 days after the insecticides were

applied indicates, however, that these compounds were effective in controlling brown planthoppers. Thus, although the compounds C-10015 and vamidothion were less persistent and appeared to have a shorter residual action, they were highly effective against planthoppers.

Table 20. Evaluation of insecticides applied as foliar sprays for rice pest control. IRRI, wet season 1969.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a 30 ^d	Dead hearts (%) 60 ^d	White heads (%) 104 ^d	Virus (%) 104 ^d	Hopper-burn ^b area (%) 104 ^d	Crop stand ^c 104 ^d	Grain yield (kg/ha) 104 ^d
C-10015	2.2	3.1	1.4	38.2	S (2)	3.3	2,565
C-8353	2.0	2.1	0.8	40.6	S	2.8	2,658
C-17018	1.1	0.9	0.7	32.9	O	1.6	3,348
DDT	2.0	3.2	0.8	49.9	O	2.8	2,698
Carbofuran	1.5	1.2	0.2	32.4	O	1.8	3,172
R-5092	2.5	2.3	0.7	43.1	S (2)	3.0	2,283
Azodrin	0.5	0.9	0.1	25.6	S	1.5	2,945
Vamidothion	1.3	2.0	1.7	49.1	S	3.3	2,352
MIPC	1.5	2.5	1.5	33.4	O	2.7	2,907
Control	3.0	2.9	1.1	45.1	S (2)	3.8	2,622
LSD (0.05)		0.45	0.43				528.6
Statistical transformation used		$\sqrt{x + 0.5}$	$\sqrt{x + 0.5}$				

^a On a scale of 0 to 5. Larger numbers means greater damage.

^b S means slight hopper burn with no distinct characteristic of complete wilting of individual hills. Number in parentheses indicates the number of replications affected.

^c On a scale of 1 to 5. Lower number means better stand.

^d Days after transplanting.

Table 21. Effect of foliar sprays on brown planthopper population: IRRI, wet season 1969.

Insecticide	Population per 10 hills					
	89 ^b			99 ^b		
	Adults	Nymphs	Total	Adults	Nymphs	Total
C-10015	23	134	157	24	13	37
C-8353	13	56	69	12	13	25
C-17018	14	24	38	17	14	31
DDT	5	5	10	3	2	5
Carbofuran	4	1	5	4	7	11
R-5092	25	73	98	26	13	39
Azodrin	19	65	84	24	10	34
Vamidothion	21	112	133	22	13	35
MIPC	12	14	26	5	5	10
Control	20	54	70	15	8	23

^aInsects were collected using a portable insect suction machine.

^bDays after transplanting.

On the other hand, C-17018, DDT, carbofuran, and MIPC appeared to have a longer residual action. Consistently low populations of both adult and nymphs were observed on these plots.

Yields obtained in plots treated with C-17018, carbofuran, Azodrin, and MIPC were significantly higher than the yield in the untreated check. The increased yields were due to the effectiveness of these insecticides against stem borers and planthoppers as well as other pests, especially whorl maggots. The plots treated with these compounds also had a better crop stand than the rest of the treatments. The plot treated with DDT, which is highly effective against planthoppers, had relatively lower yield because DDT is ineffective against stem borers and whorl maggots.

Movement of Diazinon in soils and water

A study was conducted to find out how much Diazinon moves from treated to untreated areas that are not separated by a levee and, in a second study, how much moves with water that overflows or seeps out of a treated paddy.

Knowledge of the movement of the insecticide from a treated area to an untreated area is important in determining the need to broadcast Diazinon granules uniformly. Sometimes patches of poor insect control are thought to be caused by uneven distribution of Diazinon.

The experiment was conducted in a field plot measuring 25 x 100 m which was planted with IR8. A strip 10 x 80 m was marked in the center

of this field and a strip 10 x 20 m was marked crosswise in the center of the field. Only the area occupied by the two strips in the center of the field was treated every 20 days with Diazinon granules at the rate of 2 kg/ha active ingredient normally required for the whole plot. Water was maintained approximately 5-cm deep throughout the field.

The movement of Diazinon from treated to untreated areas was bioassayed. Movement was also determined by analyzing water and soil and by counting planthoppers from treated and untreated areas. Samples were collected from the treated area and 1, 5, 10, and 15 m away from it. Water samples were collected 1, 5, and 10 days after each treatment, but plant and soil samples were obtained only 5 days after the fourth treatment. A 2- to 5-ml water sample was collected at each sample site in the field. Five soil samples, each 25-cm deep, were collected from each sampling site. These were thoroughly mixed together. From the mixture, 25 g was taken for analysis. For plant samples, 16 hills representing an area of 1 sq m were taken from each sampling site. These were divided into three parts: Roots, basal half (from plant base to a 30-cm height), and upper part of the plant. These parts from all 16 hills were pooled together and chopped into pieces 1 to 2 cm long. A 100 g sample was then taken and its Diazinon content determined.

The analysis of water samples showed that the Diazinon moved freely with the water from the treated to the untreated area. However, its concentration in water declined sharply the further the samples were taken from the treatment (Fig. 15). This difference in concentration was maintained up to 5 days after treatment, beyond which it declined to low levels in all samples. The movement of Diazinon in paddy water was not adequate, however, to produce a level of Diazinon in plants high enough to prevent insect infestations. The untreated area was severely damaged first by whorl maggots and later by brown planthoppers. The treated area showed little damage. The Diazinon content in all plant parts from the treated area was significantly higher than in the corresponding samples from untreated areas (Fig. 16).

In the second experiment, to find out how much insecticide is lost when water overflows or

Fig. 15. Diazinon content of paddy water in treated area and at various distances from treated area. IRRI, 1969.

seeps out of a treated paddy, a row of five 10 x 10 plots were planted with IR8. The first plot was treated with Diazinon at 2 kg/ha and the water was allowed to overflow every 3 days to the other plots in sequence. The first overflow was made 24 hours after treatment. The Diazinon treatment was repeated every 20 days. The water, soil, and plants from these plots were analyzed for Diazinon.

Although some Diazinon was carried from treated to untreated plots by the overflowing water, non-significant quantities were present in the plants in untreated plots (Fig. 17).

Thus, both experiments showed that although

some insecticide is carried with water, the amount is not enough to reduce the insect infestation of untreated plots significantly. Some insecticide is definitely lost from the treated field, however. Therefore water seepage or overflow must be prevented to ensure that the Diazinon treatment is fully effective. The insecticide must also be uniformly distributed for effective pest control.

Ineffectiveness of Diazinon

Applying Diazinon to paddy water is the most effective way to control common rice pests. It has been a standard practice at IRRI for the past

3 years. In 1969 it provided rather poor insect control, however. Several experiments were conducted to find the causes.

Diazinon-resistant strains of brown planthoppers

The life cycle of the brown planthopper takes 20 to 25 days to complete. Since brown planthoppers occur at IRRI throughout the year, 15 to 20 generations a year are theoretically possible. Within the 3 years in which Diazinon was used intensively at IRRI, the insect could have completed 45 to 60 generations. Such a large number of generations is ordinarily adequate

Fig. 16. Diazinon contents in plant parts from treated and untreated areas. The samples were collected at 5 days after the fourth insecticidal treatment. IRRI, 1969.

Fig. 17. Diazinon contents in plant parts from treated and untreated plots. The water from treated plots was allowed to overflow to untreated plots for 3 hours at 3-day intervals. IRRI, 1969.

to produce resistant strains.

In an exploratory test, to find out whether this is what actually happened to the brown planthopper at IRRI, Diazinon-susceptible brown planthoppers obtained from Maligaya Rice Research Center at Muñoz, Nueva Ecija (about 200 km north of IRRI) were compared with those obtained from the IRRI farm. The two populations were exposed to potted plants to which 2 kg/ha of Diazinon had been added to the water in the pots. Seven percent of the insects from IRRI and 63 percent of the insects from Muñoz died. Clearly, brown planthoppers at IRRI have some resistance to Diazinon.

Table 22. Effect of insecticides and different formulations of Diazinon applied to the paddy water on rice pest control. IRRI, dry season 1969.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a			Dead hearts (%)		Virus (%) 110 ^b	Hopper-burned area (%) 112 ^b	Grain yield ^c (kg/ha) 112 ^b
	21 ^b	31 ^b	41 ^b	40 ^b	52 ^b			
Diazinon 1 (local)	0.2	0	0.5	0	0.07	2.8	47	5,372 abcd
Diazinon 2 (Geigy)	0.2	0	1.0	0	0.08	3.2	6	6,198 ab
Diazinon 3 (over 0.8 mm)	0	0	0.2	0.12	0.20	2.5	80	4,880 bcd
Diazinon 4 (0.8 mm max)	0.2	0	0.2	0	0.02	1.0	58	5,695 abc
Super Dol Granule	0	0	1.2	0.03	0.56	3.5	75	4,107 d
Lindane + Carbaryl	0.2	0	2.2	0	0.05	3.9	90	1,446 e
Meobal	4.2	4.7	4.5	0.57	0.83	2.2	0	5,979 ab
S-4150	4.0	2.7	4.0	0.63	0.94	5.7	0	6,208 ab
Landrin	3.0	3.0	4.0	0.26	0.41	4.0	0	6,545 a
Tsumacide	3.7	4.5	4.7	0.87	0.42	4.3	0	5,901 ab
C-6989	4.5	4.0	4.5	1.08	1.29	2.6	10	4,499 cd
Control	4.0	3.0	4.0	1.20	0.72	5.0	5	4,957 bcd

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger numbers mean greater damage.

^bDays after transplanting.

^cMean values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Differences in granular formulations

The effectiveness of commonly available granular formulations of Diazinon and of other promising insecticides were tested in field plots. Each insecticide was applied at 2 kg/ha, 13, 32, 53, and 73 days after transplanting.

All Diazinon formulations were highly effective in controlling whorl maggots and reducing the incidence of dead hearts caused by borers (Table 22), but they were ineffective against the brown planthopper (Table 23). Among the Diazinon formulations, the one from Geigy resulted in comparatively small populations of brown planthoppers and in less hopper burn. The populations of all Diazinon-treated plots were too high to qualify any of these granules as an effective control agent for the brown planthopper, however. Meobal, S-4150, Landrin, and Tsumacide were effective in keeping the population of brown planthoppers significantly lower in the treated than in the control plots.

Degradation of Diazinon in paddy water

Plots were treated with 10 percent Diazinon granules broadcast uniformly on the paddy water at 2 kg/ha active ingredient every 20 days. Twelve days after the third application, water samples were collected from three locations in each plot. The three samples from each plot were mixed and a 5-ml portion was incubated with 5-ml aqueous Diazinon solution. Hexane extracts of the incubated materials were analyzed for

Diazinon in a gas chromatograph fitted with a phosphorus detector.

The insecticide incubated with water from Diazinon-treated plots was degraded completely in 5 days. When incubated with water from untreated plots, it suffered no appreciable loss even after 10 days (Table 24). Thus, its degradation was not caused by hydrolysis in water. The pH values of the samples ranged from 7.1 to 7.8 throughout the experiment, which eliminates the possibility that pH is involved in the degradation of the insecticide (Diazinon is unstable at an acid pH).

Table 23. Effect of insecticides and different formulation of Diazinon on brown planthopper population? IRRI, dry season 1969.

Insecticide	Population per 10 hills					
	73 ^b			88 ^b		
	Adults	Nymphs	Total	Adults	Nymphs	Total
Diazinon 1 (Local)	39	74	113	478	1,132	1,610
Diazinon 2 (Geigy)	54	150	204	241	543	784
Diazinon 3 (Over 0.8 mm)	69	210	279	378	448	826
Diazinon 4 (Max. 0.8 mm)	68	190	258	478	932	1,410
Super Dol Granule	37	82	119	442	948	1,390
Lindane + Carbaryl	110	573	683	797	1,250	2,047
Meobal	17	25	42	89	135	224
S-4150	23	26	49	57	112	169
Landrin	24	36	60	105	141	246
Tsumacide	64	75	139	233	267	500
C-6989	43	69	112	162	445	607
Control	44	33	77	241	663	904

^aInsects were collected using a portable insect suction machine.

^bDays after transplanting.

Table 24. Persistence of Diazinon in water samples from Diazinon-treated and untreated rice field plots. IRRI, 1969.

Treatment	Diazinon ^a (ppm)			
	Days after incubation			
	0	2	5	10
Water from Diazinon-treated plot + standard Diazinon solution	30.8	23.6	0	0
Water from untreated plot + standard Diazinon solution	27.7	25.4	22.0	21.1

^a LSD (0.05) day means within treatment: 3.7; treatment means with days: 2.6.

To determine if microbes were involved, the persistence of Diazinon in sterilized and non-sterilized paddy water from Diazinon-treated plots were compared. Sterilization was done in two ways: Autoclaving and filtration through a Millipore filter (pore size -0.45μ).

The insecticide degraded rapidly in nonsterile cultures, but autoclaving and filtration retarded its breakdown, indicating a biological degradation (Table 25). Although microflora can degrade Diazinon, the rate of degradation in these experiments was much faster than that recorded previously. Furthermore, this appears to be the first recorded build-up of the Diazinon-degrading microbial factor in the natural environment after insecticide treatment.

Table 25. Persistence of Diazinon in sterilized and nonsterilized water from Diazinon-treated rice field plots. IRRI, 1969.

Treatment	Diazinon ^a (ppm)		
	Days after incubation		
	0	5	10
Autoclaved	36.5	31.6	25.1
Millipore-filtered	35.3	27.0	21.5
Nonsterilized	36.2	0	0

^a LSD (0.05) day means within treatment: 4.7; treatment means within days: 4.3.

In another experiment, a mixture of standard Diazinon solution and water from treated plots was flushed with nitrogen gas and then incubated anaerobically in a nitrogen atmosphere. A similar mixture was shaken once a day to provide an aerobic condition.

After 3 days of aerobic incubation no insecticide was present, but even after 5 days of the anaerobic incubation, over 65 percent of the insecticide was recovered. The aerobic nature of the Diazinon-degrading microflora is significant, considering that paddy water remains aerobic by the diffusion of atmospheric oxygen and some oxygen is released by algal flora present in the paddy water.

An enrichment technique was employed to

Fig. 18. Diazinon recovered from paddy water following the first, third, ninth, eleventh, and thirteenth applications of Diazinon granules at 2 kg/ha a.i. at 5-day intervals. IRRI, 1969.

confirm the development of the microbial factor in Diazinon-treated paddy water. This was done by incubating 5 ml of paddy water from a Diazinon-treated field plot with 5 ml of about 35 ppm aqueous Diazinon solution. When the insecticide disappeared from this mixture, a 5-ml sample was withdrawn and incubated with another 5 ml of about 35 ppm Diazinon solution. Five such transfers were made.

After the first transfer, Diazinon disappeared from the incubation mixture in 96 to 120 hours. But after the fifth transfer it disappeared in less than 6 hours (Table 26).

Subcultures in a mineral medium supplemented with excess Diazinon as the sole carbon source caused turbidity in the medium. When examined for growth by staining or streaking on nutrient agar containing Diazinon, this culture solution revealed the presence of Gram-positive cocci.

The biodegradation factor for Diazinon was highly effective at 23 and 30 C, but inactive at 0 and 40 C.

The accumulation of the Diazinon-degrading factor in the paddy water was further examined in a field experiment in which the insecticide was applied in separate treatments: 13 times at 5-day intervals, seven times at 10-day intervals, four

Table 26. Diazinon degradation in serial subcultures of field water with aqueous Diazinon solution using enrichment culture technique. IRR1, 1969.

Serial subculture	Incubation time required for the degradation of Diazinon (hours)
1	96—120
2	24—48
3	12—24
4	6—12
5	6

* The initial Diazinon concentration in the incubation mixtures ranged between 14.0 to 19.0 ppm and the pH values ranged from 7.4 to 7.6.

times at 20-day intervals, three times at 30-day intervals, and two times at 40-day intervals. The plots were flooded before the insecticide applications and were not irrigated again during the next 4 days. Water samples were collected each day for 3 days after application. The Diazinon content of the samples was analyzed by gas chromatography. At the end of the experiment, an assay of the water samples from each pot was made to determine the amount of Diazinon breakdown by incubating the samples with Diazinon solution.

The Diazinon content of the paddy water of field plots treated every 5 days increased after each of the first three applications, but later declined rapidly (Fig. 18). The analyses made

Fig. 19. Degradation of Diazinon in the paddy water after application of Diazinon granules at 2 kg/ha a.i. at various intervals (amount found on first day after application considered as 100%). IRR1, 1969.

Fig. 20. Degradation of Diazinon after a Diazinon solution was incubated with paddy water which had been previously treated with Diazinon granules at 2 kg/ha a.i. every 5, 10, 20, and 40 days.

after the 5-, 10-, and 20-day treatment plots which had received five, three, and two applications, respectively, showed that the insecticide was broken down more rapidly in plots treated every 5 days than in those treated every 10 or 20 days (Fig. 19). Evidently the biodegradation factor for Diazinon had accumulated in these plots. After at least three treatments, Diazinon degraded rapidly even in plots treated every 20 or 30 days (Fig. 19 and 20).

Although these experiments show that Diazinon was not effective against the brown planthopper, the reasons are not clear. Interestingly, in all these experiments, it was highly effective in controlling whorl maggots and in preventing dead hearts. This indicates that in early applications, it was not degraded by soil microorganisms fast enough to reduce its effectiveness much. Subsequent data have shown that about three continuous treatments were required for Diazinon to become biologically degraded. It can be concluded that the development of a Diazinon-biodegrading factor in paddy fields following three or more continuous Diazinon treatments and the development of resistance to Diazinon in brown planthoppers appear to be the main causes of Diazinon's ineffectiveness at the IRRI farm.

Rice Production Training and Research

Training program

Thirty-five trainees from 14 different countries attended the annual 6-month rice production training program which began June 1. Afghanistan, Burma, Fiji, Iraq, Kenya, Tanzania, and Thailand were represented in the program for the first time. The other trainees were from Ceylon, India, Laos, Pakistan, the Philippines, U.S.A., and Vietnam. The training program emphasizes current rice science and technology, production and diagnostic skills required to achieve high yields, and fundamentals of the communication process.

The practical examination (identification of nutritional disorders and of insects and diseases of rice) given at the beginning of the program resulted in a class average score of 33 percent with a range of 4 to 82 percent. These results support the idea that the technical competence of the average "change agent" needs to be improved through specialized training in rice culture before he can assist farmers properly.

A similar practical examination at the end of the course resulted in a class average score of 92 percent with a range of 71 to 99 percent. At the end of the course, the trainees returned to their

home countries to establish similar training programs for their countrymen or to strengthen those already operating.

Training programs outside IRRI

Since 1964, over 150 individuals from 16 different countries had been graduated from IRRI's 6-month or 12-month rice production training programs and had returned to their parent organizations to teach what they had learned. Training programs are now being operated in the Philippines, Malaysia, Laos, Vietnam, Pakistan, India, Ceylon, and U.S.A.

Urvart

A Uniform Rice Variety Applied Research Trial was begun in the wet season 1968 and the results became available early in 1969. In the trial, seeds of three selections from IRRI cross IR532 were assembled with a uniform plan and all necessary chemical inputs in a kit. The kits were distributed to rice production specialists for testing at 48 locations throughout the Philippines. At each location, the three selections were planted in a non-replicated design, both with

Table 1. Performance of IR20 (IR532E576) with and without diazinon at 47 locations in the Philippines. 1968 wet season.

Treatment	Growth duration (days) ^a	Deadhearts 70 days after transplanting (%)	White heads at harvest (%)	Productive tillers/hill at harvest (no.)	Yield (kg/ha)
Luzon (28 provinces)					
Diazinon treated	126	1.7	0.6	20	6665
No diazinon	127	4.1	2.4	19	5703
Visayas (10 provinces)					
Diazinon	124	1.7	1.8	21	6418
No diazinon	123	5.1	4.3	18	5160
Mindanao-Palawan (9 provinces)					
Diazinon treated	126	0.8	0.9	21	7163
No diazinon	127	3.6	7.4	19	5835
All areas (47 provinces)					
Diazinon treated	126	1.6	1.0	21	6708
No diazinon	126	4.3	3.7	19	5613

^a Days from sowing seedbed to harvest.

and without diazinon granules. The primary purpose of these trials was to obtain data on the performance of the new selections with and without the insecticides under widely differing environmental conditions.

Performance data from 47 locations for one of the selections, IR532E576 (now IR20), are shown in Table 1.

At every location yields of the diazinon-treated plots exceeded those of untreated plots: the treated plots averaged nearly 1,100 kg/ha more. The country-wide average yield of 5,613 kg/ha for the IR532E576 plantings which received no diazinon was an indication of the genetic resistance of this selection to stem borers and certain diseases.

Minikit

When new and improved plant materials are developed, it is important to expose them at an early stage to farmers to get an indication of "user acceptance." The extension-type demonstration serves this purpose usually, but often only after the variety has been officially released. Sometimes farmers and the releasing authorities do not see the qualities of varieties in the same way, so farmers may reject "new and improved" varieties. Such differences could cause farmers to doubt the credibility of the releasing authorities and thus delay the acceptance of new technology in general.

The "Minikit" was developed to allow large numbers of typical rice farmers to evaluate "new and improved" strains in their own fields before they are officially released as varieties. In addition, the Minikit program permits evaluation of the thesis that the average peasant farmer, if given the opportunity, is capable of selecting from several rice selections growing in his farm one or more that might qualify as new varieties. Assuming farmers possess such an ability, would the releasing authorities accept the opinions of the farmers who made the judgment, and would the "superior" strain actually be released as a new variety? The latter question, in reality, is somewhat academic. Farmers will grow whatever variety or selection they like, whether it is technically a variety or

only a selection, if they have the seed.

In November 1968, several new strains of rice from the IRRI and the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture breeding programs showed promise in preliminary observation trials. These included IR532E576 (now IR20), IR127-80-1-10, and C4-113. Seeds of these strains, in addition to seeds of the varieties IR5, IR8, and C4-63 were assembled in kit form containing recommended amounts of fertilizers, granular and sprayable insecticides, and granular herbicides. These were prepackaged to permit their use in growing 50 square meters of each strain under optimum conditions. Cultural practices, prepared jointly by all organizations concerned with the Philippine national rice program, were contained in a mimeographed set of instructions enclosed in each kit.

IRRI and UPCA furnished over-all guidance in the program. Various agri-business firms in Manila supplied the necessary inputs without charge—a total of 25 metric tons of materials. Funds from the Ford Foundation Philippine grant and UPCA were used to pay for such items as printed cardboard cartons, ship and air transportation for Minikits, and supplemental labor in packaging materials into kit form.

By January 1969, over 850 Minikits had been furnished to extension officers in 56 provinces in the Philippines for delivery to ultimate users—average peasant farmers—for evaluation in the 1969 dry season (January-May). The Agricultural Productivity Commission was primarily responsible for finding farmer recipients of Minikits and for working with them to ensure the success of the effort. However, a number of kits were distributed through other organizations such as the Bicol Development Planning Board, various agricultural schools and universities, the US Peace Corps, Philippine penal colonies, various missionary groups, provincial governors, the Philippine Land Authority, the Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement, US Agency for International Development, numerous dedicated individuals, and agri-business firms.

During the growing season, and especially just before harvest, UPCA and IRRI staff members and Philippine government officials visited

farmers' fields to determine progress and to identify problems associated with the Minikit project. While some operational problems were found, it was generally agreed that the Minikit concept was valid in that farmers were able to recognize "superior" selections or varieties when given the chance to observe them on a day-to-day basis for a full season.

As expected, farmers' opinions concerning the six entries varied from place to place. In the areas where rain fell frequently, blast disease reduced the yields of C4-63. Where this was not a problem, however, farmers preferred this strain over others. Almost everywhere, farmers rejected IR127-80-1-10 because of its low tillering capacity and its very great susceptibility to stem borers (Table 2). IR532E576 was found highly acceptable and preferred in most situations for its resistance to stem borers, its short stature, its high yield potential, and its grain quality. Farmers were quick to mention relative tiller number, disease and insect reactions, and grain quality when asked which of the several selections or varieties they preferred.

For the 1969 wet season over 1,000 Minikits were packaged and distributed mainly through the same organizations as in 1968, except that the Presidential Arm on Community Development this time distributed over 200 of the units through their personnel who had undergone rice production training short courses.

By the start of the 1969 wet season (June), commercial seed production of IR532E576 had been started by forward-thinking Filipino farmers, and by November 1969, when IRRI gave this selection the variety name IR20, large amounts of seed were already on hand for those who wished to plant it.

The Minikit concept appears to have several merits, and the approach is spreading to other countries where it is being evaluated both as an extension tool and as a system that research workers might use to help them decide with confidence which new technology might best be released and recommended for farmer use.

Table 2. Average grain yield of four standard varieties and two selections at 138 locations in the Philippines. Minikit, 1969 dry season.

Variety or selection	Yield (kg/ha)
IR8	5948
IR5	5598
IR20	5942
IR127-80-1-10	4439
C4-63	5427
C4-113	5519

Pensart

If new rice selections to be entered into Minikit programs for farmers are to succeed in various environments, they must first undergo preliminary screening in typical environments.

Pensart (Preliminary Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial) was established at the outset of the 1969 wet season as a joint project of the UPCA, the Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI), the IRRI, and the agri-business sector of the Philippines in an effort to evaluate a number of new rice selections which, if good enough, might subsequently find their place in Minikits for farmer evaluation. This program was intended to supplement the testing program carried out by the BPI for many years. The wet season seems to be ideal for such a preliminary screening, because attack by diseases and the unfavorable weather make rigorous natural screening possible.

Each of the three agencies involved with rice breeding entered their most promising lines in Pensart trials at 17 locations throughout the country. Applied research kits containing all the required seeds and inputs were packaged and distributed through normal channels to certain seed inspectors of the BPI. The seed inspectors were chosen as responsible agents because they ultimately would be in charge of the field inspection activities associated with certified seed production should one of the new selections become a recognized variety. By year's end, harvesting of Pensart plots had only begun. Results of these trials will be published in the 1970 Annual Report.

Training Programs

In the Institute's resident training program, scientists and extension workers from rice-producing regions of the world carry out studies of the rice plant and learn techniques of rice production. In 1969, the Institute began training individuals in techniques of multiple cropping that include rice as the major crop.

The Institute's research training program enables young scientists of other institutions or organizations to work under the guidance of eminent scientists in different disciplines related to rice culture. Trainees possess at least the Bachelor of Science degree. They may take either a non-degree training program or one leading to a Master's degree from the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture (UPCA). Scholars who already have master's or doctoral degrees receive additional training and gain experience in a particular area by working with one of the Institute's senior scientists. All participants in the training program, in addition to their individual programs of study, attend weekly seminars at the Institute, thereby gaining a broader knowledge of rice research.

Master's degree candidates usually do their course work at UPCA and their thesis research under the guidance of Institute scientists, all of whom are members of the UPCA Affiliate Graduate Faculty. Under a special arrangement, a graduate student enrolled at another university may carry out his thesis research at the Institute. A student who was admitted to the University of Queensland (Australia) as a candidate for the Master of Science degree carried out his thesis research under the supervision of an Institute scientist. Another scholar from Pakistan conducted his thesis research at the Institute after completing course work for his doctorate at Cornell University (U.S.A.).

Non-degree scholars gain practical experience by working on a specific research project from the planning stage through final analysis of experimental data and presentation of the report

under the guidance of experienced research scientists.

A degree candidate is in residence for at least 2 years, a non-degree candidate for 6 months to 1 year.

During the year the Institute had 79 research scholars and research fellows. Eight were post-doctoral fellows, 17 were post-M.S. fellows, 33 worked on a master's degree, and 21 were in the non-degree program. Thirty-five completed their programs and returned to their home countries. Increasing numbers of applicants to the Institute's programs seek training leading to a master's degree. Applications are also received from many individuals who wish to pursue a study program leading to a doctoral degree. The Institute is developing an arrangement that would permit doctoral candidates to complete their course work at a university and to pursue their thesis research at the Institute.

Each department of the Institute received individuals for training but the Varietal Improvement Department received the largest number, followed by the Agronomy, Entomology, and Plant Physiology departments. The Agricultural Engineering, Chemistry, Soil Microbiology, and Soil Chemistry departments continued to have a relatively small number of scholars primarily because these research areas have not yet received adequate attention in most underdeveloped countries. Also less training spaces are available in these departments of the Institute. Of course, the actual number of applications received in each area was much larger than that finally accepted. All applications are considered on a competitive basis and the majority of the candidates accepted belong to institutions concerned with rice in the underdeveloped regions of the world.

A 6-month training program in rice production was held from June to November. This program is held every year to train rice production specialists and trainers of rice extension

workers. The trainees spend half of their time in the classroom, learning the science of rice growing, and the other half in the field, practicing their knowledge and acquiring skills in rice production. Considerable time is devoted to the fundamentals of communication and to the concepts and techniques of applied research. Thirty-five trainees from 14 countries participated in this training program. One had a doctoral degree, three had master's degrees, and the rest had bachelor's degrees or equivalent qualifications. Many of the 1969 graduates of the rice production training program are now training local extension workers and rice growers in their home countries. A more detailed description of this activity is found in the report of the Office of Rice Production Training and Research.

The first 4-month multiple cropping course was held from September to December. The objective of the course is to demonstrate the food production potential of a tropical environment under scientific management and to equip the trainees with the knowledge and skills necessary to operate successful multiple cropping systems involving rice and some other food crops. In the first course, all of the participants except one were Filipinos and all were college graduates. In the next course, to be organized in 1970, most of the participants will come from other countries.

During 1969, a total of 129 men and women studied and worked at the Institute for a part or the whole of the year. The number varied during the year but the total man-years amounted to 69.1, the maximum number of scholars at any one time during the year being 101. They came from Ceylon, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Pakistan, the Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam, Columbia, Laos, Nigeria, Switzerland, U.S.A., Afghanistan, Australia, Burma, England, Fiji, Iraq, Kenya, and Tanzania. Even in countries with small rice areas, interest in sending their rice workers for training at the Institute is growing, as indicated by the increasing number of requests being received from countries in Africa and Latin America.

The 129 persons who studied at the Institute in 1969 were as follows (in addition, a list of trainees and visitors who spent a short period at

the Institute and individuals who received support for advanced studies in U.S.A. is included):

Research scholars

Agronomy

MEENHON KHAN ABBASI, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan, Chemical weed control in direct-seeded, flooded rice.

CH. MANZUR AHMAD, *research assistant, Government Rice Farm, Kala Shah Kaku, West Pakistan. Effects of water management practices on the efficacy of granular herbicides for transplanted rice.

ALPHA DIALLO, project agronomist, Ministère de l'Economie Rurale, Guinea. Effects of management levels involving insect control, weed control, and nitrogen level on the varietal performance; Performance of granular herbicides in transplanted rice.

SAMSON FAGADE, research officer, Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria. Effect of plant density and fertilization on the growth characteristics and grain yield of flooded rice; Use of zero tillage techniques in direct-seeded, flooded rice.

KAZUHO MAKINO, fraternal staff worker, Allahabad Agricultural Institute, India. Studies on some cultural practices for direct-seeded, flooded rice.

JIN KOO PARK, * junior agronomist, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Weed control and effect of management levels on the grain yield of two varietal types of rice.

WITTAYA SEETANUN, second grade agricultural officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand. Effects of time of nitrogen applications on the optimum time of harvest and milling and other seed qualities of flooded rice.

PONNAMPALAM YOGARATNAM, **agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon. Use of chemicals in lieu of land preparation in flooded rice.

Chemistry

NGAMCHUEN KONGSEREE, seed quality laboratory assistant, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand. Development of a rapid screening method for rice amylose.

Communication and Extension

DIOSDADO CASTRO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. A follow-up study of the graduates of the IRRI Rice Production Training program.

CORAZÓN MENDOZA, editorial assistant, The International Rice Research Institute, Philippines. Communication factors associated with the adjustment of research trainees to their learning experiences at IRRI.

SOSIMO PABLICO, Philippines. Evaluation of the "Mini-Kit" in an applied research program.

Agricultural Economics

BENJAMIN GAON, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. The Philippine land reform program: Its effects on productivity and farm income.

CARL MONTAÑO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Yield variability and farmer's risk associated with rice response to fertilizer.

DIBJO PRABOWO, instructor, Gadjah Mada University, Indonesia. Factors influencing farm decisions with respect to the use of cash inputs in rice production in Indonesia.

RODOLFO REYES, research assistant, Agricultural Engineering Department, The International Rice Research Institute,

Philippines. Experiments in the economics of water distribution.

REYNALDO DE SAGUN, *instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Regional differences in income elasticity of demand for rice in the Philippines.

MOISES SARDIDO, instructor, University Research Center, University of Eastern Philippines. Patterns of income distribution among rice farmers in Bicol.

JERACHONE SRISWASDILEK, junior lecturer, Department of Agricultural Economics, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Response of Thai farmers to changes in profitability of rice and alternative crops.

Agricultural Engineering

VICENTE UICHANCO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Physical properties of paddy related to mechanical cultivation.

Entomology

CHING-HUAN CHENG, **junior entomologist, Department of Plant Protection, Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan. Biological interrelationships between *Nephotettix impicticeps* and some resistant and susceptible varieties.

IJAZ AHMAD DAR, *research assistant, Government Rice Farm, Kala Shah Kaku, West Pakistan. Life history and control of pink stemborer, *Sesamia inferens*.

T. YESU DAS, **research assistant, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, India. Cross resistance in selected rice varieties to four species of stemborers.

A. N. M. R. KARIM, *research assistant, Department of Agriculture, East Pakistan. Field screening of varieties for their resistance to the rice whorl maggot, *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino.

HAROLD KOONE, *manager, Office of Rural Development, U.S. Agency for International Development, Philippines. Effectivity of foliar sprays and compounds applied to the paddy water for rice pest control.

CAESAR PURA, teacher, Bureau of Public Schools, Philippines. Varietal resistance to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*.

CHANG JIN SONG, junior agronomist, Crop Experiment Station, Suwon, Korea. Resistance to *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) and *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) in some japonica rice varieties.

Experiment Station Management

MUHAMMAD ABDUS SALAM, *farm superintendent, Directorate of Agriculture, Dacca, East Pakistan. Experiment station management and operations.

Plant Pathology

CHI-LU CHU, plant pathologist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. The effect of environmental factors on the transmission of tungro virus of rice.

SUNETRA EAMCHIT, **second grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand. Seed transmission of *Xanthomonas oryzae*.

SOON HYUNG LEE, *junior researcher, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea. Virus transmission and serological tests.

LEONARDO SANTOS, plant entomologist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Pathogenicity and chemical control of *Corticium sasakii* (Shirai) Matsumoto on rice.

Plant Physiology

ANNAPANTULA BHADRACHALAM, **senior scientific assistant, Agricultural Chemistry Division, Central Rice Research

Institute, India. Factors affecting the availability of zinc in rice soils.

DOUGLAS FORNO, University of Queensland, Australia. Zinc nutrition and varietal difference in the rice plant.

MANUEL PALADA, instructor, Central Philippine University. Submergence and survival of rice plants.

CH. MUHAMMAD RASHID, research assistant, Government Rice Farm, Kala Shah Kaku, West Pakistan. Nutrient uptake by a high-yielding rice crop.

Soil Chemistry

TASNEE ATTANANDANA, assistant lecturer, Department of Soils, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Effect of temperature on the kinetics of ammonification and soil reduction in farm flooded soils.

DAE YOUNG CHO, assistant soil chemist, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Korea. Influence of temperature regimes on the chemical kinetics of flooded soils and the growth of rice.

Soil Microbiology

SANG KYU LEE, *assistant to the soil microbiologist, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Korea. Organic acid formation in rice rhizosphere.

IRENEO MANGUIAT, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Microbial transformation of nitrogen in flooded rice soils.

Statistics

MOO SANG LIM, assistant statistician, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Varietal-competition effects in rice experimental plots.

K. M. PALANISWAMY, statistical officer, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Coimbatore, India. Sampling for yield components in rice replicated field experiments.

Varietal Improvement

SOMMAI AMONSILPA, *second grade agricultural officer, Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Thailand. General rice breeding.

KRUAWAN ATTAVIRIYASOOK, *third grade officer, Breeding Division, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand. Quality testing procedures.

SUNG WON CHO, *junior agricultural chemist, Crop Experiment Station, Suwon, Korea. Quality testing procedures.

REGINA DOLORES, *Botany Department, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Cytogenetics of male-sterile lines of rice.

U SOE HLAING, *district agricultural officer, Department of Agriculture, Burma. General rice breeding.

SUNG HO HONG, *research assistant, Crop Experiment Station, Suwon, Korea. IRRI-Korea cooperative rice breeding program.

FU-HSIUNG LIN, assistant agronomist, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, China. Rice genetics and breeding.

CESAR MARTINEZ, auxiliary geneticist, Instituto Colombiano Agropecuario, Colombia. Varietal resistance to plant-hoppers.

TOMAS MASAJO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Breeding behavior and relationship of white belly and gelatinization temperature to amylose content of the rice endosperm.

KHIN NYUNT, * farm superintendent, Central Agricultural

* Completed training.

** Completed Master of Science degree.

Experimental Farm, Agriculture Department, Burma. General rice breeding.

SUVIT PUSHPAVESA, second grade officer, Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Thailand. The effect of glabrous gene on yield of rice varieties.

DHARMAWANSA SENADHIRA, *research officer, Central Rice Breeding Station, Ceylon. General rice breeding.

Research fellows

SHAMSUL ALAM, assistant entomologist, Agricultural Research Institute, Government of East Pakistan, is working on the population dynamics of common leafhoppers and planthoppers of rice as affected by crop age, varieties and season.

VICTOR AWODERU, research officer, Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria, is studying pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae*.

TEH-MING CHU, instructor, Department of Agronomy, Provincial Chung-Hsing University, Taiwan, is studying the cause of shattering in the rice grains.

ABDUR R. HAMDANDI, *rice specialist, Jammu and Kashmir State Agriculture Department, India, studied the general rice breeding program.

NARENDRA NATH KAKATI, assistant agronomist, Department of Agriculture, Assam, India, is studying weed control in transplanted rice and germination characteristics of rice varieties.

M. SALEH KHOKAR, *research assistant, Government Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan, studied general rice breeding procedures.

DONG KYUN KIM, assistant agronomist, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea, is studying sources of rock phosphate for flooded rice and rates of EPTC/2,4-D IPE herbicide for flooded rice.

V. A. KULKARNI, *assistant botanist, Agricultural Research Institute, Bihar, India, studied general rice breeding procedures.

SHENG-HUI LIAO, *graduate research fellow, UP-Cornell Exchange Program, China, studied the factors affecting the adoption of new rice varieties.

ABDUL MAJID, *assistant economic botanist (cereals), Directorate of Agriculture, East Pakistan, studied the effect of nitrogen top-dressing on grain yield of rice varieties with different growth durations.

ALLAH DITTA MASTOI, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan, is studying the biology of *Tryporyza incertulas* (Walker) and testing of granular insecticides for its control.

KAZUO NAKABAYASHI, Hokkaido University, Japan, is studying the relationship between nitrogen nutrition, chlorophyll content, and photosynthesis and photorespiration of rice leaves.

RAJ PAL PURI, senior research assistant, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, is studying rice quality testing and rice breeding procedures.

KAZUSHIGE SOGAWA, *research associate, Nagoya University, Japan, studied the mechanism of varietal resistance of the rice plant to *Nilaparvata lugens*.

DAMODAR P. TALEKAR, *agronomist, Japanese Demonstration Farm, Khopoli, India, studied general rice breeding procedures.

HIDEO WATANABE, *technical officer, Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Japan, studied photophosphorylation of the rice chloroplast.

MD. ABU YUSSOUF, *research assistant, Directorate of Agriculture, East Pakistan, studied the effect of variety,

method of planting, and fertilizer management in flooded rice.

Postdoctoral

A. K. BHATTACHARYYA, reader in agronomy, Kalyani University, India, is working on the effects of level of nitrogen on the growth characteristics and grain yields of improved varieties and promising selections; and effects of soil temperatures at different growth phases on nutrition and growth habit of flooded rice.

S. CHANDRASEKARAN, reader in agricultural chemistry, Annamalai University, India, is conducting biochemical studies of the rice rhizosphere.

JAMES COCK, University of Reading, England, is carrying out studies on the contribution of stored carbohydrate to grain filling.

HANS ALBERT GREMLI, *Institute of Agricultural Chemistry, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Switzerland, was engaged in chemical investigations on hemicelluloses of rice bran.

R. K. JANA, scientists' pool officer, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, is working on the effects of different environmental factors and soil water regimes on the growth and yield of rice; and effects of date of planting on the growth characteristics and grain yield of upland rice.

KAZUO KAWANO, *Plant Breeding Institute, Hokkaido University, Japan, participated in general rice breeding.

MD. SIDDIQUE ALI MIAH, *assistant plant pathologist, East Pakistan Accelerated Rice Research Institute, worked on bacterial blight and blast diseases.

G. N. MITRA, assistant botanist, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, is studying the quality testing and rice breeding procedures.

Rice production trainees

JOHN APIYO, district agricultural officer, Department of Agriculture, Kenya.

SYED BADER-UD-DIN, agricultural assistant, Department of Agriculture, West Pakistan.

ANICETO BAUTISTA, farm management technician, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Rizal, Philippines.

RAYMOND BWENDE, field officer, Ministry of Agriculture, Tanzania.

BOONRAWD CHAIWATANA, second grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.

NISAR-UD-DIN CHOUDRY, agricultural assistant, Department of Agriculture, West Pakistan.

REYNALDO GABALLO, provincial soil technologist, Bureau of Soils, Philippines.

GANAPATI VASUDEWAN, field officer, Department of Agriculture, Fiji.

PÁLLEGEDARA GUNARATNE, laboratory assistant, Department of Agriculture, University of Ceylon.

DOAN VAN HOA, chief of agricultural service, Directorate General of Agriculture, Vietnam.

CHAROEN KAOPORISUTHI, third grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.

U OHN KYI, farm superintendent, Department of Agriculture, Burma.

SANT KUMAR, field officer, Department of Agriculture, Fiji.

LONG, experiment station chief, Department of Agriculture, Laos.

SHAMBHU MAHAPATRA, farm management specialist and agronomist, Department of Agriculture, Orissa, India.

* Completed training.

** Completed Master of Science degree.

MUMTAZ ALI MAHAR, agriculture assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan.
MOHAMMAD AZIZ KHATTAK, agricultural assistant, Department of Agriculture, West Pakistan.
SELEMANI MWARUKA, field officer, Research & Training Institute, Tanzania.
ISAM NAJJAR, assistant specialist, Ministry of Agriculture, Iraq.
Y-BLI-NIE, chief, agricultural extension branch, Directorate General of Agriculture, Vietnam.
PRAMOTE NIPPITA, second grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.
THEODORE OLBRICH, IVS agricultural extension worker, Laos.
ABDUL RAHMAN, assistant, Department of Research and Extension, Ministry of Agriculture, Afghanistan.
CHINTAMONI SAMANTARAYA, district agricultural officer, Agriculture Department, Orissa, India.
T. K. A. SAMARASINGHE, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
P. P. SHARMA, professor of agronomy, Agricultural College, Madhya Pradesh, India.
JAGAT SINGH, field assistant (research), Department of Agriculture, Fiji.
K. B. SINGH, deputy-director, Department of Agriculture, Madhya Pradesh, India.
THAO SOUTH, provincial chief of agricultural extension, Laos.
RICARDO TANQUILUT, school farming coordinator, Pampanga Agricultural College, Philippines.
CHU-HUU TIN, chief of Angiang agricultural experiment station, Directorate of Research, Vietnam.
TRAN THI CAM TUYEN, provincial agriculture deputy chief, Directorate General of Agriculture, Vietnam.
U AYE THWIN, district agricultural officer, Agriculture Department, Burma.
K. VARATHARASA, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
VICHARN VOTONG, second grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.

Multiple cropping trainees

LAURITO B. ARIZALA, technical associate, Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement.
HIPOLITO B. AYCARDO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines.
EDUARDO A. DACANAY, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines.
EBEDESTO G. DAENOS, field supervisor, Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement.
FRANKLIN V. FERMIN, field supervisor, Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement.
JAMITO F. GENER, farm management technician, Palawan National Agricultural College, Philippines.
HERMINIGILDO GINES, instructor, Central Luzon State University, Philippines.
CANDIDO S. IMANA, technical assistant, Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement.
MUHAMMAD MANZOOR KHAN, Ministry of Education and Scientific Research, West Pakistan.
MANUEL V. LAVEGA, extension worker, Antique Cooperative and Rural Extension Service, Philippines.
FELIPE D. LOZANO, secondary school teacher, Mindanao Institute of Technology, Philippines.
BERNARDO T. MACAM, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines.
VALERIANO M. PASCUAL, assistant instructor, Central Luzon State University, Philippines.

ROGELIO T. ROSALES, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines.
EULALIO D. VERGARA, secondary school teacher, Mindanao Institute of Technology, Philippines.

Short-term trainees and visitors

SUSAN JANE ALDRICK, plant pathologist, Northern Territory Administration, Australia, spent 2 months in the Plant Pathology department to become acquainted with major rice diseases and laboratory and greenhouse techniques used for their study.
SUHIRMAN MULJODIHARDJO, Agricultural Extension Service, Lampung Province, Indonesia, spent 1½ months working on blast and virus diseases.
J. SUBRAMANYAM, assistant research specialist, Andra Pradesh Agricultural University, India, studied general rice breeding for 2 months.
B. VELAYUTHAM, assistant entomologist, Regional Research Station, Government of Madras, India, completed a 2-month training which involved a study of the green leafhopper pest of rice.
ALI ARAIN, research assistant, Agricultural Research Institute, Tandojam, West Pakistan, spent 1 month studying rice quality testing procedures.
NGO-CHAN BANG, research engineer in soil studies, Institut de Recherches Agronomiques a Madagascar, spent 2 weeks in the Soil Chemistry Department to study the analytical techniques used in the laboratory.
NGUYEN DONG GIANG, chief of agricultural extension and superintendent of the National Rice Production Training Center, Vietnam, spent 1 month observing rice production techniques and extension-oriented activities of the Institute.
YOSEF HANAEL, Israeli extension officer, Vientianne Plain Agricultural and Demonstration Farms Laos, spent 3 weeks familiarizing himself with rice production techniques.
CHONG WOON HONG, soil chemist, Korean Soil Fertility Survey Project, spent 1 month in the Soil Chemistry Department observing analytical techniques used in the laboratory and reviewing literature in the library.
DERVIN MANUEL RODRIGO, research officer (soil science), Central Agricultural Research Institute, Ceylon, spent 2 weeks observing the programs in soil chemistry, soil microbiology, agronomy, and agricultural engineering, and reviewing literature in the library.
R. SATHASIVAMPILLAI, agricultural officer, designs and testing, Maha-Illuppallama Research Station, Ceylon, spent 1 week at the Institute observing the agricultural engineering, rice production training and research, agronomy, and multiple cropping programs, and the farm operations.
C. ERNEST SAVERIMUTTU, lecturer, Hardy Senior Technical Institute, Ceylon, spent a week becoming acquainted with rice production techniques.
FR. GREGORIUS UTOMO, Indonesia, spent 2 weeks observing and becoming acquainted with rice production practices.

Advanced study in U.S.A.

MD. ERFAN ALI, East Pakistan, soils, Oregon State University.
NAGAMUTTU DEVASUNDRARAJAH, Ceylon, agronomy, Cornell University.
P. S. Y. FERNANDO, Ceylon, plant pathology, University of Hawaii.
MIR NAZRUL ISLAM, East Pakistan, rice technology, Louisiana State University.
MUHAMMED EHSAN UL HAQ TUSNEEM, West Pakistan, soils, Louisiana State University.

International Activities

Strengthening rice research at national research centers in Asian countries and encouraging cooperation among these agencies are increasingly important parts of the Institute's program. At one time, the Institute's principal contacts with various rice-growing countries came through the training program, international conferences or symposia, and staff travel. Since 1966, interest in more comprehensive cooperative undertakings has developed rapidly. In 1969, eight full-time senior scientists of the Institute's staff were residing in the cooperating countries, Pakistan, India, and Ceylon, to advise on and participate in rice research. In addition, the Ford Foundation and The Rockefeller Foundation had rice scientists on their staffs in Thailand, Indonesia, and Colombia. These scientists do research and serve as liaison officers of the Institute.

Cooperative projects

The assignments and the agreements behind them have a number of features in common. A major part of each agreement involves training of rice scientists at the Institute or elsewhere. The improvement of physical facilities for rice research is also a provision of each one. The agreements enable senior research staff of the host country to make study tours to the Institute and they enable the Institute's regular senior research staff to travel to the cooperative projects as consultants.

Training activities at the Institute, reported in a separate section, have intensified as these cooperative projects have become established. Institute-sponsored conferences on basic subjects, such as mineral nutrition or insect pests of rice, are less frequent now than formerly, but an annual meeting of cooperators to discuss specific topics has developed as a forum for the exchange of current information.

All of these projects are national programs. None, in any sense, represent a branch operation of the Institute. Consequently, the detailed results are more properly presented in publications of the country in which the work is being done.

East Pakistan

A three-way agreement between the Government of East Pakistan, the Ford Foundation, and the Institute was signed in March 1966. Basically, the agreement provides for training of young Pakistani scientists both at the Institute and elsewhere; for strengthening rice research in East Pakistan through improved facilities; for one or more resident scientists from the Institute to advise on research operations; for consultation with senior scientists from the Institute and elsewhere; and for study tours to acquaint agricultural officials of East Pakistan with the program of the Institute.

Efforts to improve the rice research capability of East Pakistan were continued in 1969: Buildings are being constructed at the new research farm at Joydevpur; a new organizational pattern for a semi-autonomous, multi-disciplinary institute—the "East Pakistan Rice Research Institute" (EPRRI) is being completed; and staff is being trained at IRRI and in the U.S.A.

Five East Pakistan rice scientists were abroad in 1969 studying in doctoral programs and one spent 3 months at IRRI as a postdoctoral fellow. Two officials from East Pakistan, Dr. Amirul Islam, Director of Agriculture, and Dr. Siddiqui Ali Miah, Pathologist, participated in the Rice Research Conference held at the Institute in May 1969.

West Pakistan

In September 1966, the Institute signed an agreement to establish cooperative work with the Ford Foundation and the Government of

West Pakistan. The objectives were to assist in improving the rice research capability of the national research agency. Under the agreement, a resident adviser was to be located in West Pakistan. Funds were provided to support training, to improve facilities, and for other activities similar to those under the East Pakistan agreement. It was also assumed that the project's technical resources would contribute to the urgent program to increase rice production in the province.

A laboratory and staff housing are under construction at the Kāla Shah Kaku Rice Center. The Ford Foundation grant provides the foreign exchange necessary for the laboratory equipment. Tractors, cultivation implements, office equipment, and rice grading equipment were purchased for both Dokri and Kala Shah Kaku with these funds.

Three Pakistani scientists completed 1 year of practical training at IRRI during 1969. One Pakistani completed his doctoral studies at Louisiana State University (U.S.A.) with a project grant. Four agriculture assistants in extension from West Pakistan attended the 6-month rice production training course at IRRI. Three other research staff members from West Pakistan are involved in graduate studies at the University of the Philippines and doing their research at IRRI.

India

In June 1967, the Institute and the U.S. Agency for International Development signed a contract implementing an agreement between the latter and the Government of India's Indian Council of Agricultural Research. The Institute became the contractor responsible for certain technical support and training functions.

As a result of this agreement, four staff members of the Institute were assigned to live and work in India as members of a team of scientists in the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. These scientists work under the direction of a chief-of-party assigned to the Institute by The Rockefeller Foundation.

This team includes specialists in varietal improvement, agronomy, plant physiology, entomology, and plant pathology. Short-term consultants may be brought into the program

from the Institute or from other agencies around the world. Consultants in the fields of bacteriology, entomology, and breeding were provided in 1969.

Thirteen Indians received training in research and in new production techniques: Four in the Institute's rice production training course, two in the field plot technique course, and seven in other areas. Consultants provided by the Institute devoted 4 man-months to bacterial leaf diseases, rice insects, and breeding.

Ceylon

A 2-year cooperative project in which the Institute is involved and which is financed by the Ford Foundation was initiated in Ceylon in September 1967. At the request of the Government of Ceylon it was renewed for a second 2-year term starting in September 1969. While the objectives of the original grant were mainly to train rice research personnel and to help develop research programs and facilities, the objectives for the second grant period were broadened to include the support of agricultural extension activities, the support of agricultural education at both the practical farm school level and the university level, and the study of crop rotations built around rice.

In September, the Institute's rice production specialist was assigned as project leader to work with various government agencies to further these objectives.

During 1969, 14 Ceylonese were abroad on project funds for training, on short study tours, or to attend conferences. Five undertook training at IRRI in the rice production training program, in rice breeding, or in agronomy. Three pursued studies at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture leading to the Bachelor of Science degree. Two did graduate work in the U.S.A. at the University of Hawaii and at Cornell University. Study tours abroad of about 4 weeks duration each were undertaken by the soils specialist at the Central Agricultural Research Institute and by the head of the Machine Design and Testing Unit at Maha Illuppallama. The Deputy Director of Agriculture for Research and the Research Entomologist represented Ceylon at the annual rice research conference at IRRI.

Thailand

Although no IRRI staff member is directly involved in the Thailand Rice Research Program, close cooperation exists through the efforts of Thai scientists and the staff of The Rockefeller Foundation. Exchange of new breeding materials, field tests for virus resistance, and cooperative experiments on herbicides and new fertilizer sources as well as on protein content of the rice grain constitute examples of mutual cooperation. In addition, personnel from the Thai Rice Research Program are receiving training at the IRRI on the graduate and practical levels.

International conferences

Two international conferences were held at the Institute in 1969. The first was organized and conducted by the Institute staff while the second was organized by the Ford Foundation with Institute staff as participants.

International rice research conference—April 28 to May 2.

This was a meeting of rice scientists from 16 countries. The program was centered on the Institute's research program and the research programs in countries with which it cooperates closely. In addition, reports were received from a number of other countries and there were many round-table discussions of widespread problems.

Varietal improvement, entomology, and plant pathology were featured at these meetings. General reviews of rice breeding at the Institute (H. M. Beachell), in India (S. V. S. Shastry), in South America (P. R. Jennings), in Thailand (B. R. Jackson), in the Philippines (P. Escuro and E. Cada), in Korea (Mun Hue Heu), and in West Pakistan (M. Shafi) were given.

Bacterial diseases were reported upon by S. H. Ou, M. Goto, H. Kauffman, and I. W. Buddenhagen who discussed varietal resistance, pathogenicity of strains, ecology, disease transmission, and chemical treatment.

Virus diseases were discussed by K. C. Ling, G. Galvez, S. A. Miah, V. T. John, and Luansark Wathanakul with particular regard to symptom-

atology, virus-plant interactions, virus-vector interactions, virus identification, and epidemiology.

Stem borer problems were reviewed and reported upon by M. D. Pathak, J. A. Lowe, and T. Everett. H. E. Fernando, Tanongchit Wongsiri, and J. A. Lowe discussed the gall midge, its distribution and importance, mass rearing, varietal resistance, and insecticide usage.

Planthoppers and leafhoppers received attention in talks given by M. D. Pathak, P. C. Lippold, and Tanongchit Wongsiri who discussed distribution and identification, chemical control, virus interaction, and varietal resistance.

Papers were given on the rice blast disease by G. Galvez and S. H. Ou, and on agronomy by H. ten Have, J. C. Moomaw, G. McLean, S. K. De Datta, and H. I. Okajima. Country reports were given for East Pakistan (R. K. Walker), Ceylon (J. W. L. Peiris), Burma (Kaung Zan), Vietnam (Pham Thanh Khan), Indonesia (K. E. Mueller), Taiwan (C. H. Huang), and Peru (Pedro Sanchez).

Rice Research and Training in the 1970's

A conference on rice research and training in the 1970's was held at the Institute from September 30 to October 3. The conference sought to identify major unresolved problems of tropical rice production and marketing; to explore the impact of probable agricultural developments in tropical rice-producing countries in the 1970's; to assess national progress in developing improved capabilities in rice production, research and training; and to discuss programs that may merit greater attention by scientists, educators, trainers, and administrators.

Throughout the conference there was a particular interest in the past, present, and future roles of IRRI. The contributions of the Institute in promoting greater production were stressed. This emphasis, however, did not imply that the conference was unaware of the vital role that other institutions have played and must increasingly play in solving world rice problems.

In summarizing their observations the conferees prepared the following statement:

In less than a decade, IRRI has essentially redesigned the architecture of the tropical rice plant and evolved, tested, and helped to place in use a new set of yield-increasing practices. As a result, a technical foundation now exists for new, high levels of tropical rice production, particularly where the climate is favorable and water is under the control of the producer. The advanced technology, therefore, ideally fits the relatively small portion of monsoon Asia where paddy is most productive. Production on rainfed fields is less affected by this technology. And production on upland soils has so far been little influenced by recent technical advances.

In view of the rapid progress in rice technology and the development of increased national capabilities in rice research during the 1960's this conference asked:

Should IRRI's initial objectives be modified? If so, what program shifts logically follow?

IRRI's program is by design dynamic. Institute staff and Board members participated fully and responsively in the dialogue of the conference. Self-analysis of programs and priorities is thus a continuing process at the Institute. The tone of the conference deliberations, however, suggested that:

- 1) Research directed toward raising average yields should be given increased depth.
- 2) Economic research and training capability should be expanded somewhat.
- 3) Promising agricultural engineering research and development efforts should be encouraged.
- 4) The training of technicians and scientists should be continued but gradually shifted toward developing a higher level of competence while retaining field experience in actual rice production.
- 5) Innovative ideas and programs for international cooperative attacks on regional and world-wide problems should be developed.
- 6) The present and potential importance of ecologically different rice-producing areas should be studied more closely.

The first goal, increased depth in research on average yields, stems from the realization that in 1 or 2 decades, population pressure on food supplies in rice-consuming Asian nations may be severe. The better rice-producing areas that have adequate irrigation water will be fully utilized. Land now viewed as marginal for rice production will have to contribute to greater output. Existing institutions concerned with such lands will contribute importantly to the solution of problems of local adaptation and improved practices and by training personnel. They will, however, look to IRRI, for the more basic discoveries which may break prevailing technology and economic yield barriers.

The second goal, expansion in economic research and training, recognizes that a more adequate understanding of

the economic and social environment in which rice is produced is essential to the development and wider adoption of improved technology: Factor and product prices, earnings, uncertainty, the marketing chain, consumer demand (domestic and export), retail prices, and producer and consumer behavior.

While the Institute should not enter directly into the policy debates from which agricultural economic policies are forged, it should help develop the research tools and the economic information which planners and policy makers use in making such decisions.

The third goal of encouraging agricultural engineering developments means particularly that emphasis should be placed on ways to lower costs and increase the earnings of operators and workers on small farms. One way might be a temporary expansion of work on techniques for drying and processing rice at the small farm and village level.

The fourth goal is continued training of technicians and scientists with a shift to greater depth. At the production level, the training of trainers will be emphasized with IRRI providing consultative help to national training programs. More programs leading to an academic degree should be available to persons who work in national centers of research and education. IRRI is also expected to build increasingly strong links with both African and Latin American institutions in collaboration with IITA and CIAT. The initial Institute goal of helping to accelerate the growth in competence and performance of national institutions is as valid today as it was 10 years ago.

The fifth goal, innovations in international cooperative programs, is required if the foregoing goals are to be achieved. IRRI's headquarters site is an inadequate field laboratory for investigating some high-priority problems. Because the competence of national institutions is rising and because of the need to study problems in their own ecological and economic setting, centers of collaborative research and testing are likely to expand considerably.

The sixth goal, greater knowledge of ecologically different rice areas, results from the lack of precise information about how much land is in rice under sub-optimal conditions. Involved are impediments to production and harvest such as moisture, drainage, sunlight, temperature, topography, insects, diseases, and economic relationships. There is need, therefore, to define combinations of varieties and production practices that best fit specific ecological and economic situations; to increase world understanding of the present and potential importance of various types of production situations; and to take these more fully into account in designing research and training programs for IRRI and national and international agencies.

Library and Documentation Center

Bibliographical services

The 348-page supplement to the *International Bibliography of Rice Research* was completed in 1969. It has 2,737 references to scientific literature selected from numerous sources. The bulk are taken from journals printed in 1968. The coverage is worldwide, and includes literature written in 23 languages.

The Bibliography is sent to libraries and documentation centers of the rice-producing countries for the benefit of rice research workers and those responsible for disseminating information on the crop. The annual supplements list virtually all the technical literature on rice published since 1951. So far, the Bibliography contains 25 566 entries arranged according to subjects and with author, geographic and specific subject indexes. Nearly all the entries are available in the Institute library. The annual supplements feature author and keyword indexing with 5-year index cumulations. The 1964 and subsequent supplements also list the available translations of papers into English. So far, eight supplements, 1961-1968, and a cumulative index for 1961-1965 have been issued.

Reference and circulation

In 1969, the library received inquiries from 37 countries. Most were requests for information and photoduplication. As in previous years, requests for Japanese literature on genetics and breeding outranked requests for information on all other aspects of rice culture. Requests came mostly from experiment stations in Malaysia and India. Libraries in several countries asked for assistance in library organization and management, selection and acquisition of agricultural materials, and the processing of special materials such as microfilm, maps, and pamphlets.

Within the Institute, there was a marked increase in the number of books and journals borrowed during the year—from 22,812 in 1966 to 38,913 in 1969. This figure is exclusive of direct library use because the library has open stacks. Likewise, figures on reference questions

received and answered by telephone are not available.

Growth of the collection

The library continued to acquire literature from the Chinese Mainland and Russia. Over 60 periodicals were added to the collection, mainly through its exchange program. The addition of 2,315 monographs (books, pamphlets, and reprints) brought the over-all monographic collection to 23,853. Other acquisitions included 82 maps, 14 theses, and 34 translations. Over 9,000 cards were added to the catalog.

Other library activities

Tables of contents of newly received journals were photocopied and circulated to bring the most current literature to the attention of the researchers. This service was extended to the Rice Breeding Department of The Rockefeller Foundation Agricultural Program in Colombia and to the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project in Andhra Pradesh, India. The service has resulted in requests for photocopies and loans of these journals. To further notify the Institute staff of the availability of new information, the library prints a monthly list of new acquisitions of books, microfilms, translations, reprints, maps, and serial titles. Copies of this list are also being sent on request to libraries of rice-producing countries where it is being used as a selection tool for the acquisition of materials.

Copies of translations of foreign-language rice literature continued to be deposited in the National Agriculture Library, U.S. Department of Agriculture, which in turn lists these in the *Bibliography of Agriculture* to make them known and more generally available to rice scientists.

The library continued to purchase and distribute books to Institute research scholars.

Bindery

During the year the bindery produced 924 volumes of periodicals, monographs, field books, theses; 376 volumes of pamphlets; 51 Princeton boxes; 83 pairs of folders; 152 name tags; 9 slide boxes; and 748 volumes of bibliography.

Experimental Farm

As in the previous years, the Experimental Farm was primarily involved in the planting of promising IRRI selections for seed multiplication and for cooking quality tests. For both seasons, 76.5 ha were planted to rice in the experiment station and an additional 10.6 ha in Tiaong, Quezon Province.

During the dry season, 162 selections were planted in the station, with the most promising selection, IR532E576, planted on a bigger scale. In the wet season, four varieties, BPI-76, C4-63, IR5, and IR22, and 18 IRRI selections were planted. Three hectares were planted to C4-63, the harvest of which was used as payment for the use of the UPCA land by the Office of Rice Production Training and Research in its training program. BPI-76 was grown for the Chemistry Department for shipment to U.S.A. and Taiwan. One-fourth of a hectare was planted to IR5 for seed purification. Over 1 hectare of IR22, the new IRRI variety, was also planted.

Fields used in the multiplication of IRRI selections were plowed twice and harrowed four times to insure that no volunteer rice grew. These operations doubled the cost of land preparation.

The Department will use an L.S.U. columnar mixing dryer during the next harvest season. With this new dryer, drying will take only 2 hours compared with the 12 to 16 hours necessary with the present flat-bed type dryer.

Due to difficulties in controlling the brown planthopper with diazinon granules, sevin, and azodrin, DDT was used at a concentration of 0.2 percent with a commercial sticker at 0.2 percent by volume with a "Hardie" power sprayer under the supervision of the Entomology Department. The results showed that two spray applications at 2-week intervals controlled the planthopper population up to 29 days after the second application.

To control weeds, paraquat was used instead of PCP because it is more economical to use.

No serious rat damage to the rice plants in the experimental plots occurred. Damage was kept to a minimum by regular baiting with poison and by dusting of rat burrows with Cyanogas. The height of the electric fence was increased by 6 inches and finer mesh wire was used to keep the rats away from the rice plants.

A total of 8,762 rats were killed by the electric fence in 1969.

Information Services

Publications

During the year the editing, illustrating, layout work, and proofreading of the 1968 Annual Report, which was set in type and printed in Hongkong, occupied the time and attention of the editorial staff. Alternate possibilities for typesetting and printing were investigated to advance the date of publication of future annual reports.

The Office provided editorial, graphic, and illustrative processing for 43 journal articles written by Institute scientists. Reprints of these articles were purchased and made available to interested scientists and institutions. The Office provided similar services for non-journal articles such as papers to be presented in seminars and conferences, and reports to agencies supporting specific projects.

The Virus Diseases of the Rice Plant, a book reporting the proceedings of a symposium held at the Institute, was published by the Johns Hopkins Press (U.S.A.) and copies were released in July.

The eighth in a series of Institute technical bulletins, *The Flowering Response of the Rice Plant to Photoperiod—a Review of the Literature*, was edited, illustrated and turned over to a Manila publishing house for typesetting. It was printed at the Institute and copies became available by December. Editorial work on the ninth technical bulletin, *Marketing Relationships for Rice and Corn in the Philippines*, was completed during the year. The 250-page bulletin is expected to become available by the early part of 1970.

Methods of Rice Field Experiments for Field Researchers and Extension Workers, a manual compiled by Mr. John Lindt, Jr., rice farm adviser with the Agricultural Extension Service, University of California, who served for a year as consultant to the Training Materials Project in Taiwan, was printed in July. The manual represents a preliminary effort to provide rice

field research workers and extension specialists with an adequate knowledge of the scientific principles and procedural guides to field experimentation with rice in the tropics. Selected rice workers in different rice-growing countries were sent copies and were requested to send in their comments or suggestions for correction or improvement of the manual.

A 62-page publication, *Rice Research and Training in the 1970's*, which reports the Rice Outlook Conference held at the Institute from September 30 to October 3, was printed in December. The conference, attended by 32 rice scientists from 13 countries, enabled the Institute to analyze the principal unsolved rice problems of the tropics and to examine its role in solving them.

Because of unexpected difficulties in staffing, the Office published only four issues of *The IRRI Reporter*, the Institute's bimonthly newsletter. The usual six issues of this semi-technical publication will be printed in 1970. *The IRRI Reporter* has a mailing list of more than 4,000 names.

The following publications were being revised toward the end of the year: The general information booklet, which describes the general nature and program of the Institute; the training program booklet describing all aspects of the Institute's international research training program; and *Cultural Practices for Profitable Rice Production in the Philippines*, a leaflet which contains recommendations for growing the new, short, stiff-strawed varieties.

Information activities

The Institute continued to receive requests to purchase or borrow the Institute films, "Harvest of Energy" and "Changing the Change Agent." Requests for published technical information and photographs for use in educational programs, commercial literature, foundation publications, or technical journals increased. Re-

Members of the press are frequent visitors to the Institute: Reporters accompany U.S. Vice President Spiro Agnew on a tour of the Institute's experimental fields in December 1969.

porters and photographers representing several publications throughout the world came to the Institute to obtain information for major articles. Television producers also sent representatives to shoot scenes and activities depicting the Institute's research and training programs.

Over 17,000 visitors of different nationalities and interests came to the Institute to learn about its activities. Six thousand came in October alone. As in previous years, most of the visitors consisted of school groups, tourists, and farmers, but an increasing number of them represented professional callings of almost every type.

Discussions, movie and slide presentations, and visits to field plots were arranged to suit the individual needs and interests of such groups of visitors. The plots near the entrance to the Institute grounds continued to serve as visual

exhibits showing non-professionals the benefits of new cultural recommendations for rice varieties.

The Office prepared three major photographic-essay exhibits during the year. The first, describing two research projects at the Institute sponsored by the National Science Development Board, was the Institute's contribution to the 1969 NSDB annual exhibits. The second, a visual aids display, was prepared at the request of the Cereal Chemistry Department to acquaint persons visiting the laboratories with its work on improving the grain, eating, and cooking qualities of rice. The third, depicting the Institute's role in developing the economy of the Philippines, was the Institute's contribution to the celebration of "The Spirit of Los Baños Day" on October 10 at the University of the Philippines' College of Agriculture.

Publications and Seminars

Staff publications

Plant Physiology

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- Chang, T. T., C. C. Li and B. S. Vergara. 1969. Component analysis of duration from seeding to heading in rice by the basic vegetative phase and the photoperiod-sensitive phase. *Euphytica* 18:79-91.
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- Vergara, B. S., R. Lilis and C. C. Li. 1969. Preliminary studies on the effect of high night temperature on the developing leaves and panicles of the rice plant, p. 21. *In Proc. 12th U.S. Rice Tech. Work. Group. New Orleans, Louisiana, 1968.*
- Vergara, B. S., T. T. Chang and R. Lilis. 1969. The flowering response of the rice plant to photoperiod: a review of the literature. *Tech. Bull.* 8. International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Philippines. 31 p.
- Yoshida, S. and A. Tanaka. 1969. Zinc deficiency of the rice plant in calcareous soils. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 15:75-80.
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Chemistry

- Juliano, B. O. 1969. An integrated approach to rice quality, p. 71-72. *In C. O. Chichester et al., ed., 101 Problems in Food Science and Technology.* (n.p.).
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Varietal Improvement

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- Chang, T. T. and O. Tagumpay. 1969. Genetic association between six agronomic characters and grain yields (abstract), p. 28. *In Proc. 12th U.S. Rice Tech. Working Group, New Orleans, La., 1968.*
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- Engle, L. M., D. A. Ramirez and T. T. Chang. 1969. The cytology of sterility in F_2 , F_3 and F_4 hybrids of indica x japonica crosses of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Cytologia* 34:572-585.
- Engle, L. M., T. T. Chang and D. A. Ramirez. 1969. Cytological analysis of intervarietal hybrid sterility in rice (abstract), p. 20. *In Proc. 12th U.S. Rice Tech. Work. Group, New Orleans, La., 1968.*
- Li, C. C. and T. T. Chang. 1969. Diallel analysis of four agronomic characters in six crosses (abstract), p. 26-27. *In Proc. 12th U.S. Rice Tech. Work. Group, New Orleans, La., 1968.*
- Parial, L., L. W. Rooney and B. D. Webb. 1969. Use of the dye-binding technique for estimating protein in milled and brown rice (abstract), p. 78. *In Proc. 12th U.S. Rice Tech. Work. Group, New Orleans, La., 1968.*

Plant Pathology

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- Ling, K. C. and S. H. Ou. 1969. Standardization of the international race numbers of *Pyricularia oryzae*. *Phytopathology* 59(3):339-342.
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- Nuque, F. L. and S. A. Miah. 1969. A rice virus disease resembling tungro in East Pakistan. *Plant Dis. Repr.* 53(11):888-890.
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- Ou, S. H. and C. T. Rivera. 1969. Virus diseases of rice in Southeast Asia, p. 23-34. *In The Virus Diseases of the Rice Plant.* Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore, Md.
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- De Datta, S. K., R. T. Bantilan and J. K. Park. 1969. Selective control of annual grassy weeds in transplanted tropical rice with α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene. *Nature* 221(5175):64-65.
- De Datta, S. K. and C. P. Magnaye. 1969. A survey of the forms and sources of fertilizer nitrogen for flooded rice. *Soils Fertilizers* 32(2):103-109.
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- De Datta, S. K., J. C. Moomaw and R. T. Bantilan. 1969. Effects of varietal type, method of planting and nitrogen level on competition between rice and weeds, p. 152-163. *In Proc. 2nd Asian Pacific Weed Control Interchange, College, Philippines* (mimeographed).
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- Sagaral, E. G., J. C. Moomaw and S. K. De Datta. 1968. Chemical weed control in mechanized drill-seeded flooded rice, p. 26-34. *In Proc. First Philippine Weed Sci. Conf.* (mimeographed).

Entomology

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Agricultural Engineering

- Khan, Amir U. 1969. Mechanizing the rice paddies. *War on Hunger Magazine* 3(9):18-21.

Agricultural Economics

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- Barker, R. 1969. The International Rice Research Institute.

- Regional Seminar on Agriculture Papers and Proceedings (ADB), Sydney, Australia, April 10-12, 1969, pp. 228-238.
- Liao, S. H. and R. Barker. 1969. An analysis of the spread of new high yielding varieties on Philippine farms. *Econ. Res. J.* 16(1):12-19.
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Statistics

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Soil Chemistry

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Soil Microbiology

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- Sethunathan, N. and I. C. MacRae. 1969. Some effects of diazinon upon the microflora of submerged soils. *Plant Soil.* 30:109-112.
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- Sethunathan, N., E. M. Bautista and T. Yoshida. 1969. Degradation of benzene hexachloride by a soil bacterium. *Can. J. Microbio.* 15:1349-1354.

Seminars

The following topics were the subjects of seminars held at the Institute during 1969. Unless otherwise stated, the speakers were staff members.

- Cooperative rice research programs of the International Rice Research Institute in other countries. Dr. McClung.
The aerobic-anaerobic interface in flooded soils. Dr. D. R. Bouldin, visiting professor, Department of Soils, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program, UPCA.
- Bright prospects for increased food production in South and Southeast Asia. Dr. Dioscoro L. Umali, dean, College of Agriculture and vice president for Agricultural and Forestry Affairs, UP.
Pesticide residues in rice soils. Dr. N. Sethunathan, visiting assistant pesticide chemist, IRRI.
The research program of the University of the Philippines. Dr. Faustino Orilla, director of research, UPCA.
The illusive tropical legume. Dr. Loy V. Crowder, visiting professor, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program, UPCA.
Effects of manure and nitrogen on growth and nutrient uptake of continuous corn on clay soil. Dr. J. L. McIntosh, visiting scientist, IRRI.
Using radio for agricultural information work. Dr. Thomas G. Flores, professor of agricultural extension, UPCA.
IRRI breeding program. Mr. Beachell.
Enzymic degradation of starch granules in germinating smooth pea cotyledons. Dr. Juliano.
Lowland irrigation requirements in the humid tropics with special reference to the Philippines. Dr. G. Levine, visiting professor of Agricultural Engineering, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program.
Rodent research center as it relates to rat control. Prof. P. J. Alfonso, chairman, Rodent Research Center, UPCA.
Agribusiness in the Philippines. Dr. Ray Goldberg, professor, Harvard Business School, Boston, Massachusetts.
Sorghum improvement in the Philippines. Dr. A. A. Gomez, assistant professor, Department of Agronomy, UPCA.
Studies on sources of vegetable proteins. Dr. K. H. Steinkraus, visiting scientist, Graduate Education Program, UPCA.
Recent rice research results in Thailand. Dr. Ben Jackson, plant breeder, The Rockefeller Foundation, Thailand.
Insect antifeeding substances in plants. Dr. Katsura Munakata, professor of Pesticide Chemistry, Nagoya University.
Peroxidase dormancy and germination of rice seeds. Dr. D. Ralph Stength, visiting scientist, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program, UPCA.
Developments in rice production training programs and applied research projects during 1968 and 1969. Mr. Golden.
Lodging-resistant rice varieties and their genetic relationships. Mr. Chukichi Kaneda, visiting assistant scientist, IRRI.
Mechanisms governing availability of nutrients to plants growing in soil. Dr. S. A. Barber, visiting professor of soils, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization.
Field tests of a simple grain dryer. Dr. William J. Chancellor, associate professor, Department of Agricultural Engineering, University of California.
Plant-water relations. Dr. Alden S. Crafts, emeritus professor of botany, University of California, Davis.
My extension experience in India—1961-1969. Mr. Ross.
Research and extension program in vegetable crops. Dr. Ruben L. Villareal, assistant professor and head, Vegetable Crop Section, Department of Agronomy, UPCA.
Development administration. Mr. Rafael Salas, executive secretary, Office of the President of the Philippines.
Protein metabolism in normal and abnormal Filipinos. Dr. Rodolfo Florentino, Food Nutrition Research Center, National Institute of Science and Technology.
Pesticide residues. Dr. H. G. S. van Raalte, chief adviser on toxicology and occupational hazards of pesticides, Shell Companies.
Stored product pests of rice and corn and their control. Dr. Renato Marcos Labadan, consultant-director on pest control, Rice and Corn Administration.
Environmental conditions affecting the growth characteristics, nitrogen response, and grain yield of tropical rice. Dr. De Datta.
Observations on rice production and improvement in Latin America. Dr. Chang.
Nitrogen turnover in soil organic matter. Dr. F. E. Broadbent, professor, Soil Microbiology, University of California.
Satisfying Japan's appetite for bananas. Dr. Ramon V. Valmayor, assistant professor and head, Horticulture Division, Agronomy Department, UPCA.
Breeding for resistance to downy mildew (*Sclerospora philippinensis*). Dr. Virgilio R. Carañgal, professor, Plant Breeding, UPCA.
The green revolution—conceptions and misconceptions. Dr. Barker.
Food grain drying and storage in Southeast Asia. Dr. Merle L. Esmay, professor of agricultural engineering, Michigan University.
Texture in food—its importance and how to measure it. Dr. Malcolm C. Bourne, visiting professor of food science, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program.
Water movement in shrinking soils. Dr. Aurelio Briones, assistant professor in soil physics, UPCA.
Some observations on the production and drying of rice in California and Louisiana. Mr. Ramos.
Solving later generation development problems. Dr. Lowell S. Hardin, program officer, Ford Foundation.
Soil-plant-water relationships for vegetables. Dr. M. Vittum, UPCA-Cornell Project Leader.
Some recent genetic studies and their significance in rice breeding. Dr. Athwal.
USAID programs with emphasis on assistance to the Philippine agricultural sector. Mr. H. D. Koone, manager, Office of Rural Development, USAID.

Innovations in agricultural curricula at the UP College of Agriculture. Dr. Feliciano Calora, director of instruction, UPCA.
Research and development of furadan. Dr. Carroll C. Cassil, manager, International Development Department, Niagara
Chemical Division of FMC Corp.
The status, problems, and prospects of agricultural cooperatives in the Philippines. Dr. Vicente Quintana, director and
associate professor of agricultural economics, UPCA.
Philippine corn downy mildew. Dr. O. Exconde, professor in plant pathology, UPCA.
Role of research stations in the development of a sound statistical system in agriculture. Dr. Burton T. Oñate, senior statis-
tician, Economic Office, Asian Development Bank.
Rice and corn and their by-products in livestock and poultry nutrition. Dr. Leopoldo S. Castillo, professor of animal
husbandry, UPCA.
Food resources in the plant kingdom. Dr. Glenn W. Burton, research geneticist, Coastal Plain Experiment Station, Tifton,
Georgia.
The objectives of annual "Recommends" publications in national extension programs. Dr. Reeshon Feuer, visiting professor
of agronomy and soils, UPCA.
Shifting cultivation in Southeast Asia. Dr. R. Huke, visiting scientist, IRRI.